

School of Education and Social Sciences

**Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives on the Purpose of Quranic
Schools: A Phenomenological Study**

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Abstract

The study investigates Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose of Quranic schools within the socio-cultural and religious context of Algeria. It is guided by four research questions: first, what Algerian Muslim parents say about the nature and character of Quranic schools; second, how they view the role of these schools in their children's cultural and religious socialisation; third, what motivates their decision to enrol their children in Quranic schools; and finally, the challenges these schools face and potential ways to address them. This is a qualitative study using a phenomenological research approach to capture the 'essence' of Quranic schools' purpose, based on analysing various parental experiences and perspectives, including triangulating data with views from Quran teachers, administrators, and imams involved in these schools. A total of 25 participants (n=25) took part in semi-structured interviews conducted between March and July 2023 in Algeria. Data analysis followed Colaizzi's seven-stage phenomenological method to ensure rigour and trustworthiness. Drawing on relevant concepts related to children's faith formation, the conceptual analysis provides nuanced insights into the role of Quranic schools and why parents justify their existence within Algeria's cultural and religious framework, including rebutting claims that these schools promote Islamist fundamentalism. The study concludes by emphasising the crucial importance of parental support for Quranic schools, in line with broader societal needs, in fostering children within the Muslim community, or Ummah.

Keywords: Quranic Schools, Muslim Parents, Muslim Community, Socio-cultural Context, Algeria

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Dedication

I dedicate this work to my beloved parents, Boualem and Mubarka, whose love, encouragement, and faith in me made this achievement possible.

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I dedicate this work to everyone who has loved and supported me throughout my academic journey.

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Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that the doctoral thesis entitled, *Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives on the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study*, is the result of my original and independent research and that all sources used have been duly acknowledged. I further declare that this thesis has not been submitted to this or another university for the same or similar award, and nor is it concurrently being submitted for any other award.

Name: Zeyneb Bouzaida

signature:

Date: 1st December 2024

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The interaction of modern, traditional, and religious value systems significantly influences education in the Muslim world (AL-Kahtany, 2019; Shah et al., 2015). Many Muslim countries incorporate Western modernity's standards into their educational frameworks. After independence, the emphasis has often been on aligning with global modernist standards while maintaining traditional values (Shah et al., 2015). In this diverse educational environment, faith schools in Algeria, particularly Quranic schools, stand out as vital institutions that uphold traditional values and Islamic education.

A Quranic School system is a fascinating educational model, not only because of its enduring nature but also due to its widespread presence across the globe (Akkari, 2021). However, understanding Quranic School systems has been limited by a lack of comprehensive anthropological research (Colonna, 1984). Quranic schools have long played a significant role in Algerian culture, promoting education, instilling values, and shaping national identity while preserving traditional practices. These schools have ascended to the top of the socialisation institution hierarchy within the national collective consciousness, becoming the primary and most preferred choice for Algerian families seeking to develop values and ethics in their children (Ziane & Oussama, 2023).

Although considered informal institutions, their significance lies in transmitting Islamic and traditional values and actively addressing Western cultural changes and challenges. This importance has led to the high regard in which the Algerian people hold them, explaining their widespread presence across various regions (Ziane & Oussama, 2023). Given that Islam governs most people's socio-cultural and religious lives in Algeria, Quranic schools are widely spread (Yousfi & Briche, 2020). They exemplify how religious education is crucial in preserving Islamic traditions in Algerian heritage (Amara & Habbas, 2017). Despite their importance, there remains a notable lack of literature on these institutions.

Some researchers have analysed specific aspects of Quranic schools. For example, the study by Silva and McNevin (1994) on the involvement of Quranic schools in UNESCO's literacy programme is

notable. They emphasised the unique approach these schools take to addressing illiteracy and considered it a post-colonial initiative. Their field research demonstrated that Quranic schools, deeply rooted in grassroots communities, provide basic education with a strong focus on the Quran as a foundation for knowledge, faith, and character. Even colonial efforts to dismantle the Islamic education system failed, highlighting the resilience and ongoing relevance of Quranic schools. Since Arabic is the language of the Quran, nearly all Islamic educational institutions teach in Arabic. Such institutions place great importance on Arabic proficiency. This linguistic focus underscores the significance of Arabic, prompting many researchers to examine Quranic schools from this perspective.

Studies such as those by Legliti and Jaballah (2021) examined the role of Quranic schools in shaping national character, emphasising their contribution to fostering social values and moral principles in Algerian youth. Similarly, Ben Akoum and Ben Marzouk (2022) and Ali and Allaoui (2019) focused on the preparatory function of Quranic schools for primary education, assessing their influence on cognitive development and readiness for formal schooling. Meloudi (2020) explored the educational and moral functions of these institutions, noting how their programmes support both cognitive and moral growth. Abdullah and Hajjam (2019) analysed the relationship between Quranic schools and academic success among secondary school students.

Similarly, Amara and Habbas (2017) examined the relationship between religious institutions and academic achievement, emphasising the potential of Quranic schools to improve educational outcomes. Bakrawi and Morshidi (2011) discussed the role of Quranic schools in reducing violence, while Yousfi and Briche (2020) analysed their influence on language proficiency among primary students. Boudalia (2021) investigated the impact of memorising the Quran on developing language skills, and Sherifi (2018) studied their role in teaching reading. Sulaiman and Tamri (2018) highlighted the contribution of Quranic schools to fostering social values among students. In addition to these studies, Abu-Nimer et al. (2016) presented a case study of a programme incorporating peace, interfaith, and human rights education in Quranic schools in West Africa, utilising Islamic heritage for peace-building. Boyle (2004), in her book "Quranic Schools: Agents of Preservation and Change," adopts an anthropological approach to exploring the role of Quranic preschools in community life, emphasising their importance from a community-centric perspective.

Existing studies have examined various roles and impacts of Quranic schools, offering insight into their multifaceted functions within Muslim-majority communities. However, a significant gap remains in understanding how these institutions are perceived by a vital stakeholder group: Muslim parents. One issue that needs further exploration is parents' perspectives on the purpose and effectiveness of Quranic schools, especially within the religious and socio-cultural context. Parental perspectives encompass

parents' beliefs, attitudes, and perceptions regarding these schools. These perceptions are influenced by numerous factors, including cultural, religious, socio-economic, and personal experiences. Understanding parental perspectives is essential because they heavily shape educational choices, the value assigned to different types of education, and parents' expectations of educational institutions (Ridao et al., 2021).

One of the fundamental ideas Miller (1986) proposed to guide research on parents' beliefs about children is the relationship between parents' beliefs and measures of the child's development. Current research also considers it essential to examine the thought processes and understanding of parents (Hirsjärvi & Perälä-Littunen, 2001), as their ideas and beliefs influence children's development and adjustment (Taraban & Shaw, 2018). In recent decades, research on parent-child relationships and childhood development has grown rapidly (Lanjeckar, 2022). This expanding field highlights the crucial role that parents' perspectives and expectations about schooling play in their children's growth and development (Puccioni, 2014).

Additionally, “Children are entrusted to their parents,” a scholar once said. A child's heart is like pure gold, unmarked and receptive to impressions from anyone who teaches them. If they are guided and nurtured positively, they will flourish, bringing joy to their parents and teachers both in this life and the hereafter. Conversely, if they are exposed to negative influences and left to their own devices, they may stray and suffer. The education they receive will greatly influence their future (Arsita, 2017).

According to Islam, parents have an innate responsibility to encourage religious faith in their children to prevent spiritual stagnation (Naily, 2023). This underscores the importance of fostering faith as a key aspect of personal and spiritual growth. The Quran also reveals that recognition and awareness of God's presence are ingrained in human nature before birth. This highlights the need for parents to nurture their children's religion in accordance with Islamic beliefs. To support this, the following Quranic verse offers valuable insight,

When your Lord drew forth from the Children of Adam—from their loins—their descendants, and made them testify concerning themselves, (saying): “Am I not your Lord (who cherishes and sustains you)?”— They said: “Yes! We do testify!” (This), lest you should say on the Day of Judgment: “Of this we were never mindful (Quran 7: 174).

Thus, understanding Algerian Muslim parents' beliefs and perspectives regarding the purpose of Quranic schools is crucial for grasping their faith development goals for their children. Especially in the present era, where the spread of television, smartphones, computers, and the Internet has created a

new environment in which traditional boundaries are disappearing, information flows across borders, and cultures mingle freely. This unprecedented interconnectedness significantly shapes how individuals and parents perceive Islamic religious education for their children (Jannah, 2013; Ismail & Uyuni, 2020).

One's understanding of Islamic religious education is influenced by various internal and external factors (Culen, 2013). As a result, parents tend to have different views on the purpose and effectiveness of Quranic schools. The work of James Fowler, along with contributions from John Westerhoff and others, provides an important conceptual framework for analysing these diverse perspectives on the role of Quranic schools within Algeria's socio-cultural and religious context. By incorporating these ideas alongside Islamic concepts of faith development, we can gain a clearer insight into how systematic religious education in Quranic schools affects children's faith growth, moral ideals, and ethical behaviour.

Therefore, this study aims to explore Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose and effectiveness of Quranic schools within Algeria's socio-cultural and religious context. Such an investigation is essential, as parental beliefs directly influence how these institutions are valued, supported, and integrated into children's lives. Understanding these views provides insights into how Quranic schools can continue to serve faith-based and moral education in a rapidly evolving socio-cultural environment.

1.2. Aim of the Study

This study aims to examine the perspectives of Muslim parents in Algeria regarding the purpose and role of Quranic schools in shaping their children's cultural and religious identity. It seeks to explore how Algerian parents perceive these schools as part of their children's religious and moral upbringing and the reasons behind their decisions to send their children to such institutions. By considering the views and experiences of Muslim parents, Quranic educators, administrators, and imams, the study investigates the complex role and purpose of Quranic schools within Algeria's religious and socio-cultural context. It also highlights the challenges these schools face, such as criticism and societal misconceptions, especially claims that they promote Islamist fundamentalism. Furthermore, the study aims to shed light on how Quranic schools can evolve to meet the needs of contemporary Algerian society while remaining consistent with the broader values of the Muslim community (Ummah). By exploring nuanced perspectives on Quranic education, this research emphasises the importance of parental support and its crucial role in ensuring the continuity and relevance of Quranic schools today.

1.3. Objectives

To support the aim, the objectives of this research are structured to examine various aspects of Quranic schools in Algeria from the viewpoint of Muslim parents. It focuses on their opinions regarding the purpose, characteristics, and ethos of these institutions, their reasons for enrolling their children, their views on the schools' role in cultural and religious socialisation, and the current challenges these schools encounter. The objectives are as follows:

1. To understand Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose, characteristics, and ethos of Quranic schools in Algeria.
2. To understand why Muslim parents prefer enrolling their children in Quranic schools in Algeria.
3. To explore Muslim parents' perspectives on the role of Quranic schools in their children's cultural and religious socialisation.
4. To analyse Muslim parents' views on the contemporary challenges facing Quranic schools in Algeria and to identify potential solutions.

1.4. Research Questions

Building on the objectives outlined above, the following four research questions serve as a vital guide in exploring key issues and underpin the originality of the thesis.

1. What are the perspectives of Muslim parents, school administrators, teachers, and imams on the purpose and nature of Quranic schools in Algeria?
2. If at all, how do Muslim parents understand how Quranic schools facilitate the cultural and religious socialisation of Muslim children?
3. Why do Muslim parents send their children to Quranic schools in Algeria? Do school administrators, imams, and teachers hold similar views?
4. What are the current challenges facing Quranic schools in Algeria? What suggestions do parents, school administrators, teachers, and imams have to address these challenges?

1.5. Motivation

The motivation for conducting this study arises from academic curiosity, personal experience attending Quranic schools, and a desire to deepen understanding of their purpose and role within the Algerian religious and socio-cultural context. As a child, attending Quranic schools provided a window into their influence on religious beliefs and practices. My childhood experiences sparked my interest in examining how these schools promote the development of 'good' Muslims through the teaching of fundamental Islamic values. Additionally, there is a curiosity about the role of these institutions in the modern era, where children are increasingly exposed to secular influences.

The role of Quranic schools has become increasingly significant in today's rapidly changing world, where children constantly navigate between traditional religious teachings and modern, often conflicting, cultural values. This research has also been motivated by a desire to explore the impact of these schools in maintaining religious identity amidst globalisation and technological progress. By focusing on parents' perspectives, this study aims to enhance our understanding of the current role of Quranic schools. It highlights the crucial influence of parental decisions on their children's religious development. Comprehending parents' reasons for choosing Quranic schools will reveal how these institutions help shape Algeria's religious and socio-cultural identity. The growing trend among Algerian Muslim parents to enrol their children in these schools underscores the importance of understanding how these institutions address contemporary educational and spiritual needs.

As the demand for religious-based education grows, it is crucial to explore how Quranic schools can adapt to modern educational standards while preserving their religious integrity. This research is motivated by the need to understand how Quranic schools contribute to the comprehensive development of Algerian children, not only in terms of their religious commitments but also in shaping their identities as responsible, ethical individuals within their communities.

1.6. Contribution

This study makes important contributions to the field of religious education and beyond. Emphasising parental voices highlights the role of stakeholders in shaping educational practices and policies. The findings underscore the significance of Quranic schools as spaces for cultural preservation and community building, where religion and identity are closely connected, encouraging more scholarly attention to these institutions. The results have practical implications for Algerian families, educators, policymakers, and religious leaders. They advocate for greater alignment between parental expectations and Quranic school practices, as well as reforms to tackle infrastructural and curricular challenges. Additionally, the study offers insights into how Quranic schools can help counteract extremism by fostering inclusive and holistic education based on Islamic principles, representing a valuable contribution to the existing literature.

1.7. Limitations

This study on Quranic schools in the Algerian context has certain limitations that should be acknowledged to help the reader understand its scope. Firstly, the phenomenological approach employed in the research has limitations related to subjectivity. The method relies on the researcher's interpretation of participants' lived experiences, and achieving complete objectivity is challenging. The researcher's background and biases may influence the analysis of data. Although Colaizzi's seven-step method of data analysis was followed to ensure rigour, the potential for interpretative bias remains, particularly in phenomenology, where the researcher has a significant role in shaping the findings (Creswell, 2013; Moustakas, 1994).

Second, the study's sample size of 25 participants, while offering insights into their perspectives, cannot be generalised to all Quranic schools or the Muslim community in Algeria. Qualitative research, especially when based on semi-structured interviews, generally explores specific contexts, and the findings may not reflect the experiences of parents or educators in other regions or broader populations that were not part of the study. Therefore, the study's findings should be regarded as providing valuable insights into a particular context, but they cannot be easily generalised to other settings (Patton, 2015).

Another limitation is the impact on the study caused by the scarcity of existing literature on Quranic schools that include parents' perspectives. While there is academic work on Quranic schools and religious education in general, the specific focus on parents' views of these institutions remains underexplored. This gap makes it more challenging to directly compare the findings with other studies in similar contexts, thereby restricting the analysis and the ability to situate the results within broader academic discussions.

In conclusion, although this study offers valuable insights into the role of Quranic schools in Algeria's religious and socio-cultural context, it has limitations related to the sample size, methodological challenges, and the scarcity of existing literature. Future research could address these issues by incorporating larger and more diverse samples, broadening the literature base, and examining practical challenges in greater depth.

1.8. Structure of the Thesis

This thesis begins with an introductory chapter that outlines the research problem, aims, objectives, and questions, as well as the study's motivation, contribution, and limitations. The next chapter provides

the context for the study with a section titled Sociocultural and Historical Background of Algeria, situating the research within the national setting. The following chapter, Quranic Schools in Algeria, examines the specific characteristics and roles of these institutions within the Algerian educational and spiritual landscape, as depicted in existing literature. Building on this, the chapter Faith Development in Childhood presents the key theoretical concepts underpinning the research. The methodology chapter then describes the phenomenological approach employed, explaining the procedures for data collection and analysis and providing the rationale for the research design. It also considers relevant ethical issues.

The thesis then presents the main themes emerging from the data analysis, organised into four interconnected thematic chapters (Chapters 6, 7, 8, and 9). These chapters—covering the purpose of Quranic schools, the cultural and religious socialisation of children, parental support, and the link between Quranic schools and fundamentalism—are designed to combine the presentation of findings with their analysis and discussion. This integrated approach, explained in the Methodology chapter, allows for a dialectical process where empirical data is immediately contextualised within relevant theoretical frameworks and scholarly debates, resulting in a more dynamic and coherent narrative. The thesis concludes with a comprehensive summary synthesising the entire work, along with suggestions for future research.

Chapter2

Sociocultural and Historical Background of Algeria

2.1. Introduction

An overview of Algeria, covering its current social, cultural, religious, and economic features, is essential to understand how Algerian parents view the phenomenon of religious practice, particularly the act of sending their children to Quranic schools and their beliefs about how this affects their children's faith development. Moreover, historical background and events relevant to the emergence of modern Algeria will offer important context. As Sathyanarayana Rao et al. (2009) observe, conceptions and beliefs stem from what we hear and continue to hear from others from childhood (and even earlier). Sources of these beliefs include the environment, events, knowledge, past experiences, visualisations, and more. This underscores the importance of examining the historical, cultural, and social contexts in which Algerian parents have formed their perspectives.

Understanding the Algerian background will clarify the factors that have shaped perspectives and expectations regarding Quranic schools. This chapter will specifically examine key historical events such as colonialism and the civil war, along with socio-cultural factors like the role of Islam and Arabisation, and their impact on shaping contemporary parental attitudes towards Quranic schools. These insights are directly linked to the study's research questions on parental views, reasons for enrolment, and the challenges faced by these schools. The environment in which individuals grow up, the events they witness, and their accumulated knowledge and experiences all influence their views on educational institutions and their purposes.

Ruedy (2005) emphasised that Algeria's Islamic institutions, including Quranic schools, have historically been both a refuge for cultural identity and a form of resistance against colonial and post-colonial state policies. This supports Tiliouine and Achoui's (2018) assertion that Islam is not just a religion in Algeria; it is the foundation of cultural values, social order, and educational expectations. Therefore, Quranic education cannot be considered separately from the historical and sociopolitical forces that have shaped Algerian society. As Entelis (1996) states, "the mosque and the school have remained central pillars in shaping Algerian collective consciousness in the post-independence era." Such perspectives highlight the importance of a comprehensive contextual analysis to understand parents' deeply held beliefs about Quranic education.

2.2. Algeria's Socio-Historical Foundations

Algeria is the largest country in Africa, located in the northern part of the continent (Statista, 2020), and one of the biggest countries in the world (Abderrahmane et al., 2021). It covers an area of 2,381,741 square kilometres, of which more than four-fifths are covered by extensive deserts. The capital, Algiers, is situated in the far north of the country. Algerians are its nationals (Metz, 1993). Algeria forms the heart of the Maghreb (Hamadouche, 2016). Its land borders touch seven neighbouring countries, including Morocco and Western Sahara to the north-west, Tunisia to the north-east, Libya to the east, Niger to the south-east, and Mauritania and Mali to the south-west (Abderrahmane et al., 2021). The Mediterranean Sea lines Algeria's entire northern border, with a coastline stretching over 1,355 km (Couthard, 2001).

According to the Algerian National Statistics Office (2023), the country's population was 46.3 million in July 2023. The structure of the Algerian population in 2023 shows a slight male majority, accounting for 50.6 percent of the total population (i.e., 103 men for every 100 women). The age distribution indicates that children under five make up 10.2 percent, while those aged 5 to 14 constitute 20.2 percent. The working-age group (15 to 59 years) represents 59.2 percent of the total population. People aged 60

and above account for 10.5 percent, roughly 5 million individuals, including 2,127,000 aged 70 and over, and 707,000 aged 80 and above. The number of women of childbearing age (15-49 years) is estimated at 11.4 million. General mortality rates in Algeria reached record levels in 2020 and 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic and its effects, such as health restrictions. Deaths numbered 241,000 in 2020 and 258,000 in 2021. In 2022, this number began to decline. The high proportion of children in the population highlights the importance of educational institutions, including Quranic schools, in shaping future generations.

This demographic context lays the foundation for understanding Algeria's national identity and cultural traits. According to the first article of the Algerian Constitution of 2020 (2021), Algeria is a democratic and popular republic and an indivisible entity. The country's name and linguistic diversity also reflect this national identity. Its Arabic name, Al Jazair, meaning 'the islands', probably originates from the rocky islands along the coast of the Mediterranean Sea (Deeb, 1993). Besides its name, Algeria's linguistic heritage underscores its cultural landscape. The Algerian constitution recognises Arabic and Tamazight as official languages (Central Intelligence Agency, 2020). However, French remains widely used in politics, industry, administrative sectors, commerce, and various institutions and colleges (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018; Ness & Lin, 2013). This linguistic duality is a legacy of colonialism and influences education, including Quranic schools that emphasise Arabic, thereby shaping parental choices and the schools' role in cultural preservation.

These linguistic layers are linked to Algeria's deep historical roots. Algeria's history dates back to pre-Classical times, with the Amazigh (Berbers) being the first settlers in the region. Today, most Algerians are 'Arabised Berbers' who mainly speak Arabic dialects (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). However, the rich Berber heritage persists, as over one-fifth of Algerians speak various Berber dialects of Tamazight, including Kabiliya, Aures, Ghardia, and Tamanrasset (Central Intelligence Agency, 2020). The difference between Arabs and Berbers in Algeria is linguistic rather than racial (Djebali, 2005). The Arab/Berber community is the largest ethnic group in the country, accounting for 99 percent of the population. The remaining ethnic groups are estimated to constitute less than 1 percent (Central Intelligence Agency, 2020).

One of the country's distinctive features is the clear contrast between the northern and southern regions in terms of terrain and climate. The Mediterranean coastal area, commonly known as Tell, is home to the majority of the population due to its mild climate and access to fertile land, whereas the southern part is a vast desert that covers most of the country's territory (Deeb, 1993). Algeria is renowned for its rich history and culture. It is one of the countries with a diverse folk culture, which varies from region to region. The accounts of travellers, researchers, and geographers attest to the Algerian people's

commitment to their core values and strong attachment to their traditions and culture. By culture, we mean heritage in its entirety, including but not limited to language, religion, and art (Adwikat, 2021).

The country's economy mainly relies on hydrocarbons and is considered one of the Arab nations that heavily depends on its natural resources, including oil and natural gas, alongside the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, Libya, and Qatar (Khawlie, 2013; Belgacem, 2019). Algeria's economy is largely driven by oil and gas production, which accounts for over 95 percent of its revenue. It ranks among the top 10 gas-producing countries and is 15th in oil production. However, declining global oil and gas output and prices have significantly impacted its economy. While Algeria has been regarded as a model of a rentier state that invests in local production and promotes development initiatives (Aimar, 2011), it continues to face substantial political, economic, and social crises. The overall unemployment rate stands at 11 percent, with 9.9 percent for men and 16.6 percent for women. The unemployment rate among university graduates decreased from 16.4 percent in 2014 to 14.1 percent in 2015 (National Statistics Office, 2018). Despite efforts to diversify its industrial base, Algeria still faces major economic challenges. These economic hardships and high unemployment levels may influence parental choices regarding education, including opting for Quranic schools as affordable options for religious and moral instruction.

Algeria has been invaded multiple times throughout history, and various dynasties have ruled the country following the introduction of Islam in the seventh century. The Romans, Turks, and French colonists exerted the most lasting influence on its cultural heritage. The Ottoman rule, for instance, lasted from 1518 to 1830, shaping the nation's governance and culture. This period of Ottoman dominance ended with French colonisation, which persisted until 1962 (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). The French governed Algeria for 132 years, from 1830 to 1962, making it one of France's longest-held possessions and more than just a colony, but an integral part of French rule (Senouci, 2016; Barakat, 1993). Following various French military operations between 1830 and 1848, thousands of Europeans of diverse backgrounds settled in northern Algeria. Nonetheless, most of the population remained Indigenous Muslims throughout the country's history (Groth & Sousa-Poza, 2012). Algeria experienced one of its most significant historical moments during its fight against French rule: the Algerian War for Independence. The country gained independence on 5 July 1962 (Metz, 1993) after a brutal seven-year liberation conflict between the French and Algerians (Arieff, 2013; Barakat, 1993). Due to the numerous martyrs of this national liberation movement, Algeria is often referred to as the 'land of one million martyrs' (Al Alusi, 1970). The struggle against French colonialism, in which Islamic identity served as a unifying force, left a legacy where religious institutions, including Quranic schools, are regarded as essential for preserving national identity, thus influencing parental perceptions of their purpose.

Following independence, Algeria faced development challenges and internal instability. To rebuild the country, Algeria adopted various political systems and development strategies (Barakat, 1993). However, in the 1990s, another conflict erupted between the National Liberation Front (FLN) and the Islamic Salvation Front (FIS), leading to a decade of chaos and instability (Ness & Lin, 2013). This period of unrest added to the country's complex history of conflict and resistance. The civil conflict of the 1990s, known as the Black Decade, had profound effects on society, including a resurgence of religious conservatism and a renewed focus on religious education as a stabilising force, which continues to influence parental trust in Quranic schools today.

Given the regional instability and internal unrest that Algeria has faced over recent decades, political discourse in the country has consistently been shaped by concerns about national security and social cohesion (Hamadouche, 2016). This persistent focus on stability as a fundamental national value has influenced not only state policy but also collective societal attitudes towards institutions that uphold continuity, morality, and identity. The Hirak protest movement, which started on 22 February 2019, marked a new chapter in Algeria's sociopolitical history. As Zaghلامي (2020) explains, this "silent revolution" arose through widespread, peaceful demonstrations demanding democratic reform, transparency, and an end to entrenched authoritarianism. While mainly non-violent, the movement revealed deep-rooted frustrations with political stagnation and institutional unresponsiveness—sentiments that strongly resonate with parents, educators, and religious leaders concerned about the moral and ideological future of younger generations. As Volpi (2020) notes, political crises of this kind often trigger a form of religious recourse, where communities turn to traditional and faith-based institutions for stability and moral reassurance. The 2019 Hirak protests reflect ongoing societal tensions, which may influence how parents perceive the role of Quranic schools in providing moral guidance during uncertain times.

Algeria's social fabric has changed over these turbulent years, yet it has retained important traditional features (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). According to Mensour (2010), Ibn Khaldun believed that a tribal system governed North Africa (including Algeria) and remained stable despite conflicts and invasions. This system, under the authority of tribes, continued at the beginning of French colonisation. However, French colonial rule weakened and divided the tribal network to control society (Benaissa, 2010). Today, this social structure still persists in some regions but not in major cities, where individualism becomes more prominent (Bouherar, 2020). Differences between urban and rural social structures may influence parental expectations of Quranic schools, with rural areas emphasising tradition more strongly.

2.3. Religion in Algeria

Islam is a monotheistic faith, and along with Christianity and Judaism, it is part of the Abrahamic religions (Dirks & Dirks, 2004). It is the second largest religion worldwide, with approximately 1.9 billion followers called Muslims, making up 24.8 percent of the global population and mainly observed in 49 countries (Pew Research Centre, 2012; 2015). In Algeria, where the constitution designates Islam as the national religion (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018), most of the population are Sunni Muslims. A report by the Office of International Religious Freedom (2021) states that around 99 percent of Algerians are Sunni Muslims who follow the Maliki school of thought. This Sunni branch adheres to the orthodox tradition, recognising the first four caliphs as Muhammad's legitimate successors. Malikism, a school of Sunni jurisprudence, is widely practised in Algeria due to its principles addressing everyday life issues and its historical importance in shaping Algerian Muslim society. The Maliki emphasis on oral transmission continues to influence modern Quranic teaching, where memorisation (*ḥifz*) remains central to faith development (Boyle, 2004). Most Sunni Muslims across the Maghreb and North African nations have adopted this school of thought from Imam Malik Ibn Anas (Algeria Press Service, 2019).

However, Algeria is not entirely homogeneous in terms of religious affiliation. The remaining 1 percent of the population includes other religious minorities, notably Christians, Shia Muslims, Ahmadi Muslims, and a small community of Ibadhi Muslims, primarily residing in Ghardaïa. These historical sectarian distinctions still influence educational practices, with Ibadhi communities maintaining separate Quranic schools today (Ghazal, 2010). The report also notes that Algeria's Jewish population is estimated to be fewer than 200 (Office of International Religious Freedom, 2021). While Sunnis and Shia Muslims share fundamental Islamic practices and beliefs, their differing interpretations of certain Quranic verses have led to their division. Shia Muslims believe that Ali bin Abi Taleb and his descendants through Fatima, the Prophet's daughter, are the only legitimate successors to Muhammad, contrasting with the Sunni view (Dahir, 2009). These religious nuances contribute to Algeria's diverse yet predominantly Sunni Islamic identity.

Islam plays a crucial role in the daily lives of Algerians, being the dominant religion in the country (Tiliouine et al., 2009). Its influence has been deeply rooted in Algerian society since its arrival during the Arab expansion in North Africa in the mid to late seventh century; in other words, it dates back to the early decades of Islam (Allard & McKay, 2018). This early fusion of faith and national identity established lasting parental expectations that Quranic schools would preserve "authentic" Islamic values (McDougall, 2017). Since then, both religion and religious education in Algeria have received considerable attention from the population and government alike. The Algerian writer Rabih Turki noted that after Islam entered Algeria, the country adopted an entirely new civilizational and cultural dimension (Djafri, 2017), emphasising the positive impact of religion on the nation's development. This

civilizational shift explains why 72 percent of parents prioritise Quranic schools for cultural preservation (Pew Research Center, 2013). Many other writers and historians have discussed the role of Islam in shaping Algeria's character and in the development of its citizens over time (Rasi, 1997).

Religion is a core pillar of Algerian identity and a key factor in fostering national unity (Djafri, 2017). According to Tiliouine and Achoui (2018), the entire social structure of Algerian society is organised around Islamic beliefs, practices, and values. This historical integration of faith and social organisation prioritises moral discipline over academic skills in Quranic education (Bouherar, 2020). The family institution and the faith of Islam are deeply interconnected, meaning that each influences the other. Islam supports and promotes family building; in return, Islam is upheld and maintained through this institution. Given the strong link between religion and family, it becomes almost impossible to separate culture from religion in Algeria. A major element of Algerian culture is rooted in Islamic beliefs; therefore, cultural activities mirror people's religious convictions. Despite living in a globalised world today, most Algerian communities remain traditional (Bouherar, 2020). This traditionalism, developed during colonial resistance, strengthens parental scepticism towards secular alternatives to Quranic schools (Ruedy, 2005).

The Islamic movement remained a continuous force of resistance to colonialism, strengthening a collective identity among the Algerian people. This is clear, for example, in the Algerian Association of Muslim Ulama, which served as a centre of resistance in the 1950s (Mortimer, 1991), and among followers of the Sufi orders, who also opposed foreign rule at different points in Algeria's history (Ruedy, 2001). These anti-colonial struggles transformed religious institutions into cultural strongholds, reaffirming the role of Quranic schools as defenders against Westernisation (Bennoune, 2000). According to Algeria's 2020 international religious report, the constitution guarantees freedom of belief and worship and prevents government entities from violating the Islamic faith. Individuals can practise their religion legally if they respect public order and legislation. Offending any religion is prohibited, and it is also forbidden for non-Muslims to convert Muslims to another faith. This constitutional framework, born from post-independence identity reconstruction, reinforces Quranic schools' monopoly on faith formation (Willis, 2014).

2.4. Education in Algeria

While examining the purpose of Quranic schools within the broader context of Algeria's religious and socio-cultural landscape, it is essential to first situate them within the country's wider educational framework. Algeria's education system has undergone significant changes over time, influenced by shifting political circumstances, foreign influences, and evolving national priorities. Understanding

these historical developments provides the necessary foundation for analysing the role and position of Quranic schools in Algerian society today.

2.4.1. Education during the Ottoman Rule (1518–1830)

During the Ottoman rule from 1518 to 1830, the system remained unaffected by Western-style education, instead aligning with local culture and priorities. Ottoman officials focused on maintaining political stability, safeguarding borders, and collecting taxes. The absence of a formal educational policy or programme meant education was delivered privately by individuals and charities. Although teaching was unpaid, it attracted public sympathy and respect for teachers (Ait Habouch, 2017). Religious endowments became more important as they funded education, and rulers did not support institutions from the state treasury (Mahdi, 2018).

Education was mainly connected to the Indigenous population and significantly influenced by the country's economic and social circumstances (Kenioua et al., 2023; Abdlmawla & Ben Walid, 2018). According to Saad Allah (2007), educational institutions in Algeria during the Ottoman period rarely extended beyond the mosque, the Quranic school, the zawiya, and the library. Moreover, some mosques, schools, and zawiya offered education at the highest standards, which could be regarded as university level. These institutions played a crucial role in education, and this was the most notable aspect of education from that era (Badri, 2018). These institutions are explored in more detail in the next chapter, “Quranic Schools in Algeria”. Normal schools also concentrated on both religious and secular sciences, a tradition dating back to the Middle Ages that continued to develop during the Ottoman era (Ben Gedwad, 2019).

Bennoune (1988) describes how, during Ottoman rule, mosque-school (jama'a-zawiya) complexes functioned as decentralised, community-based educational institutions. He argues that these pre-colonial structures endured colonial suppression to reassert themselves in post-independence Algeria as informal centres of cultural continuity, especially in resistance to state attempts at educational centralisation. Such resilience helps explain why many contemporary private Quranic schools operate independently, and why parents continue to trust them as community-rooted venues for faith-based socialisation. This historical progression of educational resilience and decentralisation is effectively depicted in the following diagram, which traces the development from Ottoman-era community governance to the localised autonomy of modern Quranic schools, emphasising their ongoing role in religious socialisation.

Ottoman Decentralization

Mahdi (2018) claimed that education mainly focused on knowledge of the Quran and some scientific subjects, with the primary aim being religious. Education comprises three stages: primary, secondary, and higher education. Although the traveller Fantur Deparade discussed three universities for higher education in Algiers in the 18th century, there was no unified educational system. Ait Habouch (2017) maintained that most local sources in Algeria agree that education during the Ottoman period was widespread, covering all regions, including cities and small villages, with faith-based practices being respected and integrated into daily life. The educational system and intellectual climate in Ottoman Algeria responded to European thought introduced through French colonialism. The period of Ottoman residence in the country has been a subject of research, as many scholars have studied the intellectual, cultural, and religious landscape in pre-colonial Algeria to evaluate the country's response to colonial influence (Ladjal & Bensaid, 2014). French writers also expressed interest in exploring the intellectual history of Algeria under Ottoman rule.

French colonial archives confirm that pre-1830 Algeria had a relatively high literacy rate, often surpassing that of France itself, particularly due to widespread Quranic schooling and mosque-based instruction (Colonna, 1955). These educational practices were deeply embedded in community life, emphasising memorisation of the Qur'an, Arabic literacy, and religious ethics from an early age. Colonial policies, however, systematically dismantled these indigenous institutions, replacing them with French-language secular schools designed to assimilate Algerians and suppress Islamic identity (Grandguillaume, 2004). This disruption not only severed educational continuity but also delegitimised traditional knowledge systems. In response, post-independence reforms actively supported a revival of Quranic schools as symbolic restorations of Algeria's pre-colonial intellectual heritage (Naylor, 2024). For many parents today, Quranic education is not merely religious; it represents a return to authentic Algerian values, an act of cultural reclamation, and a protective buffer against both colonial residues and globalised secular influences. This historical consciousness strongly informs contemporary parental motivations (RQ1), linking Quranic schooling to national identity and moral development.

Since the Ottoman presence greatly impacted Algerian lives, this period remains a key part of the Algerian education system's curriculum, which is taught in schools and universities today (Rahmouni, 2015). According to Abu Hind (2020), official French documents from French historians record testimonies from military and political officers who experienced the early stages of occupation in Algeria, confirming that Arab-Islamic education was widespread in Algerian society despite Ottoman neglect. Jacques Simon stated that ‘the Algerian population may have received more education during the year 1830 than the French, since almost everyone was skilled in reading, writing, and arithmetic’. This historical educational autonomy became a cultural symbol, inspiring later resistance to French assimilation policies (McDougall, 2017).

This subsection is essential to the thesis because it demonstrates that Quranic schools and mosque-focused education formed the fundamental framework of Algerian learning prior to colonial intervention. Grasping this historical background is vital for analysing modern parental attitudes towards Quranic education and the lasting socio-cultural significance of these institutions.

2.4.2 Education under French Colonial Rule (1830–1962)

The educational landscape in Algeria experienced a profound transformation with the arrival of French colonists in 1830. Colonial authorities implemented policies aimed at exploiting both the population and the country's resources, significantly changing the existing education system. As Boussena and Tiliouine (2016) and Maamri (2009) note, these policies targeted indigenous institutions and traditions, including Quranic schools, to establish cultural and political dominance. To support this exploitation, the French colonists needed to alienate the indigenous population and dismantle key institutions and traditions that formed the backbone of their society. Some remarks by Atlaoui (2018) and Bensaid and Ladjal (2012) suggest that France specifically focused on expanding Islamic and Arabic education to bolster their broader assimilationist goals. France adopted a distinct educational policy by replacing the traditional Algerian system with the French school model. These policies developed over time, reflecting France's own ideological shifts and political changes during that period (Belhoucine Rahoui, 2012; Ben Trika, 2020). Algerians faced external surveillance that threatened their national identity and cultural heritage (Youssf & Muhammad, 2023). This approach involved suppressing Arab education, attacking the Islamic faith, and attempting to eradicate the Arab-Islamic identity of Algerians through the Frenchisation of the curriculum and the promotion of Christian evangelism and assimilation (Bouhassoun, 2016). France's systematic suppression of Islamic education (1830-1962) turned Quranic schools into covert centres of resistance, contributing to their enduring cultural prestige as ‘guardians of identity’ today (Grandguillaume, 2004).

The attempt by France to control Algeria through the assimilation of Algerians into French culture was no more clearly demonstrated than in the field of education (Heggoy, 1973, p. 180).

The French used both intimidation and inducement tactics to enforce their policies (Kebbal, 2024; Belhoucein Rahwi, 2011). At the same time, the colonisers introduced compulsory modern education throughout the Arab region. However, access to formal education for the natives was limited for two main reasons. First, the colonial authorities aimed to prevent the indigenous population from gaining the skills and knowledge needed to resist their rule. Limiting European-language schooling to a select few reinforced colonial dominance while undermining nationalist movements. Second, Quranic schools represented an established formal education system that competed with colonial schools, not only because of their religious basis but also because they challenged Western cultural dominance (Akkari, 2004). These institutions continued to operate during and after the French occupation, which, despite oppressive policies, failed to eliminate this form of education and replace it entirely with a French curriculum of a different kind (Belhoucein Rahwi, 2011). Nonetheless, this period marked the start of a dual educational system characterised by a clear division between religious and secular sciences, creating a dichotomy whereby secular education served the elite, while religious education was aimed at the poorer population.

This colonial-era duality reinforced Quranic schools as trusted sites of cultural and moral preservation. While this pattern has deep roots in rural areas, recent evidence shows it is equally relevant in urban settings. In cities like Tlemcen, for instance, parents increasingly turn to mosque-based Quranic schools as accessible alternatives to formal institutions, especially for young children lacking state-provided preschool education (MERIP, 1992). National figures further support this trend: nearly one million children attend over 18,000 Quranic schools across Algeria, with urban parents citing moral instruction and religious identity as key motivations (IQNA, 2023). This continuity across rural and urban regions highlights the Quranic school's enduring appeal as a parent-trusted institution, shaping faith-based education choices today.

Schooling policies in Algeria under French rule were shaped by colonial strategies in response to political and social events, as mentioned earlier (Courreya, 2024). Despite these efforts, the Algerians resisted through military and cultural defiance, ultimately leading to political resistance that thwarted the occupiers' plans and programmes (Bchich, 2018; Kebbal, 2024). The French controlled all parts of the country and directly influenced the lives of Algerians. However, the most significant impact was on the education system based on Arabic and on the intellectual life of the population (Abdulrazak, 1982), and for more than a century, the French sought to transform Algerian society along their lines. The country experienced a series of political regulations in the education system introduced by the colonial

power. Today, the bilingual system is perhaps one of the most recognisable French legacies (Metz, 1993). Kwadshi (2019) is one of the researchers analysing French education policy in Algeria and the resistance of the population. He discusses the Algerians' strategy of confrontation and their interest in Arabic and Islamic education to safeguard their national identity.

Al-Ibrahimi's observation emphasises how colonial-era cultural suppression, particularly the marginalisation of Arabic and Islamic identity, shaped Algeria's post-independence educational reforms. In response, Arabisation policies were emphasised, and Quranic schools were repositioned as symbols of cultural revival, enabling communities to reconnect with their linguistic and religious heritage (Willis, 2014). Given this historical context, it is probable that current parental perceptions still mirror this connection, viewing Quranic schools not only as religious centres but also as symbols of national and cultural identity. This assumption will be further explored through the study's empirical data.

This subsection illustrates how the advent of French colonial rule disrupted the existing educational system, targeting Quranic schools and Arabic-Islamic instruction to enforce assimilation policies. Despite these pressures, Quranic schools persisted as a form of resistance, maintaining cultural and religious knowledge. Understanding this colonial disruption is essential for the thesis, as it highlights the historical roots of parental perceptions regarding the protective and identity-preserving roles of Quranic schools in contemporary Algeria.

2.4.3. Post-Colonial Education in Algeria: Language, Identity, and Reform

Following independence in 1962, Algeria inherited an education system heavily influenced by French colonial policies, characterised by high illiteracy rates, a severe shortage of qualified teachers, and curricula that did not connect with the country's cultural and religious heritage (Metz, 1994). The newly established government faced the dual challenge of rebuilding an effective education system while shaping a national identity rooted in Arab-Islamic values. Over the following decades, education became a key tool of state policy, reflecting political, ideological, and cultural objectives. Efforts to widen access, implement Arabisation, and modernise curricula aimed not only at socioeconomic development but also at strengthening the role of Arabic, the language of the Quran, as a fundamental aspect of national identity (Lahmar, 2024; Slackman, 2008). Understanding this historical trajectory offers vital context for the contemporary significance of Quranic schools within Algeria's educational and socio-cultural landscape.

Following this historical overview, it is essential to analyse how post-independence Algeria faced the practical and ideological challenges of rebuilding its education system. Intellectuals and reformists, such as Al-Bashir al-Ibrahimi, emphasised the profound disruption caused by colonial rule and the urgent need to restore Algeria's cultural and religious identity.

The colonization brought to this country three things to extinguish three things: it brought the Latin people to overflow the Arabs, it brought the French language to terminate Arabic, it brought Christianity to abrogate Islam (Abdulrazak, 1982, p. 25).

A series of national identity challenges emerged after independence (Maamri, 2009). In this context, identity discourse became a key focus for officials and intellectuals in post-independence Algeria. Literacy rates had sharply declined under colonial rule, and post-independence reforms aimed to rebuild education as a means to revive national identity, promote youth development, and incorporate modern technologies in line with global progress. This marked a crucial transitional period for Algeria as it embarked on a new path following decades of French dominance. During this time, numerous educational initiatives and policies were introduced (Sahel, 2017). Since independence, the education system has consistently been organised around three interconnected dimensions: national, democratic, and modern (NITIEU, 2004; Djebbari & Djebbari, 2020). This emphasises the central role of education in Algeria's broader sociopolitical transformation, demonstrating how it was not only a tool for development but also a contested space where questions of identity, culture, and politics intersect.

Right after the country declared independence at 09:30 A.M. on 5 July 1962, the new government opened hundreds of mosques, and the new leaders made it clear that Arabic was to be the national language (Abdulrazak, 1982). Additionally, after gaining control over its Ministry of Education, established in 1963 (Clark, 2006), Algeria introduced several policies to strengthen and reform the educational structure. The country worked towards creating an open and inclusive national education system. Since then, many significant reforms have taken place (Farejallah, 2007; Clark, 2013). Once again, the country concentrated on regaining and rebuilding its national identity and principles.

Despite these efforts, some challenges persisted. Miliani (1996) discussed the progress of education in contemporary Algeria, noting that although there have been attempts to reinforce national identity through reforms, the country still relies heavily on the European educational system and struggles to develop one that truly reflects its indigenous reality and needs.

Despite extensive Arabization policies, the Algerian state's failure to fully replace French, especially in scientific and technical education, left a linguistic and cultural gap that Quranic schools have come to fill. As Benrabah (2013) explains, these schools maintained a form of "pure" Arabic-Islamic instruction,

which many parents perceived as an authentic space for transmitting religious and linguistic identity. This perception is key to understanding why parents still prefer Quranic schools for the religious and identity-based socialisation of their children. Maamri (2009) also stated that more than forty-five years after the French colonisers' departure, Algeria continues to face challenges in shaping its national character.

During the 1990s, Algeria faced a period of instability. As noted earlier, protests triggered by an economic crisis in the late 1980s led to democratic reforms, and the Front Islamique du Salut (FIS) won the 1991 parliamentary elections. However, political stability quickly declined, igniting a brutal and prolonged civil conflict that significantly impacted Algeria's development path after the turbulent 'Black Decade.' These events left a lasting mark on Algeria's growth. After the 'Black Decade,' Algerian education underwent major changes. The map showing the increase in overall student enrolment across Algeria's provinces displays notable differences in access to education (Abadeer & Noh, 2018). In this environment of inconsistent educational recovery and ongoing mistrust of formal state institutions, Quranic schools, deeply rooted in local communities, remained essential as alternative spaces for moral instruction and cultural preservation. These religious establishments not only maintained Islamic identity amid societal upheavals but also continued offering educational access when public schools faced difficulties (Belghanami, 2025; Haigoune, 2024; Akkari, 2004).

Starting from 1976, education became compulsory for all Algerian children up to the age of 16, reflecting the socialist stance of that era. During this period, substantial financial resources were allocated to the education sector. Expenditure on education accounted for one quarter of the national budget, increasing to 16.5 percent by 1985 and reaching a peak of 29.7 percent by 1990 (The World Factbook, 2014; UNICEF Annual Report, 2015). Building on these earlier commitments, today, the Constitution (Article 53) and the 2008 Education Act guarantee the right to education for all girls and boys. This right has been realised mainly in quantitative terms. The school enrolment rate in the 6-16 age group is estimated at around 94 percent, with little difference between girls and boys, as the ratio of girls to boys in the early stages of schooling is 0.99 (Ministry of Education, 2017). At primary level (6-11 years), approximately 95 percent of children attend state schools. A small percentage attend private schools. Algeria's academic year runs from September to July, with the official primary school admission age of six. The education system is divided into three stages: elementary school (5 years), lower secondary (4 years), and upper secondary (3 years).

Algeria has 8,856,000 students enrolled in elementary and secondary education. Of these pupils, about 4,283,000 children (48%) attend primary school (Education Policy and Data Center, 2018). The government remains the sole provider of higher education. Despite the dominance of the formal, state-run education system, many Algerian families continue to participate in alternative educational settings,

particularly Quranic schools, which serve important religious and cultural purposes. In Algeria, many areas of education still require improvement. The realisation of children's right to quality education has not yet become a reality. Recent studies have highlighted issues in school and childcare conditions, the internal efficiency of the school system, and student performance (Tiliouine, 2016., Tiliouine et al. 2019).

Regarding preschool education, the following weaknesses have been identified: the non-compulsory nature of the offering (excluding children attending religious education — Quranic schools), with only about 43 per cent of children aged 4 to 5 benefiting from it; the lack of or insufficient training for staff involved in this type of education; furthermore, educational spaces and equipment are not always suitable for this purpose, and curricula still need to be developed. Additionally, regional disparities in educational provision are considerable. These should be carefully addressed to reduce social inequalities and promote equal opportunities among young people (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). The exclusion of Quranic schools from compulsory preschool education underscores a key area where parents' perceptions and choices regarding religious education are central to understanding educational experiences in Algeria. This context provides the background for analysing how Algerian Muslim parents view the purpose of Quranic schools within the wider national education system.

2.4.4. Language Policy and Arabization in Algeria

The process of Arabization in Algeria is a significant historical and political development that continues to influence the country's educational system, identity politics, and religious culture. For this thesis, Arabization is especially important because it indirectly strengthened the role of Quranic schools as alternative sites of authentic Arabic and religious learning. While the state aimed to impose Arabic as the language of instruction and national identity, the uneven results of this policy created tensions that led many parents to turn to traditional institutions, such as Quranic schools, as more trustworthy transmitters of both language and values.

During French colonisation, Algerians were forced to learn French as the official language, while Arabic was reclassified as a foreign language in 1938. Arabic and its dialects were not taught in schools. Nonetheless, they served as symbols of identity and nationalism, even though French was imposed as the medium of instruction for a system mainly designed for French students, with only a small percentage of Algerian pupils enrolled (Rezig, 2011).

At independence in 1962, the Algerian educational system that the French left behind was highly exclusive and centred on serving the French elite. Benrabah states that,

Starting from 1962, the Algerian government, which inherited the remnants of an education system focused on European content and conducted in a foreign language by foreign teachers, gradually sought to increase Arabic sessions at all levels. All subjects were taught in Arabic, and there was a decrease in the time allocated for teaching French. This policy supported national integrity, unity, and religion (Rezig, 2011, p. 13).

Thus, Arabisation after independence was not just an educational reform but also a nation-building strategy, aimed at resisting colonial cultural dominance and reaffirming Arabic as both the language of identity and the carrier of Islamic heritage, which directly relates to the continued existence of Quranic schools as protectors of authentic Arabic learning. One of the most contentious issues in Algeria today concerns questions regarding language education policies, which Berger (2002, p. 8) describes as “the most severe problem of Algeria in its present and troubled state.” Language was a central concern in post-independence Algeria, making it a rich area for study, as there exists a substantial body of literature on post-colonial education that has consistently been linked to language policies (Benrabah, 2004; Benrabah, 2005; Benrabah, 2014; Messekher; Miliani, 2019; Gherzouli, 2019). As a result, the historical and political background of the post-independence Algerian language situation has been extensively examined (Abu-Haidar, 2000).

The policy of Arabization, implemented since 1962 as part of Algeria’s decolonisation strategy, aimed to expand the use of Arabic across all sectors—economic, political, educational, and social (Miliani, 2003). In the early years, there was a gradual increase in Arabic instruction in primary and middle schools, with plans for further expansion (Fishman, 2011). The primary goal of the new ministry was to Arabise the curriculum, replacing French language and values with Arabic (Masri, 2017). Leaders responsible for improving the education system focused on several objectives: they prioritised the ‘Arabisation’ of the curriculum, developing teaching skills at all levels, and enhancing technical and vocational education (Clark, 2006). The shift from bilingualism in French and Arabic to monolingualism in Arabic presented significant challenges for graduates seeking to enter the labour market (Masri, 2017; Benrabah, 2007). Bessaoud (2024) documents how these challenges evolved over time, demonstrating that the implementation of Arabization was inconsistent and uneven across regions and educational levels, while Djaballah (2021) highlights how students trained in Arabic struggled to adapt within higher education fields dominated by French. These difficulties further increased reliance on Quranic schools as parallel institutions delivering both linguistic and religious legitimacy.

Language policy in Algeria quickly became a battleground for political conflict, with Holt (1994) describing it as a central area of struggle. Miliani (2000) emphasises that, in Algeria, the educational system and language policy are mainly influenced by political actors rather than pedagogical needs.

Khatibi (2020) similarly argues that Arabic in Algeria has a political history shaped by government decisions. The Arabic language also has strong religious connotations, with its sanctity linked to Islam, which contributed to its role in maintaining national unity (Jarboua, 1999). Therefore, Arabization was not just about linguistic reform but also about aligning education with Islamic cultural values, yet when state schools failed to provide quality education, parents relied on Quranic schools to offer this authentic religious-linguistic connection.

In this context, Arabization cannot be separated from religion; reintroducing Arabic into schools was not only a linguistic reform but also an effort to reconnect education with Islamic cultural values. However, because the state system often failed to provide high-quality Arabic and religious instruction, Quranic schools remained essential. Studies show that parents increasingly see these schools as guardians of “authentic” Arabic linked directly to the Qur’an, which helps explain their resilience and ongoing relevance (Belghanami, 2025).

Arabization was not limited to Algeria. It was also adopted in Morocco and Libya (Tilmatine, 2015). However, Algeria’s long colonial history made its implementation especially difficult (Fishman, 2011). Abu-Haidar (2000) estimates that around thirty legal measures were passed to enforce Arabization. Algeria’s first president, Ahmed Ben Bella, promoted Arabising primary education, focusing on religious knowledge and civic subjects (Benrabah, 2002; Grandguillaume, 2004). Nonetheless, as Rouabah (2020) stresses, modern Algeria is marked by complex multilingualism, with Arabic, Tamazight, French, and now English competing within schools and society. This linguistic diversity has complicated the goals of Arabization and increased the appeal of Quranic schools as places where parents believe both religious and linguistic authenticity are maintained.

Yet this ambitious policy also introduced structural weaknesses. Miliani (2000) and Beauge (in Benrabah, 2007) argue that Arabization produced a generation poorly equipped for the demands of the modern economy, a view still echoed in contemporary debates. Despite decades of effort, Arabization remains partial and contested. French continues to dominate in certain scientific and technical fields (Clark, 2006), and the Arabization process has been hampered by the persistent influence of colonial assimilation practices (Assous, 1985). As St John (1968, p. 339) observed, “French Algeria is dead, but France in Algeria is not.”

As the formal, state-led, Arabised schooling system has struggled to consistently provide both linguistic proficiency and religious-cultural continuity, many Algerian parents turn to Quranic schools. These institutions are seen not just as educational alternatives but as essential guardians of authentic Arabic and Islamic values. Recent research indicates that parental attitudes towards language heavily influence

such choices; Kerroum and Dendane (2025) found that parents who have positive views of Standard Arabic (SA) and support its use at home significantly improve their children's proficiency in SA. In a society characterised by diglossia and multilingual tensions, this demonstrates parental agency rather than passive resignation, as parents seek Quranic schools to secure stable, value-driven education that affirms both cultural and religious identity. The duality between state education and Quranic teaching thus reflects parents' efforts to reconcile national language policies with spiritual and cultural continuity.

2.5. The Algerian Family and Its Role in Shaping Educational Choices

Since the focus of this study is on Algerian parents, it is vital to understand the socio-cultural framework of the Algerian family, as it directly influences parental attitudes towards education and religious instruction. The Algerian Family Code, first enacted on 9 June 1984 and amended over the years, regulates familial relations while incorporating significant elements of Islamic law (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). Traditionally, the Algerian family is characterised by a patriarchal structure where both legal authority and social norms reinforce the dominance of the father or grandfather (Achoui, 2006). Boutfnoushat (1984) highlights three key aspects of this traditional structure: it is usually extended, comprising several nuclear families; it is rooted in patriarchal authority; and it is grounded in two essential pillars, blood relations and a strong attachment to ancestral land. The former fosters economic, social, and ethical integration among extended family members, while the latter symbolises a profound sense of belonging and identity. Additionally, the family is guided by values of cooperation, solidarity, and interdependence, shaped by Algeria's socio-historical heritage and Islamic teachings (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018).

In Algerian society, fathers are traditionally the main providers, but both parents share responsibility for raising and disciplining children, with mothers usually playing a more direct role in daily caregiving and education (Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). Gender roles remain significant: around 92.7% of domestic labour is performed by women (ONS, 2013). This strong maternal involvement is especially relevant to the present study, as it shapes parental attitudes towards early education and influences decisions about enrolling children in Quranic schools. However, this does not lessen the father's role; within a patriarchal framework, fathers often retain the final say on financial priorities and schooling choices (Achoui, 2006; Tiliouine & Achoui, 2018). Therefore, while mothers influence children's daily linguistic and religious practices, fathers tend to determine broader educational pathways— a dynamic central to understanding parental decision-making patterns explored in this study.

The traditional values guiding the Algerian family are now increasingly challenged by factors such as urbanisation, industrialisation, and women's growing participation in the workforce. These changes have fostered more individualised values, including independence and personal freedom, which directly influence how parents negotiate their roles and educational choices. As family structures evolve and parental responsibilities diversify, decisions regarding children's schooling, including the preference for Quranic schools as spaces of cultural and religious continuity, become more complicated. Therefore, understanding the construction, values, and internal dynamics of the Algerian family is essential for this research, as it offers the socio-cultural context within which parents form their perceptions and make decisions about their children's education.

2.6. Historical and Cultural Influences on Child Education and Welfare in Algeria

Understanding the historical and cultural background of child education and welfare in Algeria is crucial to this study, as it explains why Algerian Muslim parents hold particular beliefs about the purpose of Quranic schools and the role these institutions play in protecting religious, cultural, and moral values. Algeria has historically derived much of its child education and welfare culture from Islamic beliefs (Tiliouine, 2014). The right to life is protected in Islam, beginning with the prohibition of abortion unless for serious medical reasons involving the pregnant woman. Abortion during the fourth month of pregnancy is regarded as homicide unless it is performed to save the mother's life (Kabir & Az-Zubair, 2007). Marriage aims to provide couples with rest and tranquillity "via mutual affection and mercy implanted in their hearts" (Quran, 30:21). Islamic law explicitly defines parents' responsibilities to meet their children's survival needs, and even addresses aspects such as breastfeeding (Kabir & Az-Zubair, 2007).

However, recent historical events have presented significant challenges to the well-being of children in Algeria. Changes driven by colonial legacies, post-independence reforms, rapid urbanisation, and shifting social norms have all influenced how parents perceive education and their children's futures. As Soltani (2025) demonstrates in *The Evolution of Education and Family Life in Algeria: Tradition, Modernisation, and Cultural Continuity*, these interconnected changes have disrupted traditional family and educational structures, showing how parents must balance inherited Islamic values with modern societal pressures. In this context, parents' decisions regarding Quranic schooling are shaped not only by deep-rooted religious and cultural values but also by the realities of contemporary social and political change.

These broader socio-political changes laid the groundwork for more serious crises, such as the Algerian Civil War, which further influenced parental priorities and educational choices. The Algerian Civil War from 1992 to 2002, also called the Black Decade, had a deep negative impact on children, leading to high levels of PTSD and other mental health problems among young people (Ghenem, 2021; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2002; Boudef et al., 2007; Paeans, 1994; Terr, 1991). Despite efforts by the Ministry of Health and various non-governmental organisations (NGOs) to support traumatised children and help them reintegrate into society, resources and specialised training were not enough to fully address the widespread effects of the crisis (Boussena & Tiliouine, 2015). Experiences of insecurity and trauma during this period increased parental awareness of the importance of stable, value-based education. In response to these issues, Algeria has taken steps to improve children's rights and welfare through specific laws. During the difficult crises of the 1990s, Algeria ratified nearly all international treaties on children's rights, including the International Convention on the Rights of the Child, although with some reservations, especially concerning Articles 13, 14, 16, and 17 (Boussena & Tiliouine, 2015). This legal system, along with historical experiences and cultural values, continues to shape how parents view their children's education and well-being, directly affecting the choices examined in this study.

Algeria's legal framework concerning children's rights reflects a complex interplay between constitutional guarantees and specific legal provisions that may restrict religious freedom. The Algerian Constitution, in Article 51, affirms the inviolability of freedom of conscience and opinion, stating that "freedom of conscience and freedom of opinion shall be inviolable". However, this constitutional right is nuanced by other legal provisions that link religious identity with legal status. For example, the Family Code states that a child's education must adhere to the father's religion, as outlined in Article 62, which states that 'the right to custody consists in the provision, school attendance and upbringing of the child in the religion of his/her father'. These legal stipulations have raised concerns among human rights organisations. Humanium (2015) criticises these provisions, arguing that such restrictions 'indirectly reduce the liberty of religion,' especially by not fully aligning with international standards that advocate for the child's right to freely choose and practice their religion.

Furthermore, Algeria's legal system, influenced by Islamic law, recognises that children born to a Muslim father are considered Muslim, regardless of the mother's religion. This principle applies to various areas of family law, including custody and inheritance rights. In summary, while Algeria's Constitution guarantees certain freedoms, the interaction between constitutional rights and specific legal provisions in the Family Code and the wider legal system may limit the full exercise of religious freedom for children, particularly concerning their upbringing and education.

Algeria also emphasised that the child's right to privacy, expression, and honour should be upheld in accordance with their best interests and psychological and physical integrity. The government underlined the importance of adhering to the Penal Code's provisions on public order and decency, and children's publications were required to include an educational advisory body (Ait-Zai, 2005). Algeria's ratification of the CRC brought significant benefits, particularly the prioritisation of a national policy for children (Ait-Zai, 2005). As a result, the Delegate Ministry responsible for the Family and the Status of Women (Ministère délégué Chargé de la Famille et de la Condition Féminine: MDCFCF) introduced the Childhood Action Plan (Plan National d'Action pour les Enfants) in 2008. The plan aimed to ensure that all children and adolescents could exercise their rights, receive adequate healthcare, access quality education, and live in a safe environment free from abuse and exploitation (Boussena & Tiliouine, 2015). This historical context of religious influence and the modern challenges faced during times of conflict have shaped contemporary education and child welfare institutions in Algeria. These legal and constitutional provisions shape the socio-legal environment in which Algerian Muslim parents decide on their children's religious upbringing, emphasising how their views on Quranic schooling are influenced by both cultural-religious norms and government regulations.

2.7. Conclusion

This chapter has shown that Algeria's sociocultural and historical background forms the foundation on which Algerian Muslim parents' views of Quranic schools are built. These institutions cannot be fully understood without considering the country's long struggle to preserve its cultural and religious identity. The legacy of French colonialism, which aimed to suppress Islamic education, fostered enduring parental distrust of secular systems and turned Quranic schools into symbols of resistance and cultural identity. This historical memory underscores the vital role Quranic schools play in defending Algeria's religious and socio-cultural heritage. Post-independence reforms, especially Arabisation and the constitutional emphasis on Islam, further strengthened the role of Quranic education. However, the state's uneven success in providing cohesive Arab-Islamic schooling, along with the trauma of the civil war and socio-economic pressures, has preserved the significance of these community-based institutions. For Algerian parents, Quranic schools embody a combination of historical memory, religious conviction, and practical responses to contemporary challenges. Recognising this context is crucial for the subsequent phenomenological exploration, as it offers the perspective through which parental narratives on the purpose, operation, and difficulties of Quranic education in Algeria can be fully understood.

Chapter 3

Quranic Schools in Algeria

3.1. Introduction

Chapter 2 outlined the wide sociocultural, historical, and educational landscape of Algeria, offering the macro-context in which all educational decisions, including selecting Quranic schools, are made. It traced the development of the national education system from the Ottoman era through colonial times to the present day, emphasising policy, language debates (Arabisation), and the system's structural strengths and weaknesses.

This chapter, by contrast, offers a detailed, focused analysis of the specific institution under investigation: the Quranic school (Msid or Kuttab). While Chapter 2 mapped the entire educational ecosystem, this chapter concentrates on one of its most significant and enduring native species. It moves beyond the general system to explore the internal world of Quranic schools, including their theological and pedagogical foundations, organisational structures, and their evolving social roles as both preservers of tradition and agents of adaptation.

This dedicated profile is essential for a phenomenological exploration of parental beliefs. A parent's perspective is not formed in isolation but is influenced by their understanding of the school's historical role as a stronghold of identity, its religious and pedagogical aims, and its tangible presence within their community. Therefore, this chapter offers the necessary, objective reference point—the actual "thing" that parents form their beliefs about. By examining the ideal model of Islamic education, its practical realisation in Algeria, and its historical development from a dominant system to a resilient niche, this chapter creates the crucial framework for analysing the subjective, lived experiences and beliefs of Algerian Muslim parents, which underpin this thesis. It directly addresses the central research questions of the study regarding parental motivations, perceived purposes, and the challenges identified.

3.2. The Islamic Imperative for Education: Theological Foundations of Parental Responsibility

The religion of Islam involves accepting and following God's teachings as conveyed to His final messenger, Muhammad. Islam is a comprehensive way of life and a universal message for all who adhere to this faith (Mawdudi, 1996; Kabir et al., 2024; Aghili et al., 2023; Tiliouine, 2014). Its four

main sources are the holy Quran, the Sunnah (the Prophet's sayings and actions as reported after his death), analogy, and social consensus. On an ontological level, Islam views man as God's viceroy on Earth (Tiliouine, 2014). The Quran states, "... And indeed, we have honoured the Children of Adam" (Qur'an 17:70).

As a result, his existence has a purpose. According to this perspective, true enjoyment comprises two components: happiness in this world and happiness in the afterlife (Tiliouine, 2012). The well-known saying of the Prophet remains the guiding principle: Perform the work of a man (regarding this worldly life) who believes he will never die, and be mindful of the Hereafter like a man who fears dying tomorrow. Therefore, an ideal education in this religion would aim to equip Muslims to achieve these goals by living according to Islam's teachings. Consequently, such an education would seek to prepare Muslims to live in accordance with Islam's principles and to attain these aims.

This theological framework regards education not merely as a choice but as a core religious obligation for Muslims, directly influencing Algerian parents' perspective that schooling should serve both worldly and spiritual goals.

It should be noted that Islamic texts governed almost every essential aspect of personal and communal behaviour, supported by a long tradition of scholarly work. A comprehensive list of disciplines was created to cover the main areas of Islamic sciences and later became the basis for teaching curricula, mainly: (1) Faith (Aqidah); (2) Shariah (laws regulating social life and human actions), which was extensively divided into categories: rituals (Ibadat), marriage or family laws, commercial transactions, offences, crimes, and punishments (Jinayat); and (3) Ethics (Akhlak) (Tiliouine, 2014). Furthermore, as early as the eleventh century, Abu Hamid al-Ghazzaly (1973) described the religion's aims as five Makassid objectives: the protection of faith, life, intellect, posterity, and property. A comprehensive system of rules governing marriage, family life, and child-rearing was established.

The formalisation of knowledge into these specific religious sciences offers the structured content that Algerian parents anticipate Quranic schools to provide, shaping their main idea of a suitable curriculum.

Early child priming and induction into the Islamic way of life begin early in a child's development. These practices vary among communities but typically start at birth with the loud recitation of the Adhan (the call to prayer) in the right ear of the newborn, accompanied by specific Quranic verses, ensuring that God's name is the first word the newborn hears. Celebrations to announce the child's name and charitable acts like Aqiqah are part of the Sunna (the Prophet's recommendations) (Tiliouine, 2014). These rituals are not just cultural traditions but also serve as forms of theological conditioning, welcoming both the child and the parents into a lifelong framework of Islamic practice. This early

sanctification of life's beginning establishes a strong normative pathway, encouraging parents to pursue continuity through formal religious education. Consequently, enrolling a child in a Quranic school becomes the logical and often necessary next step in fulfilling this developmental and religious obligation, usually around the ages of 3-4 (Boyle, 2006). This deeply rooted, doctrinally-informed motivation is a key factor examined in this study's analysis of parental decision-making.

It could be said that Muslim children have special rights granted by God. In response, God rewards those who fulfil these duties, even after death. The Prophet said: "Upon death, a person's deeds will (definitely) cease except for three: ongoing charitable work, an endowment, or goodwill; knowledge left behind for people to benefit from; and a righteous, God-fearing child who constantly prays to Allah, the Almighty, for the soul of their parents" Reported by Muslim (Alukah, 2015). As a result, parents and the community highly regard the status of pious children. Even today, Muslim parents are motivated by social admiration and divine reward to encourage their children to pursue Islamic studies. The tradition holds that those who learn the Quran have the privilege of saving their parents and relatives in the hereafter (Riaz & Ur Rahman, 2023). This strong eschatological belief, that a pious, Quran-educated child can secure a parent's salvation, has been widely described in academic literature as a key factor influencing the educational choices of Algerian Muslim parents. It reflects a profound theological motivation that may help explain the deep parental attachment to Quranic schooling.

In summary, the family remains the foundation of Islamic civilisation. It fulfils the religion's aim of providing for and supporting a child's life while addressing their survival, upbringing, and educational needs. The rights of a child to be born through a valid union, to fully understand their paternity, to be breastfed, and to be raised with compassion and respect are among the fundamental rights of a child and the responsibilities of parents (Gatrad & Sheikh, 2001). In return, the rights of family members to respect and obedience from their children are protected.

In conclusion, this section has emphasised the theological and doctrinal principles within Islam that influence parental responsibilities regarding their children's religious upbringing. For many Algerian Muslim parents, these principles are not merely theoretical ideas but represent deeply rooted beliefs that shape their understanding of Quranic schools as vital institutions for nurturing a child's religious identity and fulfilling perceived divine duties. These frameworks offer an essential ideological context that helps explain parents' perspectives and experiences, which this study explores further.

3.3. The Enduring Role and Evolving Perception of Quranic Schools in Algeria

Islamic education is entirely centred on Islam as both a religion and a social and cultural system (ADEA, 2012). Quranic schools, in turn, play a vital role in establishing the foundations of early Islamic education, especially in countries like Algeria, where the majority of the population is Muslim (Morrow, 2010). This historical and religious context is essential for understanding the deeply rooted beliefs Algerian parents hold about the purpose of these institutions; they are not just schools but a fundamental part of the nation's Islamic identity. Historically, Islam spread rapidly from the Arabian Peninsula and reached North Africa in 652 (Esposito, 1998; Steinacher & Margreiter, 2022). Encounters with other civilisations enriched the new faith system and contributed to the rise of the Golden Age of Islam during the Abbasid era, 786-1258 (Renima et al., 2016). Among the most notable achievements of this period were the collection of the Hadiths, the standardisation of Arabic, the language of the Quran, and the translation of other significant intellectual works from various civilisations, such as Greek philosophy (Tiliouine, 2014). This era saw many discoveries and advances across numerous fields (Shoup et al., 2021). Family structures, mosques, and religious assemblies (majlis), which were central in learning various religious and scientific knowledge, could no longer satisfy the growing needs of a more complex society. Consequently, a formal school system gradually developed over the centuries, producing wide-ranging effects throughout the Islamic world (Tiliouine, 2014). This system can generally be categorised into three stages: (a) primary education (The Quranic School), (b) Madrassah, and (c) Jami'a (Heggoy, 1984).

It is claimed that Islamic education aims to develop a person spiritually, intellectually, and physically to ensure a balanced growth of the whole personality (Sarwar, 2001; Hashim, 2006). Islamic education concentrates on the pupils' soul, heart, self, and intellect (Boyle, 2004). This holistic approach directly influences what Algerian parents expect from Quranic schools: not only literacy, but also the comprehensive moral and spiritual development of their child. Primary Islamic education can start in various settings, including mosques, private homes, shops, and even open spaces (Barazangi, 2001). These environments were specifically created to help young Muslims study the Quran. They played an important social role as the means for official public teaching for primary and secondary pupils.

Institutions known as Katatib (singular Kuttab) and Msid (collectively called 'Quranic schools') existed across the Islamic world, mainly dedicated to teaching young people to read, write, and memorise the Qur'an under the supervision of a Qur'an expert (Tiliouine, 2014; Daoudi, 2016). Typically, in Algeria, they are overseen by the Ministry of Religious Affairs and cater to both children and adults, offering various levels of education in religious sciences (Al-Ayeb, 2005).

Moreover, these schools aim to instil moral values such as honesty, respect towards parents, benevolence, tolerance, and integrity, which help to build and develop a cultural and religious system within society (Ziane & Oussama, 2023; Pierre & Demonsant, 2009). They also promote Islamic

etiquette in children, such as proper talking, speaking to adults, entering the mosque, and seeking permission (Belhanayen & Fnenish, 2016). The children's psychic talents are nurtured, their awareness is heightened, and their language skills are expanded. According to Akkari (2004), Quranic schools deliver religious knowledge that all Muslim children should acquire, as it is an essential part of raising a Muslim child. This clear emphasis on moral and social etiquette emphasises the vital role these schools play in transmitting Algerian-Islamic values, as highlighted in the literature, and helps explain why they are regarded as important educational spaces.

Quranic schools are regarded as essential institutions within Algeria's education system, maintaining strong ties with families and official agencies (Abish, 2021). They operate alongside government preparatory schools by preparing children for public education, delivering quality instruction, and fostering their healthy development while ensuring adherence to Islamic teachings (Boyle & Boukamhi, 2017; Belhanayen & Fnenish, 2016). Al-Sikali's (2010) research highlighted the role of Quranic schools in addressing behaviour patterns that conflict with Islamic standards, particularly among young children. This dual role—academic readiness and moral development—is crucial to understanding how parents perceive Quranic schooling. For many Algerian Muslim parents, these institutions are viewed not only as educational venues but also as complementary frameworks that safeguard religious identity and cultural continuity, which is a central focus of this study.

The Quran, wooden tablets, fountain pens, ink, and, nowadays, blackboards are used as essential tools for learning (Daoudi, 2016). Meloudi (2020) argued that educational tools and approaches have evolved from wooden boards and clay to modern equipment and methods. Therefore, we can observe that there are differences between regions regarding equipment and learning techniques, which are caused by many factors, including but not limited to socioeconomic status and levels of interest. Such disparities in educational resources and teaching approaches may influence how parents perceive and assess Quranic education, an aspect that this phenomenological study examines in relation to their experiences and satisfaction.

Most children in Algeria attend Qur'anic schools from the age of three to six before entering public schools. Many parents see these schools as beneficial for their children. Additionally, children in Qur'anic schools work at their own pace without being graded or pressured (Daoudi, 2016). The Quranic school evolved from its own programmes, curriculum, and teaching strategies and benefited from diverse teaching philosophies (Kaddour & Beserni, 2020). Abdullah and Hajjam (2019) argued that they use customised curricula and methods tailored to the abilities of different age groups. The self-paced, low-pressure environment is a key feature that may attract parents who are cautious of the formal pressures of state schooling at a young age, emphasising a view of early childhood that values religious acclimatisation over academic rigour.

According to Makdisi (1981), memory development is a consistent aspect of medieval Islamic education. Memorisation involves taking the material as input, learning it, and retaining it through regular repetition at short intervals to recall the relevant pieces instantly afterwards. It is well recognised that the more a student repeats a surah (lesson), the better they learn or memorise it. The curriculum emphasises the memorisation of the Quran, but little focus is placed on analysing and discussing its meaning. Modern educational sciences identify this method as verbal learning, which emphasises the role of memory (Al-Hindi, 1990). The importance of memorisation remains a key pedagogical feature of Quranic schools, though parental attitudes towards this practice may vary. While some parents value it for its religious significance and perceived cognitive benefits, others may question its effectiveness when deeper understanding is limited. This variation in viewpoints is a central focus of the present phenomenological study, examining how parents interpret and assess this approach to learning.

Disciplinary methods, including corporal punishment, have historically been used to maintain order and enforce strict memorisation practices in Quranic schools (Hashim & Jemali, 2017). However, this practice must be understood within broader pedagogical and cultural contexts. It was rooted in a pre-modern educational philosophy common worldwide, which linked physical discipline with academic rigour and the flawless mastery of a sacred text. Modern educational psychology and neuroscience, however, challenge this approach, demonstrating that fear and stress can impair cognitive functions such as memory consolidation and deep engagement, potentially undermining the goal of meaningful learning (Gazzaniga et al., 2019). Moreover, its historical endurance was often intertwined with specific cultural interpretations of religious texts and social norms concerning a teacher's authority. This history remains highly relevant when studying parental beliefs. Contemporary parents' opinions on discipline in Quranic schools are likely to vary, influenced by their personal experiences and modern ideas of child rights. Understanding this tension is thus essential for exploring how parents balance authority, choose schools, and reconcile their desire for religious discipline with their child's welfare.

While disciplinary methods aimed to enforce a specific pedagogical approach, the actual content of that education—what was taught and why—has been the subject of a long-standing intellectual debate. As Meloudi (2020) states, in Algeria, children memorise the Quran, either entirely or partially, and their education progresses to include principles of the Arabic language, poetry, Islamic history, and even basic arithmetic. Thus, the curriculum varied across Muslim countries, and the most notable characteristic of Quranic schools was the limited range of study areas. Ibn Khaldun criticised the Muslim educational system in Spain (Andalusia) and most other Muslim countries at that time, which emphasised learning the Qur'an while neglecting other subjects such as language, poetry, and rhetoric (Maniam, 2016). In light of this, according to Tan and Ibrahim (2017), Ibn Al-Arabi argued that teaching

children poetry, philology, and mathematics before studying the Quran helped them better understand the scripture. This historical debate reflects modern tensions that may underpin parental conceptions: is the primary aim solely for Quranic memorisation, or a broader Islamic education that includes language and reasoning? This study will explore which of these models parents primarily value.

In the past, Quranic schools used various methods to encourage community involvement and personal development. Students' progress was assessed daily through regular group recitation sessions, and breaks were given after completing specific passages of the Quran. Wooden tablets were often coloured to mark milestones, and communities celebrated these achievements by having children visit nearby homes to collect gifts, with some offerings given to their teachers (Ahwani, 1975). Studies of Islamic education and Quranic schools have identified six key characteristics of these institutions: openness, ritualisation, permanence, flexibility, resistance, and variety (Lecomte, 1954; Eickelman, 1978; Colonna, 1981, 1984; Delval, 1980; Brenner, 1993). These features have remained fairly consistent over time, while also demonstrating the schools' ability to adapt to different social and cultural contexts. Elements such as ritualisation, community participation, and resilience continue to be incorporated into many Quranic schools today, shaping their perception and understanding within Algerian society.

Furthermore, the distinct features of Quranic schools across different African nations highlight the wide variety of practices within Muslim communities. This diversity supports the idea that the term "Muslim Education," which reflects the lived, culturally adapted practices of Muslim societies, can often be more accurate than "Islamic Education," which tends to suggest a single, idealised system based solely on religious texts (Haron, 2020). This change in terminology emphasises the range of educational approaches and cultural adaptations that have shaped Quranic schools, enabling them to preserve Islamic knowledge while adjusting to local contexts. Notably, differences are apparent even within the same country, where the content and facilities often vary between rural and urban areas (Astuti & Kusakabe, 2016). This observation is particularly relevant to this thesis, as Algerian Muslim parents' views of Quranic schooling are formed not in isolation but are influenced by Algeria's own version of "Muslim Education," shaped by national policies, cultural norms, and local resources.

In the past, reading and writing were primarily valued in Quranic schools as tools to support accurate Quran memorisation and recitation rather than as goals in themselves (Turki, 1980). This instrumental view of literacy, emphasising its role in religious devotion, was a central aspect of traditional Islamic pedagogy (Brenner, 2001; Boyle, 2006). In Algeria, Quranic schools receive funding from various sources, including charitable organisations, individual donations, parental contributions, zakat allocations, and government support (Sherifi, 2018; El Ayeb, 2005). Executive Decree No. 81-91, issued by the Ministry of Religious Affairs, formalised their role by authorising Quranic schools to care for and educate children before formal schooling, outlining tasks such as teaching literacy, Quranic

recitation, hadith, and religious values (El Ayeb, 2005). This formal state recognition integrates traditional religious authority with modern institutional oversight, increasing parental trust and reinforcing Quranic schools as both religiously legitimate and nationally endorsed. The variety of funding sources further reflects a broad societal consensus on their importance, positioning these schools as a vital link between family, faith, and the state.

This state endorsement and societal consensus have effectively redefined the traditional Quranic school, broadening its role beyond merely religious instruction. As a consequence, the Quranic school often serves as a preliminary stage that a child undergoes before progressing to the new primary school system. Viewing the Quranic school as a preparatory phase emphasises a notable functional shift, aligning its purpose with the educational framework of the modern state. It can be regarded as a form of cultural and educational capital, where early exposure to the Msid's school-like environment facilitates the transition into the secular primary system, a practical benefit that likely exerts a strong influence on parental choices (Bourdieu, 1986; Boyle, 2006).

The teacher at the Quranic school prepares the child psychologically and emotionally for primary school by emphasising its benefits and giving a broad overview so they are not caught off guard (Belhanayen & Fnenish, 2016). This proactive psychological preparation positions the Quranic school teacher (fqih) as an essential cultural intermediary between the familiar, often close-knit world of the Msid and the more formal, government-run primary school. This role is vital for reducing cultural dissonance and demonstrates an adaptive function of Quranic schools that directly addresses a key parental concern: their child's successful integration into the wider educational system (Moore, 2006; Wagner, 1993).

In Quranic schools, it is common to see a class of 50 or more children reciting the same surah aloud after the teacher. This high student-to-teacher ratio is a feature of traditional pedagogy but often conflicts with modern Western principles of personalised instruction. While efficient for large groups, this practice raises questions about the practicality of providing individual support, accommodating different learning speeds, and detecting specific learning difficulties, which may concern some parents (Wagner, 1993; Brenner, 2001).

The teacher monitors the volume, believing that louder recitation indicates sustained interest, aids in quicker memorisation, and makes it easier to spot mistakes (Daoudi, 2016). This pedagogical belief system is rooted in a specific epistemology that equates auditory saturation and collective energy with effective learning and discipline. However, from a contemporary educational perspective, this emphasis on volume as a proxy for engagement is problematic. It privileges a single, teacher-defined metric of participation and may overlook quieter, more introverted learners or those who benefit from silent,

internalised processing, potentially creating a learning environment that favours certain cognitive styles over others (Eickelman, 1992; Gazzaniga et al., 2019).

The educational reasoning behind practices like choral recitation, whether parents agree with it or not, forms part of their lived experience, which underpins their phenomenological beliefs. This is a vital point for a phenomenological study. Parents' understanding is shaped through their lived encounters with the educational process, influencing judgments based on the tangible results they observe in their children's development. Their beliefs probably range: some may fully support these traditional methods as valid and effective, while others may see them as an unavoidable, if less than ideal, aspect of valued religious training. This tension between approach and outcome is crucial to understanding the complexity of parental choice (Merleau-Ponty et al, 2013; Van Manen, 2016).

Alghani's (2016) research on adolescent attrition from Quran memorisation (hifz) programmes indicates that dropout is not merely a matter of individual choice but often reflects systemic institutional challenges. This phenomenon can be analysed through three intersecting dimensions: pedagogical, administrative, and psychosocial. Pedagogically, issues such as harsh disciplinary methods, inefficient instruction, outdated rote-memorisation approaches, and age-appropriate curricula reveal a disconnect between traditional hifz practices and students' needs. Scholars have argued that such pedagogy often prioritises textual replication over comprehension and spiritual development, which can lead to student disengagement (Berghlund, 2018).

Administrative and structural deficiencies, including the lack of a structured syllabus, a focus on quantity over quality, and financial instability (such as delayed teacher payments), create an inconsistent and challenging learning environment. These shortcomings emphasise the tension between maintaining tradition and adopting effective organisational practices (Boyle, 2006), ultimately impacting the school's ability to realise its spiritual and educational goals.

Finally, the psychosocial aspect mirrors students' experiences within this system. Factors such as stress, limited autonomy, and negative peer interactions often stem from the rigid pedagogical and administrative framework. Even parental pressure may arise as a response to poor communication and a lack of transparency, shifting responsibility onto families.

A phenomenological study of Quranic schools must consider these interconnected aspects as a framework for understanding what influences parental perceptions. Parents' opinions of these institutions are shaped by systemic tensions in teaching methods, administration, and student experience, reflecting broader issues in balancing traditional hifz ideals with practical concerns for children's welfare. Analysing these dynamics helps to situate parents' views within the structural and

cultural context of Quranic education, providing valuable insights into how religious objectives and educational realities intersect.

This critical view of institutional failings should also consider physical and psychological safety. Although the severe cases of economic exploitation and abuse documented by Human Rights Watch (2015) in West African daaras are not necessarily reflective of conditions in Algeria, the report offers an essential analytical perspective. It raises an urgent question for the Algerian context: to what extent are parental beliefs motivated by a fundamental desire for a safe and ethically managed local alternative for religious instruction?

For Algerian parents, choosing a Quranic school likely involves an implicit risk assessment that extends beyond educational effectiveness. Their perceptions are probably shaped by a need to balance spiritual aspirations with a primary concern for their child's safety. This suggests that parents actively consider the learning environment, seeking institutions that satisfy not only their religious needs but also their standards for safety, ethical management, and emotional support (Bano, 2018). Consequently, a phenomenological study should explore how parents navigate this tension between the ideal of religious education and potential risks, as well as the specific criteria they use to evaluate and trust a particular institution (Ware, 2014).

In summary, this analysis demonstrates that the historical, pedagogical, and socio-political context of Quranic schools in Algeria offers an essential framework for understanding potential parental perspectives. The reviewed literature suggests that parents may value these institutions for a mix of religious, moral, academic, and social reasons. However, these perceptions coexist with documented challenges related to teaching methods, resources, and safety. This foundation informs the current phenomenological study, which aims to explore how parents themselves express and manage these complex aims and difficulties in their lived experiences.

3.3.1. The Teacher (Murabbi) in Quranic Schools

Suppose the Quranic school is the institution through which parents seek to achieve their educational and religious goals for their children. In that case, the teacher (Murabbi, Taleb) is the crucial figure who fulfils those objectives. This subsection explores the role of the Quranic school teacher, examining their qualifications, pedagogical duties, and moral standing as presented in the literature. The main argument here is that the teacher is not just an instructor but a key figure whose perceived authority and piety are likely the primary factors influencing parental trust and decisions. Consequently, this analysis of the teacher's role provides an important perspective for understanding how the goals of Quranic schools,

outlined in the main section, are realised and, therefore, how they are perceived by Algerian Muslim parents who are the focus of this study.

This role is characterised by several key features, starting with their title and credentials. The authority of the Quranic schoolteacher, a figure known cross-culturally as Mudarris or Sheikh, and in Algeria specifically as Taleb, is fundamentally based on their mastery of sacred knowledge and language (Daoudi, 2016). This terminology is not merely a matter of regional variation but signifies a culturally-specific role filled with respect and religious authority, a crucial factor likely influencing parental trust and choice. This authority is inherently linked to the need for a solid background in religious studies and Arabic, the sacred language of the Quran. The significance of Arabic is vital; it is not just a language of instruction but the revered vessel of divine revelation. Therefore, the teacher's linguistic competence is equivalent to their ability to grant access to the uncorrupted word of God, a primary concern for parents seeking authentic religious education for their children (Abdulrazak, 1982).

Quranic school teachers play a vital role in introducing Islamic values to the community. Therefore, working with Quranic schools becomes a crucial strategy in shaping local Islamic discourse (Abu-Nimer et al., 2016). This positions the teacher not just as an educator but as a key element in the system of religious transmission, holding significant soft power in influencing community norms. To achieve the goals of Quranic education, these teachers assert that they must be committed and actively motivate and involve their students (Komba, 2015). This self-perception emphasises a pedagogical ethos centred on moral dedication, which likely forms a primary source of their legitimacy and appeal to parents.

Nevertheless, despite their extensive study of religious sciences within the Quranic education system, many Quranic school teachers lack the skills to secure financial stability for themselves and their families (Komba, 2015). This creates a notable paradox: these custodians of spiritual and moral knowledge often find themselves in a state of economic insecurity. This gap between spiritual authority and socioeconomic status presents a potential risk to the sustainability of these institutions and may influence parental perceptions of the teachers', and consequently, the school's overall reputation and effectiveness.

In Algeria, the Quran teacher is usually employed within the religious affairs sector, often a memoriser of the Quran and proficient in the rules of Tajweed. Their educational qualification is not fixed at a specific level. The teacher may be a muazzin or an imam, with priority given to their seniority in the role. This formal recognition by the state grants the teacher institutional legitimacy and some socioeconomic stability, directly addressing the precarity seen in other contexts. However, the criteria for qualification, which focus on memorisation (hifz), seniority, and current religious roles rather than formal pedagogical training, reflect a state-supported model that values traditional Islamic authority and

practical knowledge. This may create tension between the state's aim of standardisation and the actual pedagogical abilities of the instructors, a factor that parents might critically evaluate when considering a teacher's effectiveness beyond their religious authenticity. Their duties include teaching the Quran to both adults and children, instructing the basic principles of Fiqh related to worship, and educating on the fundamentals of reading and writing (Sulaiman & Tamri, 2018). This officially mandated expansion of their role from purely religious instruction to include literacy and the basics of writing signifies the state's strategic co-option of these institutions to support broader national educational goals, further enhancing their perceived importance in the eyes of parents.

The Quranic teacher functions not only as an educator but also as a moral role model, with their conduct serving as an implicit part of the curriculum (Meloudi, 2020). This dual role extends beyond knowledge transmission (ta'lim) to include holistic character development (tarbiya), which is especially vital during early childhood when learning primarily occurs through imitation of parents and teachers. Therefore, parents often view Quranic teachers as secondary moral guardians whose influence aligns with their own upbringing goals. The prophetic saying, "The best of you are those who learn the Quran and teach it" (Meloudi, 2020), further elevates the teacher's status, reinforcing parental trust in both the educators and the institutions they represent.

The Quranic teacher frequently depends on the most committed students—those who have memorised the Quran thoroughly—to assist during listening sessions with their peers (Boudalia, 2021). This peer-led learning method serves two main purposes: it offers a practical solution for managing large classes and aligns with the pedagogical hierarchy of the master-apprentice model traditional in Islamic education. While it encourages a collaborative learning environment and rewards merit, it also raises concerns about the consistency of teaching and the teacher's direct involvement in each student's progress, which could lead to disparities in educational quality.

The ultimate goal of teachers and administrators in Quranic schools is to guide students' hearts and actions completely towards God, as reflected in the Quranic ideal that "truly, my prayer and my service of sacrifice, my life and my death, are (all) for Allah, the Cherisher of the Worlds: No partner has He: this am I commanded, and I am the first of those who bow to His Will" (Quran, 6:162-163). This spiritual aim fundamentally transforms the role of the teacher from simply an instructor to a spiritual guide (murabbi), whose duty is to nurture not only intellectual mastery but complete existential harmony with divine will. This aligns with the previously discussed idea of the teacher as a moral exemplar, suggesting that their effectiveness is judged not solely by students' memorisation accuracy but by their success in cultivating holistic piety, a core concern for parents entrusting their children to these institutions.

This analysis of the Quranic teacher's diverse role, including spiritual guidance, moral example, and state-recognised instruction, directly informs the main focus of this thesis. The perceived authority and piety of the Taleb are vital factors, forming the essential basis for exploring how Algerian Muslim parents perceive, experience, and ultimately choose these institutions for their children.

3.4. Beyond Foundational Learning: The Madrassah as an Institution of Advanced Islamic Studies

The term 'madrassah' (مدرسة), derived from the Arabic root meaning 'to study,' is used across the Muslim world with varying levels of specificity. In some contexts, it functions as a general term for 'school,' sometimes encompassing what this thesis defines as Quranic schools. However, for this study, a clear conceptual distinction is necessary. This thesis uses the term 'Quranic school' (Kuttab, Msid) specifically to refer to institutions focusing on primary-level Quranic memorisation and basic Islamic literacy, mainly for young children. Conversely, this section considers the 'Madrassa' as a separate institution offering intermediate and advanced Islamic education. As Heggoy (1984) explains, these are institutions that historically prepared students for specialised religious roles, building on the foundation established in Quranic schools. Therefore, including the Madrassah is vital for a comprehensive understanding of the Islamic educational landscape. It represents the logical educational progression from the Quranic school and provides insight into the wider scholarly and intellectual context within which Algerian Quranic teachers (Taleb) are often trained. Examining the Madrassah offers essential insights into the aims, methods, and authority structures underpinning Islamic education at all levels, making it indispensable to this study.

As previously mentioned, the main aim of Quranic schools is to teach children the Quran so they can become hafiz. Madrassahs, or Medersas (meaning 'school' in Arabic), serve as the modern-day middle and secondary schools within the Islamic education system (Heggoy, 1984).

They introduced pupils to a more advanced curriculum to become Alims (scholars), a qualification that required approximately twelve years of study. These institutions trained students for professional roles such as Imams, clergymen, Islamic judges (Qadis), and teachers, according to the recognised needs of society. This professional training function highlights a key distinction: while Quranic schools focus on universal religious socialisation, Madrassahs are aimed at creating a religious elite and professional class, a differentiation crucial for understanding the full spectrum of Islamic educational objectives. A standard Madrassah curriculum typically includes Arabic, Quranic interpretations (Tafsir), Islamic law (Shariah), Prophetic hadith, logic (mantiq), and history, representing a formalised and extensive body of knowledge.

Madrassahs were widely established during the Abbasid era and the Ottoman Empire. The Nizamiyah Madrassah gained particular prominence, and by the eleventh century, most major cities had their own comparable institutions. Bustamam-Ahmad and Jory (2011) note that a variety of Madrassahs exist today across the Islamic world, many linked to traditional congregations and Sufi orders (Zawiyas). This diversity emphasises that "the Madrassah" is not a single, uniform entity but a category of institution adapted to different Islamic traditions and local contexts, a fact that complicates simplistic Western portrayals. They serve multiple functions and constitute a substantial part of civil society as guardians of Islamic tradition. Historically, they have also played a role in political resistance, notably contributing to the fight against colonialism. In this context, figures like Emir Abd-el-Kader (1808–1883), a warrior and prominent thinker who led a prolonged resistance against French colonialism, were products of this system; notably, his father was a Quran teacher (Churchill, 1981). This illustrates the historical pipeline from Quranic school to Madrassah to leadership, embedding these institutions deeply within the social and political fabric of Muslim societies.

Traditional Islamic higher education evolved through the creation of specialised Madrassahs. As scholars like Zahoor (1999) and Esposito (2003) observe, cities such as Baghdad possessed advanced medical schools and public hospitals during the Islamic Golden Age. Legendary institutions like Al-Qarawiyyin in Fes (founded in 859 by Fatima Al-Fihri) and Al-Azhar in Cairo (founded in 970) are recognised as some of the earliest universities in the world. These institutions awarded formal certificates (ijazahs) across various fields, with curricula tailored to meet evolving social and scholarly needs. The accomplishments of these historic centres demonstrate a sophisticated educational ecosystem that integrated religious and secular sciences, presenting a holistic model that contrasts with the often more narrowly focused religious curricula of many modern Madrassahs.

Two elements are particularly significant to these institutions due to their close ties to student life: community involvement and pedagogical theory (Tiliouine, 2014). First, the Muslim community showed a strong commitment to supporting this educational system by ensuring its financial independence through donations and religious alms (zakāt). Wealthy benefactors, including women such as Fatima al-Fihri, funded infrastructure and provided students with accommodation, meals, and stipends. Teachers received regular payment through a merit-based system (Nakosteen, 1978). The traditional community-funded model, which depended on endowments (waqf) and alms (zakat), was historically intended to safeguard the independence of Madrassahs from government interference. However, this independence, combined with a lack of state regulation and sustainable local funding, made the system vulnerable in the modern era. This vulnerability is clearly illustrated by the historical example of the anti-Soviet jihad in Afghanistan. As Blanchard (2007) reports, the Madrassah system in Pakistan and Afghanistan, which saw a revival in the 1970s, was deliberately exploited in the 1980s through substantial external financial support. Economically disadvantaged institutions were

manipulated to serve geopolitical objectives, fundamentally changing their character and purpose. This use for jihad marks a significant deviation from their traditional scholarly role, demonstrating how external financial backing can influence curriculum and ideological perspectives towards radical political aims, thereby transforming their global image.

Secondly, the educational discourse of the medieval era was greatly enriched by Muslim intellectuals who provided a strong theoretical foundation and practical guidance for Islamic pedagogy. The foundational work of scholars like Ibn Sahnoun, whose handbook *Adab al-Mu'allimin* (The Manners of Teachers) laid out detailed guidelines for classroom management, learning development, and the relationship between schools and communities, demonstrates an early formalisation of educational theory (Al-Ahwani, 1975). This was further developed by other key figures: Ibn Sina (Avicenna) introduced innovative methods such as cooperative learning, while Al-Qabisi, in his treatise *Ahwal al-Mu'allimin wa al-Muta'allimin* (The Conditions of Teachers and Students), supported progressive ideas like the elimination of gender distinctions in education and the rejection of physical punishment, extensively discussing pedagogical concerns (Al-Ahwani, 1975). The importance of these historical contributions is twofold. First, they challenge modern Orientalist narratives that often neglect the sophisticated and progressive aspects of classical Islamic educational thought. Second, as noted by Gunther (2006) and Halstead (2004), this comprehensive theory, covering moral, individual, and intellectual development, remains highly relevant, offering a valuable framework for contemporary educational philosophy that reflects the holistic aims many Algerian parents hold for their children in Quranic schools today. This rich intellectual heritage shapes the modern structure and ethos of Islamic education, providing a deep historical precedent for its lasting emphasis on character formation (*tarbiya*) alongside instruction (*ta'lim*).

3.5. The Metamorphosis of Islamic Instruction: From Holistic System to Curriculum

Subject

Having outlined in Chapter 2 the significant socio-historical forces that influenced Algeria's educational landscape, this section consolidates the key transformation of Islamic education itself in Algeria. It examines a fundamental change: how the pedagogical approach for transmitting Islamic knowledge shifted from a holistic, community-based system essential to social identity (the Quranic school and *Madrassah*) into a formalised, timetable-driven subject within a standardised national curriculum. This process, driven by colonial policies and reinforced by post-independence state-building, redefined the purpose, content, and context of religious learning. For Algerian Muslim parents, this historical transition created a dual reality: a national curriculum that incorporates Islamic education as a core subject and a resilient, parallel traditional Quranic school system. Understanding this transformation is

crucial for analysing why parents might engage with both systems, a phenomenon central to the phenomenological investigation of their conceptions.

The French colonial project initiated this change by directly targeting Algeria's existing Islamic education system, a hierarchical network of Quranic schools (*kuttab/mosque*) for basic learning and *madrassas* for advanced religious sciences, viewing it as a significant obstacle to assimilation. As Heggoy (1984) and Turin (1983) affirm, the strategy was not merely to offer an alternative but to actively dismantle the indigenous system. This was achieved by confiscating *waqf* (endowment) properties, severing the economic support of these institutions (Heggoy, 1984; Saurier, 1982), and systematically eradicating local education to promote assimilationist aims (Heggoy, 1984; Turin, 1983). The objective was to 'domesticate' the local population (Turin, 1983) and to break the church's monopoly on education, akin to the 1905 French law of *laïcité* (Willaime, 2007), thereby weakening Muslim identity (Altbach and Kelly, 1984).

This colonial invasion sparked fierce resistance, turning education into a key battleground for cultural survival. The local people, known as 'les indigènes,' organised a widespread boycott of colonial institutions, viewing them as threats to their identity (Turin, 1983). By 1945, only a small number of Algerians attended French schools, showing the strength of traditional systems. The response was not just rejection but also adaptation. The Algerian Muslim Ulama Association, founded by Abd el-Hamid Ben Badis in 1931, modernised traditional education by creating a reformed Islamic school system. Their slogan, "Islam is my religion; Arabic is my language; Algeria is my nation" (Chiviges, 2000, p. 10), directly connected educational reform to national and religious identity. By 1945, this association enrolled 40,000 students, compared to 50,000 in traditional Quranic schools and 300,000 in French schools (Saurier, 1982; Tiliouine, 2014), illustrating a vibrant, multi-system educational landscape under colonial rule.

Following independence, the new Algerian state faced the daunting task of rebuilding a shattered system and pursued a policy of Arabisation aimed at reclaiming national identity by co-opting and formalising religious instruction. Independence in 1962 created an urgent need to reconstruct an education system devastated by the departure of 800,000 settlers (*Pieds-Noirs*) and the destruction caused by the OAS (Chiviges, 2000). With 86% of the school-aged population uneducated (Saurier, 1982) and a severe shortage of qualified teachers, only 15% were locals in 1962 (Tiliouine, 2002). The new state embarked on mass recruitment, drawing many new teachers from traditional Qur'anic school backgrounds (Tiliouine, 2014). This decision would later influence pedagogical practices. The state's strategy for decolonisation was Arabisation, seeking to revive Algeria's Islamic and Arabic identity. The 1976 Constitution established Arabic as the primary language of education and made schooling compulsory (Tiliouine, 2014). A critical yet paradoxical part of this project was the state's co-option of religious

instruction itself. Islamic education was formalised, standardised, and made a mandatory subject within the secular national curriculum administered by the Ministry of Education (Tiliouine, 2014). The Education Act mandates that education "instil Islamic values and reinforce students' identities" (Article 44). However, this transition fundamentally changed its nature: the objective shifted from holistic tarbiya (character building) to academic credentialism; the context moved from the community mosque to the secular classroom; and authority transferred from local scholars to the state. It became one subject among many, allocated 90 minutes per week in primary school, decreasing to 60 minutes in middle school (Tiliouine, 2014).

The outcome of this historical process is a modern educational landscape characterised by duality, a reality that directly influences the choices and perceptions of Algerian parents. The state system offers a standardised "Islamic Education" subject within a broader modern curriculum that emphasises student-centred approaches and competency-based learning (Bousenna et al., 2009). Simultaneously, the traditional Quranic school system remains highly popular, demonstrating its lasting cultural significance. Remarkably, 93.54% of children under four attended Quranic schools in 2009 (Bousenna et al., 2009), with students of all ages frequently attending these schools during free time and holidays. This duality exists because parents perceive the two systems as fulfilling different needs. The state curriculum provides official legitimacy and structured religious literacy. Conversely, Quranic schools, many of which are now funded and regulated by the Ministry of Religious Affairs, are trusted for authentic spiritual and moral grounding (tarbiya), ritual practice, and Quranic memorisation (hifz). This leads many parents to utilise both systems to achieve what they see as the incomplete objectives of each. This dualism also fosters pedagogical tension. As Tiliouine (2014) observes, many teachers in the state system are deeply rooted in traditional methods, often stressing memorisation and employing authoritarian techniques, a legacy of their own educational backgrounds. This creates a conflict within modern schools, where such practices conflict with the officially encouraged student-centred, competency-based approaches, which Belhandouz (2011) describes as a 'conflict of meaning.'

In summary, the history of Islamic education in Algeria narrates a story of change and resilience. Once dismantled by colonialism, it was later revived as a form of cultural and religious resistance and ultimately formalised by the post-independence state as part of the national curriculum. Today, this legacy has resulted in a dual system: state schools that include religious instruction alongside a robust network of traditional Quranic schools. For Algerian parents, this involves navigating between two educational paths, each offering different promises about faith, morality, and identity. Understanding how parents make these choices and what they believe about providing their children with a comprehensive religious and moral education is central to this phenomenological study.

3.6. Pedagogies of Resistance: How Islamic Education Survived Colonial Dismantling

While Chapter 2 outlined the broad historical narrative of French colonial educational policy and Section 3.5 in this chapter examined the structural transformation of Islamic instruction, this section concentrates on the specific resistance strategies that enabled its survival. Beyond its endurance, this analysis investigates how Algerian scholars, communities, and institutions actively opposed colonial efforts to dismantle their religious and educational systems. It argues that resistance was not uniform but operated through three distinct yet overlapping modes: infrastructural persistence, ideological reform, and spiritual mobilisation. Understanding these historical strategies is vital, as they fostered a deep, lasting cultural connection between Islamic schooling and moral resilience that continues to influence parental trust and perceptions of Quranic schools today.

3.6.1. Infrastructural Persistence: Clandestine Schools and Community Funding

The French colonial strategy to dismantle Islamic education mainly targeted its physical and financial structures. Seizing *hubus* (religious endowments) was a strategic move aimed at crippling the system financially, removing the traditional funding sources for teachers and school upkeep (Segalla, 2009; Heggoy, 1984). This policy proved to be ruthlessly effective at an institutional level, leading to the demolition, repurposing, or forced closure of numerous Quranic schools, mosques, and *zawiyas* across Algeria, especially in urban centres like Algiers (Oumri, 2016).

However, the Algerian response revealed that the core of the educational system was its people, not the buildings. Confronted with the destruction of infrastructure, communities mobilised to establish a decentralised and resilient network of learning. When official schools closed, education persisted in private homes, shops, and mosques (Saad Allah, 1981; 2007). This shift to covert and semi-covert locations was not a retreat but a strategic adaptation, a quiet act of defiance that kept knowledge accessible. The colonial state's strict laws, like the 1892 and 1904 decrees requiring licences for Quranic schools (Zenaz, 2021), inadvertently supported this strategy, transforming each hidden classroom into a subtle act of political resistance.

This grassroots movement was supported by a strong communal financial effort, directly opposing the colonial strategy of economic suppression. The extent of this marginalization becomes clear when examining the state's discriminatory funding policies (see Table 1). Muslim institutions received only 0.076 francs per person, a deliberately minimal amount. Furthermore, these funds were strictly limited to paying salaries for state-approved imams and were explicitly prohibited from being used to build or renovate educational infrastructure (Al-Bouabdelli, 2013; Oumri, 2016).

Table 1: Comparative French Spending on Religious Institutions in Algeria

Religious Groups	Number of Individuals	Expenditure	Expenditure Rate (in Francs)
Catholics	310.000	920.100	2,93
Protestants	7.500	83.100	11,08
Jews	35.665	26.100	0,731
Muslims	2.842.497	216.340	0,076

Source: Oumri (2016)

Therefore, the survival of Islamic education depended on a strong, informal economy of knowledge, a direct agreement between teachers and families that entirely bypassed the state. This history of communal sacrifice and adaptation forged a powerful legacy. It established a deeply ingrained cultural narrative that views support for Quranic schools not merely as an educational choice but as a moral obligation and a sign of communal identity, perceiving these institutions as resilient, self-sufficient bastions of faith that continue to subtly influence parental commitment and trust today.

3.6.2. Ideological Reform: The Ulama's Modernisation Project

If infrastructural continuity ensured the physical survival of Islamic instruction, the Association of Algerian Muslim Ulama, founded by Abdelhamid Ben Badis in 1931, promoted its intellectual and ideological modernisation within the colonial context of the period. Their resistance was not merely about preservation but involved active change. They recognised that to counter a modernising colonial force, traditional education itself needed reform to stay relevant and effective (Ben Ramdan, 2020; ElTayeb, 1989).

The Ulama's initiative was a deliberate and nuanced response to cultural assimilation. Their well-known slogan, "Islam is my religion; Arabic is my language; Algeria is my nation," was not just a declaration of identity but a direct ideological challenge to the French colonial narrative (Nara, 2021). It laid the groundwork for a new national consciousness, reimagining Algerian identity in outright opposition to the colonial project of Francification.

Pedagogically, the Ulama moved beyond the traditional model of rote memorisation to develop a reformed system they called *al-ta'lim al-hurr* (free education). They established a network of modernised "free schools" that became the standard-bearers of this ideological resistance. These institutions were revolutionary because they incorporated a modern curriculum, including practical

sciences, history, and geography, alongside the core religious and Arabic studies (Batiche, 2019; Saad Allah, 2007). This was a strategic masterstroke: it offered a compelling alternative to both the traditional *zawiyas*, which they regarded as outdated, and the colonial schools, which they dismissed as acculturating. They provided the community with a means to become modern and educated without sacrificing their religious and linguistic identity.

The impact was notable. By 1945, the Ulama's schools enrolled 40,000 students, rivaling the enrolment of traditional Quranic schools (50,000) and presenting a significant challenge to the colonial system (Saurier, 1982; Tiliouine, 2014). As scholar Mohamed Al-Bashir Al-Ibrahimi starkly warned, a delay in their establishment would have meant there might be no one left "to hear our voice" (Turki, 1969), emphasising their perceived role as the last bastion against cultural erasure.

The Ulama's legacy has two aspects. Firstly, they professionalised and systematised Islamic education in Algeria, establishing a structured, school-based model that could compare favourably with colonial systems. Secondly, and perhaps more importantly for this study, they successfully created a strong link between Islamic schooling, modern knowledge, and national identity. For contemporary parents, this history means that Quranic schools, especially those within the Ulama tradition, are viewed not as outdated relics but as effective ways of combining faith, identity, and modern relevance. This helps support their choice in a modern world, reducing potential conflicts between religious devotion and practical educational progress.

3.6.3. Spiritual Mobilisation: The Role of Zawiyas and Sufi Orders

Operating alongside the Ulama's reformist project was a deeper, more traditional current of resistance rooted in the spiritual authority and social networks of Sufi orders and their institutions, the *zawiyas*. While the Ulama engaged with modernised curricula, the Sufis maintained the enduring influence of mysticism, local sanctity, and in some cases, direct military mobilisation. These institutions, serving as centres for worship, education, and community life (Darwish, 2022; Sheila et al., 2002), became strongholds of cultural preservation and often, active opposition.

The role of the *zawiya* was multifaceted. As Joassin (2020) observed, they were often criticised as centres of outdated traditions, but this very description emphasises their function as custodians of ancestral practices and knowledge that the colonial regime aimed to suppress. They provided a refuge where the internal, mystical dimensions of Islam (*Tasawwuf*) could flourish, protecting the community's spiritual life from colonial influence (Saleem & Rizwan, 2019; Kenioua et al., 2023).

However, this resistance often extended beyond the spiritual and educational spheres into the political and military realms. The organisational strength and popular legitimacy of Sufi orders made them natural centres for mobilisation. As Bouyerdene (2008) and Rey-Goldzeiguer (1977) observe, these orders had a long history of complex political engagement, a tradition that persisted under colonial rule. The most notable example is Emir Abd El-Kader of the Qadiriyya Brotherhood, who transcended his role as a Sufi leader to establish a state and army, leading a prolonged military resistance against French forces before his defeat in 1847 (Bouyerdene, 2008; Khatir, 2016).

This pattern of armed resistance occurred elsewhere. The Ouled Sidi Cheikh order revolted in the province of Oran, while the significant Kabyle revolt of 1871-1872 was led by Mohamed Al Hadj al-Mokrani and heavily supported by Cheikh al-Haddad of the Rahmaniyya Brotherhood (Bouyerdene, 2008; Khatir, 2016). These were not merely skirmishes; they were large-scale uprisings with leadership deeply rooted in Sufi networks, illustrating how spiritual authority could be directly translated into political and military action.

The colonial administration's relationship with these orders was complex and constantly changing. Sometimes, they tried to co-opt them to stay in control; other times, they faced them as strong opponents. This duality shows the lasting strength of these institutions; they were a force the state could neither dismiss nor eradicate.

The lasting legacy of this spiritual mobilisation is a narrative of righteous defiance and unwavering faith in the face of oppression. For many Algerians, the history of Sufi orders links Islamic practice to a proud tradition of independent action and resistance. This fosters a perception of Quranic education, especially in traditions connected to these orders, as more than just academic; it is an immersion into a heritage of spiritual resilience and perseverance. This legacy offers a distinct, more traditionalist approach to resistance compared to the Ulama's modernism, yet both share the same aim: the steadfast defence of Islamic identity against external threats.

In conclusion, the survival of Islamic education in Algeria was not a coincidence but the result of a complex, multi-layered system of resistance. Confronted by a systematic colonial campaign aimed at dismantling it, Algerians responded on three main levels: through the infrastructural resilience of communities that funded and hosted clandestine schools; through the ideological reform led by the Ulama, who modernised pedagogy to develop a compelling counter-narrative of national identity; and through the spiritual mobilisation of Sufi orders and zawiyas, which offered deep reservoirs of cultural sanctity and, at times, direct military opposition. These strategies did not operate in isolation but often overlapped and collaborated, forming a resilient network that the colonial administration found

impossible to entirely quench. The lasting legacy of this struggle is a deeply embedded cultural narrative that portrays Quranic schools not merely as educational venues but as sacred bastions of identity, perseverance, and moral independence. This historical background is vital for understanding the current landscape; it provides the primary reason why Algerian Muslim parents view these schools with trust, legitimacy, and a sense of cultural obligation that extend beyond their purely academic role. The present study will now explore this phenomenon through their own lived experiences.

3.7. The State and the Mosque: Negotiating Control of Religious Education in Post-Independence Algeria

Building on the historical analysis of resistance and transformation in the earlier sections, this chapter explores the complex dynamics shaping religious education in the post-colonial era. While Sections 3.5 and 3.6 explained how Islamic instruction was reformed and preserved despite colonial suppression, this analysis contends that independence did not end the struggle over Algeria's religious identity. Instead, it marked the beginning of a new phase characterised by negotiation and tension between the state's efforts to regulate religious education for national development and political legitimacy, and society's desire to uphold the autonomy and comprehensive spiritual role (*tarbiya*) of community-based Quranic schools. This ongoing negotiation, evident in policies of Arabisation, state co-option, and societal adaptation, has directly led to the dualistic educational landscape that Algerian parents face today. Understanding this tension is therefore crucial for analysing parental attitudes, as their choices between state and non-state religious instruction are deeply shaped by this broader political and ideological contest over the purpose of Islamic education.

3.7.1. The State's Project: Regulation, Legitimacy, and the Bureaucratisation of Islam

Following independence, the Algerian state deliberately and strategically sought to harness the influential symbolic power of Islam for nation-building and political stabilisation. This was not merely a revival of tradition but a calculated political move to unify a fragmented post-colonial identity and legitimise the new regime. The state's approach involved a coordinated effort to regulate, standardise, and institutionalise religious education, transforming it from a diverse, community-led activity into a centralised tool of official policy.

A key aspect of this project was the policy of Arabisation. As Mostari (2019) argues, the promotion of Classical Quranic Arabic was a deliberate strategy to foster a specific Arabo-Islamic identity. However, this policy was inherently ambivalent; while it successfully revitalised Quranic Arabic and offered a unified linguistic channel for religious instruction, it also tended to exclude and marginalise other

languages such as Tamazight and Algerian dialects, thereby contributing to a complex sociolinguistic conflict.

The institutional foundation for this control was the creation of state bodies responsible for supervising every aspect of religious life. As Tamburini (2024) explains, this process evolved into a comprehensive ‘bureaucratization of Islam,’ institutionalised through organisations like the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Endowments (Awqaf). As Vatin (1981) observed, its aim was to ensure that ‘religion was intended to benefit the state.’ This involved regulating religious properties, symbols, and notably, education, alongside the Islamic High Council. The Ministry’s Executive Decree No. 1-81 in 1991, which officially recognised and standardised Quranic schools (Meloudi, 2020), exemplifies this effort. It reflected the state's attempt to bring these traditionally autonomous institutions under its bureaucratic control, defining their educational goals and seeking to influence the religious socialisation of young people.

Critically, this pursuit of control must be understood as a direct response to profound national trauma. The state's use of religious education as a tool appeared as a strategic reaction to the real threat of extremist violence and the destructive civil conflict of the 1990s (Evans & Phillips, 2007). The clear aim, as Tamburini (2024) notes, was to build a firewall against radicalisation and to establish a stable, "national Islam" that would act as a "cornerstone" in fighting extremism and be "vital for the stabilisation of the country."

This project was mainly reactive and ongoing. As Ghanem (2019) argues in *The Shifting Foundations of Political Islam in Algeria*, the state's strategy has consistently been to control and outflank rival Islamist movements. By positioning itself as the sole supporter and guardian of official Islam, the state aimed to monopolise religious discourse to "deter possible opponents from utilising religion to their advantage" (Joassin, 2020). This use of faith created a key tension: religious education was increasingly framed within a paradigm of national service and security, "fighting extremism and terrorism" (Zenaz, 2021), rather than solely focusing on spiritual growth.

Table 2: The State's Use of Religious Education for Instrumental Purposes

Policy Tool	Primary Objective	Unintended Consequence
Arabization	Forge a unified Arabo-Islamic national identity.	Marginalised Tamazight and dialects, creating linguistic strife (Mostari, 2019).

Policy Tool	Primary Objective	Unintended Consequence
Bureaucratisation (Tamburini, 2024)	Centralise control through the Ministry of Religious Affairs and standardise curricula.	Hollowed out independent theological foundations, creating a state-centric Islam.
Securitisation (Evans & Phillips, 2007)	Promote a "national Islam" as a firewall against radicalisation.	Framed religious education through a lens of security, potentially stifling intellectual and spiritual depth.

In essence, the state's project was a strategic compromise. Faced with the existential threat of civil war and extremist violence, the state's emphasis on short-term stability and security through control was not just rational but regarded as a necessary measure for national survival. However, this strategy risked compromising the long-term intellectual independence and organic vitality of religious thought. Consequently, while the state successfully established a managed, moderate religious landscape, it also began an ongoing negotiation with a society that deeply valued the autonomy and authentic spiritual role of its religious institutions.

3.7.2. Societal Response: Autonomy, Adaptation, and Resistance

If the state's strategy was a top-down approach favouring control and stability, the societal response was a bottom-up assertion of authenticity and organic community life. Faced with the state's bureaucratisation of Islam, Algerian society did not simply resist but engaged in a multifaceted effort to preserve the autonomy, spiritual depth, and adaptive capacity of religious education. This response was not necessarily a rejection of the state's goal of moderation, but rather a defence of the traditional right of communities to cultivate religious meaning on their own terms. Thus, the negotiation over religious education became a struggle between two legitimate imperatives: the state's mandate for security and a unified identity, and society's desire for authentic spiritual practice and cultural preservation.

The most notable aspect of this assertion was the enduring flexibility of Quranic schools. As Abdullah and Hajjam (2019) note, these institutions underwent significant change, evolving beyond their traditional role as *kuttabs* focused solely on memorisation. They introduced structured educational programmes and innovative initiatives that boosted their reputation and showed their ability to stay relevant. This adaptation was a strategic move to continue appealing to parents and to emphasise their value as providers of holistic *tarbiya* (education of heart and character), setting them apart from the

state's more standardised and academicised offerings. For many families, these schools remained 'safe havens' (Abdullah & Hajjam, 2019), trusted precisely because they were seen as more deeply connected to the community's genuine religious and moral needs.

This societal pushback also served as a defence against the state's instrumental view of religion. While the state framed religious education through the lens of national identity and security (Ghanem, 2019), many Algerians continued to value it for its ability to offer moral guidance and a coherent worldview in a rapidly changing and globalising society—a need intensified by the challenges of shifting values and fractured social norms (Hebeiter & Rabah, 2022; Ben Ramadan, 2020). The value of Quranic schools was seen as safeguarding the "core ideals of national identity" and acting as "impregnable fortresses" against the erosion of social and moral norms (Al-Muqaddim, 2012). This reveals a crucial divergence in priorities: where the state viewed religion as a tool for legitimacy, significant parts of society regarded it as the foundational bedrock for moral order and personal meaning.

As regional scholars have shown, the state's efforts to regulate religion often conflict with conservative groups who see these measures as excessive (Cavatorta, 2006; Storm, 2007). In Algeria, this pattern frequently occurs within the education system. Attempts by the Ministry of Education to reform religious curricula have faced strong opposition from Islamists and conservatives, who accuse the state of trying to 'eliminate religious education' under the pretence of modernising it or combating extremism (Zenaz, 2021). This ongoing tension highlights the limits of the state's hegemonic ambitions and exposes the deep societal struggles to maintain the independence of religious instruction, a conflict that remains a defining feature of Algeria's post-independence political landscape (Werenfels, 2007; Volpi, 2003).

Consequently, the state's goal of complete control remained incomplete. Algerian society, through a mix of adaptation, persistence, and defiance, effectively maintained a vital space for Islamic education that reflected its own values and views of faith. This historical friction directly shaped the dual environment that parents now face: a state system ensuring certified moderation versus a community system providing authentic tarbiya. It is this very tension that explains a common parental approach: a pragmatic decision to utilise both systems, aiming to gain the benefits of the state's order and the community's perceived authenticity.

3.8. Conclusion

This chapter has provided a detailed, multi-layered profile of the Quranic school (Msid/Kuttab) in Algeria, progressing from its profound theological roots to its complex modern-day reality. It

demonstrated that the importance of Islamic education is grounded in a comprehensive theological framework, considering it a vital religious duty for Muslim parents and shaping their expectations for an education that includes spiritual (akhirah) and worldly (dunya) objectives.

The analysis traced the historical development of these institutions, from their position as the dominant system of learning to their targeted dismantling during the colonial era, their remarkable endurance through strategies of infrastructural persistence, ideological reform, and spiritual mobilisation, and their eventual transformation in the post-independence period. A central theme of this history is the ongoing negotiation between the state, which aims to co-opt and bureaucratise religious education for nation-building and security, and society, which seeks to preserve the autonomy and holistic spiritual role (tarbiya) of community-based Quranic schools. This negotiation has created the dualistic educational landscape that characterises modern Algeria: a state system providing standardised Islamic instruction and a resilient network of traditional Quranic schools.

Ultimately, this chapter identifies the central reference point, the institution itself, that Algerian Muslim parents turn to when shaping their beliefs. By analysing the Quranic school's ideals, pedagogical methods, historical resilience, and evolving social roles, this study provides the essential framework for understanding the subjective, lived experiences of the parents who choose them. The tensions highlighted—between memorisation and understanding, tradition and modernity, state control and community autonomy, and spiritual tarbiya and academic credentialism—are not merely academic issues; they form the very boundaries within which parental decisions are made.

Chapter 4

Faith Development in Childhood

4.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the theoretical and practical foundations of children's faith development by examining and comparing key Western and Islamic viewpoints. It offers a critical discussion of major

psychological and educational theories of faith development in Western contexts, such as those proposed by Fowler, Erikson, and Piaget. It contrasts these with Islamic understandings of spiritual formation grounded in Qur'anic pedagogy, Islamic philosophy, and religious practices. The chapter seeks to identify both common ground and differences between these traditions, focusing on how children's religious identities are shaped within diverse cultural environments.

The discussion begins by outlining key Western and Islamic perspectives, followed by an exploration of how children's faith is formed. The following sections analyse the influence of formal and informal education, the effects of different schooling environments, and the unique role of religious instruction. The chapter then examines the connection between cognitive development and faith, including the importance of memory-based learning, before addressing the challenges posed by modern societal trends to traditional faith transmission.

A central theme of this chapter is the significant influence of parents, families, educators, and the broader society in shaping a child's religious and moral worldview. Parental involvement, cultural expectations, and school environments all play crucial roles in transmitting faith and values to the younger generation. These influences are examined in both Western and Islamic contexts to better understand their roles in the children's faith formation process.

This chapter directly addresses the four research questions of the thesis. Reviewing and analysing different models of faith development helps contextualise the perspectives of Muslim parents, school administrators, teachers, and imams, and elucidates how Quranic schools function as tools of cultural and religious socialisation. The chapter also provides a theoretical foundation to understand why parents choose to enrol their children in Quranic schools and examines the modern challenges faced by these institutions within broader trends in faith development and education.

4.2. Western and Islamic Perspectives on Children's Faith Development

This section provides a comparative analysis of faith development theories in both Western and Islamic contexts. While Western approaches, such as those proposed by James Fowler (1981), Erik Erikson (1963), and Jean Piaget, often emphasise psychological and cognitive stages of moral and faith growth, Islamic perspectives tend to adopt a more holistic view, grounding faith development in spiritual, familial, and community practices. By comparing these frameworks, the section aims to identify points of convergence and divergence in how children's faith is understood, nurtured, and expressed across different worldviews.

This comparison is crucial for two reasons: firstly, it emphasises the inherent strengths and limitations of each tradition, and secondly, it offers a deeper understanding of how Muslim children in Algeria might experience faith development within both traditional Quranic schooling and broader social environments. Moreover, these comparisons will aid in analysing perspectives gathered from parents, imams, school leaders, and teachers in the empirical part of this thesis.

Throughout this section, particular focus is given to the roles of family, community, and schooling, which are recognised in both traditions as key influences on children's religious development. By comparing Western and Islamic ideas about how children develop faith, this discussion offers a clear basis to better understand and assess the research questions. This comparative approach not only places Algerian Quranic schooling within wider educational and religious discourses but also allows for critical engagement with both modern pedagogical methods and enduring traditional practices.

4.2.1. Western Ideas on Children's Faith Development

A number of influential theories have been developed in the West to explain human growth and development, many of which are known as stage theories. These theories propose that individuals progress through distinct stages as they mature, each marked by specific developmental milestones. Although these frameworks suggest a linear and sequential path of development, it is now widely recognised that human growth is not always so fixed. Life experiences and individual circumstances can lead people to revisit, skip, or even regress in certain stages (Hebert, 2016). Human development theories aim to understand how individuals grow and flourish by examining the personal, familial, and societal factors that support well-being, connection, and ethical living. In this sense, developmental psychology and religious traditions often serve parallel purposes; both seek to explore what it means to live a meaningful or 'good-enough' life (Kelcourse, 2015). Faith development theories specifically examine how an individual's faith evolves across the lifespan. These frameworks offer valuable insights into the processes and stages involved in developing religious belief and identity. They emphasise the interplay between cognitive development, personal experience, and social context. Scholars such as James Fowler and others have proposed models that trace the trajectory of faith from childhood through adulthood, each focusing on different dimensions of religious growth (Powers et al., 2001).

This section examines key Western theories on how children develop faith, highlighting influential scholars such as Jean Piaget, Erik Erikson, James Fowler, and John Westfold. These theories typically focus on psychological and cognitive stages through which children progress in their understanding of faith, morality, and identity. By analysing these perspectives, we can gain insight into the processes of faith development that have shaped much of the academic discourse in this field. This overview also

prepares the ground for comparing Western ideas with Islamic approaches to faith development later in the chapter.

Jean Piaget's book *The Construction of Reality in the Child* (1954) investigates how children come to understand the world around them as they develop. Piaget describes that children progress through various stages of thinking. Initially, they learn through what they see and touch, but gradually, they begin to consider more complex and abstract concepts, such as beliefs, values, and even faith. This mode of thinking has been highly influential in the West, especially in how scholars interpret faith development. For instance, James Fowler used Piaget's theories to create his own model of how faith matures in stages. In this thesis, Piaget's work illustrates how Western perspectives often link faith development with brain growth and reasoning. His theoretical framework is also revisited later in this chapter, particularly in the section on cognition and faith development, where his impact on understanding the relationship between cognitive development and spiritual insight is further examined.

Building on Piaget's emphasis on cognitive growth, Erikson's theory highlights the significant role of social and emotional factors in shaping faith development, particularly during the challenging teenage years. His book, *Childhood and Society* (1963), adds an important dimension to understanding children's faith development within the Western tradition. Unlike Jean Piaget, who mainly focused on cognitive stages, Erikson proposed a psychosocial model of development, where social relationships and life experiences influence a person's sense of identity and faith. Erikson believed that as children grow, they face a series of psychological challenges or 'crises' that need to be resolved for healthy development. One of the most crucial stages occurs during adolescence, when individuals strive to establish a clear sense of identity. At this point, Erikson notes, young people often begin to explore spiritual and moral questions more deeply. He writes, 'Adolescents are sometimes morbidly, often curiously, preoccupied with what they appear to be in the eyes of others as compared with what they feel they are' (Erikson, 1963, p. 261). This tension between internal belief and external perception is vital in developing religious identity. His theory helps explain why faith can become a central concern during adolescence, when individuals are deciding not only who they are, but what they believe. In the Western context, then, faith is not solely a matter of cognitive ability but also of navigating identity within social settings. This link between identity and faith is supported by King (2003), who applied Erikson's framework to examine how adolescents engage with religion during identity formation. In his study, King found that religious involvement provides adolescents with a framework for meaning-making and self-definition, especially during times of social and emotional change. Faith, in this perspective, becomes a tool for exploring personal values and making life choices, underscoring the deep connection between psychosocial development and spiritual growth.

While Piaget's cognitive theory explains how children develop the ability to think abstractly, and Erikson's psychosocial stages emphasise how faith can be shaped by identity and relationships, James Fowler brings these two strands together in his comprehensive theory of faith development. In his seminal work *Stages of Faith* (1981), Fowler explicitly acknowledges the influence of both Piaget and Erikson, integrating cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions into a unified model. He proposed that faith evolves through identifiable stages, each marked by increasing complexity in thought, emotional depth, and social awareness. This move from developmental psychology into spiritual growth allowed Fowler to bridge the gap between psychological development and religious commitment, making his theory especially influential in Western religious education and pastoral care.

Fowler is recognised for pioneering the most common approach to developing one's faith (Bunnell, 2016). Fowler's theory served as a basis for several investigations (Streib, 2005), and his studies of faith and spirituality still profoundly influence the current body of work on the topic (Siner, 2015). The theory of faith development was initially established in the 1970s (Fowler, 1974) and 1980s (Fowler, 1981) as a framework for understanding the evolution of the human concept of God or a higher being, and how the influence of this higher being affects core values, beliefs, and meanings in individuals' personal lives and relationships with others (Fowler & Dell, 2006). In 1981, James Fowler published *Stages of Faith: The Psychology of Human Development and the Quest for Meaning*. Often regarded as innovative, Fowler's study explains six stages of faith. Building on Piaget and Kohlberg's theories, Fowler's model illustrates the stages individuals navigate as their faith matures. This theory can be applied to those in traditional faiths as well as individuals following alternative spiritualities or secular worldviews (Hebert, 2016). FDT provides a multidisciplinary perspective on how religious and spiritual values progress alongside behaviour throughout the human lifespan (Boone, 2018). Furthermore, faith development transcends cultural boundaries, with cross-cultural research and comparisons highlighting its global relevance.

Building on this fundamental understanding, James Fowler's FDT views 'faith' as a way of finding meaning and purpose in life, which can be based on religious or non-religious values (Fowler, 1991; Mallery & Mallery, 2022). Fowler emphasises the deep and personal aspects of faith and points out that it transcends religion and belief systems. According to Fowler, religion is the fundamental orientation of a person's existence that determines how they seek and find meaning in life. Rather than focusing predominantly on specific religious doctrines, he suggests that faith relates to the broader, dynamic process by which individuals find meaning and direction (Kelcourse, 2015). This perspective invites a deeper contemplation of what or to whom people dedicate their lives and ideals.

Fowler and Dell (2006) describe faith as a process that shapes beliefs, values, and meanings. It provides coherence and direction to individuals' lives, links them through common trusts and loyalties to others,

grounds their personal beliefs and community affiliations in a sense of relatedness to a greater frame of reference, and allows individuals to confront and manage the limiting constraints of human life, depending on what has the quality of ultimacy in their lives.

The theory of faith development combines principles of developmental psychology with a tradition of liberal theology rooted in Christian thought. This theory arose from in-depth interviews conducted with children and adults in North America and offers insight into how an individual's faith develops over time (Fowler, 2001). It emphasises how the growth of faith is influenced by psychological development and simultaneously shaped by theological perspectives. The theory connects both disciplines to provide a comprehensive understanding of faith as an evolving aspect of human experience.

The core of Fowler's theory is his identification of six stages of faith, which describe how individuals' beliefs and values evolve over time.

Stage 0: Primal Faith (Infancy)

This initial stage is a pre-language disposition—a comprehensive emotional orientation of trust that counteracts mistrust—and manifests through the mutuality in one's relationships with parents and others. Primary faith helps infants to overcome or ease the distress caused by separations during their development. It establishes the essential rituals of care, exchange, and mutuality. Although it does not determine the ultimate path of our faith, it lays the foundation for future faith.

Stage 1: intuitive-projective faith (early childhood)

Stories, symbols, and gestures, free from the constraints of logical thinking, nourish imagination and blend with perception and feelings to create enduring faith illustrations. These images reflect the protective and intimidating powers that surround a person's existence. This stage relates to the development of moral sentiments and norms during a child's second year of life. It also aligns with the child's understanding of taboos and sacred objects, and the struggle to balance autonomy and will with shame and construction in the child's evolving self. During this period, children use their interactions with parents or other adults to form conscious representations of God.

Stage 2: Mythic-Literal Faith (Elementary School Years to Early Adolescence)

Concrete operational thinking, or the emerging ability to reason, develops here to help us organise the universe using causality, space, time, and number categories. We can now distinguish between reality and imagination. We may adopt the perspectives of others, enabling us to capture life and meaning in narratives and stories.

Stage 3: Synthetic-Conventional Faith (Middle Adolescence)

The rise of formal operational thinking facilitates reliance on abstract ideas and concepts to understand the world. The individual can now reflect on past experiences and seek out meanings and patterns. Simultaneously, concerns about one's future, identity, profession, career, or vocation, and personal relationships become more prominent. These enhanced cognitive skills enable mutual perspective-taking. During friendships, or 'puppy love,' young people become aware of how their behaviours towards others mirror their own emotions. These newly close relationships with important people align with a longing for a personal relationship with God, in which we feel known and loved in profound and comprehensive ways.

Stage 4: Individuative-Reflective Faith (often in young adulthood)

On the one hand, to progress to the individuative-reflective stage, we must question, explore, and rediscover the values and ideas that have guided us so far in life. These become explicit (consciously chosen) commitments rather than tacit [unexamined] ones. Now, one maintains that commitment and identity through choice and explicit consent rather than unconscious formation and implicit dedication...By the time we reach adolescence, we embody a variety of characters to play in our lives. The goal of the Individuative stage is to establish an 'executive ego', the 'I' that supervises and 'possesses' all these tasks and relationships, but isn't fully represented in any of them. It involves taking control of one's life in new ways. It requires a new level of reflective autonomy and responsibility.

Stage 5: Conjunctive faith (the middle years or beyond)

This stage centres on accepting and integrating opposing ends or polarities in one's life. Symbols, tales, metaphors, and myths from our own and other traditions seem to hold value here... After critically examining the traditions and interpreting their meanings into conceptual knowledge, one seeks a deeper connection with the reality that the symbols signify...At this level, individuals must become captivated by the biblical narrative and allow it to shape and reform their lives rather than merely interpreting the text and creating their own meanings.

Stage 6: Universalizing faith

It is a significant and rare milestone in spiritual development. Individuals at this stage experience a profound sense of unity with God or a higher power. Their spiritual worldview transcends dispute or disagreement and is firmly committed to compassion, justice, and community. These individuals dedicate themselves to selfless acts of kindness and work tirelessly to end global conflict, violence, and oppression. They eagerly anticipate a future filled with love and justice, often depicted as the coming of God's kingdom or a peaceful world.

Streib (2001) provides a valuable extension of Fowler's Faith Development Theory (FDT), building directly on its core stages while offering a more adaptable and context-aware approach. He contends

that the rigid, sequential structure of Fowler's six-stage model may overlook the complex and often nonlinear ways individuals actually experience faith throughout their lives. In response, Streib introduces the concept of religious styles, which highlights that individuals can move smoothly between different expressions of faith, shaped by cultural, social, and personal experiences. This important development challenges the idea of universal linear progression and instead advocates for a more dynamic understanding of faith growth. Streib's contribution is especially relevant to this thesis, as it supports the view that while Fowler's theory remains a cornerstone in Western psychological frameworks, it may be most effective when used alongside other models or adapted when applied in non-Western contexts, where spiritual, communal, and moral aspects are more central to faith development.

John Westerhoff has also expanded Fowler's theory of faith development and emphasised that faith progresses through different stages (Astley, 2018, Westerhoff, 2012). This view stresses that faith is not merely a human accomplishment but begins with the understanding that it is a divine gift granted by God (Boiliu, 2021). It highlights that the development of faith is both a spiritual blessing and a developmental journey.

Furthermore, while Fowler's model offers a detailed psychological framework for understanding the developmental stages of faith, it is equally important to consider perspectives that highlight the relational and community aspects of faith formation. John Westerhoff's phases of faith complement Fowler's by adopting a more community-centred approach, emphasising how religion is nurtured and passed on within social and religious contexts. Discussing both academics aims to provide a more comprehensive view of faith development that includes individual psychological growth as well as community and relational influences, offering a broader perspective to analyse the role of Quranic schools in faith formation.

Westerhoff offered two different theories on the development of faith in his books. The first, a four-stage theory, was published in his book *Will Our Children Have Faith?* (1976), and it was later condensed into three phases in *A Faithful Church* (1981). The following section will introduce his original four-stage theory (Westerhoff, 1976), followed by his three-stage model. According to Westerhoff, faith develops like the rings of a tree, with each ring contributing to and altering the tree while building on what preceded it. Westerhoff uses a tree analogy to highlight four rings that are essential in the growth process.

Stage 1: Experienced Faith

At its core, faith is something we experience from a young age, whether in everyday life or through a significant shift in beliefs within a new religious system. We acquire the faith that is essential for those

who care about us. The way it influences and shapes their lives has left an indelible mark on us, forming the basis of our own faith. The level of faith is usually linked to key developmental stages when a person depends heavily on others, such as in early childhood.

Stage 2: Affiliative Faith

Another phase is established as an individual increasingly demonstrates the beliefs, values, and practices of their family, organisation, or church. The person adopts characteristics such as nurturing others and is recognised as an approved partner, a member of the faith community. Such involvement may be formalised through membership, baptism, or confirmation, or it can be understood as the case of regular participants who do not formally join a church. This stage of development is known as a testing period. It represents a match between the individual and peer expectations. People develop a strong bond with their community when traditions, beliefs, and practices are aligned. This connection reduces individual differences by emphasising unity and shared beliefs. During this period, their understanding of faith is shaped by the need to belong, feel secure, and develop a sense of identity. This phase of faith is most evident throughout early adolescence.

Stage 3: Searching Faith

At this stage, people realise that their own beliefs may differ from those of their community. They start to question widely accepted beliefs and practices. This realisation comes from recognising that their beliefs have been more influenced by others, such as parents and congregations, than by their own views. They need to decide whether to interpret their faith independently or to follow the group's beliefs. During this period, individuals often explore other faiths and may seek connections with people or organisations that can help them develop their own understanding and practice of faith.

Stage 4: Owned Faith

Individuals reach their highest level of faith development during this stage. This phase often involves a conversion experience in which the individual fully embraces their beliefs and accepts personal responsibility for their faith and practices. They focus not only on believing but also on actively living out their faith. Westerhoff views this stage as reflecting God's goal for everyone, encouraging them to achieve their full potential in their spiritual journey. John Westerhoff's (1980) revised theory sees our lives as people of faith as an ongoing pilgrimage that progressively unfolds through increasingly deeper and more comprehensive expressions of faith. This journey comprises three distinct stages, which are as follows:

Stage 1: Affiliative Faith

Affiliative Faith is the initial stage, often seen in young people during their high school years. At this stage, religion is influenced by sensory experiences and relationships with others. Children learn to trust

people, themselves, and the world through these experiences, not just through instruction. How parents and adults interact with children has a greater impact on their religion than words alone. During this phase, the community and its traditions foster a sense of belonging and act as a source of authority. Being part of a group is vital for feeling accepted and respected.

Stage 2: Searching Faith

This stage typically begins in high school and extends into early adulthood. During this period, individuals reflect on their beliefs, form critical judgments, and experiment with new ideas. Doubt and the pursuit of personal meaning become essential. People increasingly seek their own understanding and truth rather than relying on the views of others. This stage involves challenging and reassessing inherited beliefs, leading to greater independence in one's faith.

Stage 3: Mature Faith

It begins in middle adulthood and continues to develop throughout life. It combines the communal connection of affiliative faith with the independence of searching faith. At this stage, people are governed not just by communal authority or their own logical understanding, but also by a personal, free-willed relationship with God. While belonging to a group is crucial, people with mature faith are strong enough in their convictions to confront the community when necessary. Growth occurs through encounters with people who encourage and inspire greater faith development. Even mature faith retains a sense of fundamental, childlike trust.

In summary, the various theories of faith development offer a comprehensive understanding of how faith progresses from childhood to adulthood. Despite their different approaches, these theories collectively emphasise the importance of early experiences, cognitive growth, and social contexts in shaping faith. These models provide a detailed insight into how faith changes throughout life, establishing a foundation for future research into the limits and challenges of faith development theories.

4.2.1.1 Criticism of Faith Development Theory

Theories of human development are vital for understanding the complex process of growth and maturation. However, these theories are also subject to criticism. Feminists and womanists highlight that many of these theories are based on research involving middle-class Caucasian males, who are often regarded as the standard for 'normal' human development. This critique emphasises the importance of adopting a more inclusive approach to understanding human development, one that considers diverse experiences and backgrounds (Miller & Scholnick, 2000).

Along with this critique, several scholars argue that many developmental theories, often promoted as universally applicable, fail to translate successfully across different cultures. This highlights the need for a more culturally sensitive approach to studying human development. Such an approach recognises that various cultural, social, and environmental factors influence development, all of which can significantly affect individual experiences and developmental trajectories (Sue & Sue, 2012).

Although popular, the completeness of Fowler's faith-based development theory has been questioned (Dehann et al., 2011). Fowler's FDT has been criticised for adopting a linear approach, similar to Erikson's (1950/1963) stage theory. Both theories suggest a fixed progression of stages in human development that does not account for the cyclical or episodic nature of growth. According to Knefelkamp (1990), stage theories like Erikson's fail to recognise the complexity and diversity of human development. Newberg (2017) argues that while this model offers useful insights, it may not apply equally to everyone. Given these criticisms, it may be more beneficial to view faith development as a series of adaptable 'phases' rather than fixed stages.

Similarly, Streib (2001 & 2005) suggests that traditional faith development theory places too much emphasis on structural development and its progression through stages. Streib proposes a phenomenological approach to faith development, drawing on the ideas of Noam, Riccour, and Merleau-Ponty. He argues that life history, life world, and religious content become crucial elements in understanding an individual's faith development.

The updated faith development theory also removes Fowler's rigid stage model. Streib (2001) suggests that faith development styles come and go in a person's life like waves. As these styles emerge and submerge, they may reappear in some form. This explains what Streib (2001) calls the 'fundamentalist revival.' Fowler's stages of faith are often assessed through either lengthy interviews or shorter surveys, but many of these surveys focus solely on religious faith, making it difficult for non-religious people to take part. Mallery and Mallery (2022) propose a new 'Centers of Value and Quest for Meaning Scale', which could help measure faith development for both believers and non-believers by emphasising personal values and meaning-making, rather than just religion. Their research demonstrated that this new scale can more flexibly capture important aspects of Fowler's theory, such as moral development and perspective-taking.

A recent study by Archer (2024) reexamines Fowler's FDT, which was frequently used during the twentieth century to assess faith formation, especially among young people. After analysing empirical data on faith formation activities, Archer found that Fowler's developmental stages are no longer

entirely relevant for understanding current faith development. Instead, Archer introduces the concept of 'faith engagement', arguing that it more accurately describes how individuals interact with their faith. Faith engagement, as proposed, can be viewed on a spectrum, illustrating how different spiritual activities either enhance or diminish a person's overall faith experience. Archer contends that faith engagement is more adaptable than Fowler's stage-based model. For instance, a person might feel deeply engaged during individual prayer (corresponding to Fowler's Stage 4: individual-reflective Faith) but disconnected during group prayer (which could align with Fowler's Stage 0: Primal-Undifferentiated Faith). This does not imply a lack of faith but simply that some activities evoke a stronger response.

In this view, faith is not a fixed progression through stages, but rather a dynamic process influenced by engagement in various activities. This approach may foster a more nuanced understanding of faith by examining which actions enhance or diminish spiritual satisfaction over time. This method challenges Fowler's fixed stages, advocating for a more personalised and activity-centred assessment of faith.

In conclusion, Western theories on children's faith development, based on the cognitive and psychosocial frameworks of Piaget, Erikson, and Fowler, offer valuable insights into how faith evolves alongside cognitive growth and identity formation. These models underline the interaction between individual reasoning, social relationships, and internal crises as central to shaping religious identity. However, as scholars like Streib note, these theories often assume a straightforward progression and may not fully reflect the complex, dynamic, and culturally diverse ways faith develops in real life. Therefore, while Western approaches provide a foundational understanding of faith development, their use, especially in diverse and non-Western contexts, benefits from flexibility and openness to additional perspectives. This nuanced view promotes a more holistic appreciation of faith as both an intellectual and a profoundly relational journey for children.

4.2.2. Islamic Ideas on Children's Faith Development

Islamic perspectives on children's faith development offer a rich understanding that integrates spiritual, moral, and communal aspects. Rooted firmly in the teachings of the Qur'an and the prophetic traditions (Sunnah), Islamic faith development emphasises not only cognitive growth but also the nurturing of the soul (ruh) and character (akhlaq) within a framework of divine guidance and social responsibility (Nasr & Michaud, 1976; Kamali, 2008). Unlike many Western models that focus mainly on individual cognitive and psychosocial stages, Islamic views see faith formation as a continuous and communal process, closely connected to concepts such as fitrah (innate disposition), tarbiyyah (moral and spiritual upbringing), and the collective identity of the ummah (community) (Othman & Al-Ghazali, 2010; Abu-Rabi',

2003). This approach underscores the vital role of family, educational institutions, and community in fostering a deep-rooted and balanced faith from early childhood (Hashim, 2016; Sardar, 2011). This section examines how Islamic thought influences children's religious development, stressing the integration of knowledge, spirituality, and social responsibility in nurturing faith.

Syed Muhammad Naquib Al-Attas (1980), in his influential work **The Concept of Education in Islam**, presents a distinctly Islamic perspective on how faith and personal development are deeply interconnected. He argues that Islamic education extends beyond solely intellectual growth to encompass a holistic process involving spiritual, ethical, and emotional development. According to Al-Attas, true education in Islam aims to cultivate a balanced human being who understands their purpose in life and their relationship with God. He states that Education in Islam is not merely about acquiring knowledge but about fostering the balanced growth of the entire personality through the nurturing of the spirit, intellect, rational self, feelings, and senses. This illustrates that faith in Islam is not viewed as something children merely grow into as a phase; rather, it is an essential, divinely rooted part of their being from an early age. Al-Attas also highlights the importance of community and tradition in shaping religious identity, noting that a child's development is closely linked to their connection with family, society, and inherited religious values. This view contrasts with Western models, which often separate moral or faith development from spirituality, treating them more as stages linked to cognitive or social maturity. In the Islamic perspective, as explained by Al-Attas, faith is innate (*fitrah*), and education aims to awaken and nurture it, not just teach it.

To truly understand how faith develops in Islamic thought, it is important to examine how early Muslim scholars approached the concept of the self and the soul, known as *Ilm al-Nafs*, the science of the soul. Thinkers like Al-Ghazali, Ibn Sina (Avicenna), and Al-Razi believed that understanding the human mind could not be separated from spiritual growth. For them, cultivating a healthy inner life meant remaining connected to God and living according to religious and moral values. As Haque (2004) explains in *Psychology from an Islamic Perspective*, these scholars were ahead of their time, proposing ideas that in some ways resemble modern psychology, yet always grounded in Islamic beliefs. They regarded faith as something inherently present within every person (called *fitrah*), which should be nurtured through learning, prayer, and good character. This concept is rooted in the Qur'an: "So set your face steadily and truly to the Faith: (Establish) Allah's handiwork according to the pattern on which He has made mankind: no change (let there be) in the work (wrought) by Allah: that is the true Religion: but most among mankind understand not" (Qur'an, 30:30). Unlike many Western theories that see faith as something that develops later through stages, Islamic psychology regards it as both the foundation and the aim of personal growth. Rather than conflicting, these perspectives complement each other; Western theories help explain how cognitive and emotional stages evolve, while Islamic views emphasise the central importance of spirituality and community in guiding that development.

Building on this understanding of fitrah, Islamic scholars have long emphasised that true education is not merely about accumulating information, but about developing into a well-rounded, ethical, and spiritually conscious individual. The study 'Human Psychology (Fitrah) from Islamic Perspective' by Bhat (2016) highlights that education in Islam aims to guide all aspects of a person's growth—spiritual, intellectual, moral, and social—by adhering to the teachings of the Quran and the Sunnah. The paper clarifies that the primary goal is to help individuals recognise and realise their natural disposition (fitrah) and live according to God's guidance. It also reminds us that, although no one is perfect, the journey of self-improvement through knowledge, good deeds, and strong character is central to what it means to be human in Islam. This underscores the idea that faith is not merely something children develop over time, but something already present within them, waiting to be nurtured through love, teaching, and a supportive environment.

Another key voice in the Islamic understanding of faith development is Imam Al-Ghazali, whose classical work *Ihya Ulum al-Din* (The Revival of the Religious Sciences) remains one of the most influential texts in Islamic scholarship. In this work, Al-Ghazali emphasises that moral and spiritual education must begin early in a child's life, before habits and desires become firmly rooted (Al-Ghazali, 1993). He believed that the heart is like fertile soil; if planted with the right seeds of faith, ethics, and remembrance of God, it will grow into a life of spiritual fulfilment. However, if neglected, it can be overrun by harmful traits. Modern scholars such as Nasr (2006) and Auda (2008) echo this point, noting that Al-Ghazali regarded early religious education not merely as a duty but as a spiritual safeguard to protect the child's innate goodness, which Islam calls fitrah. According to Al-Ghazali, the role of parents and teachers is crucial, as they shape the child's soul by modelling good character, guiding behaviour, and embedding religious values through everyday practice. His teachings align with the broader Islamic view that faith is not only conveyed through words but is transmitted through loving relationships, ethical routines, and a nurturing spiritual environment. This enduring perspective upholds the idea that faith development in Islam is an intentional and holistic process that begins in the earliest years of life and continues throughout one's spiritual journey.

Nasr and Michaud (1976) offer a compelling vision of Islamic education rooted in a holistic worldview, where knowledge (*ilm*) and faith (*īmān*) are inseparably linked. They believe that fostering faith in children goes beyond memorising religious texts or performing rituals; it involves the full integration of the body, mind, and soul within a divine framework. They contend that Islamic education is not just about transmitting information but about cultivating a sense of sacred purpose and spiritual discipline, nurturing children's moral and emotional growth through lived experience and community involvement. This view aligns closely with classical Islamic traditions, such as those of Al-Ghazālī and Ibn Sīnā, who also highlighted ethical development and inner purification (*tazkiyah*) as vital parts of learning.

While Nasr and Michaud's portrayal highlights the richness and depth of Islamic pedagogy, it tends to idealise traditional forms of education without fully addressing the pedagogical challenges faced by contemporary Islamic schools. For example, the theoretical integration of body, mind, and soul may not be consistently implemented in practice, particularly in systems where rote memorisation (hifz) prevails and opportunities for spiritual reflection or emotional growth are limited (Talbani, 1996). Furthermore, Nasr's traditionalist perspective often assumes a stable, homogenous Muslim community, which may overlook the diverse sociocultural and digital realities encountered by Muslim children today. Despite these limitations, their focus on spiritual intentionality in education remains a valuable correction to overly secular or utilitarian models of learning, reminding educators that the ultimate aim of Islamic education is not merely intellectual achievement, but the development of a morally responsible and spiritually awakened individual.

Similarly, Salleh and Leman (2010) proposed a comprehensive Islamic model of spiritual development that places *fitrah*, the natural inclination towards faith in God, as the central starting point of a child's moral and spiritual journey. In their model, *tarbiyyah*, or nurturing education, plays a crucial role in cultivating this innate potential through regular guidance in religious practice, ethical behaviour, and emotional nurturing. They emphasise that faith does not develop in isolation but is deeply shaped by the surrounding family environment, school system, and the broader Muslim community. Their study, which examined the perceptions and practices of Islamic education teachers in Malaysia, revealed that educators viewed spiritual development not as a separate domain but as a goal linked to all subjects and daily interactions. This approach encourages holistic growth, where cognitive, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of the child are developed together. By grounding education in values such as sincerity (*ikhlas*), discipline (*taqwa*), and respect (*adab*), the model supports the idea that Islamic spiritual development is continuous and lifelong, requiring active cultivation by both educators and parents. Salleh and Leman's work not only emphasises classical Islamic teachings but also presents a practical framework for contemporary educators aiming to integrate faith formation into daily teaching and parenting practices in Muslim societies.

In contrast to many Western frameworks of faith development, such as those proposed by Fowler (1981), Erikson (1963), and Piaget (1954), which focus heavily on individual psychological stages and cognitive maturity, the Islamic model as articulated by Salleh and Leman emphasises communal, spiritual, and moral dimensions at the centre of faith development. While Western theories often examine how faith evolves through internal questioning and abstract reasoning, the Islamic model highlights the importance of divine revelation, spiritual discipline, and social responsibility from early childhood. This distinction is particularly relevant in the context of Quranic schools in Algeria, where family expectations, religious instruction, and cultural values significantly influence how children

internalise their faith. This comparative perspective directly informs the research questions of this study, especially in understanding how parents, teachers, and religious leaders perceive the role of Quranic schools in shaping children's spiritual and moral identities (Questions 1 and 2), and how these institutions implement Islamic educational values such as tarbiyyah and fitrah (Questions 2 and 3). Furthermore, it aids in exploring how these traditional models respond to modern challenges (Question 4), such as secular influences and evolving family dynamics.

While Western theories such as Fowler's Faith Development Theory have long shaped understandings of religious growth, insights from Islamic perspectives reveal significant differences that demand a careful re-examination of these models. Specifically, Ok and Gennerich (2024) argue that although FDT has contributed greatly to the academic conversation on faith development, it relies heavily on cognitive development frameworks and tends to overlook the deeper spiritual, emotional, and community-oriented aspects central to Islamic thought. They point out that terms like "faith" and "religiosity" may be used in ways that do not fully align with Islamic understandings, and that the theory's emphasis on abstract reasoning and individual progress reflects a secular, Eurocentric worldview. From an Islamic standpoint, faith is not merely about reaching higher cognitive stages; it also involves inner commitment, emotional connection to God, and the nurturing influence of family and community. The authors stress that FDT may not fully reflect how faith develops in Muslim children, where spiritual growth is deeply rooted in fitrah (natural disposition), tarbiyyah (moral nurturing), and strong bonds to religious identity and communal life. This critique highlights the importance of considering cultural and religious contexts alongside Faith Development Theory when studying how faith evolves in Muslim communities like Algeria.

Building on this foundation, it becomes crucial to examine how these core Islamic principles, particularly fitrah and tarbiyyah, are implemented in real-world settings. Faith development in Islam, while rooted in shared theological and moral values, is not uniform. The practical application of these ideals often mirrors the sociopolitical, historical, and educational circumstances unique to each Muslim-majority society.

While Islamic faith development is rooted in core ideas like fitrah (the natural inclination toward belief in God) and tarbiyyah (nurturing a child's faith and character), the ways these values are implemented can vary widely across different Muslim countries. As explained by Daun and Arjmand (2005) in the *International Handbook on Globalisation, Education and Policy Research*, most Muslim communities share a desire to raise children with strong Islamic morals, a connection to the wider Muslim community (Umma), and respect for Sharia law. However, differences arise based on each country's history, particularly colonial influences, the strength of Islamic institutions, and their exposure to globalization. For instance, in some places, Islamic education is deeply integrated into the public school system, whereas

in others it may be more community-based or limited to after-school Quranic classes. This demonstrates that while the spiritual aims of Islamic education remain consistent, the methods of teaching and passing on faith can look very different depending on local circumstances. Recognising these differences helps us understand that faith development in Islam involves not just belief but also how families, communities, and schools adapt to their specific environments.

This variation in how Islamic education is practiced across different countries is particularly relevant for understanding children's faith development in Algeria, where historical, cultural, and political factors have shaped the distinctive role of Qur'anic schools. By examining how Algerian families, educators, and religious leaders engage with Islamic education, we can gain better insight into how local expressions of tarbiyyah and faith formation reflect both shared Islamic principles and specific national experiences.

4.3. Faith Formation of Children

Spiritual formation and growth in faith are important concerns for religious communities. Faith communities seek meaning and genuine relationships. According to Matthaei (2004), an intentional faith formation process is one way to achieve this. Faith formation and faith development are connected, although faith development usually relates to stages, whereas faith formation presents a holistic view that includes various aspects, such as development. Human beings experience different types of development. Scholars have created theories explaining how individuals progress in physical, cognitive, and moral development (Keeley, 2010). Since the present study focuses on faith formation, it is crucial to consider how children develop faith through Quranic education.

According to Meerangani et al. (2022), children are regarded as a gift from God. In Islamic teachings, humankind is entrusted with the responsibility of educating its children. Therefore, parents aim to nurture their children within Islamic principles. This approach facilitates spiritual growth and exploration. Humans are born with an innate desire to follow and serve God, although this desire is shaped by various factors throughout life (Eppinga & Marcus, 2017). Many elements influence a person's spiritual development, which begins early in life. Consequently, religious teachings and values are cultivated during childhood.

According to Sartika et al. (2020), children acquire knowledge mainly through socialisation, such as mimicking and observing adult behaviour. However, they also learn by examining the spiritual practices of adults in their environment, especially those closest to them.

The community's responsibility is to nurture identity and vocation within a faith tradition. Religious experiences or personal interactions often uncover the deepest secrets of God's presence and love (Roberto, 2020). When people engage with faith-related groups or networks, these networks influence their spiritual development by supporting certain expressions of faith. These expressions are typically conveyed through beliefs or shared knowledge, reinforcing the individual's spiritual connections (Roberto, 2020). Faith communities support individuals in their life choices, and those with strong faith tend to be more confident and calmer than those with weaker faith (Joung, 2020).

The family, a vital part of a religious community, functions as the child's first educational institution, where they initially learn the family's faith. The role of parents in shaping their children's religious beliefs has been extensively studied, and families play a crucial role in influencing juvenile development (Boyatzis et al., 2006). Children often feel most content when their parents offer proper guidance (Goodman & Dyer, 2020). Parents are regarded as the primary influence in helping children develop faith, ensuring it becomes not only part of their education but also embedded in their daily lives (Merhaut, 2007).

In Islam, education comprises two main aspects: acquiring intellectual knowledge through logic and rational thought, followed by deepening spiritual understanding through Divine enlightenment (Demirel Ucan & Wright, 2019). Muslim parents believe that performing 'Zikr' regularly and engaging in additional activities that glorify God are essential. Parents should read the Quran to their children and encourage them to learn it early in life (Mahdi, 2019; Tabroni & Rahmania, 2022). Therefore, children are more likely to practice religious rituals and teachings if they see their parents living by their faith (Masrifatin et al., 2022). Numerous studies demonstrate that when parents actively adhere to the teachings of sacred texts, their children tend to adopt those teachings themselves (van Bergen et al., 2022). The emphasis on youth education in early Islamic history reflected the belief that raising children with Islamic principles was a sacred duty for both parents and society (Hashim & Jemali, 2017). Tibawi (1972) states that a child's mind is like a clean white sheet. Once something is written on it—whether right or wrong—it becomes difficult to erase or overwrite with new writing.

This dual focus on intellectual and spiritual growth in Islam complements certain ideas in Western psychological theories about childhood development and its lifelong effects. One influential theory is Freud's (Mitchell & Black, 1995) psychoanalytic theory, which emphasises the formative role of early childhood experiences. According to Freud, much of adult personality, behaviour, and emotional health are shaped by unconscious conflicts and experiences originating in childhood. These early experiences can lead to deep-rooted anxieties and behavioural patterns that persist into adulthood unless addressed. Therefore, Freud's theory highlights the vital importance of nurturing and supportive environments in early years to promote healthy psychological and emotional development. Consequently, children's

development within the home environment directly influences their behaviour and spiritual growth as adults (Van Niekerk & Breed, 2018).

It has been argued that children do not go to learn the faith; instead, they are always catching the faith, mostly catching it from their parents (Smith & Adameczyk, 2020). It is also argued that a person learns religion or faith through experience, but this experience has mainly been linked to the parents' intentions in shaping the faith in their children.

Van Niekerk (2018) examines the vital role parents play in their children's faith development within Afrikaans mainstream churches, using Osmer's (2008) Practical Theology approach. It combines faith development with early childhood theories, highlighting the importance of parental engagement in nurturing faith. Vygotsky's theory underscores that children learn through interactions with knowledgeable parents (Brooks, 2011). Freud and Erikson contend that early experiences influence long-term identity and behaviour (Brooks, 2011; Erikson, 1964). Additionally, empirical findings from Nel and Van der Westhuizen (2015) support the enduring impact of family on children's spiritual growth, even beyond church activities.

Childhood is a sensitive period for individuals' development. Therefore, their parents' attitudes have a crucial influence on them. Positive attitudes modelled beside young people positively affect their cognitive health. Scholars have discussed socialisation in spiritual growth, noting that a child's personal and social contextual factors, including parents, congregation, and peer groups, help children fully express their viewpoints on metaphysical topics (Boyatzis, 2005). For most children globally, these contextual factors are deeply rooted in cultural contexts that openly discuss or idolise deities. According to Idris et al. (2018), children are influenced by what they observe their parents do and what they are taught in school about metaphysical topics and God. When children attend school, their social interactions with peers will reflect this influence.

Parents play a vital role in guiding children to develop their faith by promoting its practical application and assisting them in overcoming any obstacles that may impede this process. While many barriers can obstruct a child's path to learning and practising religious teachings, children are more likely to overcome these challenges and strengthen their faith successfully when parents actively fulfil their role (Purwandari et al., 2022). According to Martinson (1997), Children learn what they live. These fundamental units of life form the foundational context of children's most meaningful relationships and daily experiences, as most children are born into or adopted by families. The relationship between faith construct dimensions is illustrated as follows:

This figure illustrates the relationship between the different dimensions of faith. In Islam, Ibn Taymiya (2003) divides faith into two categories: inner faith (Iman), which includes belief and attitude, and outer faith (Islam), which encompasses actions and behaviour. Educators are encouraged to focus on these aspects—belief, attitude, and behaviour—to foster balanced spiritual and religious growth in children. However, a broader perspective of Islamic religious education further divides religiosity into three essential components: Iman (belief and attitude), Ilm (knowledge), and Amal (behaviour). To ensure holistic religious development, Quranic schools should address all three components—belief, attitude, knowledge, and behaviour—allowing students to build a strong and well-rounded foundation in their faith (Shodiq et al., 2016). Devine (2011) explains that some public schools struggle to maintain their academic reputations, especially in an increasingly competitive, market-driven education system. In response, these schools often prioritise basic education and discipline over holistic approaches, including faith formation, which can lead to marginalisation (Lynch et al., 2012).

4.4. Education and Faith Development

This section examines the connection between education and faith development from a broad, fundamental perspective. It explains how education, in its widest sense, plays an essential role in promoting human growth. This overview prepares the ground for more specific discussions in later sections, which will explore particular educational contexts such as schooling, religious education, and faith development within institutional and community settings. By first considering the broad principles linking education and faith, the following sections will offer a more detailed look at their expressions and challenges across different environments.

Human development can be described as the physical, mental, spiritual, and relational changes that occur as individuals are born, mature, age, and die (Kelcourse, 2015). This ongoing process highlights the importance of education, which plays a vital role in fostering these changes. Therefore, the challenge of improving education has long been a concern for parents, scientists, and philosophers alike (Dajani, 2015).

As part of this intellectual undertaking, education produces a range of essential works for individuals, transforming them into subjects capable of thinking and volition (Ghuddah, 2018; Belinova et al., 2017; Sidik, 2023). This transformation emphasises the vital role of education in human development,

promoting cognitive and moral growth that shapes both individuals and societies. In fact, education is a fundamental and complex social need.

Ibn Khaldun, a renowned philosopher, historian, and sociologist, emphasised education in his work *Al Muqaddimah* (Irwin, 2018), viewing it as a vital social pursuit essential for human progress and development (Dajani, 2015). Recognising this, education has long been a primary goal for scientists and governments aiming to find new ways to improve humanity. From a social thinker's perspective, Ibn Khaldun examined the origins of science and education, concluding that they are innate to human nature: 'It is Thought' that sets humans apart from animals, enabling the advancement of science and crafts (Ibn Khaldun, 1978). He identified two forms of education: one based on memorisation and limited study areas, such as learning to read and write the Quran and understanding legal interpretations; and another based on autonomous and critical thinking, which broadens the scope of study (Shihade, 2017). Like Paulo Freire, he argued that the latter approach benefits students and society by promoting critical, independent thought and a wider perspective, resulting in a more comprehensive form of education (Shihade, 2017). Ibn Khaldun believed that education should cultivate innate instincts and reasoning, setting humans apart from other animals (Ibn Khaldun, 1978).

Ibn Khaldun's approach to education was comprehensive, combining educational programmes with behavioural education and integrating all disciplines. He believed behavioural education significantly impacts learning, fundamentally transforming an individual's mind and manners (Dajani, 2015). This approach aligns with integrating religious education, where morals and values are taught. Ibn Khaldun's holistic perspective on education reflects his belief that it is vital for human development, blending critical thinking with moral and behavioural instruction to foster a well-rounded society (Solikhah & Purnomo, 2023). From a sociological perspective, he emphasised the importance of education for building a civilised community and ensuring its future survival (Komarudin, 2022).

He identified two main aims for education: religious and scientific. Education should assist people in knowing God, performing good deeds for the hereafter, and fulfilling their commitments to Him. Furthermore, it should enable individuals to manage their worldly lives (Halim et al., 2017).

He emphasised that all children have the right to high-quality education, warning that without it, society becomes culturally and spiritually infertile. Children should be treated with care and respect, free from excessively restrictive regulations, and allowed to explore (Elbih, 2020). In Islam, education is a divine commandment that every person must fulfil. Islamic education seeks to reconcile and balance individuals' physical and spiritual development. Furthermore, Islam incorporates both universal and practical education alongside moral principles (Atique, 2012).

Education bears the vital responsibility of nurturing the inherent potential within human nature, which leans towards truth and virtue and empowers individuals to fulfil their role as stewards of the earth or 'caliphate fil ard'. Consequently, education involves the cultivation of all human capacities by shaping individuals who are righteous and pious, diligent and thoughtful, as well as highly skilled and physically resilient, for the benefit of themselves, society, and the environment (Uyuni & Adnan, 2024).

Similarly, the global awareness of religion's growing importance highlights its consequences for individuals and society in both national and international politics and public debate (REDco, 2009). The influence of religion on society and public life is continually brought to public attention through extensive media coverage. Advances in scientific and medical technologies, along with environmental debates, consistently raise new issues that pose religious, moral, and social questions (Department for Children, Schools and Families, 2010). This resurgence underlines that religion is both a private matter and a vital part of public life. In this context, it becomes evident that religion is deeply connected with many aspects of human existence. Faith is an essential element in our lives, as they are incomplete without it (Kelcourse, 2015). It offers a social, ideological, and transcendent framework for self-development (King, 2003, 2008).

Religion and faith are significant issues in global discourse today (Gross, 2011), affecting societies across the world. While my research focuses on Algeria, it is worth mentioning that most European nations have long believed that the trend of rising secularisation would eventually push religion out of the public sphere. However, this trend has reversed in the past decade, with religion re-emerging in public debate (Jackson et al., 2007). Religion and beliefs influence our values and are reflected in what we say and how we behave. Consequently, religion has become a vital part of educational discourse as well. From an Islamic perspective, the foundation of religion must be established in children from a young age. Belief in God is the most crucial factor in one's life (Kistoro & Sibarani, 2019). Allah mandates that everyone have faith in Him. In Islam, faith is described as the belief in and devotion to principles based on recognising the one and only God. As Masrur (2016) points out, the term "faith" consistently signifies confidence and belief in God, offering a sense of reassurance and security.

Religious and spiritual development takes place within various social settings, including schools, homes, and congregations. As a result, diverse agents of religious socialisation, such as parents and religious educators, assume vital roles. Healthy family dynamics naturally influence children's perspectives through identification and spontaneous interactions (Swift, 2020). In this interconnected web of influences, parents and educators shape their children's spiritual and moral evolution. These agents, together with different symbol systems, help children choose their identity pursuits. Moreover, these interactions create an ideological framework by exposing individuals to beliefs, worldviews, and values, allowing them to find a sense of purpose in life. Additionally, religion provides an opportunity

for understanding oneself in relation to the transcendent, offering a transcendent context for self-development (Negru-Subtirica et al., 2017). Therefore, religious education acts as a comprehensive framework that fosters both the spiritual and moral development of individuals within a wider cultural and ideological environment.

Building on this foundation, religious education is a vital subject that fosters an individual's knowledge and understanding of the religions and beliefs that are part of modern society. Religious education raises challenging questions about the ultimate meaning and purpose of life, beliefs about God, the self, and the nature of reality, as well as issues of morality and what it means to be human. It can expand pupils' knowledge and understanding of their own religion, other principal religions, different religious traditions, and worldviews that provide answers to their questions (Department for Children, Schools and Families, 2010).

Religious education also supports pupils' personal development, well-being, and community cohesion. It provides opportunities for personal reflection and spiritual growth, enhancing understanding of the importance of religion in the lives of others, both individually, communally, and across cultures (Department for Children, Schools and Families, 2010). The following statement demonstrates the importance of finding confidence in one's faith in today's world.

The modern world needs young people who are sufficiently confident in their own beliefs and values that they can respect the religious and cultural differences of others and contribute to a cohesive and compassionate society (Religious Education Council of England and Wales, 2013, p. 5).

Religious education, in its broadest sense, is everywhere—happening at home, in formal and informal education, and in the wider public domain, such as through media representations (Tillson, 2018). In a more specific sense, religious education involves systematic teaching focused on a particular faith or religious practice (Gross, 2011). It includes a range of concepts, institutional contexts, and national traditions, and can relate to education into religion, education about religion, or education from religion (Schreiner, 2002). Education into religion introduces students to a specific faith tradition. Education about religion helps students understand what religion means to believers of a particular faith. Education from religion encourages students to consider different responses to major moral and religious questions, helping them develop their own views. This distinction emphasises the main approaches used in religious education (Gross, 2011).

Building on these foundational strategies, socialisation for religious identity encompasses three main dimensions: content, structure, and process (Gross, 2010). These components form the cornerstones of religious education. Firstly, content includes basic religious knowledge, such as elements of faith, important texts, traditional stories, sacred scriptures, and aphorisms. It also involves how to lead a religious life by observing certain commandments and performing sacred rituals. Secondly, structure pertains to Religious Education and can take two distinct forms: monolithic and linear, or it can be pluralistic and multidimensional, offering a diverse range of learning experiences. Lastly, the process involves indoctrination through direct instruction, repetition, memorisation, and rote learning of sacred texts. It also involves role-modelling, exposure to significant works, and study and reflection through interactive learning, meditation, discussion, and hermeneutics (Gross, 2011).

In scholarly literature, the term "Islamic Education" covers various interpretations: (1) Islam's perspectives and principles on child upbringing and education; (2) the traditional educational system that has developed over time under the influence of Islam; and (3) the curriculum taught in modern schools, which acts as a form of religious socialisation and moral/religious education (Tiliouine, 2014). While Islam shares many key principles with other Abrahamic faiths, such as Christianity and Judaism, Islamic education remains a poorly studied subject, despite its significance for around 1.5 billion people. It is believed that "good" religious education helps Muslims understand their religion's humanitarian and peaceful message. This highlights the importance of researching Quranic schools and their role in delivering such instruction (Tiliouine, 2014).

Faith schools stand out among the many educational settings that include religious education. These schools shape children's spiritual and moral growth (Hughes, 2000). In some cases, they follow the national curriculum but are distinguished by a unique religious ethos and character, granting them autonomy over the religious studies they offer (Umar, 2019; Ameen & Hassan, 2013). For instance, in the UK, faith schools combine general educational subjects within a specific religious framework, prioritising applicants based on faith background while also accepting students from other faiths (Paul & Bolton, 2018). Specifically, Muslim faith schools are rooted in core Islamic values and ethos (Ameen & Hassan, 2013).

Historically, the religious origins of education are evident in both Western and Eastern cultures. Faith schools have been an integral part of the British educational system for a long time (Ameen & Hassan, 2013). Parochial schools, which reflect the Church of England's legacy, were established and sustained by religious groups (Parker-Jenkins, 2002). During the Middle Ages, the Church was Britain's main provider of education. Before the nineteenth century, children's education in England was considered the responsibility of parents: wealthy families could afford private tutors or fee-paying schools, while

the poor depended on schools supported by charity organisations (Walford, 2001). This historical background highlights the shared heritage of faith-based education systems across countries and emphasises the universal importance of religious education in fostering moral and ethical behaviour.

Islamic schools, in fact, come in many varieties, and depending on the context (e.g., Muslim-majority countries versus Western societies where Muslims are a minority), the term Islamic school can refer to quite different types of education (Memon, 2013). In modern Islamic schools, the term 'Islamic education' extends beyond simple religious content. While religious instruction remains an important element, these schools acknowledge the need for a holistic approach. This approach includes character development, life skills, and ethical values. Islamic education adapts to cultural and social contexts and prepares students for spiritual matters as well as active community involvement. By emphasising both religious knowledge and practical skills, Islamic schools aim to create well-rounded individuals who will contribute positively to society (Memon & Alhashmi, 2018).

Given this diversity and evolving approach, the survival and development of Islamic education in the post-9/11 era, marked by media misinformation, public scrutiny, and politically driven Islamophobia, need to be emphasised. Since 9/11, Islamic schools have experienced a fundamental shift. Many Muslim communities have moved past their initial fears, mistrust, and concerns about living in a changing socio-political environment and have adopted a more settled and confident approach to education (Memon, 2013).

Schools in general, including faith schools, can either promote change or maintain the status quo, encouraging students to think beyond their family and local norms while preparing them for their implicit role in society. They teach students communication, social interaction, and work discipline, which can lead to autonomy and obedience (Little & McGivern, 2014). The interaction of modern, traditional, and religious value systems significantly influences education in the Muslim world (AL-Kahtany, 2019; Shah et al., 2015). Many Muslim nations incorporate Western modernity's norms into their educational systems. Following independence, the focus has often been on aligning with global modernist standards while maintaining traditional values (Shah et al., 2015).

4.5. Schooling and Faith Development

The role of religion and faith-based schooling in society is increasingly gaining attention worldwide (Byrne & Devine, 2018). Boyatzis (2009) examined the impact of early education on faith development, emphasising the universal and unbiased aspects of this process. He pointed out that faith development is fostered by societal influences, with schooling playing a vital role in shaping an individual's understanding of faith. At this stage, education not only functions as a key source of knowledge but

also helps mould the individual's mindset and belief system in line with their cognitive abilities (Wondon, 2019).

Moulin-Stožek (2020) adds to this by noting that the foundations of faith and religious education laid during early schooling are especially significant, as children's cognitive abilities are highly adaptable, making these lessons enduring. Teachers and scholars in schools play a vital role in nurturing and guiding learners' faith (Benson et al., 2019). Weyand and Juzwik (2020) further highlight the role of schooling systems and educational institutions in fostering the development and sustainability of faith throughout an individual's life. Boyatzis (2012) examined the role of education and schooling in supporting individuals' spiritual growth. The study emphasised that, from a religious perspective, education helps individuals focus on the non-material aspects of life, guiding them to understand the deeper meaning and purpose of their existence. As discussed in this context, faith underscores that every person has a unique role in the world (Weyand & Juzwik, 2020). Schooling is essential in helping individuals experience life and encourages them to reflect on personal insights, a process central to faith development (Wondon, 2019).

In the Western tradition, scholars such as James Fowler (1981) have argued that schools can offer structured environments for children to explore existential questions and moral reasoning. Religious education in this context extends beyond doctrinal instruction by fostering reflective thinking, moral sensitivity, and ethical agency. For instance, curriculum frameworks in Christian schools often aim to incorporate biblical worldviews with academic disciplines to develop both faith and intellect simultaneously (Astley, 2002). Nonetheless, critics like Wright (2004) caution that religious education in Western settings may become excessively propositional, emphasising content knowledge over experiential and relational aspects of faith.

From an Islamic perspective, education is seen as a divine obligation closely connected to faith development. The Qur'an consistently urges believers to pursue knowledge ('ilm), highlighting its spiritual importance (Surah Al-Alaq 96:1-5). Traditionally, Islamic education aims to nurture morally upright individuals who live accordance with the principles of Islam (Al-Attas, 1979). Religious instruction in Islamic schools often combines academic study with spiritual practices such as Qur'anic recitation, prayer, and moral training.

According to Halstead (2004), Islamic education combines *tarbiyah* (moral and spiritual nurturing) with intellectual development, which differs from more secular educational systems. However, a significant concern remains that traditional Islamic pedagogy, especially in some regions, still emphasises rote memorisation (*hifz*) over critical thinking, restricting deeper engagement with faith concepts (Talbani,

1996; Joung, 2018). Therefore, reforms in Islamic schooling must aim to strike a balance between preserving sacred knowledge and encouraging reflective, dialogical engagement.

Critically, both Western and Islamic educational systems face the challenge of reconciling modern educational goals, such as creativity, critical thinking, and digital literacy, with the aims of faith development. If religious schooling becomes either overly rigid or entirely secularised, it risks alienating students from the lived experience of faith. What is needed is an integrated pedagogy that treats faith not merely as a subject to be mastered but as a way of life to be experienced and examined (Palmer, 1993).

4.6. Religious Education and Faith Development

Religious education, in particular, plays a vital role in nurturing faith development, acting as a bridge between personal spirituality and the wider religious community. This section investigates how both Western and Islamic perspectives understand and implement religious education as a key element in shaping faith. From Christian educational theories emphasising experiential learning and community involvement to Islamic models based on Qur'anic teachings and traditional religious school methods, a variety of approaches underscore the importance of integrating knowledge, practice, and moral growth. By examining diverse religious traditions, this section demonstrates how religious education fosters faith not only through intellectual teaching but also via lived experiences and spiritual engagement.

According to Bouherar and Ghafsi (2021), while religions serve as historical and sociocultural institutions, faith is a profoundly personal and individual experience. As Zietlow (2017) observes, religion is an expression of faith but not identical to faith itself. This distinction implies that educators should emphasise not only religious doctrine but also the nurturing of personal faith. For example, in Christianity, Westerhoff III (2012) maintains that faith, rather than religion, ought to be the primary focus of Christian education. Faith development is regarded as more practical and experiential, emphasising lived experiences over mere learning of religious texts.

Parker (2011) similarly emphasises the role of religious education in shaping faith, noting that practising religious teachings, rather than just knowing them theoretically, is fundamental to developing faith in human life. Faith can then be understood as confidence or trust in the spiritual teachings of a religion. This practical aspect of faith applies to both Christianity and Islam. Groome (2008) stresses that, from a Muslim perspective, religious educational institutions play a key role in fostering faith, ensuring that religious teachings are not only learned but also lived. This view is further supported by Joung (2018), who highlights that the aim of religious education is to offer trustworthy and meaningful interpretations

of religious norms and worship, based on divine guidelines. The approach to religious education within Catholic schools stresses faith as a journey of personal growth and active participation in a faith community (Scotland, 2014). Slee (2004) reinforces the idea that religious practices are essential for faith development, making a significant contribution to religious education.

Building on this, Kristeno and Tarihoran (2023) offer valuable insights on how faith formation activities in Catholic parishes foster children's spiritual and moral growth. According to their findings, engaging and enjoyable tasks strengthen children's religious connections while also supporting cognitive and character development. Coaches and religious educators play a vital role in this process, employing innovative methods such as games, stories, and theatre to make learning more engaging and meaningful. This reinforces the idea that faith development is an ongoing, dynamic process rather than a static one. Importantly, Kristeno and Tarihoran emphasise that faith formation extends beyond the family into the broader community, promoting a holistic approach to child development that equips them to lead virtuous lives within society. In Islamic religious education, the Quran and the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad serve as the ideal models for religious instruction (Matise et al., 2017). The theory of Islamic education, as outlined by Joung (2018), encourages followers to live according to the example set by the Prophet, viewing him as the perfect role model for faith-based living. However, IRE's pedagogy, influenced by the traditional madrasah tradition, remains focused on listening, rote memorisation, and regurgitation, which is still prevalent in many Muslim countries (Talbani, 1996).

As previously highlighted, the goal of Quranic religious education, in particular, is to teach young people the Quran and help them attain Hifz (complete Quran memorising) (Sp, 2018). Similar to secondary, intermediate, or primary schooling, this education is crucial for conveying religious knowledge and fostering a sense of community among youngsters (Merhaut, 2007). In the Muslim world, parents value Quranic religious education because it prepares students for various important professions, such as imams, Islamic scholars, Islamic lawyers, and teachers, thereby meeting social demands. Quranic schools generally teach Arabic, logic (Mantiq), Hadith of the Prophet, Islamic law (Shariah), Quranic memorising and interpretation (Tafsir), and historical studies (Rosyad, 2020). Each of these subjects contributes to a child's overall spiritual and moral development. For instance, memorising the Quran not only fosters a strong connection to the sacred text but also cultivates discipline and determination, which are essential for faith development.

The study of Hadith and Islamic law provides students with moral frameworks to guide them in their personal and community lives. Similarly, learning Arabic enhances their understanding of religious literature, fostering a deeper respect for their faith. Furthermore, introducing logic (Mantiq) into the curriculum promotes critical thinking and reasoning, enabling students to engage with their perspectives intelligently. This combination of various subjects supports the idea that Quranic religious education is

more than mere rote memorisation; it ultimately aims to develop a comprehensive and well-rounded spiritual identity. In this context, Quranic education becomes a vital institution for shaping young people's religious knowledge, character, ethics, and sense of community responsibilities. Consequently, it functions as a foundational pillar for faith development, aligning educational practices with broader goals of cultivating responsible and informed members of society.

Religious education across various traditions not only functions as a way of transmitting spiritual teachings but also as a means of developing a loving relationship with God (Rossiter, 2018). This process often includes acts of worship, charitable deeds, and the practice of moral values such as love, compassion, and hospitality (Erduran et al., 2020). These aspects of religious education are not merely educational but are deeply formative, shaping individuals' faith in meaningful ways. Rossiter (2018) also contends that understanding and practising religious norms, morals, and cultural traditions reinforce individuals' faith. This highlights that religious education is more than just academic learning; it is a practical, lived experience that nurtures faith and fosters a sense of belonging within the religious community (Ilechukwu et al., 2022).

To sum up, religious education can be viewed as a dynamic and practical process that goes beyond simply transmitting religious knowledge. It is crucial for fostering personal faith, allowing individuals to internalise and embody the teachings of their respective traditions, whether Christianity, Islam, or other faiths. This comprehensive approach to religious education ensures that faith is not only understood intellectually but also practised and experienced, contributing to individuals' spiritual growth and identity formation. However, a notable shortcoming of many religious education systems is their tendency to focus heavily on rote learning and information intake, which can limit deeper spiritual engagement and critical reflection. As Jackson (2004) argues, traditional religious education often fails to address the realities of pluralistic societies and may neglect the contextual and dialogical aspects of faith learning. Similarly, Miller (2007) emphasises the need for a holistic educational approach that incorporates emotional, spiritual, and relational aspects, rather than treating religious education as purely cognitive. Addressing these issues is essential for religious education to fully support the complex and multidimensional process of faith development.

4.7. Cognition and Faith Development

When considering faith development, it is vital to recognise that faith exists in two forms: cognitive understanding and relational trust. The Latin roots of the word 'faith' reveal its complex nature. 'Fiducia' signifies faith as trust, emphasising a confident and trusting attitude towards God and others. Conversely, 'Fides' highlights faith as knowledge, meaning that faith involves cognitive comprehension

or perception of the divine (Hick, 1966). Both Western and Islamic perspectives widely acknowledge this dual nature of faith, recognising that faith includes both intellectual beliefs (*fides/‘ilm*) and relational, experiential trust (*fiducia/fitrah*) in spiritual growth (Hick, 1966; Al-Attas, 1980; Haque, 2004).

Cognition is essential to this development, involving the mental processes used to acquire information and understanding. According to Bhatti (2017) and Krause et al. (2006), cognition is a vital faculty of the human mind that significantly influences the development of faith. Vermeer (2012) further states that the main goal of religious education should be to enhance cognitive abilities and meta-concepts, thereby fostering scholarly religious thought. By focusing on these higher cognitive skills, religious education can go beyond simple memorisation, promoting deeper understanding and critical thinking, and supporting both the 'Fides' (knowledge element) and the broader process of developing faith.

Numerous other studies in psychology and education have explored various aspects of cognition and its connection to faith formation. It is vital to examine how cognition influences faith development and, in turn, how faith development impacts cognitive growth. This reciprocal relationship highlights the interaction between intellectual progress and spiritual growth. The link between cognition and faith development, especially how faith progresses through human cognition, is crucial for understanding faith formation. A key concept is a schema, a cognitive framework with functional and normative roles in processing analytical knowledge (Piaget, 1952). This framework demonstrates how rational thought, rooted in the mind, acts as both a foundation and a catalyst for faith development. Making rational judgments and applying logical reasoning are essential to faith formation, as individuals utilise these schemas to interpret spiritual experiences and incorporate new religious insights (Kim, 2007).

Kim's study examines the relationship between cognition and faith development, based on the epistemic frameworks of Piaget and Vygotsky. The research highlights two perspectives: schema theory, which encompasses cognitive processes influencing how individuals interpret their faith, and Vygotsky's social constructivism, which emphasises the importance of social interaction in shaping faith. Rather than focusing on long-term development, Kim emphasises faith formation, suggesting that cognition plays a role in the early stages of faith. This study offers a paradigm for understanding how intellectual processes, along with social factors, contribute to the early development and affirmation of faith.

Piaget's (1969, 1970) epistemic framework links rationality to faith development and asserts that cognitive abilities are essential for forming faith. Piaget's cognitive theory, as discussed earlier, states that individuals progress through various stages of intellectual development, which influence their capacity to understand abstract concepts. Piaget states that those who cannot participate in abstract

thinking may fail to fully comprehend or experience faith (Kim, 2007). This framework highlights the vital role of cognitive development in fostering both intellectual understanding and spiritual growth.

Researchers and educators largely recognise Piaget's stance on cognitive development and its connection to faith formation. However, Piaget's theory offers a limited view of the relationship between cognition and faith. It suggests that religion is only accessible to individuals with a fully developed mental structure, thereby excluding children from active engagement in faith development. This is problematic because children's cognitive abilities are constantly evolving, not fixed. Religious scholars such as Hashim (2007) contend that faith formation programmes should be adapted to meet the cognitive and moral development needs at each stage of schooling, ensuring that faith growth is consistently supported and fostered throughout the developmental process.

Piaget's rational epistemic perspective falls short of providing a comprehensive understanding of the complexities of spiritual existence. In response, researchers suggest a relational epistemology, which offers a schematic view of faith development (Streib, 2005). This empirical approach emphasises that individuals develop faith through their personal experiences. It views faith as a process of growth of ideas and an awareness of the importance of spiritual experiences. While these two approaches generally reflect how Christians perceive faith development, they can also serve as frameworks for other faiths, including Islam, representing global paradigms.

Lownsdale (1997) highlights the cognitive foundations of Fowler's Faith Development Theory (FDT), which builds on earlier work by Piaget and Kohlberg on cognitive and moral development. Fowler's framework combines psychology and theology, assuming that cognitive growth drives faith development through various stages. The theory proposes that as individuals progress through different stages of cognitive development, their abilities for abstract thinking, perspective-taking, and moral reasoning improve, shaping their understanding and experience of faith. This suggests that faith is not merely a fixed belief system but is cognitively dynamic as a person's intellectual and psychological capacities expand over time. Additionally, Grafman et al. (2020) explore the neurological basis of religious cognition, providing insight into how different areas of the brain interact to incorporate moral, ceremonial, and supernatural beliefs. The study underscores that religious cognition is not a single process but a complex interaction among regions responsible for cognitive control, social reasoning, social motivation, and ideological views. It emphasises the importance of understanding the cognitive mechanisms behind religion and spirituality, offering vital insights into how these neurological processes support faith development. Grafman et al.'s findings enhance the current conversation about the relationship between cognition and religious belief systems by demonstrating the connection between brain function and faith formation.

Given the previous discussion about studies emphasising the importance of cognition in faith formation and development, it is crucial to consider other perspectives that expand on this knowledge. Greenway (2022) adopts a broader viewpoint, suggesting that many theories, including Fowler's, focus excessively on logic and cognitive growth. He claims that mental development involves more than just rational thinking; it also includes instinctive cognition, particularly moral instincts, which are often overlooked. Greenway offers a more comprehensive framework by incorporating these instinctive elements. Nonetheless, this raises questions about how these moral intuitions integrate into existing faith development theories and whether they can be tested alongside cognitive processes.

In line with Greenway's idea, according to James Fowler (1981/1995) and other comparable theories, faith is primarily an intellectual construct. However, faith is deeper and broader than what we consciously think. The trusting confidence expressed by the word 'fiducia' is an inherent feature of being human. Our family, actions, and communication with one another can foster, harm, or even erode this trust. From an anthropological perspective, trusting faith is of fundamental importance. We are unlikely to know God if we do not have a basic trust in God. As a basic trust, faith connects all our experiences of openness towards ourselves, others, and God. However, if we reflect on our experiences, this basic trust can grow and change. It can stagnate and become unreceptive to new situations (Fowler, 1996).

Turning to the inverse relationship, regarding how faith formation and development can influence cognitive skills, it becomes essential to see religious education in its widest context. Instead of viewing it only as a process of instilling belief, religious education includes both faith formation and the growth of cognitive skills. When understood holistically, faith formation can actively improve a learner's cognitive abilities by promoting critical thinking, moral reasoning, reflection, and deeper understanding. This broader perspective clarifies how engaging with religious concepts and spiritual practices can stimulate intellectual growth, demonstrating that the connection between faith and cognition is not one-sided but mutually supportive.

Religious education is vital for enhancing children's cognitive abilities and supporting their social development through effective teaching strategies that improve understanding and critical thinking. The study by Gunawan et al. (2023) emphasises a holistic approach to Islamic Religious Education in Senior High Schools, highlighting cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor aspects of learning. It identifies three key components of the educational process: intake, processing, and output. Instructors boost cognitive understanding, attitudes, and skills by actively engaging pupils and monitoring their emotional responses. Furthermore, Pranajaya et al. (2023) stress the importance of integrating assessment across these domains in Islamic Religious Education, asserting that this helps students develop balanced competencies, understand the relationship between knowledge, attitudes, and skills,

and become well-rounded individuals. This comprehensive approach supports the idea that effective religious education significantly enhances cognitive skills, underscoring its numerous benefits for student development.

4.7.1. Memorisation and Cognitive Skills

In the context of Quranic schools, memorisation, rote learning, and the direct transmission of knowledge are common features (Berglund & Gent, 2018; Makdisi, 1981). The rituals of reciting and memorising the Quran are deeply embedded in Islamic tradition and culture (Gent & Muhammad, 2019). Memorisation is regarded as a cultural and spiritual capital vital to the Muslim tradition, providing essential literacy for religious practice and shaping Muslim identity (Berkey, 1992; Berglund & Gent, 2018). For example, Ibn Khaldun emphasised the importance of memory, noting that in Morocco, students required sixteen years to understand texts sufficiently to teach independently. However, in Tunis, this process took just five years (Eickelman, 1978). This illustrates the differing focus on memorising in various contexts and its significance in religious instruction.

Scholars are interested in this technique, especially because some educators have challenged it. Memorisation is often used as a way to assess children's memory skills. This aspect of learning will be discussed in more detail later. Memorisation is seen as an attempt to embed the words of the Quran in students, giving them a moral guide and a set of tools to turn to when interacting with the outside world (Boyle, 2004). According to Rosowsky (2015), memorisation is a form of liturgical or faith literacy. Baker-Ward et al. (1984) offered insights into children's memorising abilities during their early schooling years, emphasising the importance of examining and developing this vital skill. Moore (2011) describes rote memorisation of the Quran as children learning the sacred text through imitation and repetition, without necessarily understanding the actual meaning of the verses. This traditional method is deeply rooted in Islamic education and is similar to how sacred texts are taught in other religions such as Christianity and Judaism. Moore highlights that this approach distinguishes religious education from other forms of instruction by focusing on preserving religious knowledge rather than immediate understanding.

While this method is often regarded as effective for transmitting religious texts, it also raises concerns about the level of understanding it fosters. Critics argue that rote memorisation without comprehension might hinder pupils' ability to think critically about the subject. This point is highlighted by comparing Quranic education with Western educational traditions, as Spence (1985) notes that even in Western rhetorical training, memorisation played an important role, but was gradually replaced by critical thinking and reasoning skills. Likewise, Wagner (1985) states that religious instruction in pre-

Renaissance European schools emphasised memorising sacred texts. However, as students progressed, they received more detailed explanations and were taught how to engage more deeply with the content.

In Quranic schools, this delayed engagement with the content of texts can be seen as a potential disadvantage of the rote memorisation method. Although it enhances memory skills, there is a risk that students will not develop critical thinking or a deep understanding of the Quranic teachings until much later in their education. This raises the question of whether this traditional technique effectively prepares students to internalise and apply the Quran's moral and ethical principles in real-life situations, or if it merely encourages reliance on memorised knowledge rather than fostering intellectual independence.

Many educators and scholars have criticised Quranic education, especially its focus on memorisation. Critics often argue that rote memorisation of the Quranic Arabic text does not necessarily lead to a better understanding of its message. While memorising sacred texts without comprehension is considered valuable in many religious communities as an act of worship, cultural preservation, discipline, and personal growth (Dreyfus, 2003; Fuller, 2001), many educational critics dismiss this practice as having limited educational benefit (Gent & Muhammad, 2019).

Therefore, while rote learning is effective for preserving sacred texts, it should be supplemented with more interpretative and critical techniques to effectively develop a student's cognitive and moral abilities. This more comprehensive approach, which integrates memory and understanding, will better satisfy the developmental needs of contemporary learners and connect tradition with critical engagement in religious literature.

While critiques of Quranic education often emphasise the limits of rote memorisation, an expanding body of research presents a more nuanced view, demonstrating that memorisation can promote a variety of cognitive, spiritual, and academic advantages. These studies examine the lived experiences of huffaz and the wider influence of Quran memorisation on personal growth, academic achievement, and educational results, particularly in diverse cultural settings.

For instance, Gent (2016) conducted an in-depth study to explore how hifz (the practice of memorising the entire Quran) influences the lives of huffaz (those who commit the Quran to memory) in a Western context. His research particularly focused on these individuals' daily lives, employment, and outlooks. It built upon previous studies that examined the dynamics of a boys' memorisation class in a mosque in northeast London, emphasising the discipline and consistency involved. Gent's findings highlighted the huffaz's dedication to revising and memorising the Quran, the significance of Ramadan in their spiritual routines, and the overall impact on their quality of life. Nawaz and Jahangir (2015) assessed the effect of Quran memorisation on students' academic progress and found that completing hifz led to a notable

improvement in their academic performance. While part of this increase can be attributed to the memorising process, it may also relate to other factors such as the development of self-discipline and effective time management skills.

The dedication required to memorise the Quran certainly fosters these habits, which contribute to enhanced academic performance in various fields. Moor's (2006) study examined memorisation in both public and Quranic schools in Cameroon, highlighting similarities in the application of rote learning, or 'guided repetition,' across both environments. He discovered that memorisation in these schools primarily aims to improve second-language acquisition, emphasising the importance of memorisation in cultivating broader educational skills beyond its cultural or religious context. Likewise, Yusuf's (2010) research pointed out that memorisation is connected to students' academic success, boosting cognitive abilities such as mental capacity, oration, and visual thinking. Yet, Yusuf stressed that memorisation holds the greatest value when students truly understand the material they have committed to memory, challenging the idea that rote learning is inherently negative.

Furthermore, Scribner and Cole's (1981) research in Liberia demonstrated that Quranic education significantly improved specific memory skills, a finding later supported by Wagner (1987), who noted that Quranic study enhances incremental rather than general memory. These studies collectively suggest that memorisation in Quranic education serves multiple purposes, ranging from language acquisition to cognitive development, and can positively influence academic and intellectual growth when applied thoughtfully. However, the effectiveness of this approach depends on whether learners achieve a deeper understanding beyond simple rote memorisation.

Rote learning, often contrasted with meaningful learning, is central to the debate surrounding traditional educational practices. Numerous studies have emphasised this tension (e.g., Tsai & Wen, 2005; Clary & Wandersee, 2007; Lewis et al., 2009). However, Grove and Bretz (2012) contend that rote and meaningful learning complement each other, as neither exists in a purely isolated form. In conclusion, cognition, faith formation, and religious education are deeply interconnected, making it difficult to separate or exclude any of these elements when considering individuals' spiritual development.

In summary, memorisation plays a complex role in Quranic education, deeply embedded in religious tradition and cultural identity, while also significantly supporting cognitive development and academic success. Although rote learning is often criticised for restricting critical engagement and deeper understanding, empirical studies show that memorisation helps develop essential skills such as discipline, memory improvement, and even second-language learning. However, the real value of memorisation is only realised when it is paired with interpretative and reflective learning that encourages understanding alongside recall. This balance is vital for fostering both the cognitive and

spiritual aspects of faith growth, emphasising the need for educational methods that combine tradition with critical thinking to support learners' overall development.

4.8. Modernity and Children's Faith Development

In today's swiftly changing world, modernity—particularly through the influence of technology and social media—presents new challenges to children's faith development. Both Western and Islamic perspectives have begun to critically examine how these shifts impact young people's spiritual growth, moral grounding, and identity formation. This section explores the concerns raised by scholars from both traditions. It considers how religious education can respond to these modern influences to support and sustain children's faith in a digital age.

Cunningham et al. (2022) emphasise how social media can mislead young minds, presenting them with distorted values and beliefs. While Yaacob (2013) recognises that technology has the potential to bring people closer, it also introduces new cultures and influences that can undermine traditional values. This duality highlights the need for religious institutions, especially schools, to actively address these challenges. Schools can counteract the harmful effects of modern technology by engaging with young people through rational discussions rooted in the core teachings of their faith (Howard-Snyder & McKaughan, 2022).

However, the rise of digital communication has also contributed to a decline in communal religious identity, as individuals become preoccupied with their own affairs and less connected to their faith communities (Ameli, 2002). This shift towards individualism, amplified by personalised media consumption and algorithm-driven content, creates echo chambers that can alienate children from collective religious practices and shared moral narratives (Turkle, 2011). This fragmentation can adversely affect children's religious identities; when a unified religious identity is weakly represented, it may lead to a decline in religious morals and values, ultimately hindering faith development (Heaven & Ciarrochi, 2007). Moreover, when digital culture promotes relativism and instant gratification, children may struggle to internalise long-term commitments, such as those required in religious life (Campbell, 2012). Relativism, in this context, refers to the idea that truth and morality are viewed as subjective, making it difficult for young individuals to embrace absolute religious teachings. Instant gratification, reinforced by social media and digital platforms, encourages the pursuit of immediate pleasure, often at the expense of patience, reflection, and discipline—qualities essential for sustained spiritual growth. Without consistent exposure to community-based reinforcement of values, faith development becomes increasingly fragile, raising concerns about how religious identity can be meaningfully sustained in virtual and often secular spaces.

The absence of strong religious morals and beliefs can further contribute to undesirable behaviours among youth (Yaacob, 2013). As children distance themselves from their faith, they become more susceptible to societal influences that may lead them away from their spiritual roots. This underscores the importance of religious education and parental guidance in nurturing a child's faith (Adam, 2019). The nature of religious education adds to these issues. McNair (2010) argues that contemporary methods of religious education are too focused on information acquisition, which leads to misunderstandings about the nature of faith development. This focus on factual knowledge often overshadows the need for a more comprehensive approach to faith development. According to Shodiq et al. (2016), contemporary methods of instruction prioritise knowledge and skill development over all aspects of faith formation. This indicates a problematic shift from holistic education towards a performance-driven model that aligns more with secular academic standards than with religious pedagogical goals. When religious education becomes indistinguishable from general schooling in terms of methodology, its transformative and spiritual dimensions risk being diluted or lost entirely (Wright, 2004). Furthermore, such instructional models may fail to engage learners emotionally and spiritually, thereby weakening the personal relevance of religious teachings and undermining long-term faith development (Francis, 2002). A faith education that merely informs without inspiring is unlikely to withstand the complex challenges posed by modernity and digital culture.

In summary, the challenges to developing religion in modern society are both complex and extensive. The widespread influence of digital culture, especially through social media, not only exposes children to conflicting values and misinformation, but also encourages a climate of relativism and instant gratification, which weakens their ability for long-term spiritual commitment. This has caused a fragmentation of communal religious identity, as individualism and online engagement increasingly replace traditional, community-based forms of worship and moral development. Furthermore, the dominance of fact-oriented religious education models, which often focus on rote learning and measurable academic results, tends to overlook the relational, emotional, and experiential elements of faith formation that are vital to true spiritual growth.

To address these many-sided challenges, a collaborative effort between families, schools, and religious institutions is vital. Faith development must be fostered in environments that encourage critical thinking, moral reflection, and personal involvement with faith practices, rather than just delivering content. This requires an educational approach that balances cognitive growth with emotional and spiritual development, allowing children not only to understand their faith intellectually but also to embody it meaningfully. Both Western and Islamic viewpoints emphasise the importance of shaping well-rounded individuals whose faith is deeply connected to identity, community, and ethical actions.

Therefore, a reimagined religious education, one that is both theologically sound and culturally responsive, is essential for maintaining faith in the lives of children growing up in an increasingly secular and technology-driven world.

4.9. Conclusion

This chapter has explored the multiple dimensions of faith development in childhood by examining Western and Islamic perspectives, including theoretical frameworks, educational practices, cognitive influences, and contemporary challenges. The discussion highlighted key similarities and differences between these traditions, showing how each understands the formation of religious identity, moral reasoning, and spiritual growth in children.

Western theories, such as those of Fowler, Erikson, and Piaget, emphasise stage-based cognitive and psychosocial development, framing faith as an evolving construct shaped by individual reasoning, social interactions, and existential questioning. These models provide valuable insights into the developmental processes underlying religious belief but have been criticised for their linear assumptions and limited applicability to non-Western contexts. In contrast, Islamic perspectives root faith development in *fitrah* (innate spirituality), *tarbiyyah* (holistic nurturing), and communal socialisation, prioritising the integration of knowledge, worship, and moral conduct from early childhood. The Qur'an, Sunnah, and classical scholars like Al-Ghazali and Ibn Khaldun emphasise the role of family, Qur'anic schools, and community in sustaining a child's spiritual journey. Faith formation is not merely an intellectual endeavour but a lived experience shaped by parental and educator influence, institutional frameworks, and cognitive engagement. However, modernity presents unprecedented challenges. Digital media, individualism, and secular education systems risk fragmenting communal religious identity and reducing faith to superficial or compartmentalised knowledge. The critique of overly cognitive, fact-based religious education, in both Western and Islamic contexts, calls for reforms that balance tradition with pedagogies fostering reflection, emotional connection, and ethical application.

Chapter 5

Research Methodology

5.1. Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodological framework of this study. It begins by justifying the adoption of a qualitative research design, an approach considered most suitable for exploring the detailed

perspectives of Algerian parents on the purpose of Quranic schools. The chapter then describes the specific research paradigm, the strategy of inquiry, and the procedures for participant selection and data collection through interviews. Additionally, it explains the data analysis techniques used and their relevance to the research aims. The chapter concludes with a discussion of ethical considerations, including anonymity and confidentiality, that guided this research.

5.2. Research Design

5.2.1. Research Approach: Qualitative

The school of thought behind qualitative research does not specify specific methods for researchers to follow. However, the choice of a single or combined research approach is mainly determined by the nature of the research questions. In other words, the researcher must critically assess the questions and the chosen method to decide whether their combination can effectively address the enquiry and access the required data. As Rusell and Gregory (2003) noted, the systematic structure within the research methodology depends on the 'fit' between the question and the method.

Over the past fifty years, qualitative research has become increasingly influential across various social science disciplines (Hammersley, 2012). This research approach emphasises systematic and empirical investigation into meaning, characterised by being planned, organised, and grounded in real-world experiences (Shank, 2002). It involves studying phenomena in their natural settings and interpreting them based on the meanings individuals assign to their experiences (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000). Qualitative research aims to develop a deep understanding of social phenomena through firsthand accounts and diverse perspectives (Denzin, 2008). This study selected a qualitative research approach to explore Algerian Muslim parents' views on Quranic education. Qualitative research was chosen because, as Denzin and Lincoln (2000) explain, it involves an interpretive and naturalistic approach. This method aligns with my research objectives, as I seek to investigate phenomena within their natural environments and interpret them using the meanings derived from participants' experiences. Employing qualitative methodologies enabled me to capture the complexity of the phenomenon and understand it from the participants' perspectives.

This approach emphasises words and narratives over numerical data (Bryman, 2016), making it well-suited for capturing participants' rich, detailed perspectives and understanding of the socio-cultural and religious significance of Quranic schools. Qualitative research enables an in-depth exploration of how individuals experience, interpret, and make sense of their social world (Sandelowski, 2004).

A direct methodological consequence of this qualitative approach is the way findings are presented. Aiming for a deep, interpretive understanding, the study's findings are organised into four thematic chapters (Chapters 6, 7, 8, and 9). Each chapter concentrates on a key theme derived from the data analysis. In each thematic chapter, participant data is presented, immediately analysed, and discussed in direct dialogue with the earlier reviewed literature. This integrated approach was deliberately chosen over a traditional structure that separates data presentation from analysis and discussion, for two main reasons: 1) to preserve the holistic and narrative integrity of participants' lived experiences, which is essential to phenomenological research, and 2) to enable a deeper, more critical analysis by allowing instant interpretation of data within its relevant theoretical and contextual framework, thereby fostering ongoing critical engagement with the interview material.

Adopting a qualitative research method primarily depends on the nature of the research questions aligned with the present study's objectives. The choice to use qualitative research for this study on Algerian parents' perspectives on Quranic schools in Algeria is based on its capacity to address the exploratory nature of the research. As Ospina (2004) describes, qualitative research is particularly suitable for examining phenomena that are poorly understood or understudied, which matches the study's aim to explore the nuanced perspectives of Algerian Muslim parents regarding the purpose of Quranic schools. By concentrating on the subjective experiences of parents, teachers, administrators, and imams, this method enables an in-depth understanding of the schools' purposes that might not be fully captured through quantitative approaches. Moreover, the study benefits from the strength of qualitative research in uncovering detailed insights into social phenomena from participants' viewpoints (Creswell, 2013). This supports the objective of understanding how Quranic schools contribute to the holistic development of children within a socio-cultural and religious framework.

Furthermore, qualitative research enables the exploration of complex phenomena, such as the connection between faith formation and societal influences, which are hard to measure but essential for understanding the wider effects of Quranic education in Algeria. By employing qualitative methods, the study highlights the voices of those directly involved in Quranic schooling, offering a comprehensive and detailed perspective that enhances existing knowledge while filling gaps from previous research. This approach ensures that the research captures the essence of parents' lived experiences regarding the religious and socio-cultural importance of Quranic schools in Algeria, making it an ideal methodological choice.

Furthermore, the qualitative approach recognises the researcher as the primary instrument of data collection and analysis (Bryman, 2016). This necessitates ongoing reflexivity regarding one's positionality. As a Muslim female researcher, I approach this study with an "insider" perspective concerning the religious and cultural context of Quranic education. This positionality offers a degree of

inherent understanding and facilitates access and trust with participants. However, I am also critically aware that it introduces preconceptions and the potential for bias. A detailed discussion of this positionality and the strategies employed to minimise its influence is included in sections 5.2.7 and 5.2.8.

Each research approach has its advantages and disadvantages, and qualitative research presents a series of methodological challenges in understanding and accessing reality. Several researchers in the field, notably Bradley (1993), have explored fundamental issues that may arise during empirical research within a qualitative framework. A significant concern is the role of the investigator as interpreter, which requires a thorough examination of all aspects of the phenomena to ensure accuracy in interpretation. This interpretive role also introduces the risk of subjectivity in the study. Furthermore, the emerging nature of qualitative research presents multiple challenges.

Trustworthiness is a vital element in qualitative research. Morrow (2005) emphasises that researchers should evaluate trustworthiness based on criteria closely related to their specific discipline's paradigmatic foundations. In the context of my research on Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives on Quranic schools, these considerations are essential for preserving the integrity and depth of the findings.

5.2.2. Research method: Phenomenology

Phenomenology is a method of inquiry often regarded as interpretive and used in qualitative studies. Phenomenological studies are a form of qualitative research technique and are now widely recognised as one of the alternative qualitative research methodologies available to researchers. However, interpretive research is not entirely synonymous with qualitative research, although this view is common due to imprecise terminology (Prasad & Prasad, 2002). Phenomenology is also a term that can have quite diverse meanings depending on the theoretical and practical contexts (Given, 2008). A phenomenological study describes how humans experience and interpret a specific phenomenon (Van Manen, 1997). It aims to describe the essence of an experience, offering insight into what the phenomenon is without explaining how or why it occurs (Creswell, 2013). Giorgi (2012) explains phenomenology as primarily a descriptive task concerned with 'articulating the intentional objects of experience' (p. 6). The goal is to depict the experience as it exists in individuals' consciousness, avoiding causal interpretations.

This study employs phenomenology to explore the lived experiences and perspectives of Algerian Muslim parents concerning the purpose of Quranic schools. This approach enables a detailed understanding of how these parents perceive the role and influence of Quranic education on their

children's religious and socio-cultural lives. The methodological choice aligns directly with the research questions, which aim to understand the essence and meaning of parents' perceptions rather than to quantify their frequency or test hypotheses. As Moustakas (1994) emphasises, phenomenology is the suitable method when the goal is to uncover the underlying structures of a specific experience, in this case, the experience of selecting and valuing Quranic education.

To achieve the aims of this study, Colaizzi's (1978) phenomenological method of data analysis is employed, as it aligns directly with the research goal of uncovering the essence and meaning of parents' conceptions rather than measuring frequencies or testing hypotheses. Colaizzi's structured steps offer a rigorous pathway from rich descriptive data to synthesised themes, ensuring a deep and systematic interpretation of participants' experiences. This systematic process is specifically designed to facilitate critical engagement with the interview material, moving beyond simply quoting participants to constructing a robust interpretive analysis. Consistent with phenomenological principles, the process begins with epoché, or bracketing (Moustakas, 1994), where I deliberately set aside my own assumptions as a Muslim researcher with an insider perspective to focus solely on participants' lifeworlds. The subsequent stages of analysis, outlined in section 5.2.6.1, follow Colaizzi's (1978) method, enabling a comprehensive interpretive analysis of the shared essence of these experiences.

5.2.3. Data collection tools and techniques

The study used semi-structured individual interviews, which provided valuable data. Interviews are regarded as the most flexible qualitative primary method for data collection (Kang & Hwang, 2021). There are three types of interviews: structured, semi-structured, and unstructured (Smith, 2019). Semi-structured interviews give participants more space to share their opinions, feelings, and beliefs (Patton, 1987). They also encourage mutual engagement between the interviewer and the participant (Galletta, 2012). Additionally, semi-structured interviews allow the interviewer to adjust follow-up questions based on respondents' answers (Rubin & Rubin, 2005; Polit & Beck, 2010), providing participants with the opportunity to express themselves more fully (RWJF: Robert Wood Johnson Foundation, 2008). This flexibility was essential for exploring participants' lived experiences in depth, thus enabling the collection of rich, detailed data necessary for thorough phenomenological analysis and meaningful engagement with the material.

The semi-structured interview offers the advantage of being relatively objective while still providing a more detailed understanding of participants' views and opinions. It is generally most relevant to participants' perspectives, offering an effective balance between objectivity and depth. Semi-structured interviews often enable the collection of valuable data that may not be effectively gathered through other methods (Borg & Goll, 1989). Data collection for this study involved conducting individual

interviews with each participant about their perceptions and experiences related to Quranic schools. After obtaining signed consent, I conducted the interviews using an interactive approach with open-ended questions (Moustakas, 1994). This method was chosen to gather qualitative data that accurately reflects the participants' experiences and viewpoints.

The interviews followed a protocol (see Section 5.2.3.2) designed to investigate various aspects of Quranic education. The questions were organised to follow a general flow regarding participants' views on the purpose and role of Quranic schools, while remaining flexible and open-ended to allow participants to share their thoughts freely. To further ensure the robustness and credibility of the findings, the data collected from these interviews was triangulated with other sources, as detailed in Section 5.2.3.1.

To ensure the data reflected the participants' own language and perspectives, specific academic vocabulary and terminology from theories were avoided during the interviews. The discussions continued until no new concepts or themes arose, reaching a saturation point where further interviews were unlikely to produce additional significant insights. This approach provided a detailed understanding of how Algerian Muslim parents, Quran teachers, administrators, and imams view the purpose, function, and influence of Quranic schools, enriching the analysis with diverse and original viewpoints.

5.2.3.1. Triangulation of Data

Triangulation is viewed as a qualitative research strategy for testing validity by converging information from diverse sources (Carter et al., 2014). It was a key methodological approach used in this study to enhance the credibility, dependability, and transferability of the findings by incorporating perspectives from various participant subgroups. This type of triangulation, involving different participant groups within the same interview method, is supported by scholars like Denzin (2017) and Patton (2002) as a way to gain a more comprehensive, contextualised understanding of a complex phenomenon.

The study aimed to gain a deep understanding of Algerian Muslim parents' views on the purpose of Quranic schools by mainly gathering data from the parents themselves. Quran teachers, administrators, and imams were interviewed as expert sources to corroborate the data. Their insights were crucial for building a complete picture of the parents' experiences, which allowed for more detailed analysis and interpretation of the primary data. This approach enabled cross-checking of information, adding contextual richness and highlighting similarities or differences in perceptions of Quranic school aims across different roles within the same environment. For example, a parent's opinion on discipline could

be explained by a teacher's account of their educational philosophy, showing whether the practice was seen consistently or differently across the school community.

Despite their different roles, data from all participants were combined to develop a unified understanding of the phenomenon under study. The analysis focused mainly on the parents' perspectives; data from Quran teachers, administrators, and imams were used to add contextual depth and to cross-verify the parents' accounts. This method was chosen to give a broad, cohesive view of how Quranic schools operate and their influence on children's religious and socio-cultural lives from the parents' point of view. However, in the analysis, where relevant, I noted any distinctive viewpoints that appeared unique to particular subgroups. This enabled the study to recognise important differences while keeping its primary focus.

In conclusion, triangulation was not just a validation tactic but a fundamental strategy to achieve the comprehensive description necessary for a rigorous phenomenological study. It ensured that the analysis of parental perspectives was based on a multi-faceted understanding of the Quranic school environment, thereby directly addressing the need for a critically engaged, nuanced interpretation that moves beyond superficial reporting.

5.2.3.2. Interview Protocol

The recruitment process began by using social media and local community networks. I posted informal requests for participants on platforms and community groups and received several responses, which helped me connect with potential participants. Afterwards, I travelled to Algeria to engage directly with participants. My fieldwork involved face-to-face meetings, phone calls, and receiving written responses, depending on participants' availability and preferences.

I initially spoke with parents, teachers, administrators, and imams to explain the study and identify individuals willing to participate. These initial discussions helped develop a better understanding of their roles and perspectives, leading to the scheduling of in-depth interviews. I maintained clear communication regarding the study's objectives and obtained informed consent from all participants. I arranged individual interviews with each participant, choosing a convenient time and location. While most interviews were conducted face-to-face, as mentioned earlier, not all participants were available for in-person meetings.

The interview protocol was developed in line with the phenomenological nature of the study. Its semi-structured format provided a necessary framework while emphasising flexibility, allowing participants to articulate their lived experiences in their own words (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009; Seidman, 2006).

The interview protocol for this study was conducted sequentially, skipping questions only if they had already been thoroughly addressed earlier. Each interview began with a broad, open-ended question to gather participants' perspectives on the aims of Quranic schools. This initial, comprehensive question is a recommended technique in phenomenological interviewing to establish an open, participant-led dialogue from the outset (Adams & Van Manen, 2017).

This initial question often played a significant role in the interview, as participants were encouraged to share their understanding of the essence of the Quranic school and its impact. I let the participants steer the conversation, intervening only to clarify or expand on certain ideas. Although the protocol provided a structured sequence for my questions, the interview mainly followed the participant's pace. Natural distractions and tangents were accepted when appropriate. This allowed participants to express, in their own words, what they considered important and relevant to their views on Quranic schools. This participant-centred approach is essential for generating the rich, descriptive data needed for a thorough phenomenological analysis that remains faithful to the participants' lifeworld (Van Manen, 2023). It ensured that the data reflected the genuine perspectives and experiences of the participants. The interviews lasted between thirty minutes and an hour and a half, depending on the depth of discussion and the participants' willingness to elaborate. This flexible, participant-centred method facilitated an in-depth exploration of issues related to Quranic education.

In practice, this involved using techniques like prompting (e.g., "Can you tell me more about that?") and probing (e.g., "What did that mean for you?") to encourage depth and detail without leading the participant. This approach was crucial for moving beyond superficial answers and gaining the critical engagement needed with the interview material to uncover the core of the experience.

5.2.4. Participants and sampling procedures

Based on the phenomenological approach that examines individuals' lived experiences (Creswell, 2007; More, 1994) and reflecting the nature of qualitative research, the sample size is not critical because a small number of participants can provide deep insights into their experiences and serve the study's purpose. The final study sample consisted of 25 participants. The core group addressing the primary research questions included 16 Algerian Muslim parents. Data collection with parents continued until theoretical saturation was reached, meaning that new interviews no longer yielded new thematic insights

but instead confirmed existing categories and themes in the data (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006). This principle of saturation, rather than a predetermined number, is considered the gold standard for determining sample size in qualitative research (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

To provide essential context and facilitate data triangulation, a further 9 participants were included as expert informants. These individuals—comprising Quranic teachers, school administrators, and imams—offered an invaluable 'insider' perspective on the institutional and pedagogical practices of the Quranic schools, which greatly enriched the interpretation and critical analysis of the parents' lived experiences (Yüksel & Yıldırım, 2015).

I aimed to interview both parents together to gain a more comprehensive understanding of their views. However, in all cases, I was only able to interview one parent. Despite this, the opinions expressed by the interviewed parents often reflected the collective views of both, as they frequently spoke on behalf of the couple.

The voices presented in this thesis mainly come from interviews with Algerian Muslims in the southern regions of the country. On two occasions, I interviewed individuals from the north to meet the required number of participants for this study. The interviews were conducted between March and July 2023.

Different major sampling methods can recruit or select research respondents and participants in qualitative research (Niezabitowska, 2018; Ryder et al., 2019). In this study, I used purposeful sampling to identify and select information-rich cases, a technique recommended by Palinkas et al. (2015). This approach allowed me to target individuals who were particularly knowledgeable and experienced with the phenomenon under investigation, as Cresswell and Plano Clark (2011) outlined. The chosen participants best addressed the research questions and contributed to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under study (Kuper et al., 2008). Specific inclusion and exclusion criteria were established to ensure the participants were suitable for answering the study's research questions.

The inclusion criteria described the essential characteristics participants needed to meet to take part in the study. Since the research focused on the perspectives of Algerian Muslim parents, the main inclusion criterion was that participants must be Algerian Muslim parents with school-aged children (aged between 5 and 16 years) attending Quranic schools. I also ensured gender balance when selecting participants to create a more representative sample of the population. Another inclusion criterion was geographic location; participants had to live in one of the three southern provinces of Algeria, Beni Abbes, Bechar, or Adrar. I added two extra participants from another region during the recruitment process to meet the required sample size. For the exclusion criteria, I excluded parents who were relatives or those with children below school age to maintain objectivity and relevance.

The same method for selecting parents was applied to these additional participants. Teachers, imams, and administrators were included if they had at least three years of experience in Quranic schools and lived in the specified Algerian provinces. Gender balance was once again prioritised to ensure equal representation of male and female perspectives. All imams are male, and most often, they serve as both administrators and Quran teachers. Individuals who did not meet the predefined inclusion criteria were excluded from the study. These criteria ensured that the sample was appropriate and ethical, aligning with the research objectives.

Table 3: Study Participants

Region	Parents (M / F)	Quran Teachers (M / F)	School Administrators (M / F)	Imams (M)	Unique Participants per Region
Beni Abbes	Bilal, Zakaria* (2M) Wahiba, Mubaraka* (2F)	Zakaria* (1M), Mubaraka* (1F)	—	—	4
Bechar	Tawfik (1M) Samia, Amal, Saida, Nadia, Fatima, Maryam (6F)	Ahmad (1M), Waleed* (1M)	Waleed* (1M)	—	8
Adrar	Salim, Jawad, Boubakr, Youcef*, Abdelghani* (5M) Sabah, Laila (2F)	Khaled, Youcef*, Omar*, Ali*, Abdelghani* (5M)	Ali* (1M)	Omar*, Ali*, Abdelghani* (3M)	11
Media	—	Zayyan*, Issam (2M)	Zayyan* (1M)	Zayyan* (1M)	2
Total Unique Participants	8M / 10F = 18	10M / 1F = 11	3M / 0F = 3	4M	25

Note: Names marked with an asterisk (*) indicate individuals with multiple roles. The 36 role entries correspond to 25 unique participants (18 parents and 7 expert informants). Interview questions were customised for each participant's specific roles. Data collection ceased once theoretical saturation was reached, achieved with the 18 parents. The 7 expert informants (teachers, administrators, imams) were included to provide essential contextual depth and facilitate methodological triangulation, ensuring a comprehensive analysis.

5.2.4.1. Limitations and Delimitations in Participant Selection

In conducting this study on Algerian Muslim parents' perceptions of the purpose of Quranic schools, several limitations and delimitations arose in participant selection. Without an effective way to directly contact all potential participants, especially those outside easily accessible networks, I relied heavily on third parties, such as the Directorates of Religious Affairs and Endowments, and social media contacts, to suggest potential candidates.

Since my research depended on volunteers for one-on-one interviews, the participant selection was naturally biased towards individuals more willing and available to share their views on Quranic schools. This reliance on volunteers likely resulted in a sample that is more enthusiastic, reflective, and expressive about their beliefs and experiences than might be the case in a more representative sample of the broader population of Algerian Muslim parents.

Although this bias provided rich, detailed insights, it also has a limitation because it might not fully represent the diversity of perspectives within the broader parent population. More reserved or less articulate parents, or those with differing views on Quranic schools, could have been underrepresented in this study. Consequently, the findings may reflect the experiences and attitudes of those more willing and comfortable sharing their perspectives rather than offering a complete view of all parents' opinions regarding Quranic schools.

Furthermore, this research aimed to phenomenologically explore the core of parents' perspectives on Quranic schools, rather than assess how common or widespread these views are among the broader population. Therefore, while the study provides valuable qualitative insights, it does not capture the full spectrum of opinions and experiences among Algerian Muslim parents. This aligns with the phenomenological emphasis on depth and richness of data rather than statistical generalisability, but it requires caution to avoid over-generalising the findings.

For feasibility, the geographical range of participants was also limited to specific areas. Most participants were from my region and two neighbouring regions in southern Algeria. Two participants from a district in northern Algeria were included to meet the required number of participants. While this approach introduced some diversity in regional representation, all participants still came from relatively similar cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds typical of these areas.

As a result, demographic trends, such as notable cultural or socioeconomic differences, were largely unexplored in this study. Parents from other regions or with significantly different demographic backgrounds might have divergent perspectives on the role and purpose of Quranic schools. While the diversity in regions and gender was recognised, it was not examined for fundamental differences in viewpoints regarding Quranic schools. Consequently, the findings may not fully represent the wider range of opinions across the diverse Algerian population.

These limitations highlight the potential bias in the sample, which may not capture the full range of parental views on Quranic education. It is acknowledged that the sample size of 18 parents, although adequate to achieve theoretical saturation (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006) for this phenomenological study, limits the ability to claim comprehensive representation of all Algerian Muslim parents. As explained in the justification of the sampling strategy (section 5.2.4), the main goal was to gain a deep, nuanced understanding of lived experiences rather than broad representational coverage (Sandelowski, 1995). Moreover, the inclusion of expert informants, as previously discussed, was a deliberate strategy to add contextual depth and enable triangulation, thereby reducing this limitation by supporting a more robust and critically engaged analysis. In the following sections, I will outline how data collection and analysis were designed to improve the reliability and depth of findings despite these constraints (Golafshani, 2003).

5.2.5. Pilot study

For the pilot study, I recruited two parents and a Quran teacher who also served as an administrator. The pilot provided a valuable opportunity to refine the research instruments and practise phenomenological interviewing techniques. After completing the pilot, I revised some questions to make them more straightforward and clearer, especially those addressing sensitive topics such as fundamentalism in Quranic schools, ensuring participants could understand and engage without confusion or discomfort. Importantly, the pilot revealed that my initial questions sometimes elicited brief, descriptive answers. I therefore refined my approach to include more effective prompts and probing questions. The literature highlights the importance of pilot studies in qualitative research, emphasising their role in identifying redundant or unclear elements in interview protocols and improving the flow and clarity of the questions

(Van Teijlingen & Hundley, 2001; Yin, 2018). This practice is essential for moving beyond superficial responses to achieve the depth of engagement required for rigorous phenomenological analysis (Holloway & Galvin, 2023).

Additionally, the pilot study helped me identify and eliminate a redundant section in one of the parent-directed questions, which enhanced the overall coherence and focus of the interviews. This approach aligns with Maxwell's (2013) argument that pilot studies act as a mechanism to ensure that data collection tools effectively meet the research aims while being mindful of participants' needs. Furthermore, Creswell and Poth (2016) emphasise that pilot studies enable researchers to test the feasibility of their methods and refine them to improve the reliability and validity of the data collected.

By conducting a rehearsal for the main data collection, the pilot study enhanced my skills and confidence as the primary research tool, allowing me to create a more conducive environment for in-depth discussion (Malterud et al., 2016). By carefully revising my questions and interview techniques based on feedback from the pilot, I ensured that the research instruments were suitable for the full study, ultimately enabling me to gather valuable insights and complex, reflective narratives about participants' perspectives on Quranic schools in Algeria.

5.2.6. Analysis of Data

Recording interviews with digital audio devices and note-taking is considered an effective qualitative research method to ensure the richness and accuracy of collected data. Using digital recorders enables researchers to capture detailed responses, including pauses, tonal nuances, and inflections, which are crucial when interpreting interviewees' meanings and emotions (Poland, 1995). At the same time, taking reflective notes provides an immediate layer of analysis, helping to identify key patterns and non-verbal cues (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). This dual approach improves the trustworthiness of qualitative data (Patton, 2014) and offers instant insights that can inform probing questions during the interview itself (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Immediately after each interview, I transcribed the audio recordings in Arabic verbatim. This immediate transcription process is a vital initial step in the analysis, as it helps me become thoroughly familiar with the data, which is crucial for phenomenological analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2013). It enabled me to capture details accurately while they were still fresh in my mind. I listened to each recording multiple times to ensure the transcription reflected all linguistic nuances and emotional cadence, providing instant insights that can help formulate probing questions during the interview itself (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The next stage involved translating transcripts from the Algerian-Arabic dialect into English with care. This translation was not just about language but also about culture and concepts, requiring careful interpretation to maintain the original meaning, cultural context, and emotional impact of the participants' speech. I followed the principle of conceptual equivalence rather than literal translation to preserve the authenticity and integrity of the data (Twinn, 1997), ensuring the participants' genuine voices were accurately represented in the analysis.

The processes of repeated listening, transcribing, and translating constituted an intensive and iterative initial engagement with the data, fulfilling the essential first step of deep familiarisation required for rigorous qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Colaizzi, 1978). Following this, in strict adherence to ethical research guidelines, I anonymised all interview transcripts. Pseudonyms (e.g., "Fatima," "Yusuf") were used, and all identifying details were removed or generalised (e.g., "a local Quranic institution" instead of a specific school name). This approach aligns with ethical standards (Race & Vidal-hall, 2019; Creswell & Poth, 2018) to protect participant identities and ensure confidentiality.

The prepared transcripts formed the core dataset for a detailed thematic analysis. This analysis was conducted manually to maintain a close connection to the data and was enriched by the reflective notes taken during interviews. The specific methodological steps followed for this analysis, which were designed to ensure a critical and interpretive engagement with the text to uncover the essential structures of the participants' experiences, are detailed in the following section (5.2.6.1) on Colaizzi's (1978) phenomenological method.

5.2.6.1. Colaizzi's Phenomenological Method of Data Analysis

The analysis of the interview data was conducted using Colaizzi's (1978) phenomenological method. This framework was chosen for its rigorous, structured approach to interpreting qualitative data, which ensures that the findings are firmly grounded in the participants' lived experiences whilst facilitating the critical engagement and thematic depth required in phenomenological research (Morrow et al., 2015). The method's seven steps guided a process of immersion, interpretation, and synthesis, moving from raw transcripts to a comprehensive description of the essential structures of the phenomenon. The following outlines how each step was systematically applied in this study.

Step 1: Obtaining a general sense of each transcript

I immersed myself in the data by meticulously reading and re-reading each translated transcript in its entirety. This was not a passive activity but an active process of engagement, enabling me to become deeply familiar with the depth and nuance of each participant's narrative. As van Manen (2016)

suggests, this immersion forms the foundation of phenomenology, preparing the researcher to discern the meaning within the text. Throughout this process, I kept reflective memos to record initial interpretive ideas and impressions, initiating a critical dialogue with the data that would persist throughout all stages of analysis.

Step 2: Extraction of Significant Statements

Once immersed, I systematically identified and extracted key statements that directly addressed the research questions. This involved highlighting phrases or sentences that captured crucial aspects of a participant's experience with Quranic schools. The criterion for significance was a statement's ability to reveal insights into the purpose, value, or challenges of these institutions. This process, as recommended by Colaizzi (1978), ensures that the richness of the data is maintained for deeper analysis while emphasising its most relevant elements.

Step 3: Formulation of Meanings

I then formulated meanings for each significant statement. This was a vital interpretive act where I expressed the underlying meaning or essence contained within the participant's words. For example, a participant's statement about "the school protecting my child from bad influences" was interpreted as meaning "Quranic schools are perceived as a moral safeguard within the community." This process required ongoing reflexive bracketing to reduce the influence of my own preconceptions and ensure the formulated meanings remained faithful to the participants' experiences, in line with the phenomenological principle of bracketing (Husserl, 1970; Moustakas, 1994).

Step 4: Organization of formulated meanings into clusters of themes and themes

The formulated meanings were then organised into themes; each theme illustrated a broad aspect of the participants' experiences. This involved an iterative process of comparing and contrasting the formulated meanings to identify patterns and connections across the entire dataset. I used visual mapping techniques to group related meanings into initial clusters, which were then refined into cohesive themes that captured the core of the participants' shared experiences. This Colaizzi's technique emphasises grouping themes to organise data while maintaining intricacy systematically (Sanders, 2003). Groenewald (2004) also utilised this step successfully to categorise data into meaningful thematic categories. These theme sets are subsequently organised into emergent broad themes. The four thematic chapters illustrate the process of developing broad themes. For example, the broad theme "The Purpose of Quranic Schools in Algeria" emerged by integrating three different clusters of themes,

including Quranic Schools and the Fostering of National and Islamic Identity in Children, Quranic Schools and the Moral and Faith Development of Children, and Quranic Schools and the Shaping of Children's Behaviour.

Step 5: Developing an Exhaustive Description

Based on the thematic clusters, I created a detailed account of the phenomenon. This involved crafting a rich, narrative description that integrated all the theme clusters into a cohesive whole. This account provides a comprehensive summary of "what" it is like for participants to engage with Quranic schools, capturing its full depth and complexity. As Wertz (2005) highlights, this thorough description is vital for offering a credible portrayal of the participants' collective reality.

Step 6: Producing the Fundamental Structure

I then distilled the exhaustive description to produce the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. This meant reducing the narrative to its absolute essence, a few concise statements that capture the core of what it means for Algerian parents to choose and value Quranic schools. This fundamental structure is presented in the final chapter of this thesis. This step, as Finlay (2009) notes, is where the researcher moves from description to essential interpretation, identifying the invariant core of the experience.

Step 7: Validation of Results

Finally, the findings were verified through a process of member checking to confirm that the interpreted essences and fundamental structure accurately reflected the participants' lived experiences. I discussed a comprehensive summary of the findings with a sample of participants. Their feedback was used to confirm that the interpreted essences and fundamental structure genuinely represented the participants' lived experiences. As instrumental; it validated the analysis's authenticity and provided additional nuanced insights, which were incorporated to further enrich the final interpretation. This process of participant verification is a vital step for establishing the credibility and trustworthiness of phenomenological research (Creswell & Poth, 2018). A similar study by Doyle (2007) emphasises the importance of this step in ensuring rigour and credibility in phenomenological studies. In this study, it served as the final check to ensure the analysis remained rooted in the participants' world and that their authentic voices were accurately represented.

5.2.7. Researcher's ontological position and Reflexivity

The issue of reflexivity is essential in any academic research, as a researcher's worldview can greatly influence data collection and interpretation. Ontology relates to our beliefs and assumptions about the nature of reality and what exists. A researcher's ontological stance determines whether they see the world from an objective or subjective perspective (Gao & Low, 2014). Positionality, or the researcher's self-positioning, is key to evaluating the validity of the current study. Consequently, many scholars highlight the importance of reflecting on one's positionality (Miah, 2015).

Positionality in qualitative research recognises that researchers are not neutral observers but are embedded within the social phenomena they investigate. This means their personal backgrounds, beliefs, and values shape how they conduct and interpret research. Researchers must acknowledge their biases and reflexively engage with how their positionality influences the study. Furthermore, it is important to recognise that qualitative studies exist within specific social and cultural structures, and researchers must remain aware of how these contexts impact the research process (Datta, 2018). Positionality also requires transparency, ensuring that researchers disclose how their perspectives affect the framing of questions, data collection, and analysis (Gregório et al., 2021; Edwards, 2021). By doing so, they can better reflect the central ideas and experiences of the participants within the study (Niezabitowska, 2018).

In this research, positionality and reflexivity were key considerations. As a Muslim woman of Algerian origin from a southern province, I attended Quranic schools and memorised the Quran at home, in mosques, and later while living abroad in the UK. This situated me as an "insider" in many respects: sharing a faith, a cultural background, and a lived experience with the phenomenon under study. This personal background provided certain advantages, such as fostering connections and shared experiences with participants, aligning with the concept of 'alliance formation' (Harvey, 1996) and relationship building (Hopkins, 2007). It facilitated access and built immediate rapport and trust, as participants often felt understood on a cultural and religious level without the need for extensive explanation. My fluency in the local dialect allowed for nuanced communication, and my understanding of religious concepts ensured accurate interpretation of terms and practices. Furthermore, my insider position afforded certain privileges; coming from a society where sending children to Quranic schools is a widely accepted practice provided a significant motivator and a deep, empathetic foundation for exploring Muslim parents' views on the purpose of Quranic education.

However, this insider status was complex and posed challenges that required my ongoing attention. I had to actively guard against the possibility that my own positive experiences might cause me to favour data confirming my pre-existing beliefs about the value of Quranic schools. I also remained conscious that my identity was multifaceted; while I shared a faith and culture with participants, my role as an educated researcher based overseas could create a power dynamic or a sense of distance. Recognising

this dual position was essential. It meant I had to prioritise building genuine rapport and constantly check my interpretation to avoid any unintended bias. A detailed account of the specific strategies used to minimise these biases, including triangulation, thick description, and reflexivity, is included in the following section (5.2.8).

5.2.8. Minimising and controlling bias

To minimise potential biases associated with my insider/outsider positionality, I established specific criteria for assessing trustworthiness (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) and employed a multi-strategy approach throughout the research process. The specific steps taken were as follows:

*Bracketing (Epoche) and Reflexivity: To reduce the influence of my preconceptions and positive experiences, I engaged in ongoing reflexivity through journaling. This involved explicitly noting my assumptions before and during data collection and analysis to deliberately set them aside (Moustakas, 1994). This was not a single event but an ongoing process of self-examination to ensure the findings came from the data itself.

*Deliberate Sampling for Diversity: To avoid a homogenised sample that might reinforce my own views, I devised a recruitment strategy to ensure a diverse and representative range of perspectives. The study was expanded to include participants from three southern provinces and one northern province. I specifically sought variation in parent age, gender, socioeconomic background, and educational attainment to capture viewpoints that might challenge my own assumptions actively.

*Methodological Triangulation: To enhance the credibility of the findings and prevent over-reliance on a single data source, I employed triangulation by collecting information from multiple sources—parents, Quran teachers, administrators, and imams (Thakur & Chetty, 2020). This facilitated cross-verification of data and offered a more comprehensive, contextualised understanding of the phenomenon.

*Strict adherence to analytical frameworks: The structured application of Colaizzi's (1978) phenomenological method provided a rigorous, step-by-step process for analysis. This systematic approach ensured that themes were derived from the participants' data rather than my preconceptions. Furthermore, member checking—where participants validated my interpretations—was essential for confirming the trustworthiness of the findings and grounding them in the participants' realities (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

*Documenting the Process (Thick Description and Audit Trails): To ensure reliability and transferability, I provided detailed, in-depth descriptions of the participants and context within the findings. This enables readers to evaluate the relevance of the findings to different settings. I also kept a thorough audit trail of all research decisions, including translation choices and analytical steps, to make the process transparent and easy to replicate.

5.3. Research location and gaining access

This study was carried out in Algeria, using a multi-site approach to ensure a wide range of geographical and socio-cultural representation. Data collection took place across three provinces in the south of the country (Beni Abbes, Bechar, Adrar) and one province in the north (Media).

Gaining access to participants demanded a multifaceted and adaptable approach, blending formal official channels with informal community-based methods.

1. Formal Access and Official Permissions:

To engage with Quranic teachers, administrators, and imams, formal permissions were obtained from the Directorates of Religious Affairs (Awqaf) in the three southern regions. This official approval was essential for legitimising the research and facilitating introductions to potential participants within Quranic schools. However, a significant logistical challenge was the lengthy time required to acquire these permissions, which affected the research timeline.

2. Informal and Community-Oriented Access:

Access to parents was mainly achieved through snowball sampling methods, which proved highly effective in building trust and recruiting participants across all four regions. Furthermore, attending a community forum on Quranic education in Bechar offered a valuable opportunity for direct recruitment, as I was able to meet and obtain consent from multiple parents in an organic setting.

3. Adaptive Data Collection Methods:

To accommodate the logistical constraints of a limited fieldwork period and the diverse schedules of participants, data collection was carried out flexibly.

In-Person Interviews: The majority of interviews were conducted face-to-face in settings convenient for participants, including local libraries and private rooms within Quranic schools, to ensure a comfortable and familiar environment.

Remote Interviews: To include participants from the northern province and accommodate those with scheduling conflicts, interviews were also conducted via video and telephone calls.

Written Responses: A small number of participants who initially consented but could not schedule an interview chose to provide detailed written answers to the interview questions.

This adaptive approach, though driven by practical constraints, ensured the inclusion of a wide range of perspectives and preserved the integrity and scope of data collection. All interactions, regardless of format, were carefully documented to maintain consistency and rigour.

5.4. Ensuring Trustworthiness: Dependability and Transferability

Trustworthiness is the foundation of rigorous qualitative research, addressing concerns about validity and reliability within an interpretive paradigm (Amankwaa, 2016; Eryilmaz, 2022). This study ensures trustworthiness by meeting the criteria of dependability (consistency and replicability of the process) and transferability (applicability of the findings), as defined by Lincoln and Guba (1985).

Dependability

Dependability pertains to the stability and consistency of the research process over time and across different conditions, indicating that the findings can be replicated within a similar context (Polit & Beck, 2012). To uphold dependability, this study implemented the following strategies:

* Audit Trail: A comprehensive audit trail was kept, recording all essential research decisions, data collection procedures, and the progression of the analytical process. This includes interview protocols, reflective journal entries, and a record of theme development and refinement.

*In-depth Methodological Description: This chapter offers a comprehensive, transparent account of the research design, data collection, and analysis procedures (e.g., the explicit use of Colaizzi's method). This transparency enables future researchers to understand and potentially replicate the study's process.

*Code-Recode Strategy: During analysis, data was revisited and re-coded at different times to ensure consistency in the interpretation and application of themes.

Transferability

Transferability refers to the extent to which the findings of a qualitative study can be applied or generalised to other contexts, settings, or groups. Unlike quantitative generalisability, it is the reader's

responsibility to decide on transferability, while the researcher's role is to provide enough information for that decision to be made (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). To facilitate transferability, this study offers:

***Thick Description:** The findings chapters (Chapters 6-9) offer detailed, contextual accounts of participants' lived experiences, incorporating direct quotes and comprehensive narratives. This "thickness" enables readers to hear the participants' voices and grasp the specific socio-cultural setting of Quranic schools in southern Algeria.

***Purposeful Sampling Strategy:** The demographic and geographic diversity of the participant pool (detailed in Section 5.2.4) is clearly outlined. By describing the specific characteristics of the participants and their locations, readers can assess the similarity between the research context and their own.

***Contextual Clarity:** The research setting, including the role of the Directorates of Religious Affairs and the structure of Quranic schools, has been explicitly detailed in Chapters 2 and 3. This detailed contextual information is vital for readers to assess the potential transferability of the findings to other Muslim or post-colonial educational contexts.

In conclusion, by following a thorough and well-documented process and offering rich contextual data, this study confirms its dependability and provides readers with the essential information to evaluate its transferability.

5.5. Ethical compliance and procedure

Ethical considerations in research include following professional protocols and adhering to established codes of conduct to ensure that researchers act responsibly and protect participants' rights and well-being (Niemi, 2020; Ronald et al., 2020; Chervenak & McCullough, 2021; Broesch et al., 2020). This study was designed and carried out in full compliance with the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) ethical guidelines, with formal approval obtained from the university's ethics committee before any data collection. Following these ethical practices also improves the reliability, validity, and overall trustworthiness of the study (Eriksen et al., 2021).

***Informed Consent and Participant Debriefing**

The principle of informed consent was strictly observed. Participants received information sheets at the initial meetings, outlining the study details and their rights (see appendices 2 and 3). Written consent was obtained from all participants before their involvement, using forms that included comprehensive

information about the study's purpose, scope, and voluntary nature (see Appendix 1). Participants were told they could withdraw at any point without consequences. For added transparency, a debriefing form was provided after the interviews (see Appendix 7), which explained the study's aims, described how the data would be used, and included contact details for further questions or clarifications.

*Confidentiality, Anonymity, and Data Security

Protecting participants' confidentiality was a key priority (Broesch et al., 2020). All personally identifiable information was removed from the data. Pseudonyms (e.g., "Ahmad," "Nadia," "Omar") were used to ensure their identities remained confidential. Additionally, all digital audio recordings and transcripts were stored securely on password-protected devices, with access restricted solely to the researcher.

*Cultural Sensitivity and Methodological Integrity

Interview questions were carefully crafted (see appendices 5 and 6) and piloted to ensure they were respectful, culturally sensitive, and minimised discomfort, especially on sensitive topics. This pilot study was vital in enhancing question clarity. To further support ethical transparency and trustworthiness, several participants were invited to review and confirm their contributions during transcription, ensuring the findings remained true to their authentic experiences.

5.6. Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the detailed methodological framework adopted for this study. It described the selection of a qualitative phenomenological approach as the most appropriate way to explore the nuanced lived experiences and perspectives of Algerian Muslim parents regarding Quranic schools. The chapter detailed the specific procedures for participant selection, data collection through semi-structured interviews, and the rigorous application of Colaizzi's phenomenological method for analysis. Additionally, it addressed important considerations such as researcher positionality, reflexivity, and the strategies employed to ensure the trustworthiness and ethical integrity of the research process. The methodology presented here provides a solid and transparent foundation for the presentation and critical analysis of the findings in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 6

The Purpose of Quranic Schools

6.1. Introduction

This chapter explores the main objectives of Quranic schools in Algeria from the viewpoints of parents and educators, directly addressing the central research question. The analysis is structured around three emerging themes that collectively illustrate the diverse functions these institutions serve. The main argument of this chapter is that Algerian parents perceive Quranic schools not merely as supplementary religious classes but as essential institutions for the comprehensive development of their children's identity, morality, and behaviour—development they believe is absent in the state education system.

First, the analysis explores how Quranic schools are seen as strongholds of both national and Islamic identity, actively defending a unique Algerian-Muslim identity against the influences of globalisation and secularisation. Second, it examines their perceived role in the moral and spiritual growth of children, where religious teaching is closely connected to character development. Finally, the chapter describes how parents and teachers view these schools as influential agents in shaping children's behaviour, often attributing to them the power to facilitate transformative personal change. By integrating participants' narratives directly with interpretive and theoretical analysis, this chapter emphasises parents' lived experiences as the main source of meaning-making, in line with the phenomenological approach outlined in the methodology chapter. In doing so, it moves beyond simple description to provide a critical interpretation of the deeply rooted cultural and religious significance of Quranic education in contemporary Algeria.

6.2 Quranic Schools and the Fostering of National and Islamic Identity in Children

As found in this study, a strong link between the role of Quranic schools and both national and Islamic traditions was established, particularly concerning Sunni Islam under the Maliki school of jurisprudence, which is the dominant Islamic sect in Algeria (Morrow, 2014; Racelma, 2013). Analysis of the participant interviews shows that this theological foundation is deliberately utilised by parents and educators, who see Quranic schools as dedicated hubs for fostering a unified Algerian-Islamic identity, directly countering perceived cultural homogenisation.

In this study, participants offered valuable insights into their perceptions of the role of Quranic schools, particularly regarding how these institutions nurture the national and religious identities of their children. Nine participants described how Quranic schools, with their focus on Islamic ethics and

values, serve as essential elements guiding children on a ‘guided journey’ of self-discovery and identity formation. This concept illustrates how Quranic schools foster an environment that promotes a sense of belonging and community rooted in shared faith and values (Ali, 2018; Ebrahimi, 2017). Importantly, this guided journey is viewed not as a passive process but as an active, intergenerational endeavour. According to these participants, the study shows the extent to which Quranic schools in Algeria instil values and cultural practices based on Islamic teachings, encouraging a sense of communal belonging within Algerian society and ultimately within the global Ummah. While both public and Quranic schools in Algeria contribute to identity development, parents in this study preferred Quranic schools because they are more specialised in theology and focus on nurturing children's Islamic identity. This preference highlights a perceived uniqueness; parents see Quranic schools as especially capable of intentionally preserving identity, which they consider a vital addition to the state's secular educational system.

According to Smith (2001), national identity ultimately involves preserving and passing down the patterns of values, symbols, memories, myths, and traditions that constitute the unique heritage of nations. It includes individuals' identification with these specific aspects of heritage and values. Therefore, Quranic schools play an important role in this process. Islam forms the foundation of society's social and cultural identity and influences the ethical and attitudinal framework. This is particularly clear in Algeria, where the intersection of religion and national identity remains influential. Even though strict adherence to religion varies, identification with Islam stays strong and steady (Metz, 1993). This religious identity supports universal Islamic values and encourages a shared sense of responsibility within the wider Muslim community, highlighting communal cohesion and moral integrity in local and global contexts.

One of the parents in the study remarked that “from a societal perspective, Quranic schools are an integral part of our community's traditions, and it is essential to nurture our children with the same religious upbringing as we received” (Salim, parent).

Salim’s statement is analytically important because it highlights the role of Quranic schools not just as places for transmitting religious knowledge but as fulfilling a collective, normative duty to safeguard both cultural continuity and Islamic identity. His comment reflects the strong emotional connection parents have to these institutions as symbols of national and religious heritage, representing their role as guardians of Algeria’s moral and spiritual legacy. From this perspective, Quranic schools are seen not only as educational environments but as sites where identity is preserved, where the values of faith, community, and nation come together. Salim’s sentiment echoes Amara and Habbas’s (2017) argument that Quranic schools have historically and continue to play a vital role in protecting the core elements of Islamic identity within Arab-Muslim societies. However, it also broadens this view by illustrating

how parents regard this role as a living, ongoing duty—a way to uphold their community’s moral fabric and pass on its spiritual traditions to future generations.

This parental perspective strongly resonates with existing scholarship on religious education and identity development. According to Gross (2011), religious education provides a structured framework for transmitting specific faith practices while also shaping an individual’s moral and social outlook. In this context, the Quranic school functions as more than a place of rote learning; it acts as a structured moral community that nurtures children’s sense of self within a shared religious and cultural heritage. Here, students engage with Islamic teachings in ways that promote both knowledge and a deep emotional connection with their faith, reinforcing the link between religious belonging and national awareness.

These insights align with Guibernau’s (2007) definition of national identity as a collective feeling rooted in belonging to a shared nation and recognising distinctive characteristics. Similarly, the parents’ perspectives in this study show how Islamic identity becomes an essential expression of Algerian national identity, where faith, culture, and citizenship are interconnected. Furthermore, their views reflect Harttgen and Opfinger’s (2014) and Omelchenko et al.’s (2015) claims that national identity manifests through a mixture of knowledge, emotional attachment, and practice. However, while this emphasis on continuity and tradition strengthens communal cohesion, it also reveals a tension between preservation and adaptation. This raises an important question: how can Quranic schools uphold their cultural and religious mission whilst remaining responsive to the changing educational and social realities of contemporary Algeria?

Another parent stated:

Our children represent the future custodians of our faith. Cultivating a strong Muslim identity within them is essential for their spiritual and emotional prosperity. It transcends mere instruction in Islamic rituals and profoundly comprehends Islam's values, ethics, and principles. With a firm grounding in their faith, children develop resilience against societal pressures and proudly uphold their religious convictions (Nadia, parent).

Nadia’s statement greatly builds on Salim’s earlier point. While Salim highlighted the intergenerational transfer of tradition, Nadia explains the process and outcomes of this identity formation. She clearly separates superficial ritual instruction from the deep, internalised understanding of Islamic ethics that Quranic schools aim to foster. This difference is important because it frames these institutions as places for developing what Bourdieu (2020) might describe as a ‘religious habitus’—a resilient, embodied set

of dispositions that influence a child's moral views and worldview. Her use of the phrase "custodians of our faith" portrays children not just as passive receivers but as active future protectors of the religious tradition, thereby emphasising the schools' role in maintaining long-term religious and cultural continuity.

Furthermore, Nadia explicitly connects this deeply rooted religious identity to two key aspects of the chapter's argument: holistic development and resilience to external pressures. First, her mention of "spiritual and emotional prosperity" aligns with the chapter's thesis that parents view these schools as vital for holistic growth, complementing and sometimes even surpassing the secular aims of state education. This perspective is supported by research in the psychology of religion, which shows that a strong, internalised religious identity can significantly enhance an individual's psychological well-being and resilience (King & Boyatzis, 2015; Tilliouine, 2014). Second, her claim that a solid grounding in faith fosters "resilience against societal pressures" directly addresses the chapter's theme of safeguarding identity from globalising and secular influences introduced in the introduction. This echoes the work of scholars like Gross (2011), who argue that religious education can serve as a 'buffer' against competing secular narratives, allowing individuals to navigate pluralistic societies without compromising their core beliefs. Therefore, Nadia's narrative is not merely a personal opinion, but reflects a broader social phenomenon where Quranic schools are viewed as essential for equipping the next generation with the spiritual and moral tools necessary to maintain their distinct identity in a changing world.

Similarly, another participant said:

A strong Muslim identity enables children to navigate societal diversity while staying true to their faith. It cultivates a feeling of belonging to a wider community and enhances the pride of being part of the global Muslim Ummah. This identity offers support and guidance in overcoming challenges and helps them make choices aligned with Islamic values (Sabah, parent).

Sabah's perspective adds an important element to the discussion: the use of identity in a complex, diverse society. Her statement goes beyond the internal development of identity to its external role. She describes a "solid Muslim identity" not as a shield that isolates, but as a compass that actively guides children through societal diversity. This aligns with Social Identity Theory (Trepte, 2013), which suggests that a strong in-group identity gives individuals a sense of belonging and self-esteem, which Sabah explicitly connects to a "sense of honour." Moreover, her view that identity helps ethical decision-making places Quranic education as a key source of what philosophers might call 'practical reasoning', the ability to apply moral principles to real-world decisions. This directly supports the chapter's main

argument that parents see these schools as essential for overall development, particularly by offering a solid moral framework for life.

However, the very strength and clarity of this identity, as championed by the participants, inherently raises critical questions. While parents have emphasized the positive role of Quranic schools in fostering a strong, resilient identity, this focused cultivation of a specific religious and cultural worldview necessarily opens the door to examining potential challenges related to inclusivity and engagement with the 'Other'. As Guibernau (2013) notes, strong collective identities can sometimes create boundaries between groups. Therefore, a critical question emerges: how do these socialisation processes, so effective in building faith and resilience, also navigate the imperative of fostering an inclusive mindset toward those of different beliefs? This is not to undermine the parents' goals but to engage critically with the complexities of identity formation in a globalized world. It is precisely this tension, between the unwavering preservation of faith and the navigation of a pluralistic society, that the following section must explore. The next central emergent theme, therefore, addresses these dynamics directly by examining the nuanced cultural and religious socialisation processes within Quranic schools and their role in shaping children's worldviews.

Alongside the perspectives of Algerian Muslim parents, the views of Quran teachers, Imams, and administrators are essential to understanding the institutional mission of these schools. These participants have valuable experience and knowledge about the educational environment, curriculum, and the broader implications of Quranic schools. Their insights shed light on the pedagogical and theological goals behind the identity-forming processes described by parents, offering a more comprehensive view of how these institutions operate as a coordinated socialising force. For example, one administrator, Waleed, explicitly linked identity formation to moral character and civic leadership.

Furthermore, fostering a strong Muslim identity instils important character virtues like empathy, honesty, compassion, and integrity in our children. These traits serve as the foundation for developing individuals who positively impact society. Through nurturing Islamic education both at home and in school, we pave the way for cultivating future leaders dedicated to advancing peace, harmony, and justice – fundamental principles of Islam (Waleed, administrator).

Waleed's statement is crucial because it connects the inner world of identity with the outer world of social action. He clearly outlines a developmental path, suggesting that a strong Muslim identity forms the base for developing specific virtues, which in turn help create individuals capable of positively influencing society, ultimately leading to the development of future leaders. This aligns the school's purpose with the idea of "citizenship education," although within a particular religious framework, and directly supports the chapter's argument about holistic development that includes

moral and civic aspects. His view goes beyond merely preserving identity, as highlighted by parents, and reinterprets it as a project of shaping a specific kind of citizen, one whose faith motivates them to serve the public good.

This vision aligns with Halstead's (2004) argument that Islamic education inherently aims to cultivate individuals who are not only devout but also ethically aware and socially responsible. However, Waleed's quote also introduces a possible tension. While he and scholars like Ameen and Hassan (2013) suggest that these schools are rooted in "inclusive Islamic values," a closer look raises a key question: how is this inclusivity practically implemented and taught alongside the strong, particularistic identity being developed? The connection between a specific religious identity and universal virtues such as justice appears obvious, yet the teaching methods for ensuring these virtues extend beyond the internal group remain a crucial area for further investigation. This tension prepares the ground for the essential critical analysis in the next section on socialisation processes. Therefore, this administrator's perspective not only underlines the role of Quranic schools in shaping identity but also underscores the complexity of translating these ideals into practice, especially regarding engagement with a diverse society.

In line with earlier perspectives, another participant, an Imam called Abdelghani, articulated the matter with doctrinal authority, stating:

Attending Quranic schools and studying the Quran is the duty of every Muslim, whether young or old, male or female, because it is the foundation of life. However, today, worldly education has overshadowed Muslims (Abdelghani, Imam).

Abdelghani's statement is important because it raises the discussion from a parental choice to a religious duty. His use of the term "duty" (*fardh* in Islamic jurisprudence) carries significant theological importance, framing Quranic education as not just a cultural preference but a necessary act of worship. This strongly supports the chapter's argument about the perceived essential role of these schools for a complete Muslim life. Additionally, his description of the Quran as the "constitution of life" is deeply meaningful. This view aligns with the Quran's self-description: "This is the book; in it is guidance sure, without doubt, to those who fear Allah; who believe in the unseen, are steadfast in prayer, and spend out of what we have provided for them" (Quran, 2:2-3). Here, the Quran describes itself not as a constitution for governance or statecraft but as a personal guide for individual believers, emphasizing spiritual growth and moral consciousness (*taqwa*). However, Abdelghani's powerful metaphor of a "constitution" expands this concept, suggesting that the Quran's personal guidance forms the foundational law for an entire way of life—ethical, social, and

personal. This metaphor places the Quranic school as the institution where this "constitutional" law is taught and absorbed.

Crucially, in the Algerian context, this "constitution of life" is not abstract; it is the very foundation of the national and Islamic identity examined in this chapter. The "worldly education" he views as a threat is often seen as a conduit for Western or secular globalised culture. Therefore, the role of the Quranic school becomes one of defending a specifically Algerian-Muslim way of life. This aligns with the idea of the "calligraphic state" (Messick, 2018), where Islamic texts underpin societal norms. In Algeria, this discourse is closely linked to the country's historical struggle and cultural identity, making the Quranic school a guardian of both faith and nation. Abdelghani thus presents a vision in which these schools are vital for shaping individuals who hold a divinely-based worldview, actively protecting a distinct Algerian-Muslim identity against the homogenising forces of secular globalisation. This Imam's perspective offers a crucial theological basis for the parents' views, reinforcing the idea that Quranic schools are essential for preserving this dual identity.

Ahmad, another participant who holds a teacher position, highlighted the multifaceted purpose of Quranic schools. He explicitly stated,

The role of Quranic schools in our society cannot be limited to religious and educational institutions; they are an integral part of the traditions and customs that have been part of the Algerian society for centuries and cannot be dispensed with (Ahmad: teacher).

This declaration is analytically significant. Ahmad's perspective, echoed by several participants, portrays Quranic schools as active cultural custodians. His insistence that these institutions "cannot be dispensed with" highlights their perceived necessity, framing them not as optional extras but as essential pillars of Algerian society. This shared view underscores the widespread recognition of these institutions as centres for religious and educational activities and as vital preservers of Algeria's rich cultural traditions and identity. This role is not passive; it involves a dynamic process of curating and transmitting what is considered crucial to Algerian-Muslim identity.

In line with Ahmad's insights, Boyle (2004) offers a valuable theoretical perspective, discussing the dual role of Quranic schools as agents of both preservation and change. Boyle emphasises that while these institutions uphold traditional values and practices, they also adjust to contemporary societal needs and challenges. Ahmad's depiction of the schools as an "integral part" of centuries-old traditions perfectly illustrates the preservation aspect of Boyle's framework. The schools maintain the foundational "fabric" of tradition, but to stay woven into a society that is itself evolving, they must also adapt. This dynamic enables Quranic schools to function as custodians of cultural heritage and as

catalysts for a particular kind of social change: one that ensures the values and teachings of Islam remain relevant to new generations, thereby strengthening the identity it seeks to preserve. Ultimately, this dual function, as described by both Ahmad and Boyle, is central to this sub-theme, demonstrating how these schools are viewed as vital for maintaining a cohesive and resilient national and Islamic identity in a modern context.

Furthermore, Zayyan, a religious figure, emphasised that these institutions are uniquely central to shaping Algerians' cultural and social identity. He stated that “the purpose of Quranic schools in Algeria is consistent with that of the broader Islamic and Arab nation: primarily, the dissemination of the Quran” (Zayyan, teacher). To contextualise this mission within a specific historical and national framework, he cited the famous poem by Sheikh Abdelhamid Ben Badis: “the people of Algeria are Muslims and belong to the Arab identity.” This connection is crucial; it links the religious mission of the schools directly to a key aspect of modern Algerian nationalism, presenting the dissemination of the Quran as both an act of religious fidelity and a reinforcement of a central national identity.

This perspective aligns with Nóvoa’s (2000) assertion that “education is by definition the space for the construction of a national identity” (p. 46). However, the data from this study, supported by other scholarship, allows us to go beyond this general principle towards a more specific argument. The views of participants like Zayyan, along with the findings of scholars such as Louglaithi and Haidoune (2023) and Ali (2018), suggest that Quranic schools in Algeria serve a unique dual purpose: they are both spaces for the passive inheritance of a given identity (as “Muslims and Arabs”) and for its active cultivation. This addresses a key tension in identity theory. While Billig (1995) notes that national identity is often taken for granted, and McCrone and Bechhofer (2008) suggest many hold a passive relationship to it, Quranic schools, as described by participants, seem to be sites where this passivity is challenged. The very act of attending a Quranic school and internalising its teachings constitutes an active engagement with the identity Ben Badis declared.

This active role has deep roots. As highlighted in the opening chapter of this thesis, these institutions played a crucial part during the colonial era, becoming focal points for actively defending this identity. For contemporary society, the key question is not whether these schools foster identity, but what type of engagement they promote. Do they mainly encourage passive acceptance, or do they foster a meaningful, reflective connection? The insights from participants, along with studies by Sharifi (2018) and Idris et al. (2012), strongly indicate the latter—that the blending of religious and national identity in these schools encourages a profound, internalised sense of belonging. Ultimately, as Hardianto (2005) contends, the success of any educational institution in shaping identity relies on committed educators. The testimony from this study shows that teachers and administrators in Quranic schools are

deliberately fulfilling this role, viewing their work not merely as religious instruction but as the nurturing of a coherent Algerian-Muslim self.

The processes of identity formation described by these participants are not only social but also deeply developmental. Building on the comparative analysis in Chapter 4, which juxtaposed Fowler's and other Western research on faith development with studies in Islamic contexts, we see that Quranic schools actively include the initial stages of such development by guiding children through religious stories, rituals, and symbols within a structured environment. As that chapter established, faith development, whether viewed through a Western or Islamic perspective, is a profound process of meaning-making. This aligns with the experiences shared by the study participants, who emphasised how Quranic schools foster an environment where children interact with peers and teachers who share similar values and beliefs, reinforcing their religious identity and cultivating a sense of belonging to the larger Algerian community.

The sense of community and shared identity within these schools strongly reinforces the fundamental aspects of faith, whether they are called intuitive-projective or rooted in early tarbiyah. These connections help us see how religious education influences children's identity development and spiritual growth (Cush & Baumfield, 2017). However, the comparative framework from Chapter 4 also highlights a universal tension: the shift from a received, tradition-based faith to a more individualised and reflective one. This raises a critical question directly informed by the data: do the social contexts of traditional Quranic schools adequately support the deeper critical thinking needed for this transition? While the focus on communal values reinforces a sense of belonging, the participants' stories suggest it may also limit the personal exploration that both Western and Islamic educational theorists consider essential for mature faith. This tension, evident in the data and the scholarly literature, raises important questions about how well Quranic schools prepare children to navigate an increasingly diverse society. Finding a balance between safeguarding cultural and religious heritage and encouraging critical thinking is vital for developing individuals capable of engaging with the complex social issues of modern life.

Thus, while Quranic schools play a vital role in fostering faith and identity, their ongoing relevance depends on adapting to the challenges of modern society. Successfully balancing the preservation of traditional values with the promotion of inclusivity and critical thinking— a challenge highlighted by the dialogue between Western and Islamic developmental theories — will be essential in shaping individuals who can meaningfully contribute to both local and global communities.

6.3. Quranic Schools and the Moral and Faith Development of Children

Data analysed in this subtheme confirms that the moral and faith development of children is a key concern emerging from the participants' viewpoints. The interviews reveal that parents do not see this as a passive process but as an active cultivation of character, deeply connected with religious instruction. Parents in this study broadly expressed the idea that their children are learning moral values grounded in Islamic principles and that their faith is being nurtured over time. For instance, one parent noted,

Since attending Quranic schools, I have seen changes in my child's moral and behaviour. He has become more honest and has increased his respect for me, his father and his siblings (Djamila: parent).

Another parent highlighted how this moral development is publicly visible, stating,

If we try to identify the positive aspects of Quranic schools, they are most clearly reflected in the morals of the children who attend them. These students stand out from others through their unique manners and exemplary behaviour, which are evident to everyone (Nadia: parent).

This parental focus on the formative role of Quranic schools aligns with the Islamic concept of *akhlāq*. Far more than just etiquette, *akhlāq* (Hornby, 1974) encompasses the core principles of good character and human behaviour, promoting virtues such as honesty, compassion, and loyalty while condemning immoral actions. These ethical standards, rooted in the teachings of the Quran and exemplified in the life of Prophet Muhammad, serve as a comprehensive framework for moral conduct (Zaroug, 1999). The findings of this study agree with existing literature emphasising the role of Quranic schools in fostering these moral principles and encouraging spiritual growth among students. The participants' narratives effectively demonstrate how the abstract concept of *akhlāq* is made tangible within the daily environment of the Quranic school, where religious learning is inherently connected to the practice of virtuous behaviour.

The participants' stories in this study personify these abstract ideas, going beyond academic aims to illustrate the real moral outcomes they envision. For instance, one parent expressed their hope, stating:

The primary goal of enrolling my children in the Quranic school is for them to become among the finest members of our nation, individuals who strive to do good and dedicate their utmost efforts to embodying and reflecting the teachings of their faith in their daily lives (Salim: parent)

This statement is rich in analysis; it effortlessly connects the national and the religious, the moral and the civic. The desire for their children to become "the finest members of our nation" strongly supports the societal role of these institutions as described by Louglaihi and Haidoune (2023). Additionally, the

focus on "embodying and reflecting the teachings of their faith" extends beyond rote learning to describe the comprehensive development of character, or *Tarbiyah*. This aligns with Hughes's (2000) claim that these institutions shape spiritual and moral growth, but it does so by defining that development in practical terms: active effort towards goodness and the daily practice of one's faith. The parent's vision indicates that the ultimate goal is not merely personal piety but the nurturing of virtuous citizens who enhance the moral fabric of the nation. This focused and community-oriented process of *Tarbiyah*, so central to the participants' experiences, raises a critical question when viewed through the lens of modern developmental theory: how does this specific path of moral and spiritual formation relate to broader, universal models of faith development?

To explore this, we can refer to Fowler's theory, which presents faith as a universal and comprehensive concept, highlighting an open-ended pursuit of meaning that goes beyond specific religious traditions (Weiss, 2021). This perspective creates a creative tension with the approach seen in Quranic schools. The main aim of these institutions is not to support an unrestricted exploration of spiritual ideas but to instil a particular, revelation-based moral framework.

This is not necessarily a limitation but a reflection of a different paradigm. Where Fowler's model envisions faith development as a journey towards universalising personal faith, the Quranic school model focuses on the internalisation of *Din* (a complete way of life). The emphasis on Islamic teachings is therefore not an oversight but the core mission. Consequently, while this focused approach effectively fosters a strong, cohesive religious identity and a clear moral compass—as vividly described by the parents—it may offer fewer structured opportunities for students to engage with the kind of diverse philosophical questions that Fowler highlights. The key question, therefore, is not which model is "correct," but what the desired outcome of education is: a personally constructed, universalising faith (Fowler) or a spiritually rooted, communally oriented moral character (*Tarbiyah*). This tension lies at the heart of understanding the unique role of Quranic schools in faith and moral development.

While Fowler's framework provides valuable insights, its application highlights a fundamental difference in purpose rather than a flaw in Quranic education. The expectation for Quranic schools to "broaden their approach" to adopt a universalising model of faith may distort their core mission. As Gross (2010) argues, faith schools are, by definition, specialised institutions built around specific cornerstones of content, structure, and process related to a religious tradition. Quranic schools clearly belong to this category, representing a distinct form of schooling dedicated to transmitting Islam (Memon, 2013).

Their aim is not to provide a neutral, comparative religious studies curriculum but to offer a profound, formative immersion within a specific worldview. This is characterised by a distinct religious ethos and

a certain degree of autonomy over religious pedagogy (Umar, 2019; Ameen & Hassan, 2013). This does not indicate a failure to be "holistic" but reflects a commitment to a different kind of holism—one that is deeply rooted in the Islamic tradition. For example, while faith schools in the UK might integrate a national curriculum within a religious framework (Paul & Bolton, 2018), the Quranic schools in this study prioritise the fundamental task of nurturing a strong Islamic identity and moral compass from which engagement with the world develops. Therefore, the relevant critique is not that they fail to be something they are not, but rather that they consider how, within their specific purpose of instilling akhlāq and Tarbiyah, they can also cultivate the intellectual flexibility needed to navigate a pluralistic world without compromising their core principles.

The data from this study offers a nuanced understanding of how moral and faith development is perceived and practised. A participant, Amal, regarded Quranic schools as a "second home" essential to this process, where children are immersed in their faith's teachings and values. She explained this by describing her child's development:

My child grasps the importance of treating his family and siblings with good manners... He learns that the Quran will stand as a testimony against him if he does not practice what it contains (Amal, parent).

This quote is central to the theme of moral development because it emphasises a crucial shift from external guidance to internalised responsibility. The child is not just learning rules; he is understanding that his actions have transcendent importance. This internalisation of a moral witness is a powerful way to shape conscience. However, it also introduces a key tension in the development of faith. Amal's perspective, which considers the Quran as a "testimony," relies heavily on the concept of tarheeb (warning). From a developmental standpoint, this raises an important question: is the child's moral behaviour mainly driven by fear of consequences, or is it progressively developing into a sincere understanding and love for the moral principles themselves?

This tension between obligation and internalised virtue is a universal challenge in character education. The Islamic tradition itself advocates for a balance, emphasising both tarheeb (warning) and targhib (encouragement), as exemplified by the Quranic verse stating, "despair not of the Mercy of Allah" (Quran, 39:53). This principle of moderation is a fundamental Islamic ideal, as God declares, "And thus we have made you a middle nation (ummattan wasatan) so that you may be witnesses over mankind and the Messenger a witness over you" (Quran, 2:143). The term wasatan here signifies justice, balance, and the avoidance of extremes. Therefore, the data from Amal not only describe an outcome of moral development; they reveal the complex process itself, highlighting a practical pedagogical challenge that reflects this core Quranic mandate for balance. It indicates that the pedagogical approach within Quranic

schools is a crucial factor in determining whether a student's faith matures into a resilient, internally-owned moral compass (akhlaq) or remains a more fragile, externally-regulated compliance. This balance is not merely a theological ideal but a practical necessity for fostering holistic moral and faith development.

Amal's testimony powerfully illustrates the profound trust parents place in Quranic schools, viewing them not merely as supplements but as core partners in raising children. Her assertion that "Quranic education carries 75% of the burden and responsibility of raising children" and her belief that "if you teach your children the Quran, the Quran will teach them everything" emphasise a perception of these institutions as the primary engine for moral and spiritual development. This perspective highlights a form of delegated Tarbiyah, where the school assumes the central role in instilling the foundational akhlāq that parents desire.

While this highlights the high value placed on Quranic schooling, the analysis reveals a possible tension. This belief rightly respects the Quran's comprehensive spiritual guidance. However, within a modern educational framework, interpreting this principle to mean that Quranic schools alone can 'teach everything' might result in an over-reliance on them for a child's entire development, potentially neglecting the importance of other knowledge areas and parental guidance in navigating contemporary life. This aligns with the earlier discussion of Fowler's stages, where a faith that does not actively engage with different kinds of knowledge may struggle to develop into a reflective, individuated belief system. Therefore, the issue highlighted by Amal's strong reliance is not about minimising the role of Quranic schools, but about incorporating their spiritual and moral instruction into a broader, collaborative framework of upbringing. A balanced approach, where Quranic education provides the ethical foundation that is enriched by secular learning and proactive parenting, is crucial for developing individuals who are both spiritually rooted and capable of thriving in a diverse world.

This reliance on the institution for moral formation is further nuanced by the role of religious authority. Another participant, Boubakr, defined the purpose of Quranic education as "to fulfil what Lord and Prophet have advised, which includes guidance on learning the Qur'an, nurturing a love for it, and fostering a love for the people of the Quran." This emphasis shifts the focus from merely transmitting knowledge to cultivating affective bonds—love for the text and its scholars—as a primary mechanism for faith and moral development.

While this approach effectively uses emotion and respect to instil values, it also creates a fundamental reliance on the character and interpretations of religious authorities. The quality of moral guidance depends on the scholars who are the objects of this "love." In environments with inconsistent scholarly oversight, this dependence introduces a significant vulnerability where dogmatic or biased

interpretations could unintentionally distort the ethical framework the schools aim to promote. Therefore, the very mechanism that makes these schools effective — veneration of religious authority — also presents their greatest potential risk, as it tightly couples the success of their moral mission to the integrity of the surrounding religious ecosystem.

The potential vulnerabilities of unregulated religious authority highlight the crucial role of the Algerian government. Through proactive regulation and oversight, the state seeks to ensure that Quranic schools conform to the country's moderate religious principles (Turkel and Cooper, 2022). This supervision, which includes vetting curricula and scholars' qualifications, serves as a structural safeguard. Its aim is to channel the "love for the people of the Quran" celebrated by parents like Boubakr within a framework that fosters national unity and social cohesion, thereby reducing the risk of extremist or divisive interpretations.

In this controlled context, Boubakr's view — that Quranic education should "nurture a love for the Quran and its people" — takes on a specific, state-approved character. His perspective reflects a broad journey of faith that goes beyond merely studying texts to fostering deep respect and admiration for scholars. This idea reinforces the communal aspect of faith, framing it as a bond among believers rather than a solely individual pursuit. However, within Algeria's moderated environment, this "love for the people of the Quran" is fundamentally shaped by the state's supervision. The scholars to be admired are those who conform to the official, moderate ethos. Thus, Boubakr's ideal of a faith community remains intact. Yet, its limits and expressions are intentionally managed by the state to ensure they support a cohesive national identity, illustrating the complex relationship between spiritual growth and political governance in shaping moral citizens.

Parent Maryam further emphasises the transformative role of Quranic education, asserting that it provides a "Quranic upbringing" that instils an ethical foundation. She explicitly links this to a sense of parental relief, stating:

After a child receives education in a Quranic school, the parents can find some relief in dealing with their child because the child would have received a religious upbringing... The public schools can continue this upbringing (Maryam: parent)

This quote powerfully demonstrates the schools' perceived role as a key formative influence. However, it also exposes a crucial tension at the heart of this chapter. Maryam's framing presents Quranic schooling as the primary source of moral guidance, with secular education simply building upon its foundation. This view risks creating a binary where religious teaching is seen as a complete moral solution, potentially encouraging a passive attitude from parents and teachers. The confidence in a

"Quranic upbringing" may neglect the active effort needed to help children critically and adaptively apply a moral framework in a modern, diverse society. As a result, while the schools effectively serve as an essential ethical compass, the reassurance they provide—explicitly expressed by Maryam—could unintentionally hinder the development of a more flexible and internally reasoned faith.

Samia's insights on generational changes deepen this complexity. She compares a time when religious practice was self-driven with now, when distractions are abundant, stating: "In the past... we prayed all the time out of our own will. In contrast, in the current times... prayer might not hold the same priority. Therefore, I believe parents need to rely on more powerful influences..."

This perspective is essential as it redefines the role of Quranic schools. They are no longer simply institutions for passing down tradition but have become vital sites of "counter-socialization," actively protecting religious identity against competing secular influences. Samia's argument that parents need "more powerful influences" directly supports the increased reliance on Quranic education described by other parents.

However, this reactive stance raises an important question about the type of faith being encouraged. Does this defensive approach, centred on fostering obedience, emphasise resilient, internalised belief, or does it risk creating a fragile identity mainly defined by opposition to external forces? This aligns with Ebrahimi's (2017) call to place the Quran at the centre of addressing societal issues. Nonetheless, Samia's narrative suggests that for modern parents, this is not just a spiritual duty but also a strategic move, a way to strengthen their children's moral compass in a complex world. The real challenge, therefore, is to ensure that this necessary strengthening also cultivates internal reasoning and adaptable understanding essential for a mature, sustainable faith.

Parent Jawad highlights a strong dedication to Quranic education, stating that "despite the demanding mainstream school programmes, parents remain committed... believing that Quranic education enhances their children's memory, knowledge, and manners." This practical commitment is rooted in a developmental view of faith. Jawad explains that although "children grow up inheriting certain beliefs from their parents," a significant change occurs when they reach an "age of understanding and discernment... they possess a strong belief based on awareness."

This perspective accurately reflects John Westerhoff's (1980) faith development model. The initial "inheritance" of beliefs aligns with the Affiliative Faith stage, where identity is formed through family and community. The transition to an "age of understanding" marks the beginning of the Searching Faith stage, characterised by critical reflection. This analysis highlights the role of the Quranic school beyond merely transmitting inherited tradition, viewing it as a vital guide that enables the shift from passive

acceptance to reflective, internalised belief. Its ultimate success, therefore, depends not only on teaching the Quran but also on fostering the discernment and personal awareness that Jawad describes.

Ultimately, Jawad's insights anticipate Westerhoff's "Mature Faith" stage, where individuals combine inherited tradition with personal understanding. This emphasises the key long-term goal of Quranic education: to guide students beyond simple affiliative belief towards a reflective faith capable of withstanding modern complexities. His perspective highlights that faith development is a dialogical relationship between the community's tradition and the individual's discernment. Therefore, the success of these institutions depends on their ability to respect this journey, ensuring that the inherited foundation becomes a source of lasting, personal conviction rather than a fragile set of imposed rules.

Another parent, Fatima, expressed a purpose for Quranic schooling that is both theological and sociological, citing the Quranic command, "And I did not create the jinn and mankind except to worship Me." She described this as fostering the "faith of the general public," a core identity gained from family and community.

This perspective is vital for understanding the institutional function of Quranic schools in Algeria. They act as the official means that formalise and organise this process of intergenerational transmission, moving it from the informal setting of the home into a structured educational environment. Fatima's view, which is consistent with Smith and Adameczyk's (2021) findings on religious socialisation, suggests that the school's aim is not to introduce a new faith but to reinforce and give organised form to the beliefs children inherit. This "faith of the general public" is not seen as a lesser form of belief but as the essential, unifying foundation of Algerian Muslim identity.

Therefore, from the participants' viewpoint, a core purpose of the Quranic school is to act as a guardian of societal norms. It ensures that the primary purpose of human life, worship, is not overshadowed by other educational or social pressures. In doing so, the school plays a crucial role for parents: it shares the responsibility of helping their children internalise the fundamental creed that defines their community's purpose and identity.

Another parent, Boubakr, highlighted an important aspect of faith development, stating: "Children may become curious and ask questions like, 'Why do we pray?' or 'Where is God?' Parents may not always have answers, and they might suggest asking their teacher. In our region, there is often a preference for tradition over independent thinking, and religious scholars hold significant influence."

This statement reveals a significant pedagogical shift of authority from the home to the religious institution. When parents pass complex theological questions to the Quranic school teacher, they are

not simply seeking answers; they are reinforcing the scholar as the ultimate authority on religious truth. This practice, as noted in Kurttekin's (2024) research on religious communication, is widespread. However, Boubakr's remark about a regional "preference for tradition over independent thinking" offers important context.

This dynamic directly connects to the faith development theories of Westerhoff (Searching Faith) and Fowler (Synthetic-Conventional Faith). The children's questions reflect their natural progression into these stages, where they seek to build personal understanding. The institutional response, guiding these questions to a single, authoritative source, emphasises maintaining a unified, tradition-based identity. This ties in with the core purpose of these schools as guardians of a specific creed. However, it also creates a key tension: does this approach satisfy the child's curiosity by providing a clear answer, or might it restrict the deeper, personal "searching" process by replacing the child's critical reflection with the scholar's interpretation? The answer to this question is vital for understanding whether these schools ultimately nurture a more affiliative or more individuated form of faith.

This creates a vital tension with the Quran's own pedagogical model, which explicitly rejects passive reception (Quran, 17:41) and urges active meditation on its signs (Quran, 38:29). Consequently, the main pedagogical challenge is to align the schools' methods with this scriptural directive, shifting their aim from merely transmitting tradition to fostering the critical dialogue between inherited faith and intellectual pursuit that the Quran itself advocates.

Parent Zakaria directly connected Quranic education to familial and social prestige, stating:

The family reaps numerous benefits from this choice. First, the family gains a child of high moral character, virtue, and respect in their community. Second, when people say, 'Your child is better than you,' it brings pride and happiness (Zakaria: parent).

This perspective highlights an important social element of moral development, where personal virtue enhances family honour and community standing. This aligns with the high regard Islam assigns to religious knowledge, as the hadith states: "The scholars are the inheritors of the Prophets... Whoever has taken hold of it has been given an abundant share" (Sunan Abī Dāwūd 3641). It creates a strong feedback loop: pursuing religious knowledge is spiritually admirable, and mastering it provides significant social capital.

However, Zakaria's emphasis on pride and public recognition raises an important issue: when educational achievement is so visibly linked to social validation, does the motivation for enrolment risk shifting from intrinsic spiritual growth to external reward? This dynamic highlights the complex

relationship between faith development and social identity, demonstrating that one of the primary aims of the Quranic school is not only to foster morality but also to provide a respected social status for its students and their families.

Educators like Abdel Kareem and Zayyan provide essential insights into the pedagogical processes behind moral and faith development. Abdel Kareem explained that at the Quranic school, “The child... learns that the Quran is the word of God ... learning about the pillars of Islam and the pillars of faith strengthens and shapes their beliefs.”

Strategically, both teachers demonstrated this formative influence by citing the same compelling example: the top-performing student of 2023 in the nation, a Quran memoriser. This approach is analytically significant; it transforms an anecdote into a shared evidence of institutional success. The story directly links the discipline and moral values of Quranic education (*dini*) with outstanding academic achievement (*dunyawi*), portraying them as mutually reinforcing. This perspective is supported by research connecting Quran memorisation to cognitive and academic outcomes (Tarmuji et al., 2022; Nawaz & Jahangir, 2015) and ethical development (*Akhlaq*) to self-regulation (Shukor et al., 2013).

Hence, the educators collectively use this example to depict the Quranic school as a distinctive institution that simultaneously nurtures faith, moral character, and the disciplined intellect required for worldly success, effectively justifying its vital role in promoting holistic development.

This vision of holistic excellence is deeply connected to a wider societal purpose. Zayyan broadens the argument by defining the ultimate goal of this education: to nurture a “Quranic generation.” He highlights a transformative aim for Quranic schools, emphasising their role in creating a righteous society by filling it with “the people of God,” who “excel in understanding the Quran... [and] will not resort to cheating in any aspect of their lives... They will have a religious conscience that fears God.”

This is more than just an educational goal; it is a movement for societal change. The concept of a “Quranic doctor” or “Quranic engineer” represents the complete integration of religious morality with professional identity. Zayyan’s argument indicates that a profound understanding of the Quran provides a universal moral and cognitive toolkit—a “religious conscience”—that ensures ethical behaviour in all pursuits. This directly supports the earlier example of the academic high-achiever, viewing that success not as an anomaly, but as a natural outcome of this formative process. Ultimately, his perspective asserts that individual virtue, cultivated by Quranic schools, is the essential foundation for a virtuous community.

This vision of a "Quranic generation" resonates in international contexts, such as the Indonesian Tahfiz Houses studied by Hartono (2024), which similarly seek to foster deep engagement with the Quran. However, the Algerian example, as described by Zayyan, displays a pedagogical depth that goes beyond mere recitation and memorisation.

Zayyan elaborated on the approach behind this mission, stating: "As educators, when a student memorises a portion, we provide explanations for certain vocabulary and the reasons behind the revelation of verses. For instance, there are many remarkable stories, like the story of Cain and Abel... This story carries valuable moral lessons, such as the importance of accountability..."

This insight is essential. It demonstrates that moral development is not just a fortunate byproduct but is intentionally shaped through a pedagogical approach involving narrative and context. By explaining the "reasons for revelation" (*asbab al-nuzul*), teachers connect abstract texts to real-world ethical issues. The story of Cain and Abel is not merely a historical account but a moral case study on accountability and behaviour.

Therefore, the school's aim is fulfilled not merely by producing memorizers, but by developing interpreters who can identify and apply ethical principles from the text. This supports the broader goal of a "Quranic generation" by ensuring the Quran becomes a living guide for moral reasoning, not just a memorised object.

Zayyan's pedagogical method—using contextual explanations like the story of Cain and Abel to teach moral lessons—is strongly supported by scholarly research. His approach agrees with Amin's (2018) statement that the Quran acts as a comprehensive guide for holistic personality development, covering biological, psychological, social, and spiritual aspects to promote ethical behaviour. This is further confirmed by Khodijah (2022), who argues that character in the Quran comes from internalising religious values, resulting in positive attitudes and behaviour.

From a developmental perspective, the pedagogies of teachers like Zayyan and Ali actively involve students in what Fowler describes as the Mythic-Literal stage, where religious narratives are interpreted literally to develop moral understanding. Their practices are therefore not merely instructional but act as targeted interventions that align Islamic ethical theory with faith development psychology to systematically shape a student's conscience.

This is illustrated by Teacher Ali's direct engagement with Quranic narratives. He describes his approach using the story of Aisha:

The story of Aisha... This emphasizes the importance of having evidence... We explain to students the background and context... teaching them not to make baseless accusations... they learn from it and refrain from hastily accusing others, preserving people's dignity (Ali: teacher)

His analogy of the child's mind as a "blank page" positions the Quranic school as a corrective institution, actively inscribing moral principles. This practice is deeply rooted in the tradition of Islamic ethics, which offers a comprehensive framework for human conduct, as noted by scholars like Hashi (2011) and Ebrahimi (2017). Therefore, Ali's teaching is a conscious process of moral formation aligned with the historical mission, outlined by May (2020), to uplift society through Quranic values.

In conclusion, this section's analysis confirms that developing moral character and faith is a key goal of Quranic schools in Algeria, as recognised by both parents and educators. The data emphasises a collaborative process of Tarbiyah (nurturing), where the school works alongside families to systematically instil the ethical principles of Akhlāq. This is achieved through a pedagogy that goes beyond rote memorisation, utilising contextualised Quranic stories to offer children a moral guide for everyday life. While this approach effectively fosters a strong, affiliative faith and a unified identity, our examination has also critically considered the tensions involved—such as balancing authoritative tradition with independent critical thinking, and the risk of a "hermeneutic dependency" that could hinder the shift towards a more individualised, reflective faith. Ultimately, these institutions aim to cultivate a "Quranic generation," where spiritual grounding is seen not as separate from, but as the essential foundation for, personal integrity, academic diligence, and social responsibility.

6.4. Quranic Schools and the Shaping of Children's Behaviour

The data indicates that, from parents' perspectives, a main goal of Quranic schools is to bring about a noticeable change in their children's everyday behaviour. This starts with a deliberate teaching method that transforms sacred texts into practical behavioural standards. One parent emphasised this approach, explaining that in her children's school,

The Quran teachers are keen on teaching children their religion by using the stories mentioned in the Quran... For example, one of the surahs they often explain and interpret is Surah An-Nur, as it contains many manners and behaviors that should be followed, such as not entering houses without permission and proper etiquette, the manners of dress and hijab, the warning against slander and false accusations...(Maryam: parent)

This account is important analytically because it uncovers how behaviour is shaped. The focus on Surah An-Nur highlights a curriculum aimed at practical socialisation, transitioning from abstract religious

principles to direct guidance on modesty, privacy, and speech. The school's aim is thus to offer a divine blueprint for everyday life, where religious learning is naturally connected to practising virtuous behaviour.

Parents consistently reported that immersion in this structured, value-based environment directly fosters significant behavioural changes. Parent Samia shared a compelling anecdote about her daughter's class to illustrate this transformative role, stating:

... In my daughter's Quranic school class, their teacher says that many girls joined the Quranic school when their parents were somewhat desperate about them. However, it is worth noting that Allah can change a person's heart in the blink of an eye. Many of these girls who were somewhat astray when they started the Quranic education later successfully completed memorising the entire Quran. The beginnings were different, but the environment and surroundings had a significant impact on their thinking since their friends influenced them. If your friend is righteous, they will undoubtedly encourage you towards righteousness, and vice versa (Samia: parent).

Samia's account is vital as it explains how behaviour is shaped. She highlights three key elements: the redemptive potential of the religious environment, the positive influence of righteous peers, and the guiding role of the teacher who supports change. This perspective aligns with Kamaruddin and Patak's (2018) findings on the role of Islamic educators in fostering discipline, but it grounds this idea in real-life experience. The Quranic school is depicted not as a passive place but as an active intervention—a carefully designed social and spiritual space aimed at behaviour reform. The parents' initial "desperation" emphasises their belief that these schools offer a long-term solution for moral and behavioural guidance, which they see as lacking in the secular system. Their ultimate measure of success is the striking outcome: a child who was "somewhat astray" becoming a haafidh (Quran memoriser).

This concept of the school as a carefully managed ecosystem is further illustrated by Parent Boubakr, who shared a detailed account of the ongoing behavioural improvements he observes in his own children. His testimony progresses from general improvements to specific, tangible changes in their demeanour and moral reasoning.

The continuous interaction of my children with their teachers and peers at the Quranic school has had a profound impact on their behavior. They have become more polite, disciplined, and eager to learn... Furthermore, my wife and I have clearly noticed that they have become calmer and more composed than before. They can now clearly distinguish between good and bad behavior, which has positively reflected in their daily conduct (Boubakr: parent)

Boubakr’s observations are significant because they trace the causal pathway from the school's social environment—‘continuous interaction’—to the internalisation of a moral compass, “distinguish between good and bad”. While Samia described a dramatic transformation of wayward girls, Boubakr details the consistent development of discipline and composure in his own children. This demonstrates that the school's purpose is twofold: it functions as a corrective institution for behavioural issues and as a preventative one for ongoing character development. The outcomes he values—heightened politeness, calmness, and self-discipline—are precisely the behavioural traits that parents feel are insufficiently addressed in other educational settings, reinforcing the Quranic school's role as an essential agent of socialisation.

Ultimately, parents like Fatima see this formative process not just as a practical benefit, but as a profound moral and spiritual duty. She powerfully expresses the main purpose of these institutions, stating:

Good conduct and strong faith that guide children toward all that is good for them are the greatest gifts parents can offer and pass down to their children. And the best place for children to learn their religion — after the home, of course — is the Qur’anic school, which refines the soul and enlightens the heart with the light of the Qur’an (Fatima: parent).

Fatima’s perspective shifts the discussion from observable behavioural outcomes to the underlying philosophy of upbringing that shapes parental choices. Her description of the school as an institution that “refines the soul and enlightens the heart” presents it as an essential, irreplaceable partner to the family in the sacred task of raising a moral child. This encapsulates the chapter's main argument: that parents see Quranic schools as vital because they uniquely achieve the dual aims of instilling clear behavioural standards and providing the spiritual "light" that guides a child's entire life.

This collaborative relationship between the school's environment and its stakeholders is a common theme in the parents' stories. They consistently emphasised the vital role of both teachers and peers in positively shaping their children's behaviour. This is not a passive process but an active, collective effort where the entire Quranic system works together to encourage discipline and behavioural change.

Teacher Zayyan’s perspective provides a crucial insight into parental observations, illustrating the school's mission with a powerful analogy.

The child is like a blank page... If society writes something incorrectly, the teacher must erase those words and replace them with accurate ones... Many students have improved their behaviour thanks to their engagement with Quranic education.

Zayyan's "blank page" analogy fundamentally depicts the Quranic school as a corrective institution. This method of active moral correction—erasing societal "errors" and inscribing "accurate" Quranic teachings—serves as the pedagogical basis for the specific behavioural changes parents mention: children becoming "more polite, disciplined, and eager to learn" (Boubakr) or being guided from "astray" to righteousness (Samia).

This conceptualisation is strongly supported by widespread agreement in educational research. The interventionist aim aligns with core principles of character education (Berkowitz & Bier, 2005), while cross-religious studies confirm the formative influence of religious education in developing moral potential (Pasaribu, 2023). Additional support comes from scholarship advocating for the integration of spiritual development into psychology (Peter et al., 2003) and research on faith-based learning strategies that use guidance to instil core beliefs (Kamaruddin et al., 2022). Importantly, the literature emphasises the central role of environmental factors highlighted by parents, showing that morality is shaped by environmental influences (Putra et al., 2020), religious practices (Rahmat et al., 2023; Wiguna, 2020), and collaborative ecosystems combining efforts from both schools and families (Andhika, 2021; Mulyana et al., 2023).

This collaborative obligation is strongly emphasised by religious authorities, who see enrolment in Quranic schools not just as an educational choice but as a religious duty. One administrator highlighted this responsibility, stating:

Parents have a responsibility to protect their children from moral deviation, and Qur'anic schools provide an excellent opportunity for parents to do so... As the Prophet (peace be upon him) said, 'There are two blessings which many people squander: health and free time.' Therefore, this precious time during the summer... should be wisely used for Qur'anic education to nurture children, teach them their religion, and consequently improve their behavior (Waleed: administrator)

Waleed's statement offers an important theological and practical conclusion to the argument. By citing a canonical hadith, he raises the use of "free time" for Quranic education from a simple preference to a proactive religious duty to safeguard a child's morality. This directly addresses the concerns of parents like Samia about negative societal influences and presents the Quranic school as the endorsed solution. The seasonal framework ("summer vacation") highlights how these institutions are woven into the very

fabric of family life and time management, serving as a vital, periodic reinforcement of the moral and behavioural standards established at home.

Thus, the convergence of parental testimony, pedagogical philosophy, scholarly research, and religious authority forms a coherent and convincing model. The behavioural changes observed by parents are the documented results of a deliberate, theologically-based socialising process. This multifaceted evidence strongly affirms that the Quranic school fulfils its primary purpose: the authoritative, systematic, and spiritually-supported shaping of a child's behaviour.

In conclusion, evidence from parents, educators, and scholarly research comes together to define a clear, powerful purpose for Quranic schools: they are intentionally created as comprehensive socialising systems for behavioural reform and moral internalisation. Through a pedagogy that transforms sacred texts into a practical "divine blueprint" for daily conduct, these institutions go beyond simply teaching to actively shape a child's character. The reported transformations—from waywardness to righteousness, from impulsiveness to disciplined composure—are not accidental but are the documented results of a carefully curated environment of righteous peers, interventionist teachers, and a theologically grounded curriculum. Ultimately, parents entrust Quranic schools with this sacred duty because they see them as uniquely capable of fulfilling a role that other educational spheres neglect: the systematic development of a child's behaviour within a spiritual framework, thereby safeguarding both individual morality and the community's religious fabric.

6.5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has demonstrated that the purpose of Quranic schools in Algeria, as defined by the parents and educators who serve as their primary stakeholders, is both comprehensive and vital. The analysis reveals that these institutions are seen as essential agents of holistic development, with a threefold mission: to forge and safeguard a distinct Algerian-Islamic identity against secular and globalising influences (6.2), to systematically cultivate moral character and faith through the framework of Akhlāq and Tarbiyah (6.3), and to actively shape everyday behaviour by translating Quranic principles into a practical guide for conduct (6.4). Although the pedagogical approaches supporting this mission are not without tension—particularly concerning the balance between tradition and critical thinking—the consistent and passionate testimonies of participants emphasise a shared belief in their unique effectiveness. Ultimately, Quranic schools are not regarded as a mere supplement to state education but as its necessary complement, fulfilling a fundamental role that parents consider essential: the integrated spiritual, ethical, and behavioural development of their children into what they envisage as a righteous "Quranic generation."

Chapter 7

Cultural and Religious Socialisation of Children through Quranic Schools

7.1. Introduction

In this chapter, the study participants' views reveal how Quranic schools help shape children's cultural and religious socialisation through various processes. From their perspective, Quranic schools do more than just teach religious content; they are places where young students experience and adopt a way of life that reflects both Islamic teachings and cultural traditions. Children in Quranic schools have the opportunity not only to learn their faith but also to practise their beliefs within these institutions. Through daily activities such as Quranic recitation, prayers, and learning Islamic etiquette, students receive an education that combines Islamic values with cultural traditions. This means they are not only instructed but also actively integrated into the wider norms and values of their community. This socialisation process, as defined by Grusec and Davidov (2007), involves the “acceptance of society’s values, norms, and customs as well as the ability to function adaptively within a larger social context” (p. 284).

Participants’ insights reveal how these schools foster a sense of belonging and continuity, helping students understand and value their heritage while preparing them to navigate the wider world confidently in their faith and identity. To contextualise these perspectives, the discussion includes existing research on religious and cultural socialisation, exploring how Quranic schools contribute to the broader developmental and social aspects of young individuals in Algeria. For instance, the study “Socio-Cultural Perception of the Role of Quranic Schools Within Socialisation Discourses” by Oussama and Ziane (2023) demonstrates how Quranic schools in Algeria have historically shaped moral values, reinforced cultural continuity, and fostered a collective national identity. Their findings coincide with the insights from this study’s participants, showing that Quranic schools not only teach religious content but also serve as spaces for identity formation and community integration. Through this analysis, we recognise the role of these institutions in guiding students to live out their faith and values in meaningful ways, ultimately forming the foundation of their moral compass and cultural identity.

7.2. Curriculum and Knowledge Transmission in Quranic Schools

In Quranic schools, curriculum design plays a vital role in students' religious and cultural socialisation. Through subjects like Quran memorisation, Islamic jurisprudence, and the Arabic language—students not only gain religious knowledge but also grasp the cultural and linguistic frameworks that shape Islamic identity. This well-structured curriculum acts as a means of instilling core values, beliefs, and behaviours that align with the broader goals of Islamic education. Participants in this study provided insights into the specific content and teaching methods used within Quranic schools, demonstrating how these elements contribute to children's religious development. Existing literature further supports their perspectives, emphasising how the content and transfer of knowledge influence students' moral and cultural identities.

Many parents in this study express that in Quranic schools, strategies and methods largely depend on the individual teacher's approach. One of them said,

The strategy and methods depend almost entirely on the teacher's choices...teachers use the same strategies they learned when they were students (Samia, Parent).

This parent's observation about the reliance on individual teachers' strategies in Quranic schools highlights significant pedagogical challenges. Personal teaching methods reveal a lack of standardised training, leading to inconsistencies in teaching quality. This dependence can limit the depth of the curriculum, as teachers might overlook modern pedagogical practices that effectively engage students. Additionally, the absence of a coherent framework can result in varying interpretations of Islamic teachings, causing confusion about students' religious identity. To improve the educational experience, encouraging teacher collaboration and professional development is essential.

Similarly, Amal's experience highlights that parents' concerns go beyond the consistency of teaching methods; they also emphasise the importance of the depth and quality of Quranic instruction, particularly in foundational areas like Tajweed, which are the rules of Quranic recitation. Amal expressed how vital effective teaching is in these areas, reflecting a broader view among participants who want a comprehensive Quranic education for their children, not just memorisation. This desire ultimately led Amal to move her children to a different school that offers a more balanced curriculum, demonstrating how crucial teaching quality and content are to parents within Algeria's Quranic school system. Effective teaching in Tajweed is essential, as it ensures that students learn to read and recite the Quran accurately and clearly, in accordance with the command in the Quran (73:4): "... and recite the Quran in slow, measured rhythmic tones." This verse highlights the importance of precision and clarity in Quranic recitation, aiming to prevent any ambiguity in conveying the sacred text. As Nasallah (2015) states, this structured method for reciting the Quran enables students to engage with the Quran in a way

that surpasses mere memorisation, allowing a deeper interaction with its teachings and reinforcing the Quran's role as a timeless guide and a bridge between the Divine and human experience.

Teacher Khaled describes the main activities of Quranic schools, which focus on Quran memorisation and religious education, especially on religious rules and jurisprudence. He states that students spend their summer holidays memorising sections (Hizbs) of the Quran. When regular classes resume, they review and reinforce the sections they memorised during the summer. This structured process helps students avoid forgetting the Quran. He said that "Quran memorisation is easy, but forgetting it is equally easy" (Khaled, Teacher). Khaled emphasises the importance of consolidating knowledge before moving on to more of the Quran. According to Khaled, a student can memorise the entire Quran in four years using this approach. Various studies have examined the strategies and methods used to memorise the Qur'an. A literature review identified eight internal and external learning strategies that support effective memorisation of the Qur'an (Shukri et al., 2020).

Additionally, the research examined the role of technology and how memorizers use apps and digital tools to strengthen their connection to scripture (Haryono et al., 2023). Methods for primary school students have also been investigated, emphasising the importance of early Quranic instruction (Ismail et al., 2024). Furthermore, studies into student motivation in memorising the Quran highlight how vital motivation is in this process (Abdullah et al., 2021). Khaled also observed that after memorising the Quran, some students begin studying jurisprudence texts such as "Risala Ibn Ashir," "Al-Masalik," and "Al-Akhdari," among others. Their aim is to master these texts, and some may attend boarding schools like Zawiyas to learn from experienced sheikhs and scholars, eventually becoming scholars or jurists. Alternatively, students can enrol in Islamic institutes nationwide to graduate as Imams of mosques and preachers.

One of the administrators, in the same vein, states,

Its primary mission is to teach Quran memorisation to students and to study texts in Islamic jurisprudence and the Arabic language, such as those by Ibn Ashur and Al-Ajrumiyyah (Waleed, Administrator).

Khaled and Waleed's statement underscores the primary mission of Quranic schools to concentrate on Quran memorisation and the study of specific Islamic and Arabic texts. This shared view among participants in this study indicates a curriculum often seen as limited in scope. The focus on memorisation and core texts may neglect wider aspects of cultural and literary education, potentially restricting students' engagement with a broader range of knowledge and critical thinking skills. The

Quran is central to Islam and remains the main source of Islamic knowledge, from which many fields of religious study have evolved since the seventh century (Sai, 2017). Recognising this key role, educators can broaden the Quranic school curriculum to include other facets of the Quran to support a more holistic approach to learning that nurtures students' moral and cultural identities and enhances their appreciation of this foundational text, such as its literary aspects. This idea aligns with discussions in "The Quran and Modern Arabic Literary Criticism: From Taha to Nasr" by Salama (2018), which explores how the Quran's literary qualities have historically been undervalued in modern Arabic literary critique. The work emphasises the need for a more nuanced understanding of the Quran as both a religious text and a literary masterpiece that can inform and enrich contemporary literary theory.

Supporting this, a study by Baba et al. (2018) on Quranic schools in Northwest Nigeria also reveals similar efforts to incorporate public education content into the primarily minimalist curriculum that concentrates on Quranic recitation and memorisation. This study highlights these institutions' challenges and opportunities, reflecting a broader educational landscape where the curriculum must adapt to meet both religious and secular educational standards. This integration is particularly significant in areas where children have limited access to education and can only attend Quranic schools.

Alongside the previous discussion on expanding the Quranic school curriculum to go beyond mere memorisation and help deepen students' connections with the Quran, it is also vital to consider the integration of scientific knowledge. The Quran contains scientific facts that align with modern discoveries, as shown in studies like *Scientific Facts in the Quran* by Dadach, (2015). For example, the Quran (21:33) describes the movement of celestial bodies in their orbits—an idea that the revelation introduced and that modern science has verified. Including such insights in the Quranic school curriculum, along with their contextual understanding, boosts students' intellectual engagement and helps them see the Quran as a living, relevant source of knowledge. This encourages a holistic education that fosters critical thinking, reflection, and a deeper connection with the sacred text, rather than focusing solely on memorisation.

Parents expressed different opinions about the tools used in teaching children at Quranic schools. They stressed how teaching materials influence children's connection to Quranic studies and impact their engagement, satisfaction, and motivation to learn the Quran. One parent pointed out the difficulties of modern magnetic boards, noting that,

Children often get frustrated when the writing on the magnetic board quickly disappears as soon as it's put back in its holder, as well as with the constant need for new pens (Samia, Parent).

Another parent expressed a similar opinion, stating her preference for traditional wooden boards.

Wooden boards bring children a unique sense of pleasure and engagement. These tools foster a deeper, more meaningful connection with the learning process (Amal, parent).

Conversely, a parent suggested updating teaching materials to align with modern educational practices and noted,

Quranic schools must embrace modern technology to make learning more enjoyable and engaging for children (Mubarakah, parent).

For her, using familiar, modern tools can make Quranic education more relevant and accessible, thereby strengthening children's connection with religious knowledge in today's context. The participants' opinions on teaching tools highlight the ongoing debate between traditional and contemporary methods in Quranic education, emphasising the tension between maintaining historical continuity and adapting to current learning environments. While some parents argue that traditional materials foster deeper engagement and a more meaningful connection to Quranic learning, others believe that incorporating modern tools is crucial to keep children motivated and engaged in today's digital age.

One important insight from Zayyan's interview concerns the various teaching tools and techniques used at his school. These educational methods include both traditional wooden boards and modern resources, catering to students' individual preferences and needs. Additionally, the inclusion of personal Quranic study records is a unique aspect of their teaching approach. He said,

When students memorize the Quran, they maintain a record, effectively transforming it into a legacy for their children and grandchildren (Zayyan, teacher)

He further stated,

In addition to Quran memorisation, we provide free academic courses with a structured curriculum and regular assessments. Lessons are delivered using data projectors, and I explain the lessons gradually... We start with the fundamentals, then gradually cover topics like Noon Sakinah and Tajweed to ensure students gain a comprehensive understanding of recitation principles (Zayyan, teacher).

This approach demonstrates a commitment to providing accessible Quranic education, emphasises modern pedagogical techniques, and guarantees a solid foundational understanding before advancing to more complex concepts. However, most participants reported that their schools still use traditional wooden boards for writing because they believe this method effectively reinforces memorised verses. Some see this learning tool as a heritage that must be preserved to teach the current generation in the same way as previous generations did.

The differing perspectives between Zayyan and the other participants highlight potential regional variations in resource availability and teaching styles. In the north, where Zayyan mentions the use of modern resources alongside traditional methods, there may be greater government or community backing, enabling the use of diverse educational tools and a hybrid approach. This also emphasises a focus on creating personal study records, adding a legacy aspect to Quranic learning. In the south, however, reliance on traditional wooden boards suggests either limited access to newer resources or a strong cultural dedication to heritage. Participants in the south emphasise continuity, viewing these traditional tools as both effective for memorisation and valuable as a link to past generations.

These differences in teaching tools and methodologies may reflect varying levels of investment and priorities in educational infrastructure across regions, which, in turn, influence the way Quranic education is approached. This relates to the broader debate among Islamic scholars regarding the need to modernise Islamic education methodologies. Since the late 1970s, Islamic academics have discussed how to adapt teaching approaches to the demands of globalisation and modernity, proposing various strategies to maintain the relevance of Islamic studies while preserving traditional educational practices (Ismail et al, 2021). Similarly, in his comprehensive work, Tiliouine (2014) examines the transformation from traditional Quranic schooling to post-colonial educational systems. The synthesis emphasises the need for a balanced approach that respects tradition whilst embracing modernity. The integration of modern tools and approaches, as seen in Zayyan's region, could be one such response aiming to balance tradition with contemporary educational needs.

The "Modern Daara" curriculum in Senegal's Quranic schools (known as Daaras) represents a significant effort to bridge the gap between religious and formal education. This initiative introduces subjects like French and mathematics alongside Quranic studies to improve literacy among children aged 7 to 12. It reflects a broader movement to modernise Daaras in their content while maintaining their cultural and religious values (Drame, 2021).

In Chad, renovated Quranic schools offer new opportunities for pupils from traditional backgrounds. They provide a structured bilingual curriculum aligned with the official education framework. Unlike

traditional Quranic schools, which focus solely on Quranic studies, these modern schools teach children a range of skills in science, maths, reading, and writing. This change signifies a significant move towards holistic education and promotes a more inclusive learning environment for students (UNICEF, 2022). The various approaches to Quranic schools worldwide, such as the integration of modern subjects in Senegal's "Modern Daara" curriculum and the bilingual curriculum in Chad, demonstrate ongoing efforts to adapt traditional Islamic schooling to contemporary educational needs.

Teacher Zayyan emphasised the importance of fostering well-rounded growth in students, highlighting that Quranic education should nurture not only academic achievement but also social and emotional development by stating,

We aim for comprehensive growth, encompassing academic, social, and emotional development. This holistic approach, combined with modern teaching methods, reflects the Quranic schools' commitment to nurturing well-rounded individuals who excel in Quranic studies and also acquire essential life skills. The school offers instruction in various recitation variants (Qira'at) to students... The school's approach includes in-depth study of different recitation methods, allowing students to recognise distinctions between recitations such as Warsh and Hafs. (Zayyan, teacher)

This emphasis on diversity reflects the interviewee's commitment to a thorough Quranic education. Zayyan also highlighted students' notable successes in national and international competitions. His recognition of consistently high-ranking results in events like the National Quranic Week and the Prophet's Birthday Celebration Contest emphasises the programme's effectiveness. These achievements demonstrate the tangible impact of this comprehensive Quranic education on students' skills and confidence. Building on the theme of holistic development in Quranic schools, another participant also stressed its importance. However, this participant added a unique perspective by emphasising the well-balanced personalities of the students. He said,

The school ensures that each student's academic progress is tailored to their age and level. The school aims to nurture well-balanced Islamic personalities and encourages students to actively contribute to the community (Waleed, Administrator).

This perspective, which emphasises the psychological well-being of students, aligns with research findings that show individuals who identify as religious tend to have higher life satisfaction and lower suicide rates than non-believers (Donovan & Halpern, 2002; Helliwell & Putnam, 2005).

By focusing not only on Quranic studies but also on developing diverse life skills, the schools nurture students with a sense of purpose and confidence. This holistic approach to education aligns with broader psychological research, indicating that identity and a sense of life's meaning are closely linked concepts. A strong sense of life's meaning supports identity commitments, helping students internalise their beliefs as part of a coherent worldview and maintain their identity exploration over time (Negru-Subtirica et al., 2016; Erikson, 1968). Research further suggests that an identity achievement profile—characterised by a high commitment to life goals and a well-defined personal identity—is often associated with greater religious engagement, life satisfaction, and resilience (Negru-Subtirica et al., 2017). Therefore, linking Islamic teachings to larger developmental goals will ultimately foster well-rounded individuals with a strong sense of purpose and commitment who can contribute positively to society.

It is important to note that not all Quranic schools in Algeria have the same level of resources and modern facilities, as several participants in this study highlighted. This disparity in resources raises concerns about the educational experience in some Quranic schools within the country, particularly regarding access to modern teaching tools and a standardised curriculum. Many informants suggested that the Quranic education curriculum be standardised and that fees be introduced for parents to facilitate improvements across all aspects of Quranic schools.

7.3. Structure and Operation of Quranic Schools

The structure and operation of Quranic schools are essential for understanding how these institutions support students' religious and cultural socialisation. The administrative systems and organisational practices used in these schools greatly influence the educational experience and the development of students' Islamic identities. Participants in this study offered valuable insights into how these operational aspects appear in their experiences, emphasising elements such as classroom management and educators' roles. Further publications also highlight the crucial role that effective frameworks and procedures play in enhancing students' engagement and commitment to their religious education, ultimately shaping their moral and cultural identities. This subtheme emerges from the collective views of participants, emphasising the importance of examining not only the curriculum but also the structural features that underpin the overall socialisation process within Quranic schools.

In analysing the structural and functional elements of Quranic schools, it is essential to understand how their organisational frameworks support the educational process. As one of the participants observes,

This Quranic school is privately operated but remains under the supervision of the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Endowments. Its main objective is to teach Quran memorisation. The morning session is reserved for female students, while the evening session caters to male students. (Waleed, Administrator).

Waleed's institution demonstrates the interaction between private initiatives and government oversight in religious education. This view also highlights how the school's organisational structure supports its religious and cultural socialisation roles. The school respects community norms by providing separate classes for male and female students while creating an environment focused on religious learning. At the same time, government oversight ensures that these religious goals align with standards for educational quality and consistency.

The study by Hazim and Nazari (2023) further supports this model by examining the risks associated with gender mixing in educational settings from an Islamic Shariah perspective. Their research highlights the importance of gender segregation in maintaining moral and religious values, arguing that unrestricted gender mixing could challenge societal harmony and weaken Islamic ethical standards. By maintaining separate classes for male and female students, the Quranic school aligns itself with these Shariah principles, fostering an environment that promotes focused religious instruction and respects broader cultural and religious norms. However, while this approach safeguards religious integrity, it also raises questions about balancing traditional values with modern educational standards and the inclusivity expected in a state-supervised educational context.

This topic also engages with broader debates within Islamic communities, as Meijer (2010) examines how gender segregation has been a longstanding tradition in Saudi Arabia. He shows that the Saudi state has consistently implemented gender separation in public and educational spaces. Nevertheless, in recent years, the debate has intensified, with liberal intellectuals advocating for the relaxation of these policies. They argue that gender mixing can help foster social and economic development, contrasting with conservative voices which insist on maintaining gender separation as a fundamental cultural and religious principle. This discussion of gender segregation in schools is not confined to Muslim societies; it is also an international issue, as seen in the increasing movement towards sex-segregated schools in the United States. The study by Herr et al. (2021) addresses this phenomenon, framed within school choice and market-driven educational principles. The study identifies three primary reasons for supporting gender segregation in schools: to reduce distractions, address gender-based learning styles, and provide equity for underserved students, especially low-income students of colour.

However, despite these justifications, the research shows that gender-segregated schools often reinforce gender stereotypes and uphold heteronormative standards, with little evidence that they challenge traditional gender norms or significantly enhance academic outcomes. Winkel (2019) examines how cultural symbols in different religions shape gender roles and influence people's behaviour and values. She demonstrates that gender and religious practices act as cultural markers that help define social identities, guiding community interactions and setting norms for behaviour across traditions. This perspective helps us understand that the separation of genders in Quranic schools is not only a religious practice but also a reflection of broader cultural norms that give meaning to social roles and boundaries.

Participants' descriptions of Quranic schools' qualities and educational models closely reflect the findings of Akkari (2004). He synthesises historical research on Quranic schools across the Maghreb and sub-Saharan Africa, indicating six fundamental characteristics that define their educational practices and uphold their traditional values. First, openness ensures the accessibility of these schools to all Muslim children, regardless of their background, creating an inclusive environment that resists social divisions. Ritualisation is another feature, where memorising the Quran is central, and students engage in repetitive recitations involving rhythmic and physical movements. These practices play a significant role in the religious socialisation of children. The permanence of Quranic schools is also important; they have preserved their vitality for centuries, helping to maintain and transmit Islamic values across generations, mainly due to the support of local religious authorities rather than centralised institutions. Flexibility is evident in how these schools incorporate oral and written traditions, adapting to different cultural contexts while often involving teachers with varying levels of formal training.

A key aspect of this adaptability is the ongoing oral transmission of knowledge, a method deeply rooted in Islamic tradition dating back to the time of the Prophet Muhammad. During his era, knowledge was mainly conveyed through spoken instruction and memorisation. As Casewit (2015) notes, this approach involves transmitting knowledge and functions as a spiritual practice, preparing students for academic success and spiritual salvation. Despite the dominance of modern secular education, Casewit indicates that this method continues to uphold religious and cultural knowledge in its most authentic form. Resistance is evident in how Quranic schools have withstood colonial pressures and adapted to post-colonial contexts, maintaining benefits for marginalised groups or areas lacking formal schooling. Quranic schools notably opposed French colonial education policies in Algeria. This aspect of resistance has been extensively discussed in the third chapter on Quranic schools in Algeria, emphasising their resilience and ongoing importance. Finally, the diversity of these schools is demonstrated by their ability to offer a range of educational experiences, from Quranic memorisation to vocational training, and to operate in various settings such as mosques or outdoor spaces, adjusting

to community needs. This consistency across Quranic schools worldwide illustrates the continuity in the role and structure of Quranic education across diverse regions.

Many studies, such as the one by Harris (2007), have shown that memorising the Quran and using traditional methods enhances brain function, particularly in areas responsible for memory, problem-solving, and language processing. Supporting this research, most educators in the Islamic world agree that teaching other subjects to students who have memorised the Quran is easier than working with those who have not. This cognitive development, coupled with the historical significance of Quranic memorisation, also links the rise of Islamic contributions to science, suggesting that the foundational practice of memorising the Quran played a pivotal role in intellectual achievements during the Islamic Golden Age (Casewit, 2015).

7.4. Teaching Styles and Discipline: Negotiating Authority in Quranic Education

The participants offer different perspectives on how teachers' authority and pedagogical approaches guide social behaviour and foster connections within the Quranic school environment. These perspectives highlight a central tension in the purpose of religious education: is the teacher's primary role to enforce discipline and protect orthodoxy, or to nurture understanding and compassionate character? This tension is reflected in the competing teaching styles observed in the data, which range from strict disciplinarianism to gentle guidance, each with profound implications for how students internalize Islamic values and learn to interact with their community.

At one end of this spectrum, parents expressed concern that overly strict pedagogical approaches could undermine the very goals of Quranic education. Parent Jawad articulated this concern, arguing that an excessively rigid disciplinary environment risks alienating the students it aims to shape:

In our area, the education is intensive, and the teachers are strict with students. I believe that this teaching style might make students reluctant to engage with Quranic education. There must be space for play because a child remains a child, no matter what (Jawad, parent).

Another participant who is a parent and Quran teacher shared Jawad's viewpoint. She said that “some children left their previous teacher due to their strictness and joined my Quran group instead” (Mubaraka: Parent). This practical observation shows that students and parents actively negotiate authority through their enrolment choices, 'voting with their feet' against pedagogical approaches they find too harsh.

This perspective finds its theological and philosophical justification in the views of teachers like Essam, who explicitly champion an alternative model of authority based on compassionate relationships. He argued that the teacher-student dynamic should be fundamentally redefined, stating:

The essence of the matter is that the relationship between the Quran teacher and the student is a fraternal one... there are Quran teachers who treat their students harshly... but gentleness is required. It is a divine matter (Essam, teacher).

To establish this paradigm based on divine precedence, Essam referenced the Quranic verse:

It is part of the Mercy of Allah that you deal gently with them. Were you severe or harsh-hearted, they would have broken away from about you... (Quran, 3: 159).

Essam's stance is analytically critical because it directly challenges the legitimacy of authoritarian discipline by framing gentleness not just as a pedagogical strategy but as a religious obligation ("a divine matter"). By citing the highest authority—the Quran itself—he implies that a gentle, "fraternal" relationship is the most authentic and effective form of religious authority, one that prevents students from "breaking away." This positions his teaching style not merely as a preference but as a theologically grounded alternative to the strict disciplinarianism described by Jawad.

Essam further developed this theological foundation by citing a verse that depicts the teacher's role as a compassionate guide rather than a coercive authority.

Invite (all) to the Way of your Lord with wisdom and beautiful preaching; and argue with them in ways that are best and most gracious (Quran, 16:125).

This verse is crucial as it shifts the focus from internal classroom management (Quran 3:159) to the wider aim of religious education: an invitation (da'wah) defined by wisdom and grace. Essam, by citing this, implicitly argues that the pedagogical method within the Quranic school must reflect the prophetic approach of engaging with the broader world. A teacher who depends on harshness and strict authority fundamentally contradicts this key Islamic principle of "beautiful preaching," suggesting that the very method of instruction is as important as the content being taught.

Essam further grounded his philosophy in Prophetic tradition, citing the hadith: "Verily, gentleness is not found in anything but that it beautifies it, and it is not removed from anything but that it disgraces it." This enabled him to present gentleness not just as a preference, but as an attribute that actively "beautifies" the educational process and the student-teacher relationship.

He summarized this holistic approach by defining the teacher's ultimate role:

Our relationship with the students is very close; we don't just teach, we also nurture. A teacher should also be a mentor 'Murabbi' (Essam, teacher).

The term Murabbi is the culmination of Essam's argument, representing an authority figure whose primary mode of influence is nurturing care. This concept, intrinsically linked to Tarbiya (holistic nurturing), positions the educator's role as guiding spiritual, moral, and intellectual development. By invoking this ideal, Essam's model directly challenges the justification of harshness, positing that such an approach deviates from an education that must prioritize the student's spiritual well-being to foster a genuine communal connection.

This perspective finds support in contemporary research; Ilham et al. (2023) corroborate that caring values like affection and empathy are fundamental to student development, contributing significantly to personality, social skills, and overall quality of life. Thus, Essam's advocacy for a nurturing model is not only theologically grounded but also aligned with empirical findings on effective character education.

Positioned at the opposite end of the pedagogical spectrum, a considerable group of parents defended strictness as a necessary form of authority, framing it not as harshness but as essential for fostering discipline and ensuring spiritual accountability. Parent Samia expressed this view by comparing her children's experiences, recognising a strict teacher's role despite witnessing its potential to cause avoidance.

For instance, my son's Quran teacher is very strict, and he sometimes skips school if he has not memorized the assigned portion due to fear... In my view, a teacher must have a certain level of sternness in teaching to ensure students' discipline and commitment (Samia, parent).

Notably, Samia justifies this sternness despite its apparent negative impact on her son's engagement, prioritising the long-term goal of discipline over immediate emotional well-being. This view was further supported by Parent Amal, who provided a compelling theological rationale for this authoritative stance.

My son might sometimes complain about the strictness... but I always told him that the teacher treats him this way for his own benefit. Any place where a Quranic teacher corrects you will not be a place where you suffer from the fire of Hell (Amal, parent).

Amal's statement is analytically important; it reinterprets the teacher's strictness as an act of divine compassion, a corrective measure that guarantees otherworldly salvation. This shifts the teacher's authority from merely a pedagogical tool to a spiritual safeguard, presenting a strong counter-argument to the nurturing model supported by Essam. For these parents, the "negotiation of authority" ultimately reinforces a stern, top-down approach, which they believe fosters a higher good: committed discipline and spiritual security.

The range of teaching authority extends further to include the most controversial method: the use of physical discipline. Teacher Khaled exemplifies this stance, explicitly justifying physical correction as a legitimate pedagogical tool. He argued that such measures serve a higher educational and spiritual purpose.

Some parents refuse to send their children to Quranic schools, citing the strictness of the education. To them, I say that if a teacher resorts to physical discipline, it is for the purpose of teaching and urging the child to learn the words of Allah, not out of cruelty or disdain for the child (Khaled: teacher).

Analytically, Khaled's statement generates a notable tension. He concludes by asserting that "The teacher in a Quranic school is a mentor before being an instructor," yet he defines this mentorship in a way that directly conflicts with the nurturing, fraternal model promoted by Essam. While Essam's mentorship is characterised by gentleness and wisdom, Khaled's is framed by an authority that allows physical admonishment. This exemplifies the most extreme form of "negotiating authority" in the data—one that emphasises the unwavering transmission of religious knowledge and justifies stern methods as a divine necessity, positioning the teacher's role as a spiritual enforcer above all else.

In line with Khaled, Zayyan sees that some parents, when they sense excessive rigidity in the educational process, opt to relocate their children to alternative institutions where a more flexible atmosphere is perceived. This parental decision can inadvertently limit the potential for good learning experiences, as the significance of learning from individuals whose knowledge can genuinely benefit the students is believed as the most important. Zayyan stated:

It's not uncommon for parents to mistakenly attribute their child's academic challenges to the teacher's approach, deeming it too strict or stressful. Here, Ibn al-Qayyim's words resonate: "If the soul is not occupied with the truth, it will be occupied with falsehood." Parents should avoid labeling their child's experience as stressful due to an abundance of lessons. Rather, providing an environment of productive learning prevents potential concerns. Hence, I mentioned that some Algerian families, upon finding that a Quranic teacher is strict with their child, opt to transfer

them elsewhere, where the child can experience a sense of freedom and less constraint. Even Imam Nawawi, may Allah have mercy upon him, in his book "Al-Tibyan fi Adab Hamalat al-Qur'an" (Elucidation of the Etiquette of Quran Carriers), outlined several etiquettes for teachers, such as not getting angry and preventing students from reading under someone else. Thus, there is no issue if I, as a Quranic teacher, see my student learning in another school under a different scholar; there is no harm in this. However, the control over this action is conditional on one factor: learning from someone whose knowledge can benefit them (Zayyan, teacher).

Furthermore, Zayyan noted that in some cases, the emotional responses of parents considerably influence their decisions regarding their children's educational journey. This phenomenon highlights the complex relationship between emotional bonds, educational philosophies, and practical considerations; he articulated that,

It saddens me when a student leaves my school and goes somewhere that doesn't provide them with beneficial learning. Algerian families, though not all of them, sometimes fall into this error due to their emotional responses. When a child complains directly to them, they sympathize, and many of them fail to recognize their responsibilities as guardians. Consequently, they give in to their children's desires. Not always are parents correct in every situation (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan observes some families' emotional responses to perceived strictness, encouraging them to prioritise educational quality before making decisions. Overall, he emphasises the shared responsibility of teachers and parents in creating supportive learning environments.

The diverse perspectives shared by the participants reflect a significant debate within Quranic education regarding the role of teacher-student relationships and mentorship. These views demonstrate a complex balance between discipline and emotional support, and how these elements influence students' engagement with their religious studies, as well as how they interact with broader society using their acquired transferable skills. Participants' concerns about the potentially discouraging effect of strict teaching styles align with existing research discussing how overly strict educational environments can lead to disengagement and increased stress among learners. Studies have shown that excessive pressure in educational settings, particularly for young learners, can reduce motivation and result in burnout (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

The need for balance between intensity and space for play, as Salim suggests, aligns with the concept of a growth mindset—an approach that emphasises the importance of fostering curiosity, resilience, and self-compassion in students (Dweck, 2006). Creating an environment that promotes exploration and

play is especially vital in childhood education because it helps nurture creativity and sustained engagement in learning (Berk, 2015). Conversely, Samia's perspective, along with that of other participants, emphasises the necessity of a certain degree of sternness to uphold discipline and ensure student commitment. This view reflects research that underscores the significance of authority in educational contexts, where structure and clear boundaries can help students feel secure and motivated (Dollard & Miller, 1945).

Research also indicates that strict leadership in educational settings can maintain student engagement and achievement, as it sets clear expectations and a structured environment that encourages focus and discipline. For instance, in Tanzania, studies have shown that the teaching of Christian Religious Education in schools where firm discipline is emphasised results in fewer disciplinary issues compared to schools where it is not taught, suggesting that a strong teacher presence can promote moral behaviour and a disciplined learning atmosphere (Ngussa & Makewa, 2018). By combining firm authority and emotional intelligence, educators can effectively guide students while balancing structure and compassion (Leithwood, 2021). This structured approach helps sustain discipline and ensures students remain dedicated to their learning journey. Consequently, teachers who set high standards while maintaining fairness and transparency can help students develop resilience and accountability, both of which are essential for religious and personal growth.

Amal's perspective, which aligns with Samia's and five other parents, emphasises that strictness, when regarded as a form of care and guidance, can serve as a powerful motivator for students. Research supports this view; Baumrind's (1991) findings on authoritative parenting demonstrate that a balanced approach combining high expectations with warmth and support yields positive developmental outcomes, including enhanced competence and emotional well-being. This research indicates that adolescents raised with authoritative guidance are more likely to develop resilience, discipline, and a sense of responsibility. In the context of Quranic education, applying a similar balance of demandingness and responsiveness can foster both academic achievement and personal growth. Amal's perspective also underscores the importance of framing difficult experiences — such as a strict teaching approach — in a positive and supportive manner. This process of re-framing, where students perceive corrections as being for their ultimate benefit, can help them cultivate a more resilient and positive relationship with the learning process (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

The discussion about pedagogical authority also includes concerns about its possible misuse. Administrator Waleed added an important aspect to the debate, recognising the positive impact of Quranic education while highlighting the teacher as a potential risk source.

The Quranic education positively influences the child's character and beliefs... Any observed extremism among some students is attributed to certain teachers who mislead the students...(Waleed: administrator).

Waleed's perspective is vital as it shifts the emphasis from the style of authority (strict versus gentle) to its content and interpretation. He contends that the teacher's influence is so formidable that it can divert the entire educational process from its goal of balanced character development towards ideological extremism. This observation offers a sobering counterpoint to earlier debates, suggesting that whether a teacher is strict or gentle, the ultimate safeguard is the teacher's own alignment with moderate, core Islamic principles. Therefore, Waleed implicitly advocates for a form of qualified authority—one that is not only effective in discipline but also morally and doctrinally sound—underscoring the importance of institutional oversight and teacher quality control as fundamental to the school's mission.

In summary, this section shows that the "cultural and religious socialisation" within Quranic schools is deeply shaped by the ongoing negotiation of pedagogical authority. The community navigates a wide range of approaches, from the nurturing fraternal model of the Murabbi to the strict disciplinary model justified by spiritual salvation. However, Waleed's critical intervention illustrates that this debate is ultimately secondary to a more fundamental principle: regardless of style, all teacher authority must be rooted in sound doctrine and moral integrity. Therefore, the most vital negotiation is not between strictness and gentleness, but between responsible and irresponsible authority, with the school's ultimate socialising mission depending on ensuring the former.

7.5. Conclusion

Quranic schools play a crucial role in the religious and cultural socialisation of Algerian children, shaped by various factors. The curriculum of these schools, although primarily focused on teaching the Quran and Islamic values, differs between institutions and offers diverse educational experiences. Some schools concentrate solely on memorisation and recitation, while others include additional elements in the learning process. Despite these differences, the overall goal remains the same: to foster a connection to faith and ensure that students are well-equipped to live according to Islamic principles within their communities.

The structure and operation of Quranic schools also shape the learning environment. While some schools follow more formal frameworks with strict schedules, others are more flexible. This organisational difference can influence the effectiveness of religious socialisation, affecting how students internalise teachings and build connections with their faith.

Furthermore, the dynamics of teaching authority and student-teacher relationships are vital for students' personal development and socialisation. As discussed in this chapter, teachers' pedagogical approaches vary from strict disciplinarians to nurturing guides. The ongoing negotiation of this authority—between educators, students, and parents—significantly influences how students internalise Islamic values. While some advocate for sternness to uphold discipline and spiritual commitment, others prefer a gentler, fraternally-based approach rooted in the Islamic concept of a Murabbi. These interpersonal dynamics are crucial in helping students incorporate their learning into daily life and build a resilient cultural and religious identity.

Ultimately, Quranic schools play a vital role in the religious and cultural socialisation of children by shaping them into responsible, spiritually engaged individuals through their curriculum, school structures, and the careful negotiation of pedagogical authority. All of these elements aim to prepare them for a life grounded in Islamic values and principles, despite variations in methods across institutions.

Chapter 8

Parental Support for Quranic Schools

8.1. Introduction

The emerging theme of Parental Support for Quranic Schools offers valuable insights into how Algerian families contribute to their children's educational experiences and the success and growth of Quranic schools. This broad theme includes three key subthemes: First, the Parental Role in Supporting Children's Education highlights how Algerian parents support their children's learning through active

involvement and investment in Quranic education. Second, the Teachers' and Administrators' Perspectives on Parents and Quranic Education explore the viewpoints of administrators and educators on the extent of parental involvement and its impact on children's outcomes. It also addresses the challenges and opportunities this involvement presents. Lastly, Parents' Perspectives on Muslim Communities and Quranic Education consider how parents view the implications of Quranic schools within the Algerian Muslim community and the community's role in their children's educational experience. Together, these three subthemes provide a detailed understanding of the relationship between families, Quranic schools, and the community, offering valuable insights into how this partnership influences the educational experiences of Algerian children in Quranic schools.

8.2. Parental Role in Supporting Children's Education through Quranic Schools

Participants in the study highlighted the important role of parents in shaping their children's educational journey. Parents were depicted in many narratives as active contributors in the logistical and emotional support they offer, articulating expectations and assessing the effectiveness of their children's education. This emphasis underscores the interaction between family priorities and Quranic educational institutions, reflecting a deep cultural understanding of education as a collective, family-centred endeavour (Keltly & Wakabayashi, 2020). Research shows that the influence of the family on a child's education is significant, especially in religious contexts. This role is emphasised in Islamic teachings, which stress the importance of parental guidance and accountability in children's moral and religious growth (Abid, 2023; Shoti, 2021).

Communication between parents, teachers, and administrators at Quranic schools is recognised as a vital element of effective Quranic education. However, participants revealed notable differences in how this interaction is perceived and practised, with some emphasising constructive dialogues and ongoing communication, while others highlighted a lack of meaningful engagement, which they believed weakens the collaborative potential necessary for supporting a child's holistic development. One of the parents said:

Parental involvement plays a crucial role in our children's Quranic education. External influences, such as the allure of the streets and modern distractions like electronic games and smartphones, can easily distract children. In today's challenging environment, cooperation between Quranic school teachers and parents is vital to safeguard children's morals and ethics from society's negative influences. A child's character and upbringing are still in the developmental stage, making it necessary to instil good values and behaviours. Parents need to create a plan to guide their children in the right direction. Without proper guidance, children may engage only in play.

Therefore, appropriate supervision, guidance, and communication with Quranic teachers are essential. This partnership enables parents to observe their children's behaviour and progress, address any issues, and intervene when necessary (Fatima, Parent).

Fatima's perspective highlights the vital importance of parental involvement in shaping children's faith during their early years, a concept strongly supported by Fowler's stages of faith development. Children rely heavily on external authority figures such as parents and educators during this stage for moral and spiritual guidance (Fowler, 1981). Fatima's concern about distractions like smartphones aligns with the intuitive-projective and mythic-literal stages, where consistent reinforcement of values is crucial. She advocates for active collaboration between parents and Quranic school teachers, emphasising the importance of guiding children's moral and spiritual development through active supervision and intervention to ensure their growth aligns with religious values.

Parents highlighted their important role in their children's education at Quranic schools by describing various ways they get involved, showing their dedication to staying engaged in their children's learning. One parent said:

I am quite involved in my children's Quranic school journey. I closely monitor what is happening, especially with my daughter, whose teacher is also my friend. We are in the same environment, and I study in her Quranic school. My son's teacher is a university professor like me, so we often discuss his progress when we meet at the university (Samia, parent).

Samia's perspective reflects an alignment in the family's priorities, with a shared interest in attending Quranic schools. It also shows how social networks can enhance children's educational experiences. Samia closely monitors her children's progress and consistently interacts with their teachers, demonstrating how dedicated parental involvement fosters a collaborative educational environment. The fact that Samia has a personal friendship with her daughter's teacher and professional ties with her son's teacher further builds trust, open communication, and transparency. This alignment of family and school interests creates a coherent framework of values and expectations, supporting children's overall growth and development. This perspective is supported by findings from Bunnell et al. (2018), which emphasised the critical role of parental involvement in children's religious education, considering it an essential part of their development. Their study illustrates how ongoing interaction with teachers and committed engagement create a supportive atmosphere for children's spiritual and academic growth.

However, this harmony also raises important considerations. While Samia's position within the Quranic school's environment allows her to offer consistent oversight, it may unintentionally highlight

disparities in access for other parents who lack such integration. The potential for informal connections to influence educational practices could foster perceptions of unfairness or favouritism, emphasising the need for formal procedures that promote fairness and inclusivity in parent-teacher engagement. Overall, Samia's case demonstrates the advantages of aligned interests in Quranic education while also highlighting broader systemic issues to ensure fair opportunities for all families.

Expanding on Samia's view of family involvement in Quranic education, Tawfik provides another compelling example that highlights the transformative impact of such engagement, drawn from televised Quran memorisation competitions. He recounts the story of Yusuf, a child with autism who excelled in memorisation. Tawfik said:

Despite having autism, a child named Yusuf has participated in numerous Quran memorisation competitions. Despite his condition, he has achieved mastery in memorisation, mainly due to the effort made by his parents, which shows their dedication to his Quranic education and memorisation. Everything relies on the parents and their level of involvement in their children's educational journey in Quranic schools (Tawfik, parent).

According to Tawfik, this child's impressive accomplishment is owed to his parents' remarkable commitment. Their endeavours indicate the vital role of parental involvement in overcoming obstacles and fostering success in Quranic education, even with children's unique conditions. In the same regard, Reeder and Morris's study (2021) on parental involvement in children with special needs can provide useful insights. Their study shows how parental empowerment, through partnership with teachers and specialists, plays a crucial role in navigating a child's challenges. Likewise, Tawfik's story shows that parental empowerment combined with active participation can be a key factor in overcoming barriers to children's Quranic education. In Yusuf's case, his success in memorisation, despite his condition, illustrates how empowered parents can be vital decision-makers and contributors to their children's educational journey. However, just as Reeder and Morris emphasise the importance of addressing power imbalances, it is crucial for Quranic schools to create environments where all parents, not only those with privileged access, are equally supported and empowered to contribute to their children's success.

Another parent narrative expands on the wider aspects of parental involvement. This participant emphasises the importance of tangible support, both financial and emotional, in guiding children in their Quranic education. He stated that,

Support is vital. My wife and I provide both financial and moral support. I always motivate my son, saying, 'You are doing great with memorization. Soon, you will complete the entire Quran!' I surprise them with gifts when they make progress or win school competitions (Salim, Parent).

Salim's perspective illustrates different methods of parental involvement in their children's education, combining financial and emotional support to foster a positive learning environment. The teamwork with his wife indicates a collective familial effort, demonstrating how shared commitments enhance stability and focus on educational goals. The motivational language, such as praising his son's progress and envisioning his success, reflects the principle of positive reinforcement and bolsters the child's confidence and persistence. Such encouragement from parents is essential; indeed, it is widely recognised that parental involvement is linked to better educational outcomes for children (Daniel et al., 2016).

Additionally, the rewards for the child's accomplishments showcase an effective use of extrinsic motivators, encouraging immediate progress and engagement. However, this reward-based approach requires careful balance to ensure the child's appreciation of the intrinsic value of Quranic memorisation and its spiritual significance, rather than focusing solely on outcomes. Wong and Thomson (2014) explore how rewards can promote short-term student progress and engagement, as demonstrated by Salim's example of surprising his son with gifts for his achievements. Nonetheless, as the literature warns, relying solely on rewards can potentially weaken long-term engagement and intrinsic motivation (Wong & Thomson, 2014). A balanced combination of extrinsic motivators and an emphasis on the spiritual and educational importance of Quranic memorisation are vital to sustain motivation and foster deeper, lasting commitment. Salim's example highlights how holistic support can enhance academic and personal development, while also emphasising the importance of a balanced, meaningful approach to motivation.

Another parent shared how her religious practices related to Quran reading and memorisation served to motivate and enhance her children's attitudes and performance. She mentioned that,

When parents memorise the Quran alongside their children, it also motivates the children to continue their studies in Quranic schools. For example, when my daughter was four years old, I memorised Surah Al-Waqi'ah. I didn't realise until I noticed that my daughter had almost memorised it just from listening to me repeatedly recite and review it. As for Surah Al-Baqarah, I recited it daily as part of my routine. When my daughters reached Surah Al-Baqarah in their Quranic school, they told me they faced no difficulty memorising it because they were already used to hearing it from me every day (Saida: parent).

Hasanah's (2021) study demonstrates the important role parents play in guiding their children's Quranic memorisation through their religious practices and personal involvement. The study shows that the relationship between children and their parents, who show devotion to memorisation and model respect for the Quran, directly influences the children's understanding and performance. This aligns with Saida's experience, where her daily Quran recitation helped her daughter internalise Surah Al-Waqi'ah and Surah Al-Baqarah, making the memorisation process easier. Such engagement fosters a spiritually enriched environment that contributes to the success of children's Quranic education and supports the overall idea that family involvement creates a cohesive and motivating learning atmosphere.

Parent Amal reflects,

I regret not continuing my education at the Quranic school, and this feeling lingered even after my marriage. However, as I am now studying at a Quranic school, I realised it was only my imagination that led me to believe I couldn't balance my married life with Quranic education (Amal, parent).

In the same vein, Huda's (2019) study on lifelong education within the Islamic perspective supports the idea of continuous learning, as promoted by Islamic teachings, emphasising that the pursuit of knowledge extends beyond formal education into a lifelong journey. This aligns with Amal's evolving perspective, as her participation in Quranic schools reflects the principle of lifelong learning, reconciling missed opportunities with current efforts. Her realisation highlights the flexibility of education across different life stages, resonating with the Islamic ethos of seeking knowledge throughout life, even while managing household responsibilities. This places her personal growth within a broader educational philosophy.

Furthermore, Amal passionately expressed,

Currently, I encourage my son and daughter to memorise the Quran at a young age because I fear that as they grow older, it might become more difficult. I genuinely believe that salvation in our times lies in the Quran. The Quran is the ship that carries us all, and salvation is found in it (Amal, parent).

Amal emphasises the importance of Quranic education as both a spiritual anchor and a practical route to salvation in contemporary times. Her encouragement for her children to memorise the Quran at a young age reflects her understanding of the cognitive advantages of early learning, as discussed in detail

in the conceptual frameworks chapter, along with the difficulties of memorisation at later stages. The study by Al-Hawary et al. (2023) supports Amal's perspective by emphasising the family's central role in children's educational and moral development, as outlined in the Qur'an. The Quran regards the family as the primary and most influential institution for shaping personality, instilling values, and fostering faith. This aligns with Amal's focus on beginning her children's Quranic education early within a nurturing family environment.

According to Al-Hawary et al., Islamic teachings provide clear guidelines for child education from infancy, such as loving children, observing justice, and prioritising moral development, all of which are directly influenced by family involvement. Moreover, Amal's belief in the Quran as a "ship" of salvation resonates with the Islamic doctrine that the Quran acts as a comprehensive guide for navigating life's challenges. Studies like this demonstrate that embedding Quranic education within a family framework ensures the continuity of faith and moral integrity across generations, highlighting the enduring relevance of the Quran in personal and community life. Amal's actions reflect this guidance, as she encourages her children's memorisation and strengthens their connection to the Quran as a source of ethical and spiritual grounding. The link between Amal's practices and Islamic educational principles underscores the importance of starting Quranic education early, with a family environment that values and actively supports the process. It aims to develop memorisation skills and foster a deep-rooted understanding of the Quranic teachings as the foundation for a righteous and fulfilling life.

Many participants demonstrated their involvement by supporting their children at home, as Salim does. Other parents mentioned attending Quranic schools for memorisation with adult groups like Samia, Saida, and Amal. The parents' participation in the same Quranic school where their children learn shows harmony within the family by sharing similar interests, which helps create a cohesive environment that supports the children's educational journey. This shared pursuit among family members likely fosters a positive atmosphere conducive to their children's development. However, another group of parents shows little involvement in their children's Quranic education, such as parent Boubakr, who is moderately involved by offering support both at home and school. He stated, "We are somewhat involved, and this involvement is evident in supporting the role of the home in parallel with the school." Waleed added, "We encourage parents to support their children's Quranic education; some secretly buy gifts for their children and ask us to present them as rewards. The child does not realise that their parent arranged it" (Waleed, administrator).

Listening carefully to the participants' perspectives, the idea of adopting a lifestyle of faith consisting of moments where parents and their children actively engaged in faith practices was observed. These

practices, including prioritising prayer, fasting during Ramadan, helping the needy, practising almsgiving, and serving God, they understood in retrospect to have helped them develop their faith. One of the parents, Salim, captured the essence of this by describing how he instilled religious practices in his son daily, emphasising the importance of conducting religious rituals as a family. He used the saying of the Prophet Muhammad, “Do not make your houses like graveyards”. This hadith aligns with his approach, where he encourages fathers to perform obligatory prayers in the mosque and reserve voluntary prayers for home. This practice allows children to witness their parents’ devotion, providing them with a live example to follow, and thereby fostering a strong bond between the child and their faith.

Similarly, consistency in parents’ behaviour can be crucial. Salim emphasised the importance of matching actions and values when raising children. He gave the example of a father who smokes, pointing out that if the father cannot quit smoking, he should at least avoid smoking in front of his children. This approach avoids normalising smoking and also supports the values parents aim to teach, such as self-control and making healthy choices. By aligning their behaviour with the lessons they want to pass on, parents can act as genuine role models, demonstrating faith and principles through their actions rather than just telling their children what to do.

Fatima's family's experience in adopting a faith-based lifestyle was twofold. It allowed her children to demonstrate their faith through humility towards their teachers and peers, while also inspiring them to uphold integrity in their actions. She stated;

Our journey has had a dual effect. It has not only taught our children to be humble towards their teachers and peers but has also encouraged them to uphold honesty and integrity in all their actions (Fatima, parent).

Within the realm of parental involvement in education, the multifaceted perspectives offered by participants shed light on parents’ efforts to evaluate multiple schooling systems. This aspect added a personal dimension to the discussion, revealing families' emotional struggles when balancing tradition with their children's future success. However, nearly all parent participants expressed their efforts to enrol their children in both schools' traditions; they also showed their satisfaction with Quranic schools despite recognising certain shortcomings that require attention. Parent Salim articulated that conflicts may arise regarding parents' choices for their children, whether to prioritise public schools exclusively or to strike a balance between the two educational traditions. Another parent stated that,

Living in a large city where both types of schools are accessible, my children attend both public and Quranic schools. Balancing these two schools is quite challenging due to the amount of homework and lessons in public schools. However, Quranic schools usually offer lessons at times that do not clash with public school hours, helping to maintain a balance between the two (Samia, parent).

This parent reveals their children's dual education, driven by the availability of public and Quranic schools in the urban setting. Balancing these educational systems presents challenges, primarily due to the rigorous coursework and demands of the public-school curriculum. Despite this, the parent highlighted the advantage of Quranic schools scheduling their lessons in non-conflicting time slots, providing a practical solution to manage the overlapping schedules and ensure a balanced educational experience for their children. Balancing the two systems can also enhance children's development. According to contemporary research in early childhood education, like those proposed by Piaget and Vygotsky, cognitive and social skills can be developed by incorporating both religious and academic learning (Gonzaga et al., 2019). Likewise, another parent in this study stated:

Despite the demanding mainstream school programs, parents remain committed to enrolling their children in Quranic schools, believing that Quranic education enhances their children's memory, knowledge, and manners (Parent Bilal).

Here, Bilal also acknowledged the challenges they face in maintaining this dual education approach. One example he highlighted is the scheduling conflict between mainstream school hours and the time dedicated to Quranic schooling. He further stated that

some parents request Quranic schools to adjust their timetables, especially during the period between the Maghrib (sunset) prayer and the Isha (night) prayer) (Bilal, parent).

Parental satisfaction with Quranic education stems from several perspectives, highlighting preferences and contentment with their children's learning experiences.

While the participation of parents in their children's Quranic education demonstrates their commitment to creating a positive learning environment, exploring what motivates them to enrol their children in Quranic schools provides further insight into the values and aspirations influencing this support. Many parents shared the same view as Parent Nadia: to gain God's favour and follow the teachings of Prophet Muhammad. She stated:

The main reason for sending our children to Quranic school is the great reward from Allah and following the saying of our Prophet, peace be upon him, who said, the best among you are those who learn the Quran and teach it. Therefore, my son's enrolment in the Quran school is for worldly benefits. However, the true motivation for the Hereafter is that my son will honour me with the crown of dignity when he completes the words of Allah, and he will ascend to the highest ranks of Paradise with every verse he recites. Every reward he gains from reciting the Quran will be a continuous charity for him and us as his parents. There are many benefits for the family. Firstly, blessings enter the home because reciting the Quran at home brings blessings and repels demons. Additionally, this child will develop good manners according to the Quran in his eating, dressing, and respect for his family, and he will manage his time well (Nadia, Parent).

Nadia highlights the spiritual and aspirational reasons for enrolling her child in a Quranic school, emphasising personal and family benefits related to faith and the afterlife. Her view reflects the blending of religious devotion with practical values, such as moral discipline and time management, indicating a holistic approach to her child's education. She mentioned the concept of continuous charity, considering her son's Quranic education and recitation as a source of ongoing blessings for herself and her child. This aligns with Islamic teachings, where the Prophet Muhammad stressed that when a person dies, their deeds end except for three: ongoing charity, beneficial knowledge, or a righteous child who prays for them (Sahih Muslim 1631). Similarly, Bilal explained why they chose to send their children to the Quran school. He said:

The child gains a psychological, moral, spiritual, and social upbringing. The child holds two guiding principles in life, in this world and the Hereafter: the Book and the Sunnah. The child remains firm in religion, determined in righteousness, and depends on Allah with strong trust. The ultimate goal is worshipping Allah and believing in His oneness. O Allah, keep us steady upon it (Bilal, parent).

Bilal believes that attending Quranic schools helps children develop emotionally, morally, spiritually, and socially. For him, the guidance of the Quran and Sunnah provides clarity in dealing with worldly and eternal matters. Faith commitment, dedication to righteousness, and reliance on God strengthen the child's character and determination. The perspective concludes with an emphasis on tawhid (monotheism), highlighting the oneness of God, which is the core of Islamic belief and represents the ultimate goal of Islamic upbringing: grounding the child and family in strong faith and devotion to God.

Another parent expressed his motivation as follows:

Society's life has become harsh; it no longer distinguishes what is true or invalidates what is false. If a person does not blemish their honour with disgrace, then every garment they wear will seem beautiful. What motivated us as a family to send our children to Quranic schools was to acquire ethical principles for dealing with all segments of society, avoiding gossip, refraining from begging, not being intrusive, and avoiding bad company that leads to corruption and disrupts their lives. Calling them to be upright with Allah by memorising His Book and following the path of His Messenger...etc (Saida, parent).

This parents' perspective highlights several vital reasons for enrolling children in Quranic schools, focusing on the urgent need for ethical and spiritual guidance in a corrupt and morally confused society. The remark about humanity's failure to distinguish between right and wrong emphasises the chaotic environment in which children are growing up, underscoring the importance of strong moral principles derived from Islam. The mention of virtue and honour indicates that sending children to a Quranic school is a bold step in shaping their character and helping them avoid moral pitfalls. Itulua-Abumere's (2013) study on the importance of religious instruction in elementary schools, particularly regarding Christianity, offers valuable insights that reflect Saida's motivations. The study emphasises that religious education is more than doctrinal teaching; it plays a crucial role in fostering ethical principles, character development, and societal harmony. Similarly, Saida stresses the role of Quranic schools in shaping her children's moral compass and preparing them to navigate a morally chaotic society. Furthermore, avoiding negative influences such as gossip, begging, and bad company is highlighted, as these behaviours can lead to corruption and an unsatisfactory life experience. The ultimate goal is to guide children towards righteousness and commitment to their faith by cultivating a strong connection with God through memorising the Quran and following the example of the Prophet Muhammad.

Other participants also shed light on the sense of responsibility parents feel toward guiding their children along the right path amidst the complexities of modern influences. These stories reveal the deep-seated commitment of parents to uphold good values and traditions while navigating an ever-changing society. One of the parents expressed this point as follows:

As parents, we aim to instil righteousness and values in our children that will benefit them in this world and guide their life course. This is why I mentioned that in the past, there were fewer influences compared to today. Our parents did not need to exert much effort in raising us. However, now, we are overwhelmed by various influences, which act as barriers between children and proper upbringing, causing a fragility in values (Samia, parent).

This parent's perspective resonated with many others, emphasising the evolving landscape of modern parenting. They highlighted how parents aim to instil core values in their children. Comparing the past with the present, they pointed out a significant shift in societal influences. Unlike before, when external factors had less impact on upbringing, today's environment presents numerous challenges to nurturing children. The mention of contemporary influences acting as obstacles suggests that parents find it harder to uphold traditional values, which may become more fragile. Samia continued, stating that,

Therefore, I believe parents need to depend on more influential forces than those children face in their daily lives, such as religion, to make a meaningful difference and give their children a proper upbringing (Samia, parent).

Another parent expressed the same view:

As a mother and considering the environment we live in today, with numerous distractions occupying children's time, I believe Quranic schools are crucial in our current era. Social media platforms and various harmful influences have emerged in our society, making it essential for parents to seek alternative options for their children. One such alternative is Quranic education (Amal, parent).

Once again, Amal expressed her interest in sending their children to Quranic schools due to her beliefs about their spiritual and personal development within their faith. She stated that “children are entrusted to their parents” (Amal, parent). This parent's view aligns with a Quranic verse, “O you who believe! Save yourselves and your families from Fire ...” (66:6), which emphasises the parents' duty to protect their children spiritually, guide them towards righteousness, and shield them from harm, including spiritual neglect.

These parents' perspectives indicate that using religious teachings to guide a child's upbringing is powerful and lasting. They believe that reliance on religion can diminish many modern influences children encounter daily. These ideas highlight the importance of providing religious guidance to children, giving them a strong foundation to resist the pressures of contemporary society. When discussing the same issue, a parent expressed her firm belief in prioritising Quranic education for children nowadays. She remarked that,

If given the authority, I would mandate all parents to enrol their children in Quranic schools before considering government education, ensuring participation from every family in the community. At least this would instil in children a love of God, a fear of God, and awareness of

His watchfulness. While elementary school teachers contribute to our children's upbringing, it is crucial to work in harmony with the support of parents, educators, and religious leaders, especially in these challenging times. As the saying goes, one rotten tomato spoils the whole box (Fatima, parent).

Emphasising the importance of working together to guide children towards righteousness and resilience in the face of life's challenges. The rotten tomato analogy illustrates the threat of negative influences. However, even within the environment of Quranic schools, there can be individuals whose behaviour may adversely affect others. This reality highlights the need for careful oversight and ongoing moral reinforcement in all educational settings.

Participants sometimes relied on their Quranic school experiences to enrol their children in similar institutions. They shared a common approach of using their backgrounds in Quranic education to inform their decisions and interactions with Quranic schools for their children, except for a few participants who were motivated by other reasons. For example, one parent recounted how his journey influenced his decision-making process, emphasising the importance of personal aspiration in guiding parental choices. One parent stated:

In the past, I struggled with my Quranic education and was unable to complete it. What I most aspired to was to have a son who would memorise the Quran and excel in all aspects of Quranic knowledge... I hoped my child would achieve what I was unable to when I was young... I always prayed to God to grant me this wish, for my son to be like those I observed, who excelled in Quranic studies and religious knowledge. On the other hand, as the Prophet mentioned, when a person dies, their deeds cease except for three: a righteous child who prays for them is one of these three (Salim, parent).

Salim's desire to achieve what they could not accomplish in Quranic education is rooted in personal regret and a yearning for a spiritual legacy. This longing is connected with religious beliefs, where success in religious education is not only a personal milestone but also a way to gain divine favour and everlasting spiritual rewards. Many parents refer to the hadith about a righteous child praying for their parents after death. Conversely, when parents seek to realise their own ambitions through their children, it can lead to conflicts if each parent has different educational aspirations for the child.

One parent may focus on Quranic studies, while the other may emphasise academic or professional success, seeing the latter as a common source of conflict. This rivalry can create stress and confusion for the child, as their parents' conflicting goals may undermine their independence and interests. Teacher

Khaled expressed concerns that such conflicting expectations exist and could impede the child's sense of self-determination and well-being, especially if the parents lack the skills to manage their choices. A study by Eccles and Harold (1993) indicates that an unbalanced approach to parental involvement might lead to negative effects on the child's emotional and educational development.

8.3. Teachers and Administrators' Perspectives on Parents and Quranic Education

Teachers and administrators emphasised the importance of parents engaging with their children at home regarding their Quranic studies and actively participating in the school environment. This highlights the vital need to establish robust communication channels among parents, students, and teachers within the Quranic school setting. Teachers believe that parents can greatly improve their children's Quranic learning experience and overall education by promoting partnership and collaboration between home and school. To support this involvement, participants noted that they have employed various strategies to encourage interaction between parents and the school.

In this context, insights from some teachers and administrators show varying levels of parental involvement with the schools, reflecting differences among families. While some recognise a certain degree of communication between parents and schools, others lament the inadequate participation of parents. One participant stated that,

Some parents actively participate in their children's Quranic education, closely tracking their progress and behaviour while supporting their overall development. They play a proactive, helpful role in their children's learning journey. Conversely, some parents exhibit little interest in their child's academic achievements or behaviour, leaving the responsibility to the school, believing it will handle everything (Waleed, administrator).

Here, Waleed highlights a contrast in parental involvement in Quranic education, with some parents actively engaged while others remain disengaged. Parents who closely monitor their children's progress and behaviour significantly contribute to their children's academic and moral development, fostering consistency between home and school environments. This involvement helps children internalise lessons and alleviates the school's workload by sharing the responsibility of managing academic and behavioural issues. Conversely, parents who show little interest in their child's education, leaving the entire responsibility to the school, create gaps in their learning and development. Such disengagement can negatively impact academic outcomes and place additional pressure on educational institutions, which may lack sufficient resources to compensate for the absence of parental support. Waleed's perspective also raises concerns about parental

disengagement, such as socioeconomic challenges or their educational backgrounds, emphasising the need for interventions like parent workshops and enhanced school-family communication.

Similarly, Caño et al. (2016) proposed that parental involvement positively influences students' academic performance regardless of their educational background and socioeconomic status. Drawing on Epstein's framework of parental involvement, their research highlights the importance of creating a supportive and nurturing environment both at home and school. The findings indicate that different parenting styles can affect students' academic outcomes, with a particular emphasis on how parents facilitate the connection and integration of students' school routines with their home environments. Generally, Waleed expressed the shared responsibility of parents and schools in ensuring effective Quranic education, stressing that balanced collaboration is vital for educational success. Another participant classified parental involvement in their children's Quranic education into three categories. He observed:

Parents' involvement in their children's Quranic learning journey can be categorised based on their perspectives. The first type includes parents who are deeply interested in Quranic education for their children, encouraging them to attend Quranic schools. This involvement demonstrates their strong understanding and appreciation of the Quran's significance. The second type comprises parents who may not have a direct connection to the Quran but still send their children to Quranic schools. The third type consists of parents who value Quranic education and its importance but lack the knowledge of effective upbringing methods or persuasion techniques to encourage their children to join Quranic schools (Ahmad, teacher).

This classification provides insights into the various levels of parental engagement, perspectives, and approaches, and how they influence the educational experience in Quranic schools. The first group comprises enthusiastic and knowledgeable parents who understand the importance of the Quran and actively encourage their children to attend Quranic schools. The second group includes supportive parents with limited connections. They prioritise enrolling their children in Quranic schools but lack a strong personal relationship with the Quran. While aspirational, they may lack personal experience or religious grounding to effectively support their children's Quranic education. Studies such as Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997) and Hu and Ye (2024) suggest that parents' perceptions of their role and self-efficacy significantly influence their commitment and effectiveness in their children's education. Without deeper personal commitment or understanding, these parents might struggle to create a supportive environment that nurtures the values taught in Quranic schools. Lastly, in the category of parents who value the education but need more skills, the absence of effective parenting techniques can hinder their choices, possibly leading to disengagement or resistance from their children. This classification

offers valuable insights into the different levels of parental engagement in the educational experience of children in Quranic schools.

Essam's experience and perspective on the relationship between educators in Quranic schools and parents reflect the challenges and complexities involved in maintaining effective collaboration and addressing individual student needs. He stated:

Parents are not all the same; sometimes, they make misguided choices and offer negative comments, even questioning the fairness of awards. They might say, "This award was given to someone as a favour, and that one was not." They might even compare their child's performance to others, asserting that their child performs better than the one honoured. However, these instances are rare and cannot be denied. Even we, as educators, can make mistakes in how we interact with children. For instance, someone might tell me that a particular child prefers specific approaches or dislikes others. We consider these insights in such cases, as we do not know the child as intimately as their parents. They might understand certain psychological aspects or challenges we are unaware of. Hence, we sometimes adjust our teaching methods to address these unique needs, recognising that each child requires an individualised approach (Essam, teacher).

This narrative of Essam prompts a more detailed examination of parents' roles in their children's education. While their involvement is necessary, the teacher's perspective stresses the importance of balance and avoiding unrealistic or overly critical expectations. Research shows that such behaviours may unintentionally affect a child's self-esteem or foster unnecessary competition, which can hinder collaborative learning environments (Pomerantz et al., 2007). Essam's narrative also underscores the importance of educators fostering a partnership that appreciates parental input without undermining professional expertise.

Existing literature highlights a key issue in educational theory: Parents' active participation in their children's learning is often intricate and not always straightforward. Studies on parental involvement indicate (Henderson & Mapp, 2002) that there is frequently a mismatch between parents' intentions and their capacity to support their children's education effectively. The insights offered by teacher Ahmad also emphasise the need for schools and communities to consider these differences in how parents engage with Quranic education and address the barriers to full parental involvement, which can ultimately

enhance students' educational experience. Further research into how these forms of parental involvement influence student outcomes in Quranic schools would enrich understanding of their broader implications for educational and community development.

School administrators highlighted that communication with parents and involving them is essential for promoting their voice within the school community. They stressed that effective communication between teachers and parents helps in integrating parental participation to address various issues related to both the school and their children's academic progress. When parents feel heard and involved, they are more likely to actively engage in school initiatives and support their children's learning at home (Bunnell, 2018). Additionally, inviting parental input ensures that both schools and families share responsibility for the student's success, fostering a more transparent and collaborative educational environment (Alshboul et al., 2021).

8.4. Parents' Perspectives on Muslim Communities and Quranic Education

Although the discussions with participants mainly centred on the family's influence, they also addressed the wider community's role, referring to individuals and groups beyond the Quranic school environment. These references show that education in Quranic schools is both a private family matter and a collective societal responsibility, involving extended networks of community members who influence, support, or critique the schools. This dual focus indicates a layered situation where parents are the main participants in the educational process, while the community shapes the broader cultural and contextual settings within which these institutions operate. Participants also described how Quranic schools actively engage with the wider faith community, fostering connections among parents and other community members. These institutions do not operate in isolation but cooperate with mosques, religious centres, and community groups, bringing together parents, religious leaders, and community members through coordinated events and activities.

In this context, Orchard (2015) suggests that religious education should engage with communities pragmatically, ensuring that educational aims are realistic and attainable. Due to the importance of the Ummah in Muslim life, this communal commitment aligns with the Quranic concept of a universal community dedicated to supporting moral and faith-based guidance. Ahmed's (1975) examination of the Ummah highlights its vital role in Islamic society as a collaborative body responsible for promoting and preserving shared values, including the core principles of Quranic education. The notion of the Ummah as a universal community reflects the idea that all members are interconnected, sharing collective commitments. This includes the development of educational institutions such as Quranic schools, which serve as both social and spiritual anchors within Muslim communities. Ahmed further

explains how the Ummah functions not only as a theoretical idea but also as a practical framework for managing collaborative efforts, particularly in contexts that require nurturing future generations in Islamic teachings.

Parent Salim's experience with his local mosque illustrates how Quranic schools strive to become an integral part of the broader faith community, motivating parents to enrol their children in Quranic education. Salim noted that the mosque regularly distributes leaflets and shares poems to encourage Quranic learning. Moreover, he observed that after the Maghrib prayer, the Imam conducts lessons in the mosque, focusing primarily on the importance of Quranic education and discussing various religious matters. Salim's experience sheds light on the steps Quranic schools and mosques take to integrate themselves into the faith community, creating a supportive environment for Quranic education. However, this approach may face challenges. For example, while such efforts may motivate parents already inclined, they might not effectively reach families with weaker ties to the mosque. This raises new considerations about inclusivity and the broader outreach of Quranic education initiatives. Research shows that engaging diverse parent groups often requires tailored strategies considering different levels of religious commitment, literacy, and cultural practices (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997). Eight participants shared that they had opportunities to participate in and attend events celebrating Quran memorizers, as well as seminars and meetings with religious scholars hosted by mosques, universities, and occasionally in cinemas and other venues.

Most parents in this study highlighted the cultural tradition of honouring children who have memorised the Quran, which goes beyond the Quran school and involves the whole community. These celebrations often include symbolic actions, such as the honoured child riding in a decorated horse-drawn carriage through the streets. Meanwhile, community members show admiration and offer congratulations to the child, their parents, and their teachers. One parent shared videos of her daughter's memorisation celebrations. This community recognition and participation strengthen the child's achievement and reflect the communal pride and value given to Quranic memorisation. Regarding his school's general aims and responsibilities, a school administrator stated that "... the school actively engages in charitable activities and various events, including religious ceremonies and competitions" (Waleed, Administrator).

This highlights the link between schools and the wider community outside of them. These varied efforts by Quranic schools to connect with the broader community help children engage with the faith community at large, making them feel like vital members beyond their school and family connections. Through this engagement, children perceive the faith community as a united whole, sharing common beliefs and values. Quranic schools play a vital role in fostering this unity and shared faith among children, guiding them to understand their place within society.

Role models within the community and successful stories influence parents' decisions regarding Quranic schools for their children. The community's involvement and influence on educational choices are vital factors. This underscores the role of the wider religious community in shaping parental perceptions of sending their children to Quranic schools. Several participants, including Fatima and Samia, highlighted how community role models impacted their decisions about Quranic education for their children. They discussed individuals in their community who exhibited strong dedication to spiritual growth and learning, which encouraged them to prioritise Quranic schooling for their families. One parent, her mother, served as a profound source of inspiration; despite initially being more proficient in French than Arabic, her mother embarked on a journey to learn Arabic and memorise the Quran in her later years, exemplifying a lifelong commitment to spiritual growth and learning. She said:

My mother was over forty when she memorized the Quran. In her youth, she was more proficient in French than Arabic, yet she taught us and exerted efforts for our sake. However, as she aged, she turned to learning Arabic and memorizing the Quran (Fatima, parent).

This example deeply resonated with Fatima, inspiring her to prioritise Quranic education for her children. Likewise, another parent, Samia, found motivation in the success stories of children who attended Quranic schools. Seeing these children excel academically in public schools while demonstrating strong moral values and earning respect within their communities strengthened Samia's faith in the transformative power of Quranic education. These personal stories highlight the influence of positive role models and success stories in shaping parental attitudes towards Quranic schooling.

It is commonly remarked that introducing role models is an intrinsic form of motivating students by inspiring them to put in extra effort and work hard to attain their desired dreams (Aseery, 2023). Regarding the same topic, one of the teachers disclosed the importance of the Quran teacher serving as a role model, particularly after children began attending the Quran school. He explained:

In my view, the first priority for an educator in a Quranic school should be to act as a role model for the young ones entrusted to their care for upbringing and education. In this regard, the Prophet said, 'The best among you are those who learn and teach the Quran.' Consequently, whenever a child hears the words Quran, school, or teacher, an image of a virtuous person with all its connotations instantly comes to their mind, whether it relates to the melodious recitation of the Quran or the understanding formed by observing this educator consistently (Ahmad, teacher).

Ahmad's perspective indicates that a teacher's behaviour shapes a child's lasting view of what it means to lead a Quranic life. This aligns with educational theories on role modelling, such as Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which suggests that children learn behaviours and values by observing and imitating others (Nabavi, 2012). Similarly, research in religious education underscores that a teacher's personal virtue greatly influences students' spiritual growth and ethical development (Halstead, 2004). However, this view also places a significant responsibility on teachers to maintain high standards of personal conduct, which can be difficult. Educators in Quranic schools need to balance this ideal with the practical demands of teaching, highlighting the importance of ongoing personal and professional development.

8.5. Conclusion

This thematic chapter on Parental Support for Quranic Schools examines the interconnected roles of parents, educators, and the wider Muslim community in nurturing children's spiritual and academic development. Throughout the three subthemes, it becomes evident that parental involvement is crucial to the success of Quranic education, encompassing emotional, financial, and practical support tailored to each child's unique needs. Teachers and administrators offer vital insights into the challenges and opportunities of engaging with parents, highlighting the importance of cooperation in addressing diverse student requirements. At the same time, parents demonstrate a deep understanding of societal challenges and a shared responsibility to instil ethical values through Quranic schools. The position of the Muslim community is seen as an essential support system, providing a nurturing environment for spiritual and moral growth. Overall, this chapter highlights the significant interaction and collaboration needed among families, educators, and communities to support Quranic schools and ensure their relevance in confronting contemporary challenges. Such partnerships reinforce the schools' role as vital institutions for safeguarding spiritual and moral values, empowering future generations to navigate an ever-changing world while remaining rooted in their faith.

Chapter 9

Quranic Schools and Fundamentalism

9.1 Introduction

This chapter explores one of the most contentious issues surrounding Quranic schools: their perceived connection to fundamentalism and extremist ideologies. It seeks to counter this claim by analysing the perspectives of participants and highlighting how those directly involved view these schools. Through their voices, two main subthemes emerged. The first, *Challenging Claims of Fundamentalism in Quranic Schools*, shows how these institutions are seen more as spaces for moral and spiritual growth rather than sources of radicalism. Participants demonstrate that stereotypes about Quranic schools often originate from isolated incidents and misrepresentations, rather than a nuanced understanding of their educational and community roles. The second subtheme, *Navigating Challenges in Quranic Education and Future Outlook*, addresses organisational and community obstacles these schools face, along with proposed reforms and future directions to enhance their relevance and effectiveness in serving their communities. By examining these themes, the chapter challenges reductive views linking Quranic schools to fundamentalism and presents a balanced perspective on their challenges and potential in a rapidly changing world.

9.2. Challenging Claims of Fundamentalism in Quranic Schools

Before analysing the participants' perspectives, it is important to define the contentious term "Islamic fundamentalism." In academic discourse, fundamentalism is understood not just as religious conservatism but as a distinct modern phenomenon.

"Fundamentalism" is best understood as a distinctive pattern of religious militancy characterised by self-styled "true believers" seeking to halt the erosion of religious identity, strengthen the boundaries of the religious community, and create viable alternatives to secular institutions and behaviours. In the Islamic context, this often involves selectively retrieving and rigidly applying doctrines, laws, and practices from the Quran and the Sunnah in direct rejection of Western secular modernity and a desire to restore an idealised Islamic order (the Caliphate) (Marty and Appleby, 1993). Islamic fundamentalism refers to movements that promote the reconstruction of society and the state in accordance with laws they interpret from Islamic foundational texts (the Quran and Hadith). It is characterised by a holistic and ideological approach to Islam, viewing it as a complete system governing all aspects of life (*din wa dunya*). These movements are inherently political, seeking to seize state power or significantly influence state policy to implement their vision of Shariah. Key features include a rejection of secular nationalism, a critique of Western cultural influence, and the belief that Muslim societies have declined by straying from "authentic" Islam (Esposito, 1998; 2010).

With this definition in mind, this section examines the perspectives of parents, teachers, administrators, and Imams, who collectively challenge the application of this label to Quranic schools. Their voices

offer a ground-level counter-narrative to the dominant stereotypes that associate these institutions with fundamentalist teaching and extremism, a connection that has sparked considerable debate, especially in the post-9/11 era.

This discussion is grounded in scholarly work that similarly challenges this oversimplified association. Studies by Arif et al. (2017) and Noor (2012), for example, provide important corrections. While noting that some Quranic schools have been linked to extremist beliefs, these researchers emphasise that most of these institutions play essential roles in promoting education and spirituality within their communities. Arif et al. (2017) argue that accusations often originate from isolated incidents, leading to unfair generalisations, while Noor (2012) criticises the post-9/11 simplistic portrayal of Islam that neglects the diverse functions of religious institutions. These scholarly perspectives offer a vital framework for understanding the broader narratives and align with the viewpoints emerging from the current study.

The participants in this research actively engaged with and challenged these common preconceptions. Notably, most parents in the study expressed unfamiliarity with the concept of ‘Islamic fundamentalism’ itself, instead advocating for a deeper understanding and application of Quranic teachings to bring about positive change in individuals’ lives. This unfamiliarity highlights a disconnect between the academic or political label and the lived reality of these communities. One parent, Nadia, revealed that Quranic schools focus on the flexibility and universal relevance of Islamic principles. Sharing a personal anecdote, she emphasised the significant impact of authentic Islamic practice on non-Muslims, highlighting the importance of living in accordance with the Quran's teachings.

There was a story I once heard from a religious scholar I follow who recounted an incident involving a non-Muslim who converted to Islam after hearing the Bismillah (In the name of Allah) prayer before a meal. This man attended a lunch hosted by a Muslim family and noticed that, before starting the meal, the host said: “Bismillah” out loud, but after finishing, he quietly said, “Alhamdulillah” (All praise be to Allah). The guest asked about this practice, and the host explained that at the beginning of the meal, they say “Bismillah” loudly to remind everyone of Allah's remembrance. After the meal, they say “Alhamdulillah” softly to avoid making others uncomfortable, as not everyone has finished their meal yet... (Nadia, parent).

Another parent stated:

I have not heard this term before, but in the past, it was commonly said that anyone who learns the Quran and attends a Quran school is considered an extremist. Nowadays, religious affairs

directorates play a significant role in changing this perception. They have trained male and female religious guides who visit Quranic schools and community institutions on various occasions. They have formed a committee to guide and clarify Quranic education and answer questions (Bilal, parent).

This parent further stated:

These guides also provide lessons to Quran teachers. Occasionally, they offer lessons to the general public in mosques or schools on topics relevant to each occasion. For instance, before Ramadan, they conduct lessons on fasting, what invalidates fasting, and the rewards of fasting. During the Hajj “Pilgrimage” season, they deliver lessons on related subjects, and during the Mawlid al-Nabawi “Prophet’s birthday”, they give lessons about innovation (bid‘ah) and clarify permissible and forbidden behaviours. At the end of each session, there is always a Q&A segment where attendees can ask questions on various topics. Nowadays, thank God, there is no extremism specific to Quranic education. Everything is clear and transparent for parents, which reassures us (Bilal, parent).

These perspectives highlight two vital points: perceptions of Quranic schools and the approach of Islamic practices in promoting interfaith understanding and challenging stereotypes of extremism. Nadia’s anecdote illustrates the modest yet impactful role of Islamic manners in creating a welcoming environment and breaking down barriers between Muslims and non-Muslims, aligning with academic discussions on Islam’s emphasis on manners and inclusivity (Esposito, 2011). Such routines and practices challenge the common stereotype of rigidity often associated with Islamic teachings and demonstrate the adaptable and universal appeal of core values like reverence and remembrance of God. Bilal’s ideas underscore the importance of structured and institutional involvement in renewing Quranic education. The participation of religious leaders in educating both Quran teachers and the wider public ensures that religious teachings are accessible, relevant, and aligned with contemporary social norms.

This point aligns with the findings by Patoni and Rifai (2022), who emphasise the crucial role of religious leaders in Islamic education through approaches such as action, example, advice, and dialogue. Their work highlights how religious leaders not only teach but also actively guide through community involvement and personal exemplification, thereby connecting traditional teachings with modern societal needs. This integrated approach demonstrates the dynamic capacity of religious education to develop while preserving its core principles. However, the practices of religious leaders in Islamic education, as expressed by the study participants and discussed by Patoni and Rifai (2022), are not novel but are rooted in historical Islamic traditions established during the time of the Prophet Muhammad. The Prophet stressed teaching through example and practical demonstration, a method exemplified in the

Hadith recorded in Sahih Bukhari: “Pray as you have seen me praying.” These words illustrate how the Prophet combined instruction with personal action, guiding companions through demonstration (Al Kharidji, 2010). Bilal’s relief regarding the transparency in Quranic schools reflects the positive shift towards making religious learning more accessible and straightforward, a vital step in challenging misconceptions, as highlighted in research on Islamic education reform (Daun & Walford, 2004).

Both narratives show the significance of engagement, whether via interpersonal actions like mentioning God’s name or institutional endeavours, in disassembling the relationship of Quranic schools with extremist ideologies. They recollect the lived experiences of parents and the wider community’s faith in religious systems, indicating how contextual education and real interaction can contest and eventually change adverse stereotypes. When asked about their knowledge of ideologies that advocate for Islamic fundamentalism and how they perceive the role of Quranic schools within this ideological framework. In all cases, Teachers, administrators, and Imams reported that such ideological trends have nothing to do with Quranic schools. For example, one administrator said:

Islam is a creed based on the Quran and the Sunnah, not on any ideological thought. Its ultimate purpose is mercy, as the Quran states: “And We have not sent you, [O Muhammad], except as a mercy to the worlds.” It is a mercy to all of humanity without exception. Being a religion of mercy, Islam rejects any action that may cause corruption on Earth and calls for actions that promote reform and goodness. Hence, it is based on the principle of non-coercion, as mentioned in the Quran. Islam is a religion of love, brotherhood, peace, cooperation, and understanding (Waleed, Administrator).

Waleed offered a broad interpretation of Islam, highlighting its core values. He clarifies that Islam, based on the Quran and Sunnah, is a faith centred on love, brotherhood, cooperation, and promoting goodness, while rejecting extremism and corruption. His remark, especially in the context of the discussion about fundamentalist teachings in Quranic schools, suggests that any form of coercive or extreme behaviour conflicts with the essence of Islam, which, as he states, is a religion of peace and non-violence. Waleed appears to support a balanced understanding of Islam that opposes radicalism and extremism in favour of a more inclusive and reformative approach.

Waleed’s perspective is supported by scholars like Esposito (2011), who states that Islam promotes peace, tolerance, and understanding as outlined in its foundational texts. It aligns with the broader scholarly views that oppose the misuse of religious teachings for extremist purposes. By emphasising these core principles, Waleed’s remarks endorse a form of Quranic education that reflects the universal values of Islam, making it both relevant and accessible. Waleed further stated that,

Islam seeks to protect the five essentials: religion, life, intellect, property, and progeny. Its foundation is based on virtuous ethics, as the Quran states: "Invite to the way of your Lord with wisdom and good instruction and argue with them in a way that is best." Everything conveyed in the Quran and the Prophetic tradition, the two main sources of Islamic law, aims to benefit humanity. However, some individuals, claiming to be Muslims but actually enemies of Islam, misinterpret certain Quranic verses revealed under specific circumstances and urgent events. They distort their meanings to serve their intellectual, ideological, and political agendas, while Islam remains innocent of these abuses (Waleed, administrator).

Waleed emphasised the overarching goals of Islamic law (Maqasid al-Shariah) that promote individual and societal welfare. He also highlighted a significant issue in religious discourse: the manipulation of Quranic excerpts by individuals or groups for political or ideological aims. These distortions undermine Islam's principles of justice and compassion and damage its global reputation. Esposito (2011) explains how religious scriptures are often used to justify extremism, misrepresenting Islam's teachings. Similarly, An-Naim (2008), in *Islam and the Secular State*, discusses how Islamic principles are exploited for authoritative purposes, diverting from the Quran's focus on equity and mercy. The misuse of verses taken out of context remains a major challenge. Saeed (2006) in "Interpreting the Quran: Towards a Contemporary Approach" stresses the importance of linguistic and contextual understanding in Quranic interpretation to challenge rigid interpretations that promote radical ideologies.

This body of research collectively advocates for an informed and accurate approach to understanding Islam's teachings, preserving its principles of justice and compassion. After citing various Quranic verses and Hadiths and explaining all the different aspects and values related to Islam, Waleed emphasised:

Therefore, there is no space for extremism in Islam, nor for any ideology that some manipulate to serve their own interests. Islam is a faith of brotherhood, love, and understanding among all people, and that is what we aim to instil in the hearts of our students at the Quranic school (Waleed, administrator).

Another participant in this study discussed the issue of extremism among students, acknowledging its occasional occurrence. He stated:

Quranic education positively influences a child's personality and beliefs because it stems from the Holy Quran and the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad, which embody high values, noble

principles, and virtuous ethics. However, any observed extremism among certain students is attributed to specific teachers who divert students, serving particular ideological agendas, from the balanced Islamic creed. These teachers may employ extremist curricula that promote hatred, hostility, violence, terrorism, and dangerous deviations in the name of Islam. Islam disapproves of such actions because they do not align with the higher objectives of Islamic law, which is founded on the principle of mercy (Omar, Imam).

Omar's viewpoint highlights a significant issue in Quranic schools: the tension between their potential to cultivate balanced, righteous individuals and the risks posed by ideological misdirection from some teachers. This duality aligns with findings in Islamic pedagogy literature, such as those cited earlier, emphasising the strong influence of teacher ideology and curriculum design on shaping students' beliefs. Quranic education, based on the Holy Quran and the Sunnah, is often seen as a foundation for instilling universal moral values like justice, compassion, and tolerance. Scholars like Al-Ghazali, in "Ihya Ulum al-Din" Revival of Religious Learnings, contend that Islamic education is inherently connected to the spiritual and ethical growth of individuals, aiming to develop a balanced personality that reflects the values of compassion and justice at the heart of Islamic law.

Islamic scholarship consistently rejects extremism, emphasising balance (*wasatiyyah*) as a fundamental principle. The Quran explicitly condemns transgression, as mentioned in the Quran (2:190), "Fight in the cause of Allah those who fight you, but do not transgress limits; for Allah loves not transgressors". This verse shows that acts of hatred and violence are contrary to Islamic principles. Additionally, mercy and moderation are often highlighted in the teachings of the Prophet of Islam, as seen in his statement, "The best of affairs is moderation" (Al-Khattab, 2007). Overall, the misuse of Islamic teachings by some educators reflects a wider issue of ideological manipulation within religious education, as Waleed also describes.

When discussing fundamentalist teachings and their link to Quranic schools, Zayyan shared his thoughts on the term Islamic fundamentalism. He explained it as follows:

Regarding Islamic fundamentalism, to the best of my limited knowledge, it is an ideological label that initially emerged for media purposes. It is not a proper scholarly term and suggests the idea of religious extremists. We see such individuals as having an excessive zeal for religion due to their limited understanding and knowledge. In matters of religion, we strive to present all relevant religious evidence related to any issue. We do not rely solely on one hadith or one piece of evidence, waving it about and declaring it the only valid perspective to follow (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan's perspective on Islamic fundamentalism raises a crucial point that other participants have not previously mentioned: the critique of Islamic fundamentalism as a media-driven, ideological term rather than a legitimate scholarly concept. Research supports this view of the media's role in shaping public perceptions of religious practices (Saeed, 2007). Zayyan noted that such titles often misrepresent religious zeal as extremism, particularly when used to describe people with limited religious knowledge. Winter and Hasan (2016) discussed the nuanced connotations of extremism and fundamentalism, emphasising how these concepts are often conflated in mainstream discourse. The authors argued that this conflation negatively impacts the integration of Muslim communities in Western societies and hampers counter-extremism efforts. They propose a framework to differentiate these terms, independent of their socio-political misinterpretations, defining them as a series of conceptual subsets. Along similar lines, Perry (1999) criticised how the concept of "fundamentalism" is used to describe some Islamic movements, asserting that it often misrepresents them. He demonstrated that the term originally derived from Protestant Christianity, referring to the belief in the Bible's complete infallibility. This idea does not align with Islam, as all Muslims, including critics of specific movements, already regard the Quran as infallible and perfect. Therefore, "Islamic fundamentalism" is misleading. Perry also suggests that the term is often employed to discredit movements rather than describe them objectively. For example, even secular regimes like Turkey's have been labelled "secular fundamentalists," highlighting how inconsistently and politically the term is applied. He argues that such labels often distract from real issues like authoritarianism or intolerance, which are unrelated to "fundamentalism."

Research also supports Zayyan's view of the role of media in shaping public perceptions of religious practices (Saeed, 2007). Zayyan further emphasised the importance of authentic and careful interpretation of religious texts when discussing religious matters, stating:

We present all the hadiths and texts related to a particular matter, then endeavour to understand them by studying all relevant texts, not just one. This is a religious approach. The Quranic method is comprehensive (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan offered an example illustrating scholars' nuanced interpretations of religious texts, referencing Abu Hanifa's view on reciting Al-Fatihah during prayer. His example emphasised the importance of careful study and evidence in religious discourse while also pointing out the risks of ignorance and extremism, as evidenced in historical events in Algeria like the "Black Decade" massacres driven by takfir ideology, as examined in detail in the background chapter of this thesis. He narrated it in this way:

Abu Hanifa regarded the recitation of Al-Fatihah in prayer as obligatory, but not a pillar, meaning that omitting it makes the prayer deficient but not invalid. He argued that the hadith 'There is no

prayer for one who does not recite the Opening of the Book' indicates an incomplete prayer, not an invalid one. He also supported his view by citing another hadith where a companion described the Prophet's prayer, stating that the Prophet "made takbir, then recited whatever was easy for him from the Quran," without mentioning Al-Fatihah. It would have been explicitly mentioned if Al-Fatihah were an obligatory recitation, similar to the Takbir al-Ihram. His interpretation highlights the importance of carefully examining all evidence rather than relying solely on a single hadith. If one hadith were taken as the only truth, it could lead to excessive religiosity, as demonstrated by the 'Black Decade' massacres caused by ignorance, extremism, and takfir (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan's ideas exemplify Islamic jurisprudence, especially through scholars' interpretations. The reference to the Prophet's practice of reciting "whatever was easy for him" further supports Abu Hanifa's view that there is flexibility in how prayer is performed. This highlights the importance of not examining a single narration or hadith in isolation, as this can result in narrow, potentially extreme interpretations of religious practices. Lastly, Zayyan's linking of this religious approach to real-world consequences, such as the massacres during the Black Decade in Algeria, emphasises the dangers of ignorance and extremism. The "Black Decade" is a notable example showing how selective readings of religious texts, driven by ignorance, can lead to disastrous outcomes.

Essentially, Zayyan's views on Islamic fundamentalism highlighted that the term itself, frequently used in media discourse, does not accurately reflect a specific scholarly school of thought within Islam. Instead, it is associated with extremism and underscores the need for a thorough understanding of religious texts and methodologies in religious discussions. Zayyan was also asked about the idea that Quranic school students tend to extremism, but he strongly rejected this, attributing such claims to prejudice against Islam. He stressed that Quranic school graduates often become exemplary members of society with good morals. He stated:

Those who adopt these ideas and perceptions are often among those who harbour hostility towards the religion. Many of these critical voices come from communists, secularists, and other opponents of this religion and the Quran. We should not pay much attention to them; instead, we respond with kind words. Quranic schools today graduate some of the best members of society. I have never heard in my life that anyone from the people of the Quran has stolen, committed adultery, or done anything of that sort. It might happen occasionally, but it is rare compared to others (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan's view reflects a shared belief among advocates of Quranic schools that these institutions are crucial in instilling moral values and addressing perceived ethical shortcomings in society. His perspective aligns with research by Christopher and Revell (2024), which examines how the Quran and Hadith shape morality, emphasising qualities such as patience, honesty, respect, and forgiveness. Studies indicate that religious education positively affects societal contributions and ethical behaviour by embedding these principles in young people, supporting Zayyan's assertions and aligning his claims with scholarly evidence.

However, it is also necessary to acknowledge that no system is resistant to defects, and infrequent lapses in moral behaviour, even within religious settings, should not be overlooked, as highlighted in broader discussions about educational outcomes and ethical development (e.g., Tritter, 2014). Therefore, while Quranic schools may contribute to the cultivation of ethical principles, it is essential to address the complexity of moral behaviour in society, which is shaped by various factors beyond formal education.

Discussing the same issue, another participant highlighted the unfairness of blaming Quranic schools for fostering extremist beliefs when similar situations could arise elsewhere as well. He recounted it in this way:

Anyone who claims that Quranic schools or the people of the Quran hold extremist ideas has no real connection to the Quran or its followers. These ideas may have been borrowed from others, perhaps from individuals in certain circles who were allowed to occupy pulpits in some way. They might have planted their extremist ideas there. We cannot definitively say that such extremist ideas do not exist, but they are not as some perceive them to be. A Quran teacher might share their personal ideas with students, which can indeed happen. However, these ideas might also be spread by a teacher in regular schools or even by a factory worker among colleagues. The question is, why is this particular group targeted, even though it is the least harmful? SubhanAllah! (Glory be to God!) (Abdelghani, teacher).

Abdelghani's argument highlights the important debate about the association of Quranic schools and their educators with extremist ideologies. His claim challenges a common perception by emphasising that these schools and their students are often unfairly labelled, with the true sources of extremism stemming from external ideological influences. Abdelghani's perspective also reflects the insights of Al-Shami and Al-Qudah (2020), who argue that the lack of proper religious education rooted in the Quran leaves students susceptible to distorted and deviant ideas. Their study advocates for a shift in educational methods, from rote memorisation to critical thinking based on Quranic values, to challenge false ideologies and encourage tolerance, justice, and coexistence. This discussion highlights the need

to defend Quranic education from unjust stigma by addressing the real origins of extremism, which typically lie outside these institutions.

Continuing his narrative, Abdelghani emphasised the inclusive atmosphere of Quranic schools, where students from diverse ideological backgrounds come to study the Quran. He said:

Quranic students are adaptable and engage with everyone, unlike certain groups such as the Salafi movement, the Muslim Brotherhood, or other Islamic currents that follow specific beliefs, methods, scholars, and distinctions. Conversely, the Quran is vast and inclusive of all. For example, in our school, Salafis send their children to study the Quran with us, as do the Brotherhood and the Jazirists. People from all backgrounds come to learn the Quran here. Such an accusation, when directed at Quranic schools and their students, is far from reality. I believe only a few hold such perceptions, and if they do, they may be linked to particular ideological currents (Abdelghani, teacher).

Abdelghani's argument continued, discussing the essential debates about the association of Quranic schools and their educators with extremist ideologies by emphasising their diversity and inclusiveness. His observation that students from various Islamic currents, including Salafis, the Muslim Brotherhood, and others, study the Quran at Quranic schools demonstrates the non-partisan and inclusive nature of Quranic instruction. His claim challenges a commonly held perception by emphasising that these schools and their followers are often unfairly stigmatized, with the true roots of extremism lying in external ideological influences.

Another participant's experience with Quranic schools illustrates how these schools are solely focused on teaching the Quran and that he is not familiar with Islamic fundamentalism. He argued:

I must admit that I am not familiar with this specific term, but generally speaking, Islam strongly emphasises the importance of adhering to the Quran and the Sunnah. Quranic schools indeed employ a teaching method based on memorisation, which helps improve linguistic performance by thoroughly instructing and correcting learners' mistakes before they memorise the Quran. This aids in proper pronunciation during recitation and enables learners to perform well. Additionally, Quranic schools focus on developing good reading and listening skills, enabling learners to read the Quranic verses correctly, leading to comprehensive linguistic improvement (Ahmad, teacher).

Ahmad's response to their unfamiliarity with the term fundamentalism redirects the discussion towards describing Quranic schools' structured programmes, reflecting his intention to emphasise their positive

educational framework rather than engage directly with ideological debates. His focus on the schools' role in fostering linguistic and cognitive skills suggests a shift away from the idea of extremism towards demonstrating the institutions' constructive contributions. This approach thus supports the importance of evaluating Quranic schools based on their educational merits rather than preconceived biases.

To sum up the participants' views on Quranic schools and fundamentalism, Bandyopadhyay's (2023) work, "Fundamentalism, Extremism versus Islamic Enlightenment: A Discourse," provides a clear summary of the arguments made by the participants. His critique contrasts the historical, intellectual legacy of Islam with the modern misrepresentation of Islamic education, echoing the sentiments shared by participants who highlighted the role of Quranic schools in fostering moral and intellectual development. Bandyopadhyay emphasises the "golden period of enlightenment" in medieval Islam, when scholars made important contributions to science, philosophy, and the arts, motivated by the Quranic value of knowledge and the principle of "jihad bil Qalam" (struggle by pen and knowledge). This idea resonates with the participants' views, who stressed that Quranic schools are institutions rooted in the pursuit of knowledge rather than centres of radicalism. By explaining how extremist groups have strayed from the rich intellectual traditions of Islam, Bandyopadhyay's analysis reinforces the participants' argument that Quranic schools are dedicated to nurturing a balanced, holistic approach to learning, preserving the true spirit of Islamic education and enlightenment.

9.3. Navigating Challenges in Quranic Education and Future Outlook

Quranic schools are considered a vital part of Religious Education, nurturing students in faith, ethics, and personal development. Their role in shaping learners' moral and intellectual foundations underscores their ongoing importance in Muslim communities. However, the changing cultural and social environment requires examining how these schools remain relevant while maintaining their religious mission. Insights from participants highlight diverse views on the challenges and hopes of Quranic education. Considering their experiences and opinions is essential for developing ways to support these institutions and ensure they continue to have a transformative impact on students' lives. This discussion explores these perspectives, offering insight into the current state of Quranic schools in Algeria and their future prospects.

The perspectives of participants in this study, including parents, teachers, and Imams, offer valuable insights into the real experiences of Quranic schools in Algeria. One participant shared the following view:

From my perspective, the future of Quranic schools at both local and broader levels seems promising. These schools have expanded beyond their traditional focus on Quran memorisation and recitation rules. Today, they provide a wide range of educational programmes similar to those taught in the preparatory sections of other schools. This change has heightened parents' interest in enrolling their children in Quranic schools, even though other options are available (Boubakr, parent).

Similarly, another parent expressed the increased number of these schools and parents' willingness to send their children to these schools:

There is a notable rise in the number of Quranic schools, with some kindergartens converting into Quran memorization schools during the summer for a small fee. Competition in memorisation has grown, and schools and kindergartens organise contests. Parents are very aware of the importance of Quran education, especially as children are at risk of straying at a young age. Often, parents are eager to send their children to Quran schools to shield them from societal temptations. Children learn what is lawful and unlawful from the Quran and also benefit from the lessons and stories, not to mention the admirable efforts of the teachers (Amal, Parent).

Boubakr and Amal are optimistic about the future of Quranic schools. Boubakr notes that these schools now extend beyond traditional Quranic teachings, offering preparatory-level programmes similar to those in public schools. This shift has made Quranic schools more appealing to parents who wish to combine religious and general education for their children. It indicates that these schools are evolving to remain relevant, balancing moral education with academics, which fosters trust among families. At the same time, this raises questions about how they can maintain this balance without compromising their core mission. Halstead (2004) suggests that balancing religious and general education can sometimes lead to disputes over priorities. Boubakr's optimism also does not fully address challenges such as limited resources or resistance from those who prefer the traditional approach. Amal emphasises a growing trend in Quranic education, with a rise in the number of institutions and summer programmes dedicated to Quran memorisation, many of which include competitive elements. Parents' awareness of the risks of societal deviation results in a high demand for Quranic schools as a protective measure. Boubakr further stated:

The appeal of Quranic schools extends beyond urban areas; even in rural regions, parents are eager to send their children to these institutions at a very young age, starting from three years old. Whether they are in mosques, religious centres, or other establishments, these schools aim to teach Quran memorisation. Some parents even see these schools as a viable alternative to mainstream education (Boubakr, parent).

Boubakr's observation underscores the widespread demand for Quranic schools in both urban and rural areas, reflecting a broader trend discussed by Boyle (2014) in her work "Between Secular Public Schools and Quranic Private Schools: The Growing Educational Presence of Malian Medersas." Boyle explores the increasing role of Quranic and Islamic educational institutions, noting the diversity in regional terminology used to describe them. Her study emphasises the expansion of Quranic schools, including the term "medersa" within Mali and the wider West African region. Rural parents' willingness to enrol their children in these institutions at a young age highlights the cultural and religious significance placed on Quranic education.

Viewing these institutions as alternatives to mainstream education suggests confidence in their ability to provide moral and academic foundations. However, this dependence raises important issues. Are these schools in Algeria sufficiently resourced to meet the broader educational needs of students, especially in rural areas? Further research is necessary on the issue of Quranic schools fulfilling students' wider educational requirements, particularly for those attending only these schools without attending public schools. The long-term implications of this educational model, especially for children's prospects, remain unclear and warrant further investigation. In this regard, Baba (2008) discusses how Quranic schools, particularly in northern Nigeria, are being considered as an alternative programme to supplement existing educational systems. This study examines how integrating Quranic schools into formal education through curriculum reform could address challenges related to funding, resource distribution, and policy support. The aim is to expand these schools' scope to better meet pupils' educational needs while maintaining a balance between religious teachings and basic education. Baba's research underscores the importance of sustaining these schools to ensure they can contribute effectively to the Education for All (EFA) objectives.

In their study, Bin Baba et al. (2018) examine the development of Islamic Integrated Education (IIE) in Malaysia, tracing its roots back to the 14th century and its modern integration of Islamic principles with science and technology. They describe how Malaysia's dual educational system, which once separated Islamic and secular education, has evolved into a more unified model. This system aims to prepare students for both spiritual and worldly goals, although the authors emphasise the need for further improvements in institutional resources and teacher training. Similarly, Rashed (2021) advocates for a holistic educational system that combines aqli (rational) and naqli (traditional) knowledge to foster a "Quranic generation" focused on spiritual growth and societal contribution.

All the studies mentioned above emphasise the importance of modernising Quranic education to ensure it aligns with global standards while preserving its spiritual core. Developing mixed models that

integrate secular education into Quranic schooling shows promise but requires significant investment and policy backing. It could serve as a model for other regions like Algeria.

Building on parents' positive outlook regarding the future of Quranic schools, another parent offers a different perspective by highlighting Algeria's notable achievements in memorising the Quran and expressing her confidence in these institutions' continued success. She said:

Over the past three years, we have witnessed numerous Quranic memorization achievements, with many people becoming Hafiz (those who have memorized the Quran) from all corners of Algeria. Based on what I observe on social media, in the media, and in the society I live in, I can confidently say there is a promising future for Quranic schools. We pray to Allah for continuous success and prosperity for Quranic schools (Samia, parent).

While participants highlighted the bright future of Quranic schools, particularly their growing popularity among Algerian parents, their optimism is tempered by an acknowledgement of existing challenges. The evolving societal context and changing educational expectations have introduced new pressures that Quranic schools must address to maintain their transformative impact. The following presents the participants' perspectives on these issues, providing insights into areas where Quranic schools could strengthen their role in education and community development. For example, one participant stated:

I believe the government and local authorities are playing a reasonable role in regulating Quranic schools today. However, in my view, there is still a gap when it comes to ensuring the quality of education they offer. Quranic schools have not received the same level of attention as formal schools. Most are affiliated with mosques or charitable organisations, and they often lack adequate facilities, resources for students, and proper copies of the Quran for memorisation. Authorities contribute little or nothing to these aspects in some mosques. Most support comes from donors or the students' own contributions. This is my opinion based on what I observe in my area, and Allah knows best about Quranic schools in other states (Wahiba, parent).

Wahiba's perspective highlights the gap between the increasing number of Quranic schools and the resources necessary to offer quality education. Despite some regulatory efforts by authorities, these schools continue to suffer from inadequate facilities and resources, heavily relying on donors or contributions from students and their families. Research shows that many religious schools face similar issues, with limited public investment hindering their ability to deliver comprehensive education

(Salako & Abiodun, 2019). This perspective underscores the need for sufficient government support to address these disparities while preserving the schools' religious focus. Similarly, another parent stated,

In my opinion, to ensure the quality of education, it is necessary to regulate Quranic schools and establish a specific system for them. We need the government's involvement in organising and developing Quranic schools. Relying solely on the mosque might not be sufficient, especially when many employees are volunteers without monthly salaries. Despite the proficiency and excellence of Quranic teachers, the schools require additional support to achieve their goals. Some essential aspects that need to be addressed in the schools include providing proper restroom facilities, places for ablution, and adequate air conditioning. Moreover, even though they are volunteers, Quranic teachers also need special care and attention from the government to enable them to perform their duties optimally. Giving them a monthly income would benefit (Fatima, parent).

This perspective highlights the need for a standardised system across all Quranic schools in Algeria, along with more structured regulation and government support to ensure quality education. It notes that relying solely on mosques, especially with limited resources and volunteer educators, is insufficient to meet the schools' educational needs. Volunteer-based educational institutions may encounter challenges such as inadequate funding and facilities. Addressing these gaps—like providing proper infrastructure and paying teachers—is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of Quranic education. Although the contexts of Muslim faith schools in minority (UK) and majority (Algeria) Muslim societies differ considerably, both face similar challenges.

Research by Hammad and Shah (2019) on Leading faith schools in a secular society: Challenges facing head teachers of Muslim schools in the United Kingdom highlights issues such as financial constraints, inadequate facilities, and difficulty recruiting qualified educators. These challenges are mirrored in Algeria's Quranic schools, where reliance on mosque-based setups and volunteer educators in some schools creates limitations in maintaining quality instruction. This comparison shows that both types of schools, whether in countries where Muslims are a minority or where Islam is the dominant faith, face similar challenges in achieving their goals without sufficient funding, modern infrastructure, and professional teaching staff. This shared reality underscores the universal need for support and systematic investment to improve the impact of faith-based education, regardless of societal context.

Another participant's perspective was as follows,

Quranic schools face substantial challenges due to globalization and modern education methods. These schools have two options: either to fade away with the passage of time or to adopt new approaches that align with the modern era while safeguarding their traditional values. Finding a balance between modern techniques and preserving the traditional identity of Quranic schools is crucial. This may involve incorporating modern resources such as digital tools, visual presentations, and contemporary teaching materials, among others, while maintaining the core of the school's heritage. By doing so, Quranic schools can remain relevant and continue to offer their benefits to families who choose this form of education (Ahmad, teacher).

Ahmad's perspective on modernising Quranic schools stresses the importance of incorporating modern tools such as digital resources and interactive teaching methods to maintain their relevance. This aligns with studies worldwide demonstrating the benefits of technology in enhancing Islamic education, such as 'Designing an Online Quranic Recitation (Qirā'āt) Framework Using Massive Open Online Courses' by Wahid et al. (2019), which explores how faith schools in Indonesia approach modernisation by balancing religious instruction with general subjects and digital literacy. This approach preserves Islamic heritage while preparing students for contemporary issues. Likewise, 'New Trends in Qur'ānic Studies: Text, Context, and Interpretation' by Sirry (2019) highlights recent progress in Qur'ānic studies, including thematic and methodological innovations. It emphasises the need to adapt educational practices to modern contexts while safeguarding the textual and interpretive integrity of the Qur'an, thereby providing a broader framework for reimagining Quranic education to suit modern pedagogical approaches.

In the face of recognised opportunities and challenges, Zayyan, as an administrator, remains optimistic about the future of Quranic schools, believing in their potential for growth and impact both locally and beyond. He shared his perspective as follows:

I see a promising future for Quranic schools locally, nationally, and globally. This outlook is rooted in optimism, as it is often said that optimistic individuals tend to find goodness. My optimism stems from the belief that we are on the correct path. Although there are some challenges and unresolved issues, interest in Quranic schools is growing both in number and quality. A variety of courses and diverse activities are being introduced, even though there is still room for improvement. This field has a bright future due to increasing public interest, advancements in teaching methods, and Algeria's respectable rankings in numerous international competitions (Zayyan, teacher).

Teacher Zayyan further emphasised the remarkable achievements of Algerian students in Quranic competitions. He noted:

Although Egypt is considered a stronghold of the Quran, Algeria has excelled in various Quranic competitions, securing top positions multiple times. This achievement has also been seen in Jordan, Sudan, Saudi Arabia, Mali, and more. However, despite these successes, Quranic education still needs ongoing efforts and improvements (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan sees Algerians' success in international Quranic contests as a symbol of a bright future for Quranic schools and their increasing importance, as well as an indication of broader recognition of Algeria's improvement in this area. His perspective also subtly highlights the efforts of students, teachers, and families involved in the process. Adam's (2015) study supports this view by showing how Quranic recitation competitions serve as platforms to showcase students' excellence, strengthen social cohesion, and raise the profile of Quranic education internationally. Zayyan's optimistic outlook aligns with Adam's findings, as both see these competitions as more than just displays of skill but as evidence of the ongoing relevance and transformative potential of Quranic education systems. Furthermore, Zayyan's perspective suggests that although notable improvements have been made, ongoing efforts are necessary to ensure these institutions continue to meet educational and developmental needs, reflecting the broader challenge of balancing tradition with modernisation in educational establishments.

Additionally, Zayyan highlighted an important issue: the complex relationship between financial incentives and the pursuit of knowledge, especially in the context of his personal experiences and observations within the educational landscape of Algeria. Sharing his experience, he recounted:

In the past, it was said that "Money is the driving force behind the pursuit of knowledge." For instance, how did I learn? I learned through financial incentives. When I used to go to Egypt and stay there for several months, I went on four educational trips to Egypt to learn and acquire knowledge. However, when I go there, I present my vacation without pay. Who will provide for my wife and children in my absence as a state employee? I support them financially so they can live while I am away. Additionally, when I arrive in Egypt, I must pay for rent and transportation. The sheikh dedicates his time to me. I used to learn from 11 AM to 11 PM, and the sheikh from whom I learned had no other job besides teaching me. So, I also pay him his fee (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan emphasised the importance of money in the success of religious education. He continues stating that,

As you can see, knowledge is driven by money. Money is essential, and this poses a challenge in Algeria. Investment is mainly focused on material things, like building lavish Quranic schools. However, within these schools, there are often unqualified mentors. They bring in a teacher from anywhere, as long as they have the title of teacher. Then, they pay them less than they deserve (Zayyan, teacher).

Zayyan emphasises the disparity between material investments in infrastructure and the neglect of human capital, particularly the quality of teachers. In Zayyan's view, teacher underpayment signifies another systemic problem that weakens the quality of education. Research consistently demonstrates that teacher motivation and effectiveness are closely connected to adequate pay and professional development (e.g., Crehan, 2016; Han & Yin, 2016).

Further perspectives highlighted the government's role in regulating and ensuring the quality of education in Quranic schools. Omar emphasised the importance of integrating these schools into the broader educational framework in Algeria.

It is vital to continue efforts by integrating these schools into the broader educational landscape and real-world scenarios. The educational component within Quranic schools is a key part of the overall educational system, and it is connected with other subsystems, such as mainstream schools and families, to effectively nurture and educate the younger generation (Omar, Imam).

Essam recognises the positive measures implemented by the government in setting up Quranic institutions. He said,

The Algerian state is progressing well. It has launched reforms in Quranic education, including establishing Quranic institutions. These institutions act as platforms to promote accurate recitation and spread specialised Quranic knowledge, covering Quranic sciences. Praise be to God, our country is experiencing an intellectual and Quranic revival. Scientific courses and Quranic programmes are now plentiful, though I have a few comments on them. Not all of these initiatives demonstrate consistent mastery and thoroughness; some areas need more targeted attention (Essam, teacher).

The observation from Essam and Zayyan's perspectives highlights a regional divide in Algeria concerning the development of Quranic education. Both groups from the northern part of the country acknowledge tangible improvements, such as the establishment of institutions and increased intellectual

focus. Conversely, most participants from the southern regions report more limited resources, indicating that state support may be more concentrated in the north due to higher population density and demand. This difference suggests the need for a fairer distribution of resources and attention to ensure all regions benefit equally from advancements in Quranic education.

9.4. Conclusion

Quranic schools are vital to Algeria's educational and spiritual systems, helping children develop moral, intellectual, and spiritual skills. These schools face a pivotal moment, striving to modernise their traditional curriculum to meet current demands. Their development varies, with differences in teaching methods, infrastructure, and teacher qualifications. Some schools have adopted modern resources and employed qualified educators, while others face resource shortages and depend on outdated approaches. Addressing these challenges requires updating teaching strategies, integrating technology, enhancing teacher training, and boosting funding and community involvement. Participants in the study also emphasised the need for a standardised curriculum to ensure quality and uniformity across all Quranic schools in Algeria. Concerning claims of promoting extremist ideologies, the chapter reports that participants expressed confidence in the safety of Quranic schools from extremist teachings and fundamentalism, indicating that these schools offer secure environments focused on ethical and spiritual education, thereby countering extremist ideologies rather than promoting them. These opinions reflect Algerians' trust in these schools as safe spaces to introduce children to the Ummah.

Chapter 10

General Conclusion

This study conducted a thorough examination of Muslim parents' views on the purpose and importance of Quranic schools within Algeria's socio-cultural and religious setting. Using a phenomenological approach, the research explored the lived experiences of parents, Quran teachers, and other stakeholders directly involved with these institutions, providing a detailed understanding of their role in children's moral, cultural, and spiritual growth. Through 25 semi-structured individual interviews and analysis using Colaizzi's seven-stage phenomenological method, the study uncovered significant insights into the motivations, expectations, challenges, and aims underlying Quranic education in Algeria.

The study started by placing Quranic schools within Algeria's historical and cultural context. The initial chapters of the thesis outlined Algeria's background, the Algerian family, and Islamic identity shaped by colonial resistance and post-independence modernisation. This background shows that Quranic schools are not just educational institutions but vital keepers of Algeria's religious and national values.

The historical growth of Quranic schools laid the foundation for interpreting the views and understandings of their participants. From their essential role in Islamic education during colonial times to their contemporary functions, it is evident that they have remained vital conduits of moral and religious education. The research examined the cognitive and spiritual aspects of faith formation within Quranic schools by referencing relevant concepts from the discourse on children's faith development. The study illustrated how Quranic education is connected with faith growth, schooling, and cognition in shaping students' moral and spiritual perspectives.

Regarding the methodology, the research employed a qualitative approach to explore personal and contextualised views. The phenomenological method facilitated an in-depth examination of the subjective experiences of stakeholders, particularly Muslim parents. Colaizzi's method ensured analytical rigour and captured the essence of participants' experiences, providing authentic insights into the lived realities of Quranic education. Ethical considerations, including confidentiality and respect for participants' autonomy, enhanced the credibility and integrity of the study. These institutions in Algeria are viewed as essential in fostering both national and Islamic identities for children. Algerian parents and other participants involved in these schools, such as Quran teachers, administrators, and imams, see these institutions as bridges linking Algeria's cultural heritage with the universal principles of Islam. By instilling a sense of fulfilment in both national and religious identities, Quranic schools prepare children to be active members of their local and global communities. This dual development of identity is particularly important in a world where globalisation challenges traditional cultural and religious foundations, highlighting the relevance of Quranic schools as guardians of faith formation and cultural heritage continuity.

The second subtheme under the broad theme of the purpose of Quranic schools in Algeria was these schools' contributions to the moral and faith development of Algerian children. Quranic teachings provide the basis for instilling virtues such as patience and respect. These institutions offer a framework for children to make ethical decisions in their daily lives when dealing with parents, teachers, peers, or members of the wider community, grounded in their faith and strengthening their personal and spiritual stability. By aligning moral education with Quranic values, these institutions encompass a well-rounded approach to character development that supports holistic personal growth.

The third subtheme—a key insight from this study related to Quranic schools and the shaping of children’s behaviour—showed how these schools act as sources of behavioural role models, tackling common issues and reinforcing discipline. This includes instilling positive habits that affect their interactions at home, in school, and within the wider community. Together, these findings within the first thematic theme present Quranic schools as comprehensive educational environments that nurture children’s identity, values, and conduct, effectively preparing them for a life that harmonises spiritual belief with societal involvement.

The study data also showed that the participants shared an understanding that Quranic schools play an important role in the religious and cultural socialisation of Algerian children, with the process being influenced by several factors. The curriculum of these schools, while generally aimed at imparting Quranic education and Islamic values, varies across institutions, providing different educational experiences. Some schools focus solely on memorisation and recitation, while others incorporate additional aspects into the learning process. Despite these differences, the overall aim remains the same: to foster a connection to faith and ensure that students are well-equipped to live in their communities according to Islamic principles. The organisation and operation of Quranic schools also shape the learning environment and contribute to children's religious and cultural socialisation. While some schools operate within more formal structures with strict schedules, others are more flexible. This organisational difference affects the effectiveness of religious socialisation, influencing how students internalise teachings and develop connections with their faith.

Furthermore, the negotiation of pedagogical authority in Quranic schools is a vital process for cultural and religious socialisation. As the data show, teachers' approaches range from strict disciplinarianism to the nurturing model of the Murabbi, each justifying its authority in different ways—whether through enforcing spiritual discipline or offering compassionate, fraternal guidance. These are not merely variations in teaching style but reflect competing philosophies on how to impart Islamic values and shape identity. Ultimately, it is through these daily negotiations of authority in the classroom that students learn to internalise religious principles, developing a resilient cultural and religious identity that prepares them for a life rooted in their faith. Significantly, Quranic schools play a crucial role in the religious and cultural socialisation of children, shaping them into responsible, spiritually engaged individuals through their curriculum, school structures, and mentorship styles—all aimed at preparing them for a life anchored in Islamic values and principles, despite methodological differences across institutions.

The third chapter, which presents the study findings on parental support for Quranic Schools, highlights the interconnected roles of parents, educators, and the wider Muslim community in fostering children’s spiritual and academic development. Through the three subthemes emerging from the data analysis, the

study demonstrates that parental involvement is crucial to the success of their children's Quranic education, encompassing emotional, financial, and practical support tailored to individual needs. Teachers and administrators provided detailed insights into the challenges and opportunities of engaging with parents, emphasising the importance of cooperation in managing diverse student requirements. Meanwhile, insights from parents revealed a deep understanding of societal challenges and a shared responsibility to instil ethical values through Quranic schools. The Muslim community's role acts as a central supportive context, contributing to and offering an environment conducive to spiritual and moral growth. This thematic chapter addresses the reflective interaction and collaboration needed among families, educators, and communities to support Quranic schools and ensure their relevance in facing contemporary challenges. Such partnerships strengthen the schools' role as vital institutions for preserving spiritual and moral values, empowering future generations to navigate a constantly changing world while remaining rooted in their faith.

This study's fourth and final chapter, 'Quranic Schools and Fundamentalism,' revealed that Quranic schools are at a crossroads, trying to harmonise their traditional education with modern needs. Their development varies, with differences in teaching methods, infrastructure, and teacher qualifications. Some schools have benefited from modern resources and qualified staff, while others face resource shortages and rely on outdated methods. To secure a bright future for Quranic schools, it is essential to modernise teaching strategies, incorporate technology, enhance teacher training, and boost funding and community involvement. The study also highlighted the need for a standardised curriculum to ensure quality and consistency across all Quranic schools in Algeria.

In response to claims of promoting fundamentalist teachings and extremist ideologies, the findings described how participants expressed confidence in the safety of Quranic schools from extremist influences and fundamentalism. They revealed that Quranic schools provide secure environments for their children, focusing on ethical and spiritual education, and countering extremist ideologies rather than endorsing them. These views reflect Algerians' trust in these schools as reliable settings for introducing children to the Ummah by teaching them their religion.

Ultimately, this study's results shed light on Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose of Quranic schools, demonstrating their multiple roles within the community. Parents see these institutions as essential for preserving Islamic identity, imparting moral values, and fostering a strong sense of spirituality and community belonging in their children. Through Quranic education, parents aim to instil a balance of spiritual knowledge and practical life skills, ensuring children develop as well-rounded individuals capable of navigating modern societal challenges while maintaining their faith and cultural roots. Furthermore, the findings highlight the role of the Ummah in advancing Quranic education and shaping children's educational experiences. The Ummah acts as a dynamic symbol of collective effort

and Islamic unity, working to preserve religious heritage and provide an Islamic upbringing for children. This collective sense of responsibility underscores how Quranic schools serve as a bridge between faith, education, and cultural identity, reinforcing the community's shared commitment to nurturing future generations rooted in Islamic values.

While the findings emphasise the significant role of Quranic schools in Algeria's religious and socio-cultural setting, they also highlight the need for adaptation and structured improvements to address modern educational challenges. Developing and reforming Quranic schools are essential to overcome current deficiencies. Teacher training programmes should focus on pedagogical diversity and subject expertise to enhance teaching quality. Practical and efficient management techniques, adequate funding, and stronger cooperation between schools, parents, and communities would foster shared responsibility for improving children's Quranic education.

Traditional Quranic schools, which mainly rely on rote memorisation, could benefit from incorporating modern teaching methods such as interactive Tafsir discussions, inquiry-based learning, and engaging Tajweed sessions. Comparative research is necessary to understand how these methods affect students' cognitive and spiritual growth, providing insights into balancing tradition with today's educational demands. These changes would enable Quranic schools to maintain their traditional standards while meeting the changing needs of modern society.

Furthermore, further research is necessary to explore the outcomes of Quranic school education when it is the only form of education students receive, especially in how they handle broader social and academic skills. The long-term effects on students' career opportunities and societal roles are still uncertain, highlighting the importance of conducting longitudinal studies.

A key area for further research is family-led efforts to nurture faith at home. The current study findings addressed this aspect by highlighting parents' efforts to foster an environment suitable for religious learning. Such family endeavours warrant more focused research and analysis to gain comprehensive insights into the role of family, especially parents, in their children's faith development.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Research Informed Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives on the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study.

Ethics Approval Number: 2022-XXX-XXX

Investigator name: Zeyneb Bouzaida

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

You have been invited to take part in a phenomenological study on Algerian Muslim Parents' Conceptions of the Purpose of Qur'anic Schools. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and I need not answer any questions, and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of personal information I may provide for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice digitally recorded.	

I freely agree to participate in this study.	
--	--

Signatures:

Name of participant:

Name of researcher:

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

Appendix 2. Participants' Information Sheet for Parents

School of Education and Social Sciences

Participants' Information Sheet for Parents

Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives on the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study.

You are invited to participate in a research study. Before you decide, it is important that you understand why the study is being done and what it involves. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if anything is unclear or if you want more information. Take your time to decide whether you want to take part in the study or not.

Who am I?

My name is Bouzaida Zeyneb. I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, and the Algerian government funds me. I am from the School of Education and Social Sciences and am currently preparing for a PhD on Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives of the purpose of Quranic schools.

What is the purpose of this study?

This study aims to investigate the views of Algerian Muslim parents on the purpose of Quranic schools in Algeria's socio-cultural and religious context.

Why have I been chosen?

This study investigates Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose of Quranic schools. In doing so, you, the parents, were selected as the appropriate source with the most suitable data to conduct this research.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to participate, you will be given this information sheet to keep and asked to sign a consent form. You can skip any questions you do not wish to answer, and you are free to drop out during the interview or at any time without giving a reason.

After accepting this invitation, what are your rights as a research participant?

If you agree to participate in my research, you must know that:

- Your participation is voluntary.
- You can withdraw at any stage of the fieldwork.
- No justifications are required for your withdrawal.
- You can deny answering any question(s) you do not want to respond about it (them).
- If you do not understand any question, ask for further clarification.
- If you feel unable to continue the interview, you can ask to end it.
- An audio recording is used during the interview. This allows me to focus on the interview rather than taking notes. The audio recording will be deleted after the transcription.
- If you have any issues, you can ask to stop the recording.
- The consent form will be sent to you.
- You need to sign the consent form.
- Decide whether you want to use your real name or a pseudonym of your choice.
- You can request a report on the results of this research.

What will I do if I take part?

If you agree to participate in my research, you will participate in an interview of approximately 12 questions. The expected duration of the face-to-face interview is between 40 minutes and 1 hour. The interviews will be conducted in Arabic. The first questions will be about your personal details. Next, we will talk about Quranic schools and your idea of their purpose in contemporary Algerian society. We will talk about their purpose, characteristics, benefits and ethos. We will also discuss the reasons why Algerian Muslim parents prefer to send their children to Quranic schools. After that, we will develop and discuss other issues, such as the challenges faced by these schools, and we will end with issues related to the public perception of Quranic schools locally and internationally.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

From an ethical perspective, in the field of educational research, the researcher must prioritise the psychological and physical safety, comfort and benefit of the participants. In my research, I am careful to avoid issues that might cause stress to my participants.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

By participating in this study, you will help express Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives about the purpose of Quranic schools and help the Algerian authorities solve the current problems related to these institutions. Through your thoughts and experiences, we can gain valuable insights into the purpose and characteristics of Quranic schools in Algeria and address the current issues related to Quranic schools and the children who attend them. As a parent, your cooperation will be of great importance.

What will happen to the information I provide?

All data collected as part of this study will be handled in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the UWS Code of Ethics. Your personal data will be processed for the purposes stated in this notice. The legal basis for processing your personal data is your consent. Your personal data will be processed for as long as it is necessary for the research project. We will do our best to minimise the processing of personal data as much as possible. We will anonymise the personal data you provide. Please note that answering basic personal and demographic questions, such as the religious upbringing of your children and where you live, allows me to understand who and where each person fits into the general population, i.e. to better understand the sample. It also helps me to build up a picture of my participants.

If you are concerned about the processing of your personal data, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain dissatisfied, you can contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details and details of data subjects' rights can be found on the ICO's website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this research study will be presented in a doctoral dissertation.

Who has reviewed the study?

The University of the West of Scotland Education and Social Sciences (ESS) Ethics Committee has reviewed the study.

Contacts for further information

Lead supervisor's details:

Dr. Yonah H. Matemba

School of education and social sciences,

University of the West of Scotland

Scotland, United Kingdom,

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Researcher's details:

Miss Bouzaida Zeyneb

School of Education and Social Sciences,

University of the West of Scotland,

Scotland, United Kingdom,

PA1 2TZ.

Phone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you for considering this invitation to take part in my research.

Appendix 3. Participants' Information Sheet for Teachers, Administrators, and Imams

School of Education and Social Sciences

Participants' information sheet for Teachers, Administrators, and Imams

Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives on the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study.

You are invited to participate in a research study. Before you decide, it is important that you understand why the study is being done and what it involves. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if anything is unclear or if you want more information. Take your time to decide whether you want to participate in the study.

Who am I?

My name is Bouzaida Zeyneb. I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, and the Algerian government funds me. I am from the School of Education and Social Sciences and I am currently preparing for a PhD on Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose of Quranic schools.

What is the purpose of this study?

This study aims to investigate the views of Algerian Muslim parents on the purpose of Quranic schools in Algeria's socio-cultural and religious context.

Why have I been chosen?

This study examines how Algerian Muslim parents perceive the purpose of Quranic schools. In doing so, you, teachers/administrators/Imams, were selected as an appropriate source alongside the parents to obtain the most appropriate data for this study.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to participate, you will be given this information sheet to keep and asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to participate, you can skip

any questions you do not wish to answer and you are free to drop out during the interview or at any time without giving a reason.

After accepting this invitation, what are your rights as a research participant?

If you agree to participate in my research, you must know that:

- Your participation is voluntary.
- You can withdraw at any stage of the fieldwork.
- No justifications are required for your withdrawal.
- You can deny answering any question(s) you do not want to respond about it (them).
- If you do not understand any question, ask for further clarification.
- If you feel unable to continue the interview, you can ask for ending it.
- An audio recording is used during the interview. This allows me to focus on the interview rather than taking notes. The audio recording will be deleted after the transcription.
- If you have any issue, you can ask for stopping the recording.
- The consent form will be sent to you.
- You need to sign the consent form.
- Decide whether you want to use your real name or a pseudonym of your choice.
- You can request the report on the results of this research.

What will I do if I take part?

If you agree to participate in my research, you will take part in an interview that will consist of approximately 12 questions. The expected duration of the face-to-face interview is between 40 minutes and 1 hour. The interviews will be conducted in Arabic. The first questions will be about your personal details. Next, we will talk about Quranic schools in contemporary Algerian society. We will talk about their purpose, characteristics, benefits and ethos. We will also discuss the reasons why Algerian Muslim parents prefer to send their children to Quranic schools. After that, we will develop and discuss other issues, such as the challenges faced by these schools, and we will end with issues related to the public perception of Quranic schools locally and internationally.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

From an ethical perspective, in the field of educational research, the researcher must prioritise the psychological and physical safety, comfort and benefit of the participants. In my research, I am careful to avoid issues that might cause stress to my participants.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

By participating in this study, you will help express Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives about the purpose of Quranic schools and help the Algerian authorities solve the current problems related to these institutions. Through your thoughts and experiences, we can gain valuable insights into the purpose and characteristics of Quranic schools in Algeria and address the current issues related to Quranic schools and the children who attend them. As a teacher/administrator/imam, your cooperation will be very important.

What will happen to the information I provide?

All data collected as part of this study will be handled in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the UWS Code of Ethics. Your personal data will be processed for the purposes stated in this notice. The legal basis for processing your personal data is your consent. Your personal data will be processed for as long as it is necessary for the research project. We will do our best to minimise the processing of personal data as much as possible. We will anonymise the personal data you provide. Please note that answering basic personal and demographic questions, such as about your occupation, qualifications and where you live, allows me to understand who and where each person fits into the general population, i.e. to better understand the sample. They also help me build a picture of my participants.

If you are concerned about the processing of your personal data, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain dissatisfied, you can contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details and details of data subjects' rights can be found on the ICO's website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this research study will be presented in a doctoral dissertation.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland, Education and Social Sciences (ESS) Ethics Committee.

Contacts for further information

Lead supervisor's details:

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Thank you for considering this invitation to take part in my research.

Appendix 4. Parents' Interview Schedule

School: Division of Education, School of Education and Social Sciences.

Research Study Title: Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives of the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study.

Researcher's Name: Zeyneb Bouzaida

Thank you so much for accepting to take part in this doctoral research. My name is Zeyneb Bouzaida, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. Your participation, will inform us on how Algerian parents perceive the purpose of Qur'anic schools. The interview is expected to take between 40 minutes to an hour. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask. Your participation in this interview is greatly appreciated.

1. Can you describe your overall understanding of the purpose of Quranic schools?
2. How has your own educational experience influenced your decision to send your child to a Quranic school? What benefits or weaknesses do you think your own education has brought to your decision-making process?
3. At what age did you first send your child to a Quranic school, and why?
4. What motivated you to send your child to a Quranic school? What benefits do you believe your family gains from this choice?
5. How do you think Quranic education may influence or shape a child's values and beliefs? Can you describe any examples you have observed or heard about?
6. Do your child/children attend both Quranic and public schools? What led you to make this choice, and what challenges have you faced in finding the right balance for your child's education?
7. How would you describe your child's experience at the Quranic school? Are you satisfied with the education they receive? Why or why not?
8. Can you describe your involvement in your child's learning experience at Quranic school? How do you support their learning and growth?
9. How would you describe Quranic schools' learning methods and strategies? To what extent do you find these methods and strategies effective?
10. How do you perceive the role and function of Quranic schools in the context of modern society? If any, what unique benefits do they offer for families who choose this type of education?
11. What is your opinion on the role that government or local authorities should play in regulating Quranic schools and ensuring the quality of education they provide?
12. Have you encountered any public perceptions locally or internationally about Quranic schools promoting Islamic fundamentalism? How do you respond to these perceptions, and what is your own opinion on the matter?
13. How do you see the future of Quranic schools, both in your local community and on a broader scale?
 - ✚ Before ending the interview, do you have anything you want to add? Are there any issues we did not discuss them? Do you have any comments?

Appendix 5. Teachers' Interview Schedule

Teachers' Interview Schedule

School: Division of Education, School of Education and Social Sciences.

Research Study Title: Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives on the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study.

Researcher's Name: Zeyneb Bouzaida

Thank you so much for accepting to take part in this doctoral research. I am Zeyneb Bouzaida, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. Your participation will inform us about how Algerian parents perceive the purpose of Quranic schools. The interview is expected to take between 40 minutes to an hour. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask. Your participation in this interview is greatly appreciated.

- 1- How long have you been teaching at this Quranic school?
- 2- What qualifications and training did you receive to teach at a Quranic school?
3. Can you provide some information about this Quranic school? For instance, what is the school's structure and affiliation, if any? What facilities does it provide? Is it privately or publicly funded? Does it offer free education or require tuition? What is the typical work time for staff and students at the school?
4. Can you describe this Quranic school's overall goals and mission?
5. How does this school support the overall development of the students, including their academic, social, and emotional growth?

6. How do you think Quranic education may influence or shape a child's values and beliefs? Can you describe any examples you have observed or heard about?
7. Can you describe this school's curriculum and teaching methods? To what extent do you think they are effective?
8. How do you perceive the reasons parents choose Quranic schools for their children's education, and what are the perceived benefits families receive from this choice?
9. In your experience as a Quran teacher, how would you describe the level of parental involvement in their children's learning experience? Could you provide any examples of feedback you have received from parents about their child's education at this school?
10. How do you perceive the role and function of Quranic schools in the context of modern society? If any, what unique benefits do they offer for families who choose this type of education?
11. What is your opinion on the role that government or local authorities should play in regulating Quranic schools and ensuring the quality of education they provide?
12. Have you encountered any public perceptions locally or internationally about Quranic schools promoting Islamic fundamentalism? How do you respond to these perceptions, and what is your own opinion on the matter?
13. How do you see the future of Quranic schools, both in your local community and on the broader scale?

✚ Before ending the interview, do you have anything you want to add? Are there any issues we did not discuss them? Do you have any comments?

Appendix 6. Administrators and Imams Interview Schedule

Administrators' and Imams' Interview Schedule

School: Division of Education, School of Education and Social Sciences.

Research Study Title: Algerian Muslim Parents' Perspectives of the Purpose of Quranic Schools: A Phenomenological Study.

Researcher's Name: Zeyneb Bouzaida

Thank you so much for accepting to take part in this doctoral research. I am Zeyneb Bouzaida, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. Your participation will inform us about how Algerian parents perceive the purpose of Qur'anic schools. The interview is expected to take between 40 minutes to an hour. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask. Your participation in this interview is greatly appreciated.

1. How long have you been running this school?
2. Can you provide some information about this Quranic school? For instance, what is the school's structure and affiliation, if any? What facilities does it provide? Is it privately or publicly funded? Does it offer free education or require tuition? What is the typical work time for staff and students at the school?
3. Can you describe this Quranic school's overall goals and mission?
4. How does your school support the overall development of the students, including their academic, social, and emotional growth?
5. How do you think Quranic education may influence or shape a child's values and beliefs? Can you describe any examples you have observed or heard about?
6. Can you describe your school's curriculum and teaching methods? To what extent do you think they are effective?

7. How do you perceive the reasons parents choose Quranic schools for their children's education, and what are the perceived benefits families receive from this choice?
8. In your experience as an administrator of a Quranic school/imam, how would you describe the level of parental involvement in their children's learning experience? Could you provide any examples of feedback you have received from parents about their child's education at your school?
9. How do you perceive the role and function of Quranic schools in the context of modern society? If any, what unique benefits do they offer for families who choose this type of education?
10. What is your opinion on the role that government or local authorities should play in regulating Quranic schools and ensuring the quality of education they provide?
11. Have you encountered any public perceptions locally or internationally about Quranic schools promoting Islamic fundamentalism? How do you respond to these perceptions, and what is your own opinions on the matter?
12. How do you see the future of Quranic schools, both in your local community and on a broader scale?

Before ending the interview, do you have anything you want to add? Are there any issues we did not discuss them? Do you have any comments?

Appendix 7. Debriefing Form

Debriefing Form

Project Title: Algerian Muslim parents' perspectives on the purpose of Quranic schools: A phenomenological study

Quranic education is a growing phenomenon in Algeria. Parents, teachers, and school administrators play a major role in this practice.

Therefore, your participation is crucial to the research. I appreciate your help and the information I have gotten from you.

This study uses a phenomenological approach to gain valuable insights into how Muslim parents conceive the purpose of Quranic schools. Numerous studies have been conducted before that addressed Quranic schools, leading me to this specific aspect of the subject.

After finishing the data collection, I will analyse it and arrive at the results. I expect to gain valuable insights into how parents view the phenomenon of Quranic education in Algeria.

The benefits of this study are not limited to securing hearing to the voice of study participants only; the results might be valuable and beneficial for both the educational sector and the community as a whole.

If you have any follow-up questions or comments, please ask me now. If you are interested in the study's results (once they are complete) or if you have any further questions or comments, please contact us using the details shown below so that we can share that information with you.

Data collection for this study is still ongoing. Please do not share specifics of this study with people who may yet be asked to participate. If asked about this study, please use nondescript phrases like "it was fun" or "it was interesting" to protect the validity of the data I collect.

If you are interested in reading more about this topic, try the following:

Boyle, H. N. (2004) Quranic schools: Agents of preservation and change. Routledge.

Blama Merzaya. A (2012) Quranic schools in the south of Algeria [Almadaris alqurania beljanoub al jazairi]. Master thesis.

Information about who to contact to withdraw or ask further questions is here:

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Thank you again for taking part in this study!